

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC)

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WP1 – T1.2

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Abstract

The Annual Summary Report (ASR) reflects the results of the work achieved during the calendar year. The ASR for year 3 covers the period from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024.

The main achievements of PARC for the period are the followings:

Main achievement 1: A list of priority research topics for the second phase of the Partnership

The prioritisation process has resulted in a list of ranked priority topics for the next few years of PARC. These priorities will guide the partners in initiating new research and development projects.

Main achievement 2: Support for the commission in preparing its roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments

The PARC roadmap for the implementation of the New Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) was communicated and discussed as part of the preparation of the roadmap for phasing out animal in chemical safety assessments. The ten principles guiding the implementation of the NGRA support the conduct of change towards the implementation of new approach and methodologies [AD2.1 - Status report on NGRARoute]. The Partnership is involved in the Commission's work.

Main Achievement 3: Starting of the European HBM survey

Human Biomonitoring (HBM)-aligned studies targeting the general population have progressed to the sampling phase in one of three population groups (children, teenagers, or adults) across various countries, including Poland, Denmark, Belgium, Norway, Estonia, and Israel, while sampling efforts have continued in Slovenia and Poland. In Germany, the sampling phase for adults has been completed. Final effect biomarker & health outcomes that will be followed were selected.

Main Achievement 4: Occupational exposure

Occupational studies are progressing well, with protocols finalized, training materials prepared, and ethical approvals obtained in several countries. Sampling campaigns are expected to be fully underway by early 2025. The occupational healthcare project focuses on hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics, and disinfection/cleaning products. These exposures will primarily be studied in hospital settings in 11 countries. The occupational electronic waste project

performed in 13 countries has established the study protocols, contacted companies and defined the analytical plan.

HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) are derived for the general population and for workers for aluminium and its compounds, for arsenic and pyrethroid metabolites.

Main Achievement 5: Pilot studies on environmental program

Under the environmental program on monitoring, the 2 pilot studies have made progress:

- Endocrine Disrupting compounds (EDCs) are analysed in air, water, soil and biota (fish), using a combination of bioassays, target analyses and suspect screening (ideally covering the full EDC list). More than 200 samples were collected throughout the EU covering 4 matrices and different scenarios and reference sites.
- Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) are studied in two complementary approaches: A baseline study using existing monitoring data on diffuse PFAS contamination, and a series of case studies focusing on the transport and transformation of PFAS from known sources to aquatic recipients. Data covering up to 70 different PFAS is currently being collected in a harmonised protocol. While the PFAS baseline study addresses diffuse PFAS contamination in the environment, the PFAS case studies focus on PFAS emission sources and subsequent pathways to the aquatic environment, with particular interest in the role of precursors.

Main Achievement 6: Human biomonitoring data accessible into integrative exposure assessment models.

The PARC partners have developed and implemented access to national human biomonitoring data in the exposure simulation tool Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA), a component of the PARC Toolbox. This collaborative effort between risk assessment agencies and partners involved in biomonitoring studies has made these data findable, accessible and interoperable, while complying with the rules of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the transparency regulation. The toolbox allows aggregated and mixed exposures. It has been presented to risk assessment agencies and risk managers.

Main Achievement 7: 1st report listing New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) used in PARC

In this report, NAMs are defined as any valid and relevant technology, methodology, approach, strategies, or combination thereof that can provide information on chemical hazard, exposure, and risk assessment to reduce, refine or replace animal testing. A list of the assays under development among the PARC projects has been published [D5.1-1st New approach methodologies report], sorted by the five prioritised endpoints in the case of human health (Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens, Endocrine Disruption (Thyroid), Metabolic Endocrine Disruption, Immuno-toxicity and developmental/adult Neurotoxicity). Some NAMs were described for hazard assessment in the case of environment.

Main Achievement 8: Reviewing substance-specific Risk Assessment (RA) depending on intended use

Case studies reviewing selected methodologies and approaches for regulatory RA have been finalized. A mapping of substances subject to assessment in multiple legal frameworks was done. In this study, substances registered or authorised for the EU market were identified and their presence in different legal frameworks analysed. It illustrated the importance of coordination and communication in the chemical assessment processes. In another case study, inconsistencies in the regulation of antimicrobial substances were identified, as well as existing and missing links between different pieces of chemicals legislation. Further, the implications of the hazard

classification under Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) in different regulations were examined.

Main Achievement 9: A first catalogue of analytical laboratory

The first Europe-wide catalogue of analytical laboratories for human biomonitoring and environmental monitoring has been published online. This catalogue facilitates access to competent laboratories for setting up research or monitoring studies.

Main Achievement 10: Sustainable by Design (SSbD)

Efforts were undertaken to promote knowledge sharing and education aimed at establishing a systematic approach to SSbD both within PARC and among external stakeholders. Test cases were developed to evaluate the applicability of the EC SSbD criteria and methodology, involving stakeholders across the value chain. The SSbD toolbox was computationally implemented, culminating in version 0.1, which features a comprehensive suite of tools and databases for conducting safety and sustainability assessments.

Key Words

Summary report, Period M21-M32

List of abbreviations

AA: Anti-Androgenicity	MIEs: Molecular Initiating Events
ADHD: Attention, Deficit, Hyperactivity, Disorder	ML: Machine Learning
ADI: Acceptable Daily Intake	MLE: Maximum Likelihood Estimation
ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion	MoA: Mode of Action
AE: Affiliated Entity	MRA: Mixture Risk Assessment
AEP: Aggregated Exposure Pathways	MRI: Mixture Risk Indicator
AI: Artificial Intelligence	mRPI: modified Reference Point Index
ALI: Air Liquid Interface	MS: Member States MTA: Material Transfer Agreement
AO/ AON/ AOP: Adverse Outcome/ AO Network/ Pathway	M4M: Metadata 4 Machines
API: Application Programming Interfaces	NAMs: New Approach Methodologies
ASR/ AWP: Annual Summary Report/Work Plans	NER: Named Entity Recognition
ATAC: Assay for Transposase Accessible Chromatin	NERC: New and Emerging Risks of Chemicals
BBB: Blood Brain Barrier	NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment
BCSFB: Blood-cerebrospinal Fluid Barrier	NGTxC: Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens
BERT: Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers	NHs: National Hubs
BIODA: Documentation of Biological Organisms	NHCs: National Hub Coordinators

BMD: Benchmark dose	NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points
BNNs: Bayesian Neural Networks	NLP: Natural Language Processing
BPR: Biocides Products Regulation	NOAEL: No Observable Adverse Effect Level
BSLMM: Bayesian Sparse Linear Mixed Model	NTAs: Non-Target Organisms
CA: Consortium Agreement	NTE: Neuropathy Target Esterase
CAAT: Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing	NTP: Network Tome Protocol
CAG: Cumulative Assessment Groups	NTS: Non-Targeted Screening
CAP: Common Agricultural Policy	NUTS: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
CEN: European Committee for Standardization	OATP: Organic Anion Transporting Polypeptides
CEC: Chemicals of Emerging Concern	ODK: Ontology Development Kit
CDIF: Cross-Domain Implementation Framework	OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
CG: Core Group	OELs: Occupational Exposure Limits
CKAN: Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network	OO: Operational Objectives
CL/ ML: Chemical Leader/ Methodology Leader	OoC: Organ-on-Chip
CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging	OPs: Organophosphorus Compounds
CMS: Content Management System	OPEs: Organophosphate Esters
COPCSD: Common Open Platform on Chemical Safety Data	OSOA: One Substance One Assessment
CPDC: Common Platform for Data on Chemicals	PAH: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
CPR: Cosmetic Products	PBK: Physiologically Based Kinetic
CRA: Chemical Risk Assessment	PBMC: Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells
CRO: Contract Research Organization	PBPK: Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic
CRUD: Create, Read, Update, Delete	PBTK: Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic
CSS: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability	PCBs: Polychlorinated Biphenyls
CT: Coordination Team	PDB: Protein Data Bank
DART: Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity	PEC: Predicted Environmental Concentrations
DBS: Dried Blood Spots	PEH: Personal Exposure and Health
DDI-CDI: Data Documentation Initiative-Cross Domain Integration	PFAS: Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
DEPB: Data and Ethics Protection Board	PFDP: PARC FAIR Data Policy
DILI: Drug-Induced Liver Injury	PG: Project Group
DIT: developmental Immunotoxicology	PFOS: Perfluorooctane Sulfonate
DL: Deep Learning	PKH: Partnership Knowledge Hub
DM: Decision Memo	PM: Project Manager
DMP: Data Management Plan	PMT: Persistent Mobile and Toxic
DNELs: Derived No-Effect Levels	PNEC: Predicted No Effect Concentration
DNT/ANT: Developmental and Acute Neurotoxicity	
DoA: Description of Action	

DRF: Data Reporting Format	PoC: Prof of Concept
DSW: Data Stewardship Wizard	POD: Point of Departure
EAR: Exposure-Activity Ratios	POP: Persistent Organic Pollutant
EATS: Estrogen, Androgen, Steroidogenesis, and Thyroid	POS: Part of Speech
EBD: Environmental Burden of Disease	3PPF: Three-Point FAIRification Framework
EC: European Commission	PPB: Plasma Protein Binding
ECHA: European Chemicals Agency	PPPR: Plant Protection Products Regulation
ED/ EDCs: Endocrine Disrupters / endocrine disrupting compounds	PT: Proficiency Testing
EDA: Effect-Directed Analysis	PWES: Prioritisation and Early Warning System
EECR: Exposure Equivalentents for Cancer Risk	QA/QC: Quality Assurance / Quality Control
EFSA: European Food Safety Authority	QAF: QSAR Assessment Framework
EFP: Electric Field Pulse	QAWG: Quality Assurance Working Group
EFP MRT: Electric Field Pulse Motor Response Test	QIVIVE: Quantitative in vitro / in vivo Extrapolation
EHR: Enterohepatic Recirculation	QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship
EMA: Multielectrode Array	RA/RM: Risk Assessment / Risk Management
EMBL: European Molecular Biology Laboratory	RAC: Regulatory Acceptable Concentrations
EMG: Effect Marker Group	RAiD: Research Activity Identifier
EMT: Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition-migration	RBAC: Role-Based Access Control
EQS: Environmental Quality Standards	RCOHR: Research Center One Health Ruhr
EOF: Extractable Organic Fluorine	RE: Relation Extraction
EOSC: European Open Science Cloud	REAL: Real Exposure Concentrations
EUCLEF: European Chemical Legislation Finder	RED: Rapid Equilibrium Dialysis
EU-CPDC: EU Common Platform for Data on Chemicals	RfDS: Reference Dose
EU-NAP: National Action Plan for Plant Protection Products	RGPD:
ESRs: Early-Stage Researchers	R&I: Research and Innovation
ERA: Environmental Risk Assessment	ROR: Research Organization Registries
EV: Extracellular Vesicles	ROS: Reactive Oxygen Species
EWS: Early Warning System	RPE: Retinal Pigmentary Epithelium
FA: Food Additives	RQ: Risk Quotient
FCS: Fetal Calf Serum	RRM: Rapid Response Mechanism
FF: Food Flavourings	S ² CIE: Syntactic, Semantic, and Contextual Information Extraction
FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	SAM: Stress Addition Model
FDA: Food and Drug Administration	SBML: Systems Biology Markup Language
FDP: Fair Data Point	
FIP: FAIR Implementation Profiles	
FIT: FAIR Implementation Taskgroup	

FSR: FAIR Supporting Resources	SCCS: Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety
GA: Grant Agreement	SCOS: Simple Knowledge Organization System
GB: Governing Board	SETAC: Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation	SES: Socio-Economic Status
GEQUAS: German External Quality Assessment Scheme	SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals
GFF: Go Fair Foundation	S2PD: Science-to-Policy Dialogue
GHS: Global Harmonized System	SAICM: Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management
GIVIMP: Good In Vitro Methods Practices	SF: Stakeholder Forum
GIS: Geographical Information System	SG: Specialty Group
GMP DWH: Global Monitoring Plan Data Warehouse	SIT: Semantic Implementation Team
GNN: Graph Neural Networks	SKOMOS: Simple Knowledge Organization System
GPR: Gaussian Process Regression	SKOS: Simple Knowledge Organization System
GS: Grant Signatory	SO: Specific Objectives
GSB: Grant Signatory Board	SOP: Standard Operating Procedures
GUPRIs: Global Unique Persistence Resolvable Identifiers	SOSA: Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator
HA: Hazard Assessment	SPM: Suspended Particulate Matter
HBM: Human BioMonitoring	SPME: Solid Phase Microextraction
HBM GV: Health-based Guidance Values	SPSF: Standard Project Submission Form
HDMA: High-Dimensional Mediation Analysis	SS: suspect screening
HDMM: High-Dimensional Multivariate Mediation	SSbD: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design SSO: Single-Sign-On
HESI: Health and Environmental Sciences Institute	SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
HIA: Health Impact Assessment	STOP: Source to Outcome Pathways
hMNR: human Multi-Neurotransmitter Receptor Assay	SUD: Use of Pesticide Directive
hiPSC: human induced Pluripotent Stem Cell	SVM: Support Vector Machine
HRMS: High Resolution Mass Spectrometry	SVOCs: Semivolatile Organic Compounds
I-ADOPT: Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property	SWB: Silicone Wristbands
IATA: Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessment	T/TL: Task/Task co-leaders
IB: International Board	TBBPA: Tetrabromobisphenol A
ILMERAC: International Liaison group on Methods for RA of Chemicals in food	TCA: Tricarboxylic Acid Cycle
IPM: Integrated Pest Management	TCBPA: Tetrachlorobisphenol A
IPR: Intellectual Property Rights	TDM EG: Thyroid Disruption Method Expert Group
ISCED: International Standard Classification of Education	
IVB: In Vitro Battery	
IVIVE: <i>in vitro</i> - <i>in vivo</i> extrapolation	
JRC: Joint Research Centre	
KARC: Key Areas of Regulatory Challenge	

KCC: Key Characteristics of Carcinogens	TEER: Transepithelial Electrical Resistance
KEs: Key Events	TIM: Tool for Innovation Monitoring
KERs: Key Event Relationships	TOPA: Total Oxidisable Precursors Assay
KIC: Knowledge and Innovation Communities	TTC: Toxicological Threshold of Concern
KPIs: Key Performance Indicators/Impact	THSD: Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors
LCA: Life-cycle assessment	THTM: Thyroid Hormone Transmembrane Transporters
LLM: Large Language Approach	TKTD: Toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic modelling
MAF: Mixture Assessment Factor	TR: Thyroid Receptor
MB: Management Board	TRC: Test Readiness Criteria
MCA: Metabolic Control Analysis	TRF: Transcriptomic Reporting Framework
MCD; Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis	TRHR: Thyrotropin Releasing Hormone Receptor
MCRA: Monte Carlo Risk Assessment	TRL: Technology Readiness Level
MDC: Metabolic Disrupting chemicals	UCWG: Use Case Working Group(s)
MDTA: Material and Data Transfer Agreement	UI: User interface
MEA: Multi Electrodes Array	UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme
MEC: Measured Environmental Concentrations	US-EPA: US Environmental Protection Agency
	US-NTP: US National Toxicology Program
	USD: Use of Pesticides Directive
	VAMR: Visual and Acoustic Motor Response
	VMRT: Visual Motor Response Test
	WBE: Wastewater-Based Epidemiology
	WFD: Water Framework Directive
	WGCNA: Weighted Gene Correlation networks for analysis
	WHO: World Health Organization
	WoE: Weight-of-Evidence
	WP/ WPL: Work Package / WP co-leaders
	WWTP: Wastewater treatment plants
	ZAPID: Zonal Authorisation Procedure Improvements and Developments
	ZFe: Zebrafish embryo

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1. Explanation of the work carried out and overview of the progress

1.1 Objectives

PARC is set up to consolidate and strengthen European public Research and Innovation (R&I) capacities in Chemical Risk Assessment (CRA) to protect human health and the environment and has an objective-oriented structure to answer the end-users' needs. Linked to this general objective are three specific objectives (SO) around which the nine Work Packages (WP) of PARC are structured and for which 13 realistic, measurable, achievable and verifiable operational objectives (OO) are developed.

PARC has elaborated a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) which presents PARC's vision, challenges it will respond to and how it will achieve its expected impacts. It also presents PARC's progression along its strategic Partnership impact pathways and showcases its contribution to scientific, societal and economic impacts.

All WPs closely interact on transversal topics, and the R&I activities developed under WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP8 benefit from the support of WP2, WP3, WP7 and WP9

Fig.1. Links between WPs and objectives

Summary of progress for the period M21-M32:

Specific PARC objectives are:

Specific objective 1:

- **Set up an EU-wide sustainable cross-disciplinary network to identify and agree on research and innovation needs and to support research uptake into regulatory CRA.**

PARC, with its consortium involving both regulatory and academic scientists and being in close dialogue with EU and national regulatory agencies, is in a unique position to incorporate new advances in monitoring, hazard, exposure and RA for human health and environment.

Four cross-cutting WPs in charge of management and coordination (WP1), establishment of a common science policy agenda (WP2) and development of synergies, collaborations and awareness (WP3) and capacities (WP9) collaborate with all partners to achieve the following operational objectives (OO).

OO1: Set up and operate a high-level group of EU and national representatives engaged in regulatory RA and risk management, to strategically steer PARC

PARC has made significant progress in setting up and operating a high-level group of EU and national representatives engaged in regulatory RA and Risk Management (RM).

The PARC governance bodies (Governing Board (GB), Management Board (MB), Grant Signatory Board (GSB)) continue to interact through regular meetings and consultation to steer and manage the Partnership.

The development of a strong network has been facilitated through meetings with the GB, which have allowed the review of PARC progress and discussions on future priorities.

During 2024, the MB and the partners submitted the 1st Periodic Technical and Financial Report (PTFR), drew up an ASR for 2024 and prepared the Annual Work Plan (AWP) Y4 for discussion with the GB. The partners met at the consortium meeting with the GB representatives to exchange information on the progress of their work and discuss synergies with external initiatives. A

mapping of needs was carried out throughout the year to identify the strategic priorities for the coming years and the resources available within the Partnership (see OO3). This collaborative work involved numerous exchanges and discussions with partners and European agencies. Seminars were organised in Autumn 2024 with the Chemical Leaders (CLs) to present the state of the art and the needs for research and innovation in micro- and nano-plastics, nano-materials and PFAS.

During 2024, Regular communication and connects [twice/year] between EPAA (including representatives from the 7 sectors) and PARC leaders were organised to exchange progress and direction on NAMs. During these meetings, PARC leaders interact with EPAA, as a key NAMs stakeholder, on their main proposals for project design, policies, and progress, to facilitate future uptake of the developed methodologies as these could have a significant impact on the EPAA industry sectors.

A collaboration agreement with NORMAN Association has been approved in November 2024 and collaboration with JRC on PARC specific projects continues.

OO2: Expand a long-term sustainable network of National Hubs that interact with stakeholders to exchange and feed expertise, knowledge and needs into the Partnership and promote uptake of PARC's results

In 2024, continuous dialogue with **National Hub Contact Points** (NHCP) was maintained through surveys, meetings, and a PARCopedia group, translating NHs needs into actionable steps. More than 430 organisations constitute the National Hub (NH) network and 27 to 28 NHs answered to the survey. The annual survey highlighted challenges like resource limitations and securing co-funding, discussed in NHCP meetings in Austria and Belgium. These meetings shared good practices and success stories, aiding NH development. Data from the survey refined the monitoring framework, with a third survey planned for January 2025 to enhance stakeholder engagement and address ongoing challenges.

The PARC Stakeholder Forum (SF) was also consulted on the mapping of needs and were invited to attend the consortium meeting and to join PARCopedia groups.

Two SYNnet Forums took place back-to-back with International Conferences (SETAC, European Environmental Mutagenesis and Genomics Society Meeting).

In terms of sustainability, in 2023, a survey on the exit strategy was conducted, and its analysis led to the first PARC Exit Strategy Plan and sustainability report, submitted in May 2024. The report emphasized the need for sustainability in activities like HBM and Toxicology, suggesting frameworks for embedding these activities in legislation and central coordination at the EU level. These conclusions were shared with NHs and PARC's boards, and further meetings are planned to discuss exit strategies, culminating in a physical meeting in early 2025.

PARC coordination follows also the activity of the EU Partnership Knowledge Hub (PKH) to gather a return of experience of the different Partnerships. Cooperations with EU research infrastructures are on-going on specific topics (EIRENE, Elixir).

OO3: Define common research and innovation strategies with transparent criteria and implement a prioritisation process to address the regulatory knowledge needs for chemical RA and management

A large part of the second prioritisation round was performed along this year. After having gathered the regulatory needs of the GB members through a survey, the long list was refined and shortened to focus on the ones nominated by the EC and / or at least 3 GB members. These selected needs were then further discussed with the EU agencies who also expressed their Key Areas of Regulatory Challenge (KARC), and assessed by the MB to categorize them based on the PARC capacities. A webinar on June 18, 2024, organized by EU agencies, discussed

research priorities and challenges in regulatory science to inform the PARC research community. The ECHA KARC was updated.

Finally, the needs were shared with the NHs and the SF to get their top priorities and with the IB to identify ongoing activities outside Europe. A final ranking step was performed with the GB and the final assessment was then shared with the consortium to pave the way for future PARC project proposals.

Fig. 2: Mapping of Needs topics

Table 1: Top 5 needs ranking

Topic	Need Description	Task	GB votes
New Approach Methods (NAMs) for Replacing Animal Testing	How to use NAM for CLP classification and OEL development.	T6.1, T6.3, T6.4	10
Battery Chemicals	Biomonitoring of workers (e.g., lithium, cobalt, nickel salts, also fluorinated compounds and ionic liquids).	T4.1, T6.2	9
Persistent Mobile Toxic (PMT) /very Persistent very Mobile (vPvM) Substances	*/** Monitoring in soil, water, and biota.	T4.2	9
Chemicals Leaching from Plastics and Rubber Tyres	** Close data gaps on chemicals leaching from plastics for human health, including non-intentionally added substances to plastics.	T5.1	9
Co-exposure to Multiple Chemicals	Further development of methods for health and environmental risk assessment of co-exposures to multiple chemicals.	T6.2	9

Flame Retardants	Data needed on human exposure and effects (general population) + substitutes.	T4.1, T6.2	8
Benzophenones and UV Filters	*/** Collection of exposure data across Europe.	T4.1	8
New Approach Methods (NAMs) for Replacing Animal Testing	Develop NAMs to replace animal testing for hazard endpoints (e.g., acute fish toxicity).	T5.2	8
Substances in Welding Fumes	Collection of biomonitoring data for workers (e.g., manganese).	T4.1	7
Chemicals Leaching from Plastics and Rubber Tyres	More environmental monitoring on fate and behaviour of tyre additives, including PPD and metabolites.	T4.2	7
Developmental and Reproductive Toxicology (DART)	Development of NAMs (including developmental immunotoxicity and developmental neurotoxicity).	T5.2, T6.2	7
Neurotoxicity	Development of NAMs (DNT, ANT, DIT); Identification of reliable positive and negative reference chemicals for NAM reliability testing and validation.	T5.2	7
Natural Toxins	Data on human exposure and effect: Mycotoxins (e.g., enniatins, alternaria).	T4.1	6
PFAS	Studies on the properties, behaviour in the environment, ecotoxicity and human toxicity of PFAS other than PFOS, PFOAS and PFHxS.	T5.1	7
PFAS	Develop fast and efficient analytical methods for PFAS in products and articles.	T6.4	7
PFAS	General Population: Develop knowledge on alternatives and substitutes.	T4.1, T6.2	6
Immunotoxicity	Study the effects of chemicals on the immune system, particularly in sensitive populations (e.g., children); Identification of critical windows of development of the immune system to develop a NAM based battery to assess developmental immunotoxicity.	T5.2, T6.2	6

After the needs had been identified by the GB Principal Representatives and the EU Hub, they were assessed and discussed with the MB. The consultation of the NHs, SF members and the International Board (IB) on these needs was followed by an expression of interest from the GB members, who voted on their top 15 priorities, enabling a ranking of needs according to the number of votes received for each. This table represents the priorities that received the highest number of votes from the GB. All the results of this process will be shared with the PARC consortium, and a top-down and bottom-up prioritisation process is planned.

Chemical groups			Endpoints	Tools / Methods
Molecular structure	Use-defined	Complex mixtures	Neurotoxicity	Early warning signals
PFAS	Flame retardants	Substances in welding fumes	Immunotoxicity	Replace animal testing for hazard endpoints
Bisphenols	Pesticides, fungicides	Pollutants in wastewater effluents	Carcinogenicity	Monitoring methodology
Phthalates	Battery chemicals	ED mixtures	DART	Co-exposure
Heavy metals	UV filters - benzophenones	MOCS	Bioaccumulation	Systematic in vitro/silico battery to steer generation of chronic toxicity data for vertebrate species
Natural toxins	Vitamins	MOSH / MOAH		Sensitivity of non-bee pollinators to biocidal active substances
Material-related	Environmental Fate	Chemicals leaching from plastics and rubber tires		
Monomers	PMT/vPvM			
2D materials	Chemicals and biodiversity			
Fibres				

DART: Developmental and Reproductive Toxicology
PMT/vPvM: Persistent, mobile and toxic; very persistent and very mobile
MOCS: More than One Constituent Substances
MOSH / MOAH: Mineral Oil Saturated / Aromatic Hydrocarbons

Legend:
 Already in PARC
 To be discussed
 Not a priority

Fig. 3: Overview of expressed topics

On the top of this prioritization round, in February 2024, the EEA and ECHA sent a request to the PARC's Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM) related to a sharp increase in mono-n-hexyl phthalate concentrations in urine samples from children and adults in Germany and Denmark. The aim is to identify the extent and source of exposure to this phthalate in Europe. In collaboration with the GB, the request's eligibility was assessed. A specific working group was formed, and the feasibility was assessed. A tiered approach was proposed, and a new project coordinated under the task 2.1 was launched, collaborating with Task 4.1 for biomonitoring data, Task 4.2 for environmental/indoor air data, Task 6.2 for source modelling, and Activity 6.4 for consumer product screening.

OO4: Actively foster the regulatory uptake of knowledge produced under the Partnership in chemical RA and regulatory processes

PARCopedia, a community platform for knowledge exchange and CRA innovation, was launched in November 2023. By September 2024, it had grown from 50 to nearly 900 users, including members from academia, authorities, and the private sector. Efforts are ongoing to increase community engagement.

A draft roadmap for NGRA was created, aiming for regulatory uptake in European chemicals legislation. Following the European Commission's roadmap announcement in July 2023, NGRAroute activities were aligned with the COM Roadmap. The focus shifted to contributing to COM working groups and preparing for a workshop in October 2024.

The NGRAroute has also been acknowledged in two documents published by the European Commission in 2024:

- European Commission (2024): Proposal to establish a Subgroup on Test Methods in CARACAL. In 52nd Meeting of the Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (CARACAL). <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/a0b483a2-4c05-4058-addf-2a4de71b9a98/library/4fa23357-4bbb-4f8f-a46b-fa9b784a7300/details>

- European Commission, Cronin M (2024): Report of the European Commission workshop on "The Roadmap Towards Phasing Out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments" –

Brussels, 11-12 December 2023. Edited by: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2873/34576>

According to our procedure, a call for new Chemical Leaders (CLs) and Methodology Leaders (MLs) was issued, evaluated, and approved. Meetings were held to discuss roles, responsibilities, and future activities. The AWP for Y4 was prepared, and groups for EDCs and nanomaterials were established in PARCopedia. Webinars in preparation of the GB of 13 November 2024 were organised on nano- and micro-plastics, nanomaterials and PFAS. Recommendations were made by GB members for PARC to have more a role in following activities on nanomaterials and nano and microplastics performed by outside initiatives and to provide regular update and promote targeted PARC projects to fill identified RA gaps.

The progress of the work performed on the mixture RA with the development of databases and tools helping in the HBM data analysis, real life mixtures and identification of key drivers were also presented to agencies and risk managers.

During the annual WP6 workshop in April 2024, risk managers were engaged, and progress was discussed with DG SANTE, EFSA, ECHA, and JRC. Three project meetings were held throughout the year, where case study leaders presented their results. The progress done on integrative risk and exposure assessment (WP6 Task 6.2) was disseminated to the PARC IB and SF, and results were shared at the Eurotox 2024 conference in Copenhagen. EFSA and RIVM organized a session on integrative RA of chemical mixtures using HBM data, showcasing models and tools developed by PARC. Four expert speakers from ANSES, BPI, and WR shared insights on innovative strategies and regulatory implementation.

A PARC MB scoping paper on validation-related activities within PARC to progress new methods and approaches for hazard and RA of chemicals (available on PARC website) has been presented to CARACAL meeting in June 2024.

OO5: Promote cooperation with other research & innovation Partnerships, programmes and activities across Europe and foster European leadership at the international level for research and innovation in chemical RA

Efforts to expand the synergies network within PARC continued, involving multiple partners. The interaction strategy between SYNnet and WPs was revised to better address internal needs and gaps. Exchanges with WP, task, and project leaders aimed to identify relevant external scientific activities and promote formal synergies. A form for collecting expressions of interest from external projects was added to PARC's website, leading to dedicated meetings and updates on interested projects.

A collaboration agreement with the NORMAN Association was developed and signed by the two parties. The first SYNnet Forum was held alongside the SETAC annual meeting in Spain in May 2024, and the second alongside the European Environmental Mutagenesis and Genomics Society Meeting in Croatia in September 2024. Planning for the third SYNnet Forum, to be held at the EUROTOX 2025 conference in Athens, began, with announcements made on PARC's website and social media.

A workshop on synergies with external initiatives was organized at the Consortium Meeting in May 2024, featuring presentations from several external projects (ASPIS, EURION, Biodiversa+, NORMAN). A second workshop was organised during November 2024, involving projects from the ENKORE and Green Deal Clusters.

EPAA (including representatives from the 7 sectors) and PARC leaders met twice in 2024 to exchange progress and direction on NAMs. During these meetings, PARC leaders consulted with EPAA, as a key NAMs stakeholder, on their main proposals for project design, policies, and progress, to facilitate future uptake of the developed methodologies as these could have a significant impact on the industry sectors.

OO6: Effectively and transparently communicate and disseminate knowledge produced by the Partnership, ensure public accessibility to results and increase citizens' understanding and awareness of the principles of European chemical RA

In 2024, the PARC website was continuously maintained and updated. Key developments included visualizing research projects, HBM laboratories, output indicators, and opportunities on an interactive map. A new survey creation functionality was added, and the PARC leaflet was translated into national languages and uploaded to the website.

PARC's social media channels on LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and X were regularly updated with new content, including progress updates, interviews, and results. A dedicated group managed the content, holding weekly meetings to discuss news and events. New social media campaigns were launched, featuring posts on HBM studies and interviews with key PARC actors.

The Science Digest newsletter, highlighting the latest PARC publications, was published eight times in 2024. The PARC community on Zenodo was maintained, and the general newsletter, PARC Sampler, was published twice in collaboration with the content management group.

An exhibition titled "Healthy Horizons: Our Journey to Create a Safer Chemical World" was organized during the PARC Consortium meeting in May 2024. It featured informative displays, interactive installations, and a survey to gather insights on improving research translation into policy.

The procurement process for a representative citizen survey was completed, with translations handled by NHCPs. Focus groups were organized in several countries, and data analysis has begun. Surveys on risk perception were conducted in Greece and Slovenia, with results analyzed and a report prepared. A series of webinars on risk communication was also developed.

Efforts to map stakeholder surveys were initiated, involving consultations with various boards and stakeholders. A trilateral meeting was held to design a survey for regulators and policymakers. A bibliometric analysis for May 2022 to December 2023 was prepared, and output indicators were visualized for the PARC website.

NHs ensure the communication, dissemination and discussion of PARC results and produce feedback about national views and needs for further discussion in the boards.

Specific objective 2:

- Set up joint EU research and innovation activities responding to identified priorities in support of current regulatory RA processes for chemical substances and to emerging challenges.

OO7: Develop and implement annual research and innovation work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA

To ensure the delivery of PARC operational outcomes, activities are organized into **projects** under various tasks and work packages. The Project Review Process was applied to existing and new project proposals. In 2024, 72 existing projects, including 16 case studies, were reviewed by 10 Contact Points and nearly 100 reviewers from 15 organizations. Project descriptions were updated based on reviewer comments, and their status is tracked in the PARC project portfolio.

For Year 4, 23 projects requested time extensions, categorized into limited and significant extensions. Additionally, 18 new projects were reviewed and included in the PARC Project Portfolio, bringing the total to 81 projects, including 18 case studies.

Besides regular on-line meetings (every 6 weeks), two physical meetings to organise the review and follow up of projects within T2.1 were held in 2024, in Helsinki and Vienna, along with regular online meetings. An online meeting where all PARC Project Managers (PMs), Projects reviewers

and contact points and WP/Task leaders were invited held on September 30, 2024, to gather feedback on the review process.

OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in the former European HBM Initiative (HBM4EU) and support the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes

HBM

Under task 4.1, the general population HBM aligned studies have entered in the sampling phase in one of the 3 population groups (children, teenagers and adults) in different countries (Poland, Denmark, Belgium, Norway, Estonia, Israel), have continued in Slovenia and Poland. Germany has finalized the sampling phase in adults.

Fig. 4: PARC HBM regions (Blue: North countries, Green: East Countries, Yellow: Central Countries, Orange: South Countries)

[P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability] on the way to collect occupational data during general HBM studies has finished and reported recommendations for future general population surveys.

The project, [P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem] focused on identifying chemical compounds for occupational exposure surveillance, highlighting PFAS and Mycotoxins. Despite initiating a mapping exercise to prioritize chemicals and assess institutional capacities, delays and unresolved challenges led to the decision not to extend the project beyond three years and to end it. A project final report will analyse the concepts and provide recommendations for future work in this field.

The occupational healthcare project [P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey], involving multiple partners, focuses on hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics, and disinfection/cleaning products. These exposures will primarily be studied in hospital settings in 11

countries. Study protocols, target groups, and training materials have been finalized, with sampling set to begin in late 2024 to early 2025 after obtaining ethical approvals from partners.

The occupational electronic waste project [P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste], performed in 13 countries has established the study protocols, contacted companies and defined the analytical plan.

Within the framework of the project [P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_Derivation of HBM-GVs], eight substance dossiers as basis for the derivation of HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs) or HBM Exposure Equivalents for Cancer Risk (HBM-EECR) have been drafted, respectively for DHHB (diethylamino hydroxybenzoyl hexyl benzoate, Uvinul® A plus), lambda cyhalothrin, benzophenone-3, diisononyl phthalate (DiNP), diethylhexyl terephthalate (DEHTP), aluminium, nickel, and chromium VI.

The project [P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO] has progressed in its investigation to link HBM and Health data with the development of questionnaires and guidelines for the identified biomarkers of effects.

The occupational waste management project [P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste] has finalized study protocols, target groups, and training materials. Ethical approvals have been obtained by most partners, and sampling campaigns have begun in several countries [countries], with others set to start early 2025.

The final selection of biomarkers of exposure for the PARC Aligned Studies and occupational studies has been done and first round of Quality Assurance / Quality Control (QA/QC) were organised with an excellent cooperation with G-EQUAS Scheme.

The HBM data landscape work was finalized, identifying main platforms like the Personal Exposure and Health platform (PEH) and IPCHEM for hosting HBM data. Operational definitions for HBM datasets were proposed, and FAIR implementation profiles were drafted.

The feasibility of federated systems for privacy-preserving analysis was assessed, but it was decided not to implement this further. Metadata schema and templates for HBM data were improved, and a customized PARC metadata collection tool was developed. The conceptual part of the HBM ontology work was finalized, and common vocabularies were identified for linking HBM datasets to international standards.

A tailored Geographical Information System (GIS) tool for integrating HBM with environmental and geospatial data was created, and preliminary mapping of resources for non-target screening analysis was conducted.

ID	Project Title
P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO	General population HBM survey
P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL	Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys
P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven	Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system
P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_SRU ¹	Occupational survey in the healthcare sector

¹ AMD-101057014-80: Paul Scheepers, who was the main scientific contact for the Dutch affiliated entity Radboud University Medical Centre - PARC acronym "RUMC", ended working for RUMC and started working for Stichting Radboud University – PARC acronym "SRU", as of 01/06/2022. The termination date of RUMC was effective as of 01/06/2022. Stichting Radboud

P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL	Occupational survey in the waste management sector
P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA	Propose health-based HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs)
P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO	Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposure and health concerns
P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO	Further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU
P4.1.5_a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO	Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

Environmental monitoring

Under T4.2, the pilot project [P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU] consists of six steps which are the common framework of all environmental and multisource projects which is tested with the design and implementation of PFAS and EDCs environmental monitoring.

EDCs are analysed in air, water, soil and biota (fish), using a combination of bioassays, target analyses and suspect screening (ideally covering the full EDC list).

PFAS are studied in two complementary approaches: A baseline study using existing monitoring data on diffuse PFAS contamination, and a series of case studies focusing on the transport and transformation of PFAS from known sources to aquatic recipients.

For the baseline studies, data covering up to 70 different PFAS (depending on the dataset), provided by 10 countries, is currently being collected in a harmonised protocol and processed for the statistical analysis.

Nineteen PFAS case studies were launched to address five research questions:

- What is the role of precursors in the environmental fate of PFAS?
- How far can PFAS precursors be transported from a source in the terrestrial/aquatic environment?
- How do environmental conditions (e.g., soil type, temperature, organic carbon content) and PFAS molecular structures (chain length, functional group) influence their transport to aquatic recipients?
- Can non-target methods contribute to establishing a “PFAS fingerprint”, which might improve our understanding of pathways?
- Can fingerprinting be used for source identification and can it be embedded in monitoring?

The studies use a combination of methodological approaches such as target analysis, suspect screening, non-target analysis, and determinations of PFAS Total, such as Extractable Organic Fluorine (EOF) and Total Oxidisable Precursors Assay (TOPA). The environmental compartments include biota, soil, groundwater, surface water, marine/brackish water, wastewater, sludge and solid particulate matter.

Within the general framework, the partners have defined a workflow covering all aspects related to QA/QC of the sampling and analytical data provided by the laboratories, data transfer to the database before statistical analysis and interpretation.

University was added as new affiliated entity of the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) acting as Beneficiary in PARC, as of 01/06/2022.

Following the prioritization framework previously described, the partners involved in the project [P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe] organized different working groups focused on data sources, IT infrastructure, and case studies to further develop and test the tool. The IT infrastructure group worked on automating the prioritization concept, while the data sources group identified relevant databases. Collaboration with the Early Warning System (EWS) in T8.2 was also emphasized, with a joint workshop held to explore integration and shared tools.

Initiated in 2024 in close collaboration with the Task 4.1 in charge of HBM, the project [P4.2.c_Y3_Human Exposure] aims to i) generate personal environmental exposure data for the participants in the General Survey and ii) to generate knowledge of environmental non-food exposure sources to chemicals, focusing on the indoor environment, drinking water and soil (mainly related to homegrown vegetables).

ID	Project Title
P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU	Establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors
P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS	Applications of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring
P4.2.c_Y3_Human exposure_AU_INERIS	Human exposure to organic contaminants from non-food environmental sources

Sampling and analytical innovative methods

Under T4.3, development of innovative sampling and analytical methods are on-going to be used in different environmental, food safety and HBM to enhance the screening capacity to trigger early warning signals about chemicals of emerging concern.

ID	Project Title
P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QAQC_WR	QA/QC requirements for High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) and Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) -based screening approaches in environmental, food and human matrices
P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU	Illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/ Non-Targeted Screening (NTS)/ Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) approaches as a contribution to early warning system and harmonized framework from environment-food-human
P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data processing workflow_EHESP	Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS. Identify gaps / necessary methodological improvements for retrospective use of NTS HRMS data (digital sample freezing platform) and EU capacity in terms of centralized data repository
P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern
P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH	Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I. human community (wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment) and II. environmental exposure assessment (screening of wastewater treatment plant

	effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern into the water cycle).
P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.
P4.3.3.b_Y2_EO2-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring chemicals of emerging concern in sentinel animal species
P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- <i>Food items exposure _ANSES</i>	Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based/EDA screening methods on food samples

OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA

The aim of PARC is to enable all the scientific communities involved in CRA, as well as risk managers and stakeholders, to have access to high-quality data by facilitating their accessibility, interoperability and usefulness for research. In the context of Open Science, PARC promotes harmonisation of data and exchange between different actors (scientific community, health agencies, regulators, policy-makers, etc.) and disciplines (exposure science, toxicology..., etc.) to promote transparency, support RA, and allow for reuse. It ensures data and associated information is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) and addresses the challenges for data exchange in line with the GDPR related challenges for data exchange. The actual FAIRification of data is supported by data champions, data liaisons and a FAIR implementation task group that have been nominated and trained. A workplan on FAIRification actions was drafted and data use cases were initiated (see D7.2).

A methodology for assessing progress towards the WP7 Key Performance Impact (KPI) of 80% of PARC data being FAIR has been developed. This involved defining the unit of data in PARC and evaluating existing approaches for assessing FAIRness. The initial evaluation was largely manual but will become increasingly automated. A key outcome is a checklist for PARC authors to complete alongside publication submissions, summarizing data and its deposition. This process will be rolled out in late 2024 and early 2025, accompanied by webinars to enhance the FAIRness of PARC data.

In the third year, continuous training for Data Champions, Liaisons, and the FAIR Implementation Task Group (FIT) focused on FAIR implementation through interactions with the PARC community. Key activities included the establishment of a general GO FAIR wiki and a three-point framework for FAIRification to centralize training materials. Improvements were made to the FAIR supporting resources qualification pipeline, enhancing the experience for future facilitators. WP7 also engaged with the ELIXIR Toxicology community on FAIRification of toxicological research output and hosted a successful training course on FAIR data and databases in Ljubljana, Slovenia. The training pyramid model continued to be effective, with knowledge transfer progressing from data liaisons to data champions and building FAIR awareness within the PARC consortium.

The HBM4EU central data and PEH platforms were continued. Work was performed to support harmonization and quality control. The HBM landscape was finalized for further discussion (see OO8).

The landscaping activities for the PARC data landscape were organized into dedicated projects or clusters. Reports on the environmental data landscape are still in preparation. The landscaping of toxicology data is ongoing, with surveys and FAIR implementation profiles (FIPs) being developed.

The architecture of the PARC Data Hub was refined to incorporate FAIR semantic metadata, enhancing data interoperability and reusability. Prototyping focused on User Interface (UI) development for metadata capture and testing Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN, open-source data management system for powering data hubs and data portals) extensions for geospatial metadata standards. The first version of the Data Hub Portal was created, featuring a clean design, structured navigation, and robust technical infrastructure. The metadata repository service was developed, with custom filters, metadata standards, and search capabilities.

Chemical RA dashboards were created for HBM laboratories and environmental monitoring networks, featuring data normalization, harmonization, and automated data ingestion.

OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for hazard, exposure and RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake

Hazard assessment

In WP5, Task 5.1, the strategy for hazard identification and characterisation of mycotoxins (*Alternaria* toxins, Enniatins) aims to fill the established data gaps. Similarly, a project concerning Bisphenol A (BPA) identified analogues and alternatives and several priority substances. A significant part of the testing plans was performed during the year and results were obtained for different toxicological endpoints.

ID	Project Title
P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE	Hazard identification and hazard characterisation of the mycotoxins enniatins and <i>Alternaria</i> toxins in order to close data gaps and improve RA for human health
P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR	Hazard assessment of BPA alternatives to close data gaps of concern for human health and improve their RA
P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent	Toxicity assessment of naturally occurring toxins on aquatic organisms
P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU	BPA alternatives and associated mixtures (data gaps and NAM development)

The focus of Task 5.2 is on the improvement of the current hazard characterisation paradigm by establishing comprehensive testing strategies that logically combine novel methods with well-established approaches, preferably in a tiered manner. In brief, the relevance and readiness of new technologies, e.g. genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, high-content analysis microscopy, high resolution mass spectrometry, and human inducible pluripotent stem cell technology, will be evaluated for the assessment of (eco)toxicological endpoints such as non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption and (developmental) neurotoxicity, thereby leveraging OECD's and PARC's Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) frameworks. Projects involving the development of NAMs, *in vitro* tests, *in vivo* tests and *in silico* models have set up research and development work, the sharing of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and the dissemination of their results.

The close collaboration with ongoing clusters of research projects such as ASPIS^[1] and EURION^[2] allows PARC to initiate some projects that will move forward the development of AOPs and Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATAs) for six endpoints: neurodevelopment, endocrine disruption (EURION), carcinogenicity (ASPIS), organ toxicities (ASPIS), metabolic disruption (EURION), immunotoxicity. The main pathways of these adverse effects are addressed jointly by projects in WP5 task 5.2. Innovative methods and tools for toxicity

testing and modelling and task 5.3. Quantitative Systems Toxicology and development of new AOPs and physiologically based toxicokinetics models Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK).

ID	Project Title
P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE	Non-genotoxic carcinogens (NGTXCs)
P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE	Metabolic Endocrine Disruption
P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU ²	Endocrine disruptors – Thyroid hormone system disruption
P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm	Immunotoxicity
P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_UU	Neurotoxicity

Under Task 5.3, the development of Physiologically Based Kinetics (PBK) and quantitative systems toxicology has been continued on different questions regarding the generation or identification (of existing) in vitro kinetics data and their integration into the PBK models. The case studies will focus on absorption (inhalation, oral), distribution (human blood-brain barrier), and metabolism (isoform specificity, gut microbial metabolism) in relation with hazard characterisation studies for mycotoxins, PFAS and pesticides. The three projects made progress during the year by carrying out transcriptomics studies (P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR), continuing developments on the description of new AOPs and supporting the development of the AOP wiki [P5. 3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_INSERTM], and in the implementation of case studies bringing together experts in modelling and the study of ADME processes [P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology_Fraunhofer].

ID	Project Title
P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR	Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment.
P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm	AOP Development
P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer	PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology

Exposure assessment

Monitoring of Human and of the environment are key components of the exposure assessment and as such both are addressed below under OO9 and therefore not included in this section.

Under WP6, the project [P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO] focuses its activities on developing the external exposure pathway of chemicals from different sources of exposure. The case studies developed under this project have progressed in several aspects of source to dose chain in the indoor environment (eg Exposure to lead via premise plumbing, assessing the contribution of sources to indoor pollution, including evaluation of indoor source to dose models for Semivolatile Organic Compounds (SVOCs) (mainly plasticizers) with field study data, suitability of dust exposure for human RA, systematic review of plasticizer sources and concentrations in European

² AMD-101057014-80: The affiliated entity "DTU National Food Institute" sent the request to the Coordinator to change its PARC acronym "DTU Food" in "DTU". The acronym DTU Food was replaced by DTU in the WPs where they are contributors.

indoor environments) and outdoor environment (eg. Exposure to Cadmium arising from fertilizer, Metal hotspot in Slovenia and in Belgium near an industrial site, Exposure to lead from soils using isotope Pb, PFAS hotspots in Belgium, Role of aerial deposition of PFAS on the environment and subsequent human exposure signature) and new ones were initiated.

The project, [P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES] focuses on estimating aggregate exposure from various sources and routes for both occupational and general populations. During the year, the project continued development and application of the aggregate exposure strategy, including a decision tree for aggregating sources and routes, and approaches for population-based and worker-based exposure. They performed a deeper investigation of data and models for each case study, with bibliographical research to construct dedicated databases. They continued integration of more sources and routes into the strategy, supported by sub-working group meetings held every two months on: Pyrethroids in occupational environment, Metals Cd in consumer products, Metals Cd in general and occupational environments, PFAS in general and occupational environments and in consumer products, and Plasticisers in occupational environment. A procedure to link exposure model outputs and integrating variability and uncertainty was developed. This project continues to advance the understanding and assessment of aggregate exposure through extensive collaboration and methodological development.

In the context of [P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM] HBM data from European studies were harmonized and uploaded to the MCRA software, enabling progress on case studies. Hazard data were collected and organized, and statistical analyses were implemented in MCRA. The strategy developed to perform mixture risk assessment was applied to HBM datasets from 10 European Member States, covering various chemicals and effects. During year 3, the strategy was applied to HBM dataset from 10 European Member States: 15 data sets for heavy metals and kidney effects, 15 data sets for heavy metals and DNT, 9 data sets for CAG NAM and CAG NAMS, 21 data sets for PFAS and immune effects.

Within PARC, collaborations have been established with projects under A6.2.1. and T8.2 to utilize chemical information for aggregated exposure assessment and EWS. Contacts with T4.2 were made to address the urgent need for data on mono-n-hexyl phthalate activated in the context of the rapid response mechanism. Outside PARC, collaborations have focused on national authorities responsible for enforcing chemicals legislation, the ECHA forum for enforcement, and the group of five member states (SE, NO, GE, NE, DE) responsible for the PFAS restriction proposal. In response to an urgent request from the GB to address the enforcement of the PFAS restriction proposal, a new project (P6.4.3b_Y3_ENFORCE_KEMI) was initiated in 2024, with regular biweekly meetings involving partners.

RA

The work done in Task 6.1 "integrative approach for testing and assessment" is closely related to regulatory RA, necessitating active involvement of regulatory partners to ensure outcomes meet regulatory needs. Periodic meetings were held between project managers and representatives of ECHA, EFSA, and JRC, either jointly or separately, depending on the topic.

The international collaborations are also important with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Health and Environmental Sciences Institute (HESI), ILMERAC (International Liaison group on Methods for RA of Chemicals in food). A collaboration with the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) was initiated to use utilize their organ-on-a-chip system Emulate.

Projects under Task 6.1 have for objectives to assess the relevance of AOPs and NAMs related to key events and key event relationships. The project collaborates with other complementary ongoing EU projects. The work resulted in a refined definition of biological considerations and improved templates. Comprehensive weight of evidence assessments was started.

For endocrine disruption, the work was divided into two subgroups focusing on 1) Thyroid hormone system disruption and 2) Anti-androgenicity. An overview of relevant AOPs was created and continuously updated for each endpoint. Relevant methods were mapped to the AOP networks and conceptual models.

For genotoxicity, various non-animal tools are available or under development, and some of them have been used for regulatory purposes for some time now. A draft AOP network was developed based on AOPs present in the AOP-Wiki or in literature and an inventory of non-animal methods for genotoxicity was compiled. Development of the AOP network and quantitative modelling of different Key Event Relationships (KERs) within this network are on-going.

For systemic organ toxicity, the project is focusing on liver fibrosis and complements activities performed in project RISK-HUNT3R. The project made significant progress in the development of the IATA for liver toxicity.

ID	Project Title
P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM	Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated NAMs
P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Endocrine Disruption
P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Genotoxicity
P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Systemic Target Organ Toxicity

Under T6.2, the project P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPB_INERIS focuses on refining and developing PBPB models for human RA and mixtures RA. The aim is to address the sensitivity of different population sub-groups, aggregate multiple exposure routes, and interpret HBM data and chemical mixtures. The project studies several prioritized chemical families: PFAS, pesticides, metals, bisphenols, and mycotoxins. The project continued to describe physiology changes across developmental stage, to integrate gender specific differences, develop and refine PBPB models for prioritized compounds. The description of in utero exposure and placental transfer processes, including transfer across the blood-brain barrier. The work done in collaboration with T8.3. on the harmonisation and incorporation of models has made good progress.

The project [P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM] developed a strategy for RA of real-life chemical mixtures, organized around prioritizing mixtures, collecting and organizing HBM and hazard data, and performing mixture RAs. Five case studies were performed:

- pesticides causing brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition (CAG-NAN);
- pesticides causing functional alterations of the motor division (CAG-NAM);
- PFAS and immune effect;
- heavy metals and kidney effects;
- heavy metals and Developmental Neurotoxicity (DNT) (IQ loss).

Training sessions were provided to partners and stakeholders, including EFSA, on using HBM data in mixture RAs.

ID	Project Title
P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO	Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies

P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES	Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures
P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS_AUTH	Refinement and development of PBPK models for human RA
P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures _RIVM	New RA and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures

Concerning, products and materials, the project P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU evaluates information on substances in products and materials for enforcement activities and life cycle assessments. Surveys and interviews with enforcement agencies identified gaps and needs, leading to the development of project P6.4.3.b_Y3_KEMI and a case study on mono-n-hexyl phthalate, addressing urgent data needs expressed via the PARC rapid response mechanism. An inventory of chemical databases was completed and submitted as a scientific paper, initiating further actions in 2024. The case study on mono-n-hexyl phthalate evaluated existing information structures and tracked data for regulatory and enforcement purposes, supporting empirical measurements in environmental and human matrices. Additionally, the project reviewed information structures for life cycle assessments, evaluated the impact of data quality on Life-cycle assessment (LCA) toxicity assessment, and identified areas for improvement. A case study on plasticizers in vinyl flooring demonstrated links between databases and LCA models.

The collective results provide a comprehensive picture of data sources and methodologies for assessing chemicals in products and materials, guiding future development of information structures. These insights are relevant for enforcement agencies and regulatory initiatives, such as the SCiP database and digital product passports under the Ecodesign and Sustainability Products Regulation.

The project "P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KEMI" aims to develop proof-of-concept methods for chemical identification to support the enforcement of chemical safety legislation. This project specifically focuses on additives in high-volume plastics and PFAS in various articles, addressing crucial needs identified in project 6.4.3a.

During 2024, significant progress was made in developing a systematic workflow for compliance testing of a broad PFAS restriction. This workflow, created through workshops with analytical scientists, regulators, and inspectors from Sweden, Norway, and Finland, includes a tiered approach using total fluorine measurement, organic fluorine screening, and target screening methods. Empirical testing of these methods was conducted on various articles, including treated textiles, packaging, electronic components, and chemical products. An inter-laboratory comparison for a subset of these articles was initiated and is expected to be completed in 2025.

HIA

Under task 6.2, the project on Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD) and Health Impact Assessment (HIA) focused on several key activities. The central hub, P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS, coordinated with other linked projects to gather data for EBD calculations, address methodological hurdles, and develop indicators. During 2024, the selection criteria for case studies were refined to prioritize EBD/HIA estimates, integrate health costs, consider multiple health effects, and focus on PARC-prioritized health effects (endocrine disruption, neurotoxicity and immunotoxicity). Several case studies were initiated or further developed, including studies on pyrethroid exposure and Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), heavy metals and cancer, arsenic exposure and cancers, lead exposure and cardiovascular diseases and chronic disease, influence of waste co-incineration in a cement plant on cancer burden, lead (Pb) and methylmercury (meHg) and IQ loss in Children in Europe.

ID	Project Title
P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADataAvailability_VITO	Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS	Improvement of HIA methodologies
P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS	Case studies on HIA
P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO	Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators

Under Task 6.3, several reviews of RA methodologies have been started to evaluate the state of the art of different regulations, (Cosmetic product regulation, Biocide product regulation, REACH), and understand differences and similarities. They are based on the substances' intended use across legislations, the effect specific RA (endocrine disruption, genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, developmental neurotoxicity, and skin sensitisation), and the tools, criteria and methods used, also including RA for the occupational setting.

The different case studies have significantly progressed in their mapping exercise.

Case Study number	Case Study Title
P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU: Review of substance-specific RA	
CS12_MethodOSOA_SU	Methods to identify coordination needs towards a 'one substance one assessment' approach.
CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL	Identification of differences and loopholes in the regulation of plastic additives
CS14_BiocidesRA_SU	Identification of loopholes for substances with biocidal properties.
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI: Review of effect-specific RA	
CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH	Skin sensitisation and RA methodologies
CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB	Evaluation of RA approaches used for cosmetic ingredients with endocrine-disrupting (ED) concern
CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS	Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches.
CS15_DNT_SU	Evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies
CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI	Use of non-guideline in vitro studies for ED assessments
CS18_ED-classes_BPI	New hazard classes and test requirements for endocrine disruption
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU: Review of tools, criteria, and methods used in RA	
CS1_CARB_SYKE	Comparative analysis of risk-based decision benchmarks in the EU regulatory frameworks
CS2_RiskReduction_SU	Identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of RA for reducing risk.
CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL	Use of regulatory information in workplace chemical RA
CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS	Assessment of the approaches used to address secondary poisoning under current chemical

	regulations and identification of possible improvements needed to achieve an adequate protection of wildlife
CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG	Protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations: Differences and similarities of prospective and retrospective RA for pesticides
CS8_OccupReproDev_KI	A review of guidance values targeting occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants
CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND	Practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment
CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU (new case study year 2)	Status of chemical data gap filling approaches across EU regulations

Work done under Task 6.4 will also promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of NAMs for use in chemical RA for human health. Interviews and online survey with chemical risk assessors has been undertaken and used to conduct an in-depth analysis to identify the key factors and drivers for a successful implementation of NAMs in regulatory RA practice.

The project [P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapSurvey_UNIBAS] aims to facilitate the use and regulatory acceptance of NAMs in chemical RA. It involved a scoping exercise and expert consultation through literature reviews, interviews, and surveys. The project identified the current status and barriers to NAMs integration.

The project [P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRA_applied in practice_NIPH_VKM] focus on implementing systematic review methodology in chemical RA. It includes three sub-projects: creating a tool for evaluating the internal validity of in vitro studies (INVITES-IN), translating core terms of chemical RA into systematic review language, and developing a tool for evaluating the external validity of in vitro studies.

The project [P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT] project involves four parts] conducted a survey on the readiness of computational NAMs using Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for RA, with results being analysed. The review part of the project is collecting experiences on ML and AI QSAR NAMs for hazard identification, aiming to develop a framework for transparent reporting of AI/ML predictions. The analysis and case studies part included studies on environmental and human health endpoints using ML models, providing examples of transparent model predictions.

ID	Project Title
P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS	Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU regulatory RA landscape
P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH	Next generation RA applied in practice
P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT	Landscape and readiness of computational NAMs based on advanced AI and ML approaches for chemicals' next generation RA

Environmental RA

Under WP6, several projects and scoping activities have been launched to develop environmental RA methods that support and promote efficient identification of mixtures, overall protection of biodiversity, several projects are on-going.

In T6.3, case studies in the project P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU: Review of tools, criteria, and methods used in RA assess the current environmental RA.

Case Study number	Case Study Title
CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS	Assessment of the approaches used to address secondary poisoning under current chemical regulations and identification of possible improvements needed to achieve an adequate protection of wildlife
CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG	Protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations: Differences and similarities of prospective and retrospective RA for pesticides

Under T6.4 several projects aim at better assessing effects on overall biodiversity and the possibility to simplify (i.e. less resource demanding) the methods used for the environmental RA (ERA). The projects are:

- exploring the ways to simplify PEC calculations within the environmental RA frameworks;
- developing a protective environmental RA with reduced complexity and resources including only the information and processes proved to be relevant by ecosystem monitoring and effect modelling;
- ensuring that results of any independently performed environmental RA for a Plant Protection Product (PPP) can be used as a benchmark for other PPPs;
- developing and exploring how landscape-based environmental RA integrating landscape structures and aggregated (several crops) and combined (several pesticides) exposures can be used to improve the current RA methods;
- aiming to promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of NAMs for use in chemical RA for the environment;
- advancing the regulatory assessment of unintentional mixtures in the environment.

ID	Project Title
P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIX CS2_UFZ	Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory RAs through the use of monitoring data and NAMs
P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIB AS	Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU regulatory RA landscape
P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT	Landscape and readiness of computational NAMS based on advanced AI and ML approaches for chemicals' next generation RA
P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI	Clarify regulatory needs – Transform EU strategies into regulatory useable research projects
P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXP CS2_SLU	Reduce complexity of models for predicted environmental concentrations of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity
P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFF CS3_UFZ	Reduce complexity of models for predictions of environmental effects of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity

P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_RPTU ³	Benchmark ERA to support the transition towards a holistic paradigm
P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII	Quantify effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape RA informing on environmental impacts

Integrative modelling and RA

Concerning RA of mixture, Task 6.4 will support the regulatory RA and handling of chemical mixtures in Europe with several projects. Case studies have been initiated to test different approaches to handle mixture in different regulatory areas and to provide results of the usefulness (or lack thereof) of the Mixture Allocation Factor (MAF) in other regulatory areas beyond REACH.

Under this activity, three projects are ongoing: “Optimizing regulatory RA and RM of chemical mixtures in Europe” (P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_RWTH_OPREMIX) and “Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory RA through the use of monitoring data and NAMs” (P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ_MONAMMIX), Skin sensitization – effect of mixtures, current practices, and gaps (P6.4.1.c.Y3_CS_RegH_SKINSEN) has started in May 2024.

The 6 case studies of the project [P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_RWTH_OPREMIX] have progressed and delivered a policy brief in May 2024, some presentations in congress and the writing of publications.

The 9 case studies of the project (P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ_MONAMMIX) have also progressed in the review of methodologies, creation of curated mode of action database, development of a mixture risk indicator, review pollution in different locations (rivers, arctic marine environment), identify new mixtures in drinking water.

The HBM4EU central data platform was supported as the PEH data platform. A software tool for schema-based harmonization and data validation was developed and improved, allowing data providers to prepare their datasets for end-to-end data exchange with the MCRA modelling platform. This tool supports harmonization and quality control of newly generated datasets added to the PEH platform or IPCHEM.

Under WP6 and in close collaboration with WP4, HBM data from European studies were harmonized and uploaded to the MCRA software, enabling progress on case studies. Hazard data were collected and organized, and statistical analyses were implemented in MCRA. The strategy was applied to HBM datasets from 10 European Member States, covering various chemicals and effects. During year 3, the strategy was applied to HBM dataset from 10 European Member States: 15 data sets for heavy metals and kidney effects, 15 data sets for heavy metals and DNT, 9 data sets for CAG NAM and CAG NAMS, 21 data sets for PFAS and immune effects.

Training sessions were provided to partners and stakeholders, including EFSA, on using HBM data in mixture RAs.

New approach methodologies

Work began on harmonized templates for standard toxicological data, with existing templates used for short-term internal data exchange and long-term templates being developed. List of in vitro methods in relation with AOPs and IATAs were identified. The regulatory readiness of assays

³ AMD-101057014-80: The University of Koblenz-Landau (UKOLD) has terminated as affiliated entity of the Beneficiary UBA on 01/01/2023. The University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU), former Technical University of Kaiserslautern (UKL) remains an affiliated entity of BfR (as it has the same PIC number) but now gathers the parts assigned to the Campus Landau. The contributions and obligations of the former University of Koblenz-Landau to PARC were taken over by RPTU from 01/01/2023.

performed by partners were assessed by partners under WP5. PARC collaborates with the AOP community and contributes in the update of the AOPwiki and associated tools.

An action on FAIRification of omics data was identified, with a working group established to create a workplan for omics data reuse. The metadata capture template for in vitro studies was refined and tested.

The Working Group on PBK modelling collaborates with the T8.3 to harmonise and incorporate models in the toolboxes. Some of them were also included in the SSbD developed under WP8.1.

The mapping of exposure models is ongoing through extensive collaboration and methodological development.

Specific objective 3:

- Strengthening existing capacities and building new transdisciplinary platforms to support chemical RA.

OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA

Under T8.1, concerning operationalization of the SSbD framework, efforts have focused on developing an efficient communication plan and infrastructure for effective interaction between science, policy, and users. This included dialogues with the EC, stakeholders, and the chemical industry to identify gaps, barriers, and incentives for the EC Joint Research Center (JRC) framework. In-depth interviews and focus groups with 10 companies provided insights into their approaches to safety and sustainability.

The computational implementation of the SSbD toolbox was carried out, resulting in version 0.1, which includes a comprehensive list of tools and databases for safety and sustainability assessments. The toolbox's primary interface, server infrastructure, and key functionalities were established, ensuring smooth user interaction and connectivity with external tools. A new SSbD Wizard was developed to guide users through the assessment process, and an SSbD scoring system was introduced to convert assessment outcomes into scores.

Test cases were defined to test the applicability of the EC SSbD criteria and methodology, engaging stakeholders along the value chain. The second iteration of the BPA and alternatives case study was conducted to extract key learnings and provide feedback for toolbox development. Knowledge sharing and education efforts focused on developing a systematic approach for SSbD knowledge sharing and training within PARC and with external stakeholders. A report on stakeholder needs for SSbD was published, and a manuscript for a peer-reviewed publication is in preparation to outline SSbD learning goals and address core knowledge and skills related to chemical innovation.

Under T8.2, standardized protocols for EWS tools are also being developed, focusing on suspect/non-targeted/EDA-based tools for environmental and human samples, with detailed protocols for effect-based monitoring of suspended particulate matter and wastewater. Metabolomics-based biomarkers and computational tools, including AI methods and bioinformatics algorithms, have been defined. A literature analysis of existing AI systems in EWS is ongoing.

Efforts include selecting databases with chemical structure and identifier information to develop methods for identifying and prioritizing new substances. Emphasis is on Big Data Analytics for processing large data volumes in real-time. Two case studies [Suspended particulate matter in German rivers, fish for food consumption in Greek rivers] have been initiated to validate early warning monitoring tools and a prioritization framework.

The EWS computational system concept involves systematic searches for NERCs using data mining and curation. A systematic scoring system for ranking substances is being developed. The AOP-helpFinder tool was updated to assist researchers, and stakeholder mapping and questionnaires were devised to evaluate needs and expectations. Work on the policy interface of the EWS includes evaluating synergies and differences between PARC and EU EWS, with guidelines for adopting NTS and effect-based data being developed.

In T8.3, the development of the general framework for integrating models was guided by user requirements from case studies, other PARC projects, and external stakeholder feedback. The conceptual framework, covering the source to effect and impacts continuum, was refined iteratively for various modeling activities, including exposure assessment, toxicokinetic simulation, HBM exposure assessment, QSAR modeling, and RA. Initial efforts focused on identifying domains and model classes, outlining key entities and properties, and mapping modeling tools to workflows and user requirements. Harmonization of conceptual models across domains was initiated.

For the technical framework, a focus group defined components for model interoperability and workflow connections. Automatic interfacing between modeling tools was explored using Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). The inventory of modeling tools was updated, and integration with the PARC data hub was explored. Work began on developing a general interface for accessing the model network. Several case studies are ongoing to evaluate and guide the development of individual models and platforms.

OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new analytical, toxicological and fit-for-purpose networks of laboratories and research centres

PARC is consolidating already existing analytical, toxicological and fit-for purpose networks of laboratories and research centers but it will also develop new ones.

During the first year of PARC the activities of T9.1 have focused on (i) the extension of the network on HBM laboratories in the framework of PARC capitalising on the work done in the HBM4EU initiative, in which the first European network of HBM laboratories was built; and (ii) the mapping and cataloguing of the first inventory of air quality monitoring laboratories. As a result of these activities, a total of 240 HBM laboratories and 65 laboratories focusing on air quality monitoring have been included in the PARC laboratory catalogues (see D9.1).

Consultations with WPs on laboratory networking needs and existing networks were ongoing, especially with WP4 on HBM and environmental monitoring. The structure and characteristics of laboratory catalogues were defined and the first catalogue provided and accessible. This laboratory networks is created by field, starting with HBM laboratories, followed by air and water domains. For HBM laboratories, a detailed questionnaire was designed and implemented, and an interactive laboratory map was launched in May 2024. For air laboratories, a questionnaire was designed and launched in October 2024 to collect analytical capacities. An advertisement was published to invite European laboratories to join the network. Work on water laboratories began with a survey in February 2024, but response rates were low. A working group was formed to design a specific questionnaire and attract more laboratories. Efforts to expand networks included social media publications and contacts with existing networks like AQUILA and NORMAN.

Work on the (eco)toxicological laboratory network started early, with a survey designed to collect information on capacities.

Other activities focused on developing networking activities and promoting less developed networks. Initial coordination activities were defined, but implementation is ongoing.

A transversal activity in task 9.3 on harmonisation of quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) of laboratory analysis is organized into five working groups (WGs), four focusing on chemical

analyses and one on toxicity testing. Each WG completed an inventory of existing definitions, protocols, and criteria, emphasizing chemicals, application domains, and techniques used in WP4 and WP5. They also prepared the first draft of guidance documents.

Task 9.3 interacted with WP4 to align on laboratory approval and comparability for HBM studies and reporting formats. Input was provided for the PARC website, and synergies with external networks and projects were explored through online meetings.

0013: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA

PARC WP9 held three in-person training courses on FAIR data and databases, Chemicals Exposure and Modelling, and Health RA of Chemicals, as well as a SSbD Boot Camp. WP9 also developed also e-learning materials, including video presentations, a FAQ sheet on standardized sample collection, and an e-book on *in silico* models and read-across tools. These materials will be part of a training library under development. The mechanism for staff exchange was disseminated at the Consortium Meeting and in the PARC Sampler, with identified funding opportunities for trainees.

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per WP

1.2.0 Summary per task

The deliverables of PARC approved by HaDEA are available on the PARC website: [Deliverables | Parc](#)

➤ WP1

T1.1: Overall executive management and support of the Partnership

- All the PARC consortium and governance bodies met according to the calendar fixed in the deliverable D1.2 “PARC governance process timeline” and properly followed the procedures for the preparation of the deliverables and additional deliverables due for the period M21-M32, including the AWPY3 due M24, the AWPY4 due M32, and this ASR for Y3 due M32.

- The PARC CT organised the PARC Consortium meeting at University UMIT TIROL -University for Health Sciences and Technology, Hall in Tirol city Austria, on 13-16 May 2024. Meetings of the Governance Bodies (online and physical) took place regularly over the period M21-M32 (11 MB meetings, 2 GB meetings and 1 GSB meeting).

- The preparation with the partners of the first PTFR of PARC (M1-M18) officially started in September 2023 (M17) and ended in March 2024 (M23). The PTFR was validated by HaDEA in August 2024 (M28) and the first interim payment was distributed to all Beneficiaries and Affiliated Entities in August 2024. The review meeting with HaDEA and external experts took place in April 2024 (M24).

-The PARC CT launched the PARC Junior Community on January 2024.

- The PARC CT with the MB wrote a collaboration agreement with NORMAN which was signed by Anses on behalf of the Consortium on 11th of December.

- An amendment of the GA was launched in autumn 2024. A new amendment of the GA was submitted to HaDEA during the period in order to include new PARC partners and proceed to the related changes in resources and budget of PARC.

T1.2: Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans

- The PARC CT submitted the AWPY3 in February 2024 (D1.8) which included the PARC project Porte-Folio. The ASRY3 (D1.9) was prepared by the PARC CT, the MB and TLs and the PMs and was submitted in December 2024. The AWPY4 (D1.10) is being prepared by the PARC CT, the MB, the TLs and the Project managers for submission in January 2025. The PARC CT ensured the submission of the deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones due during period M21-M32 to the EC with the required justification in case of delay.

- The processes for the review of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones and projects were applied by the PARC partners during the period in order to ensure the quality and proper follow-up of the contractual documents.

T1.3: Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership

- The indicators framework (output, outcome, impact indicators) has been further refined in collaboration with the MB, GSB and the GB and presented with positive feedback during the May 2024 Consortium Meeting, NHs and stakeholders. Data collection has been initiated early 2024 through the WP co-leaders (WPLs) for the output indicators.

- T1.3 has continued to work in order to improve the set of indicators (output, outcome and impact) in collaboration with the MB, GSB and the GB, NHs and stakeholders. This has led to the definition of a list of 12 output, 8 outcome and 8 impact indicators in the indicator framework. In M21-M32, T1.3 notably focused on refining outcome and impact indicators. This cohesive indicator framework was outlined during the Consortium Meeting in May 2024 in the general assembly as well as discussed during the dedicated NHCPs meeting and the GB meeting. Preparatory work for the collection of data for outcome and impact indicators are underway for a collection in early 2025.

T1.4: Ethics framework

The monitoring of ethics issues and production of relevant reports was facilitated through several tasks and Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB) meetings in 2024. Shared digital infrastructure has been set-up on the PARC SharePoint to facilitate access to and review of ethics documents in line with the guidelines provided to the PARC partners. An ethics workshop has also been organised end of 2024 to sensibilise partners to ethics issues and outline PARC ethics guidelines.

➤ WP2

T2.1: Priority setting

- Project Review Process: the project review process was successfully applied to all existing projects and new project proposals for Year 4, ensuring thorough evaluation and transparency. A total of 90 projects were reviewed by around 100 reviewers from 15 different organizations, including updates to project descriptions and systematic follow-up through a project portfolio.

- Second Prioritization Round: it was conducted to identify and document the needs for future PARC activities through fact sheets, which were scored and refined in collaboration with WPLs and TLs. These needs will steer future activities and priorities for Years 4 to 7.

- Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM): it was initiated in response to a request related to Mono-n-Hexyl Phthalate (MnHexP) exposure in children, leading to the launch of a new project in collaboration with Task 4.1 (biomonitoring), Task 4.2 (environmental data), and Task 6.2 (source modeling).

T2.2: Knowledge management and uptake to policy

- Successful establishment and further development of the PARCopedia platform since November 2023. It has since grown significantly, with almost 900 registered users by the end of September 2024. The platform has continued to evolve with improvements in functionality and the creation of internal processes for content generation and community building. Establishment of groups for EDCs and nanomaterials and PARCopedia wiki articles prepared for the chemicals and methodologies.

- NGRARoute roadmap activity: development of guiding principles for a future NGRA network and identification of work streams and tasks for the further work on a roadmap to establish NGRA in EU chemicals legislation, summarised in Deliverable AD2.1.

- Establishment of collaborative structure with the EU Commission's work on a "Roadmap towards phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments" and with other stakeholders.

- New CLs and MLs were nominated for nanomaterials, microplastics and NGRA after a call. Individual annual work plans were established for the CL/ML work.

T2.3: Sustainability and exit strategy

- Finalization of the survey on the exit strategy in early 2024 sent to the NHs involved in Task 2.3.

- Key areas for post-PARC sustainability, such as HBM, toxicology, and environmental monitoring, while recommending central EU coordination for these activities were identified.

- Discussions have been scheduled with WPLs and TLs to better know their visions on the exit strategy and prepare a physical meeting in early 2025.

- The 2nd survey on NHs led to an expansion of the NH network to 430 organizations by mid-2024. This survey helped to identify ongoing challenges, such as resource limitations and stakeholder engagement, while sharing good practices through NH meetings and supporting future sustainability efforts.

- Continuous dialogue with the NHCPs was maintained in 2024 through the annual survey mapping the needs of the NHs, the NHCP meeting and the PARCopedia group created for the NHCPs. These initiatives facilitated ongoing communication and translated NH needs into actionable steps through discussions during the two NHCP meetings. For example, the annual survey, which was completed by 27 out of 28 NHs, revealed key insights on challenges such as resource limitations, engaging non-scientific members, and securing co-funding for HBM studies. Based on these findings, the NHCP meetings in Austria and Belgium provided a platform for discussing good practices and sharing national success stories, contributing to the overall development of the NHs.

➤ WP3

T3.1: Building effective interactions

- IB members provided input on selected PARC activities including the prioritization process and general recommendations on improving international collaborations and PARC's exit strategy, among others.

- Following several consultations valuable feedback was provided by SF members on the future PARC activities and prioritization process. This was communicated to the MB.
- By holding online meetings and the annual (hybrid) meeting, closely working together with the elected SF co-chair, the dialogue with members of the SF was conducted, their needs identified and addressed in the best possible way.

T3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness

- The implementation of the activities foreseen in the communication and dissemination strategy has continued as foreseen. The PARC social media channels on LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram and X have been regularly updated with new content, including progress updates, interviews and results. Eight Science Digest Newsletters and two PARC Sampler newsletters were issued. Public project deliverables and the links to all peer-reviewed publications produced under the projects were made available via the PARC website.
- The information populated on the website was enriched with visualisation of (i) research projects, (ii) HBM laboratories on an interactive map, (iii) output indicators, and the functionality to create surveys directly. indicators, and the functionality to create directly surveys.
- Outreach activities were reinforced with the organisation of focus group discussions in five countries.
- The exhibition entitled “Healthy Horizons: Our Journey to Create a Safer Chemical World” took place during the Consortium meeting. It gave the opportunity to partners, SF, IB and GB members and representatives of external activities to interact and learn more about PARC activities, projects and outputs.

T3.3: Networking and Synergies

- Two “Workshops on Synergies with External Initiatives” were organized at the Consortium Meeting (in person) and in November 2024 (online).
- Two SYNnet forums took place back-to-back with International Conferences.
- Through the above activities and from expressions of interest received from external Projects, potential new synergies were identified and the work to promote the establishment of collaborations and synergies continued.
- A collaboration agreement with NORMAN was concluded. Collaboration with JRC also continues.
- Potential new synergies were identified and the work to promote the establishment of collaborations and synergies continued. Two SYNnet forums took place back-to-back with international conferences (list the conferences) and webinars with EU projects were organized (list the cluster projects).

➤ WP4

T4.1: Human Biomonitoring

- In the general survey, many countries have started sample collection while others finished for different age groups.
- The final selection of biomarkers of exposure for the PARC Aligned Studies has been done. The first round of PARC QA/QC was completed and the second round is ongoing.

- Occupational studies are progressing well, with protocols finalized, training materials prepared, and ethical approvals obtained in several countries. Sampling campaigns are expected to be fully underway by early 2025.

T4.2: Environmental and multisource monitoring

- Coordinated monitoring campaigns on EDCs and PFAS have started to establish the overall process for environmental and multisource monitoring, integrating state-of-the-art methods and building networks and infrastructures for future monitoring.

- A project has started to improve our knowledge of chemicals of concern in the living environment, supporting the HBM PARC aligned studies and linking internal to external human exposure.

- A prototype of an online tool for prioritisation of chemicals has been developed.

T4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

- Innovative methods have and will push the human and environmental exposure assessment forward by identifying the chemicals to focus on in future monitoring, enabling fingerprinting of chemical mixtures, and improving sampling techniques in HBM.

➤ WP5

T5.1: Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern

- Data collection continued, focused on prioritized BPA alternatives and mycotoxins. Concerning activities on natural toxins, an ongoing dialogue has been put in place between project managers and EFSA, in order to keep EFSA updated about the progress of the work done, to facilitate the uptake of the results into EFSA assessments.

- A Call for tender for our first TG+ study (TG+ enniatin B1) has been published and the Contract Research Organization (CRO) selection is being finalized.

- Concerning environmental health, data collection for the natural toxins project (cyanotoxins) was finalized and continued for prioritized BPA alternatives, considering now mixtures.

T5.2: Task 5.2. Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

- For the hazard identification, the development of innovative methodologies continued on the five endpoints for human health: immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid) and metabolic disruption and for ecotoxicology based on i) in silico and modelling tools, ii) invertebrate animal models, iii) vertebrate models and iv) complex microbial community, leading to a proposal of a new project on regulatory readiness.

- A whitepaper on regulatory readiness and how to improve regulatory readiness of NAMs in PARC was published.

T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs

- All case studies made progress over the year.

- In year 3, the Core Group (CG) with expertise in methods for AOP development & the three Specialty Groups (SG) and the Effect Markers Group (EMG) including subgroups continued their

activities. The SGs and EMG finalized the inventory on the available AOPs and identified the AOPs that they considered to be their priorities for further development or for build-up.

- Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) data was generated in the case studies.

➤ WP6

T6.1: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals

- Active and fruitful collaborations were established with JRC, OECD, and related research initiatives RISK-HUNT3R and EURION.

- More frequent in-depth discussions took place with ECHA, EFSA and JRC on the different projects, to ensure regulatory relevance as well as applicability of the results achieved.

T6.2: Integrative exposure and RA

- HBM data were harmonized and incorporated in PARCToolBox. The developed methodologies for mixture and aggregate exposure and health impact assessment were applied to prioritized case studies such as PFAS, metals, pesticides and phthalates. Kinetic models were further developed and parametrized for identified gaps and needs for human lifelong exposure including sensitive populations (in view of case studies). In collaboration with T8.3, models were further implemented in PARC tool toolbox (eg. MCRA) and/or in Systems Biology Markup Language for FAIR PBK models. Scientific publications were started.

- Meetings and webinars were organized to present the methodology, tools and progress of the case studies under the respective projects, including regulatory context and relevance as well as stakeholder interactions. Representatives from EFSA, EEA, JRC, ECHA and DG SANTE, ENVI and GROW were invited to these events and bilateral discussions were also started to work closer together in the current and future projects.

T6.3: Review of RA methodologies

- Case studies reviewing selected methodologies and approaches for regulatory RA has been further implemented and refined. During the reporting period, two case studies were finalized; CS14 (P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU - CS14_BiocidesRA_SU - Identification of loopholes for substances with biocidal properties,) finalized in M24 and CS19 P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU - CS19_DataGapFilling_DTU- Status of filling data gaps approach across EU regulations) finalized in M30. Conclusions and recommendations for these 2 case studies will be shared within the policy/regulatory community beginning of 2025. One additional case study, CS20 (Understanding the implementation and use of NAMs in pesticide dossier in both the human health and environment, was initiated in M25.

- Meetings were organized to present and discuss the progress of the case studies under the respective projects, including regulatory context and relevance as well as stakeholder interactions. Representatives from ECHA, EFSA, EEA, and JRC were invited to the meetings.

T6.4: Transposing results to regulatory RA methodologies

- Active collaboration and discussions of regulatory relevance with regulatory bodies has continued and been further developed, for example with ECHA, EFSA, national authorities and

ECHA FORUM.

- Mapping and landscaping of regulatory gaps and needs has been further developed and/or concluded, for example in the areas of mixtures, use of NAMs, enforcement and ERA.

➤ WP7

T7.1: FAIR Data Policy and implementation

- Finalisation of a scientific paper on the PARC FAIR data policy.
- Finalisation of the train the trainer sessions and cohort of FAIR Facilitators qualified.
- Training of data liaisons/PARC community on FAIR data implementation.
- Implementation of running versions of Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), under the ELIXIR, as the online Data Management Plan (DMP) platform.

T7.2: Data libraries

- Finalization of landscaping of existing databases and data platforms and making available the analysis of their FAIRness ongoing for domains other than HBM.
- Milestone achievement – PARC DataHub Architecture.
- Toxicology cluster established and running effectively to create reference FIPs for toxicology space including landscape mapping and available FAIR enabling resources covering also omics data, imaging data and AOPs.
- Implementation of identified data management use cases and ongoing identification of new use cases).
- Enrichment of the set of controlled vocabularies at PARC level, as well as domain-specific standards.
- First steps towards implementation of cross-domain interoperability framework (CDIF) for CRA.
- Consolidation and reporting on the approaches, tools and instruments developed in the first three years.

T7.3: Innovative analyses

Efforts to implement and identify use cases for statistical and analytical techniques are actively underway, with a focus on developing user guidelines and demonstrating the utility of these approaches through selected use cases. The task has successfully completed a gap analysis of uncertainty assessment methodologies and applied these findings to domain-specific cases. Initial benchmarking and scoping of data mining and AI/ML tools have been partially achieved, contributing to the development of a harmonized FAIR evidence representation framework. Additionally, work has started on building a consistent FAIR data exchange schema to integrate information from diverse sources and on harmonizing ontology use in text mining for AOP development. Enrichment of existing background knowledge resources through multi-modal data analysis is also progressing, enhancing the overall knowledge base for chemical risk assessment.

➤ WP8

T8.1: Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)

- Task 8.1 has achieved significant progress in fostering a science-policy-user interface for SSbD innovation:

- Test cases, including a study on BPA and its alternatives, provided valuable insights for toolbox refinement, while computational tools were tested to inform future development. Knowledge-sharing initiatives, such as a platform for education and training, were launched to support stakeholders both within and beyond PARC. A survey of stakeholder needs was reported, and a manuscript outlining contributions to a learning agenda on SSbD was prepared, emphasizing goals, target audiences, and key competencies for advancing chemical innovation. These efforts collectively strengthen the foundation for integrating SSbD into innovation processes and regulatory frameworks. In particular main achievements are:

- Continued inclusive dialogue with the EC users, and stakeholders inside and outside PARC, identifying gaps, barriers, and incentives related to the JRC framework.
- Conducted in-depth interviews and focus groups with 10 chemical companies to understand their approaches to safety and sustainability in innovation processes from an SSbD perspective.
- Released version 0.1 of the SSbD toolbox, featuring an extensive list of safety and sustainability tools and relevant databases accessible via the main interface (<https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/>).
- Completed test cases encompassing tools for different SSbD steps, defining use cases to test the applicability of EC SSbD criteria and methodology while engaging stakeholders along the value chain.
- Gained initial experience with running selected computational tools, identifying important questions for future development of the toolbox.
- Established a knowledge-sharing platform on SSbD.
- Developed an efficient communication plan and infrastructure blueprint for an effective science-policy-user interface.

T8.2: Scientific and technical basis for an EWS on chemical risks

- Collaborative efforts resulted in development of detailed protocols for early warning monitoring tools with a particular focus on Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) and wastewater.

- Key advancements include defining metabolomics-based biomarkers, supported by computational tools utilizing AI and advanced bioinformatics for their interpretation in line with introducing NAMs in the RA process. A literature analysis of existing AI systems was conducted to assess their reliability and usefulness. Additional databases were selected to facilitate the development of computational methods for systematic identification and prioritization which was continued. Existing studies were reviewed to identify potential case studies for validating EWS tools humans and products and two case studies were initiated.

- Additionally, databases were identified and integrated to support computational methods for identifying NERCs. Big Data analytics were leveraged for real-time processing of complex datasets. A systematic scoring system for chemical ranking was developed, incorporating multicriteria decision analysis while identifying knowledge gaps for future EWS design.

- Efforts to align policy with technical progress included stakeholder engagement to align outputs with needs and harmonize PARC tools with EU EWS developments. Furthermore, the AOP-helpFinder tool was updated to assist researchers in capturing relevant existing data to develop new Adverse Outcome Pathway. The policy working group developed guidelines for the adoption of non- NTS and effect-based data and contribute to a publication within Task 4.3 on handling signals in an EWS.

T8.3: Integrative models

Task 8.3 contributed to enhancing FAIR data sharing and model integration within the PARC framework by participating in WP7 steering and semantic implementation teams. It established technical components and levels of interoperability for data exchange, interfacing, and workflow automation across the model network. Automatic interfacing between modeling tools was explored, such as using APIs to link INTEGRA and MCRA. The modeling tool inventory was updated and its integration with the PARC data hub was examined. Efforts also included developing a general interface/access point for the model network and initiating case studies to refine and validate individual models and platforms.

➤ WP9

T9.1: Laboratory networking

- HBM: a catalogue of 243 laboratories and detailed information on analytical experience and capacities (collected through detailed questionnaire) for 103 laboratories was established. This information has been fed to the HBM laboratory network interactive map (<https://www.eu-parc.eu/hbmlabnetwork>) and will be included in the laboratory network dashboard.

- A first inventory of air/indoor laboratories and design and implementation of detailed questionnaire to collect information about their analytical experience and capacities was made.

- A first inventory of water laboratories and creation of a working group to draft the detailed water laboratory questionnaire is ongoing.

- A comprehensive and aligned approach to collect information on expertise in the field of Articles/consumer products is discussed with WP6.

- A first inventory of (eco)toxicology laboratories and drafting of specific detailed questionnaires is done in collaboration with T9.2.

- An interactive tool (dashboard) to show the capacities of the HBM laboratory network has been designed. This tool will be implemented in collaboration with T9.2 and WP7 under the PARC Data Hub.

- A first list of coordination and linkage activities was defined as well as a list of criteria and measurable indicators to ensure the coordination and activity of the networks and the promotion of the less developed networks.

T9.2: Building exposure monitoring capacities

- Development of initial catalogues of HBM studies, cohorts, projects, networks, and other relevant information was started.

- Catalogues of environmental monitoring networks/projects were further developed (Power BI) and sent for updates to partners.

- Initial catalogue of consumer product databases was developed, in cooperation with WP6.

T9.3: Joint activities – harmonisation

- Inventory of existing QA/QC protocols, guidances, criteria in chemical trace analysis and hazard assays completed.
- First drafts of PARC QA/QC harmonised guidances with minimum criteria written.

T9.4: Training

- Elaboration of a form where website users may indicate available training on the topic of risk assessment.
- Organisation of three face-to-face training courses, and development of the first online resources (videos and a FAQsheet).
- Preparation of dissemination, application and evaluation materials for each of the trainings.
- Dissemination of PARC staff exchange initiative on PARC website, social media and PARC Sampler.

1.2.1 Work package 1: Coordination and Management

1.2.1.1 Task 1.1. Overall executive management and support of the Partnership

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Participants: All GSB members and WP co-leaders

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

➤ Follow-up in the management of the Consortium Governance Bodies and their procedures

- A PARC Consortium was organised by WP1 at University UMIT TIROL - University for Health Sciences and Technology, Hall in Tirol city Austria, on 13-16 May 2024. Over these four days, the PARC Consortium meeting brought together all PARC participants, and included: a MB meeting, a GB meeting, a general assembly with all PARC partners, a Synergy workshop, a SF meeting, an IB meeting, a NHCPs meeting, poster sessions and an exhibition. The PARC Consortium meeting brought over 170 participants on site and over 180 online.

- Meetings of the Governance Bodies (online and physical) took place regularly over the period M21-M32. For the PARC MB, one physical meeting took place at University UMIT TIROL - University for Health Sciences and Technology, Hall in Tirol city Austria, on 13 May 2024; additionally, the PARC CT organised monthly online MB meetings from January 2024 to December 2024 (11 in total). For the PARC GB, one physical meeting took place at University UMIT TIROL - University for Health Sciences and Technology, Hall in Tirol city Austria, on 16 May 2024 and one online meeting was organised on 13 November 2024. For the GSB, one online meeting took place on 17 January 2024 on order to validate the AWPY3 and its budget and to discuss the reporting, and the new projects in PARC. For all these meetings, minutes have been made available on the PARC Consortium SharePoint.

- The PARC Consortium Governance Procedures established during the first period of PARC were implemented during this period.

- Setting up and administration of the tools and structure for the day-to-day management and close follow-up of the Partnership activities

The PARC Coordination Team (CT) regularly updates the internal communication platform (PARC Consortium SharePoint) to provide shared access to current and up-to-date internal information and working documents and collaborative workspaces with the consortium and for the different boards. It notably provides access to:

- Updated versions of the PARC Handbook describing the internal requirements and specifying the common rules to be followed by all PARC Participants. It is a living document, updated continuously and evolving throughout the implementation of PARC.
- Templates and tools and instructions on how to complete these for the monitoring and reporting of PARC, including templates for the preparation of the ASRY3 and AWPY4, templates for the description and extension of the projects, templates for deliverables and milestones, templates for Decision Memo (DM) etc.
- A maintained up-to-date contacts list of the different PARC boards (GB, GSB, MB, and NHCPs) and of the consortium (Beneficiaries and Affiliated Entities and Associated Partners).

- During this period, the PARC CT enriched the PARC Consortium SharePoint for document sharing and collaborative working within the PARC Consortium boards and Hub contact points for the different PARC management bodies (GB, GSB, MB and NHCPs).

- The PARC CT continuously assists PARC participants on many specific administrative and financial questions related to the implementation.

- Financial issues, setting up and administration of the tools and structure for the close follow-up of the Partnership budget

- The PARC CT launched an amendment to the Grant Agreement in July 2024 and the PARC internal budget was updated to reflect the changes included in the amendment. The PARC internal budget was also updated taking into account the projects selected to start in Year 3 and on-going projects that were extended in preparation of the AWP for Year 3.

- As part of the preparation of the first PTFR, the PARC CT provided individual support to partners to report expenses in line with both the Horizon Europe and the Consortium own requirements, in particular with reporting expenses in the information system EMDESK. Each partner's organisation was in charge of reporting their expenses at task level and PARC internal project level in EMDESK. The PARC CT verified the consistency of expenses reported by each partner against the provisional budget planned at task and PARC internal budget level.

- The PARC CT compiled the expenses data reported by each partner and prepared individual summary sheets of the information to be input in the EC portal by Beneficiaries. Additional support was provided to partners for inputting the information in the EC portal when required. The PARC CT then verified individually the Financial Statements completed by Beneficiaries prior to including them to the PTFR. In addition, the PARC CT liaised with partners and coordinated the response to the periodic report revision request with regards to changes and clarifications requested to the financial part.

- The data collected during the first financial reporting has been compiled and presented during PARC Consortium and governance meetings. This enabled highlighting the budget consumption over the first 18 months of PARC. This data was also used to present the current levels of budget

commitment and consumption at WP, Task, projects and partner levels during budget review meetings organised with WPLs.

- Following receipt of payment of the EU contribution from HaDEA with regards to Reporting Period 1, the PARC CT prepared the payment distribution to Beneficiaries taking into account PARC internal funding and payment distribution rules. The first interim payment for the Period 1 of PARC (M1-M18) was distributed to all Beneficiaries for their institution and for their affiliated entities in October 2024. Each Beneficiary was in charge of distributing to each of its affiliated entity the amount due to them for the first period of PARC according to the PARC internal rules of calculation.

- In order to being able to provide the relevant level of support to the Consortium, the PARC CT has been strengthened with the recruitment of an additional person with a focus on financial issues starting in January 2024.

➤ Contractual documents generated by PARC activities

The PARC CT prepared contractual documents generated by PARC activities:

The CT presented the project of collaboration with NORMAN during the MB meeting on 04/03/2024. The collaboration agreement was commented and discussed with the MB over the summer 2024. MB members approved the DM for authorizing ANSES as PARC Coordinator, to sign the collaboration agreement with NORMAN on 11th of December 2024.

The PARC CT collected the requests for changes received from the PARC Participants that were integrated in a third amendment of the PARC GA launched on 23th of July 2024.

➤ Communication

- The PARC Junior community was established in 26th January 2024 as a community for students, postdocs, Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs) and fresh graduates working in PARC to connect with their peers and share career milestone through bimonthly lunchtime meetings and to stay up to date with career/training opportunities through email newsletter. This community was launched by the PARC CT in close collaboration with WP3. Per October 2024, there are more than 80 members from almost 50 different organizations. PARC Junior Community has a PARCopedia account which shares regular updates about the community to the public, as well as a private PARCopedia group where members can have specific discussions in the different fora available. There has been a total of four lunchtime meetings in 2024. There has been a total of four lunchtime meetings in 2024, including sessions given by guest speakers from EC (on its vision regarding chemical safety) ANSES (on CT perspective in establishing PARC), and EEA (on scientific communication). The community is still growing and is open to collaborating with external networks and communities. PARC Junior is currently collaborating with ASPIS Academy and SETAC to prepare a SETAC 2025 session dedicated to ESRs.

- The PARC CT contributed to articles and news items to feed the PARC website in close collaboration with the WP3.

- Rules regarding publications, dissemination and communication activities available in the PARC Handbook were regularly reminded to PARC partners over the period.

- The PARC CT launched two WP1 bulletins during the period M21-M32, one in February 2024 and one in August 2024, in order to provide information about recent and ongoing general and WP1 processes.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.1.2 Task 1.2. Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Participants: All WP co-leaders, NHCPs, NHCs, DOMG (BE), INSA (PT), NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

➤ Preparation and submission of AWP and ASRs

The PARC CT submitted the AWPY3 (D1.8) initially due M20 with a bit of delay in February 2024 (M22). Further to revisions by the PARC MB, Task co-leaders and participants, a revised version of the D1.8 was submitted in March 2024 and then in June 2024 to HADEA.

- The ASR for Year 3 (D1.9) was prepared by the PARC CT, the MB in collaboration with the Task co-leaders and the project managers and submitted in December 2024 (M32).

- The AWP for Year 4 (D1.10) is under preparation. The preparation of the AWPY4 by the PARC CT, the MB in collaboration with the Task co-leaders and the project managers, started in September 2024 with the submission and review of new projects to be started from Y4 of PARC and of projects with a request of extension. A formal vote of the new projects to be started Y4 took place during the MB meeting on 4 December 2024. The submission of the AWPY4 is planned in January 2025 (instead of December 2024 initially planned in the GA).

- An online meeting of the GB was organised on 13 November 2024 to discuss the new projects for Y4 and discuss the drafts of the ASRY3 and second AWPY4. A meeting of the GSB will be organised in January 2025 in order to validate the budget for the year 4 of PARC before the submission of the AWPY4 to HaDEA.

- The PARC CT elaborated a timeline for the revised SRIA due in the beginning of 2025.

➤ Follow-up of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones

- The PARC CT organised the review of each Deliverable and Additional Deliverable with the support of the MB and ensured the submission of the deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones due during the period (M21-M32) of PARC to the EC with the required justification in case of delay.

➤ Assistance to the PARC NHCs in defining the NH contributions and activities in PARC

- The PARC CT continued to support the PARC National Hub Coordinators (NHCs) in the management of the NHs. The coordinator participated in the NHCPs meeting on 27 May 2024 to present PARC progress and had the return of experience of the NHCs. The PARC CT participated in the NHCPs meeting on 05 December 2024 during which the NHCPs were able to discuss their work and relations with important stakeholders with an interest in PARC in their countries. The participants concluded that sharing experience among countries was extremely important to

ensure PARCs success. The discussions led to promoting finding balance between human health and environmental protection, and ensuring a two-way dialogue between scientists and policy makers at the national level.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D1.8	AWP Y3 including PARC project Portfolio	ANSES	M20	M22	
D1.9	ASRY3	ANSES	M32	M32	
D1.10	AWP Y4 including PARC project portfolio	ANSES	M32	Planned submission: M33-M34	The submission of the AWPY4 is planned M33 or M34 in order to be able to finalise the review of both new projects for Y4 and projects with an extension, proceed to the vote by the MB, and validate the budget for Y4 with the GSB in January 2025.

1.2.1.3 Task 1.3. Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership

Leader: DOMG (BE), INSA (PT)

Participants: All WP co-leaders

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Activities performed in the 3rd year included:

- The set of indicators (output, outcome and impact) has been further refined in collaboration with the MB, GSB and the GB, NHs and stakeholders. A list of 12 output, 8 outcome and 8 impact indicators has been defined. This indicator framework was outlined during the Consortium Meeting in May 2024 in the general assembly as well as discussed during the dedicated NHCPs meeting and the GB meeting.
- Presented the first numbers on output indicators in the first PARC periodic report.

- Identified potential barriers that could undermine the achievement of desired outcomes and impacts, and monitoring and discussing mitigation strategies (meetings held with WPLs T1.3-W7: 22/01/2024, 15/02/2024, 16/09/2024; T1.3 -WP4: 16.01.2024; WP9 (July?).
- Regular inter-task meetings with T2.3. for the development of sustainability indicators.
- The outcome and impact indicators have been defined in collaboration with MB, GSB and GB, NHs and stakeholders. The collection of data is ongoing with the support of respective partners.
- In close collaboration with WP3, task 3.2, easily interpretable indicator leaflets and communication elements on outcome and impact indicators have been initiated.
- First output indicators were published on the PARC website.
- Continued the discussions with the EEA to ensure input from PARC in, and synergies with, the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) indicator framework being developed by the EC. A method to capture PARC's contribution to the EU indicator framework for chemicals is under development.
- PARC is active in the EC's Partnership Strategic Coordination process and took part in the surveys, hearings and workshops organised in this process (e.g. Biennial Monitoring Reports 2024; admin burden workshop in September 2024; hearing on the PKH draft opinion on European Partnerships in FP10, SF meeting in December 2024).

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.1.4 Task 1.4. Ethics framework

Leader: NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

Participants: All WP co-leaders

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

- The Deliverable D10.4 Ethic Assessment report for Year 2-3 (OEI - Requirement No. 5) has been submitted to the EC in May 2024. The D10.4 focuses on ethics issues related to the activities that were implemented during the second-third year of PARC.
- DEPB meetings have been organised (physical meeting on 02/07/2024, online meeting late 2024 under preparation and participation to the May 2024 Consortium Meeting (including for DEPB ethics external advisors)) to discuss relevant ethics issues for PARC and to finalise the preparation of relevant ethics reports (annual ethics reports & PTFR ethic annex).
- A digital infrastructure is being set-up and improved on the PARC SharePoint to facilitate storage and/or access to key ethics documentation, hence facilitating the ongoing ethics review and monitoring by the DEPB.

- A dedicated ethics workshop is under preparation and scheduled for late 2024. This workshop intends to familiarise PARC partners with ethics guidelines previously developed and communicated, as well as to sensibilise participants to key ethics issues of relevance for the Partnership's activities.

- Episodic ethics questions from partners (sent to T1.4 and/or DEPB) have been reviewed and answered.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D10.4	OEI - Requirement No. 5	ANSES	M20	M25	Collection of required information took longer than anticipated. The finalisation and formal review (and formal approval) of the report required a DEPB meeting which was organised in early 2024.
D10.5	OEI - Requirement No. 7	ANSES	M32		

1.2.2 Work package 2. A common science and policy Agenda

A WP2 meeting took place in Vienna, October 14th – 16th of 2024. The meeting promoted the dialogue between the Task Leaders and partners and fostered a harmonised understanding of the common science policy agenda. DG RTD was also present and joined in the discussions on how to best promote this dialogue and make it more impactful; as well as in the discussions on the exit strategy.

1.2.2.1 Task 2.1. Priority setting

Leader: ANSES (FR), ECHA (EU), EFSA (EU)

Participants: EAA (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), ISS (IT), GCSL (EL), DGS (PT)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

- PARC prioritisation process including a process for project review and approval

To ensure the delivery of PARC operational outcomes by the different work packages, most of the activities in PARC are done through projects grouped and organised under the tasks/activities within PARC's work packages. To select projects that will be included in the Project Portfolio, T2.1 partners prepared a project review process that has been applied to all existing projects and to all new project proposals for Y4.

In total, 72 existing projects (including 16 case studies) have been reviewed by 10 Contact Points from Task 2.1 (EEA, EAA, DGS, ISS, GCSL, ECHA, EFSA, ANSES, BfR, UBA) and nearly 100 reviewers (from 15 different organisations) from March to June 2024. Contact points from JRC also made some recommendations. Project description documents have been updated by the project managers taking into account the comments made by the reviewers. The project reports and key landmarks are closely followed, and their status is reported in an Excel file: Projects Report-Landmark-D-AD-M. This follow-up table is included in the PARC project Portfolio in annex of the AWP.

For Year 4, 23 projects requested an extension. For this purpose, T2.1 partners prepared a project extension process including two different cases: case with limited extension (an extension ≤ 6 months and/or an extension of the budget $\leq 15\%$) and case with significant extension (extension of time > 6 months and/or extension of budget $> 15\%$ and/or modifications of the objectives of the project).

For Year 4, 18 new projects have been reviewed by 6 T2.1 Contact Points (CPs) (ANSES, EAA, EEA, ISS, GCSL, BfR) and 40 reviewers from 12 different organisations.

An Excel file (PARC Projects cluster) with the list of the Tasks, Activities and related Projects for each WP is regularly updated on the PARC ANSES SharePoint. This excel file contains some information about the project managers and deputy project managers, and also who is assigned as contact point and reviewer for each project. The Zotero database of projects is also regularly updated by T2.1 co-leads to include information related to the review of the projects and to publications related to the projects. Contact Points and Reviewers use it to cluster the projects by topic, to make links between the projects using tags on keywords.

Two T2.1 physical meetings have been organised in 2024: one in April in Helsinki (ECHA headquarters) and one in October in Vienna (EAA headquarters). Regular online meetings with T2.1 partners have been also organized (5 meetings). Moreover, an online meeting was organized on the 30th of September 2024 to which project managers, WPLs, TLs T2.1 reviewers and CPs attended. The aim of this meeting was to collect some feedback regarding the review process of the projects and to discuss proposals for improvement.

To inform and inspire the PARC research community, a webinar on "Research needs for protecting human health and the environment - an EU agencies perspective" has been organized on 18th of June 2024 by EU agencies (ECHA – EFSA – EEA) ([Events - ECHA \(europa.eu\)](#)). The aim of this meeting was to present the latest research priorities and challenges, particularly in regulatory science, identified by the EU agencies, enhancing their understanding of where their work can have the most impact.

➤ Completing PARC's second prioritisation round

After mapping the needs through a survey sent to the GB's Principal Representatives, and compiling the feedback received (see results in [D2.4 1st Mapping of needs report](#)), the needs were refined and, in some cases, clarifications were required. A shorter list of needs was then

selected from these suggestions and input provided by the EU agencies (EEA, EFSA, ECHA) was considered (KARC), as well as needs suggested by the European Commission. Task 2.1 organised 2 webinars (21st of February 2024 and 1st of March 2024) and a hybrid workshop at ANSES (11th and 12th of March 2024) to discuss the selected needs, and factsheets were drafted for each topic (whether if a group of substances or an endpoint). In the beginning of June 2024, Task 2.1 with the help of the coordination team, launched the consultation phase of this prioritisation process. The NHs, SF, IB and the GB were consulted as a first step, each with a specific focus. Feedback was compiled and considered for the second phase of consultation (mid-October to mid-November), during which a ranking of the different needs was carried out by the GB members. The MB was kept closely involved throughout the whole process. A final list of needs to be possibly addressed by PARC's future activities and a prioritised list was then shared among the PARC consortium, paving the way for future PARC project proposals.

➤ Processing new requests under the Rapid Response Mechanism

In February 2024, EEA and ECHA initiated PARC's RRM. The new request was prompted by a sharp increase in the concentration of mono-n-hexyl phthalate in urine samples from kindergarten children and adults in Germany and Denmark, respectively. The aim of the application is to identify the extent of exposure to this phthalate in Europe and the source of exposure. Task 2.1 in collaboration with the GB assessed the eligibility of this request (see criteria in the rapid response report D2.5). A specific working group was formed, the feasibility of the request was assessed and the response document, validated by the MB, was sent back to the applicants (17th of May 2024). A tiered approach was proposed to carry the work forward. A new project under Task 2.1 has been launched to meet this need. This project is in close collaboration with other tasks such as Task 4.1 for biomonitoring data and method harmonisation, Task 4.2 for environmental/indoor air data, with Task 6.2 for source modelling and Activity 6.4 for consumer product screening.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D2.4	1st Mapping of Needs report	ANSES	M18	M22	

1.2.2.2 Task 2.2. Knowledge management and uptake into policy

Leader: BfR (DE), INSA (PT)

Participants: AUTH (EL), UOB (UK)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

➤ A2.2.1. PARCopedia

After the successful launch of the platform in November 2023, work on PARCopedia conducted during PARC Y3 so far has focused on continuously improving its functionality and user experience, on further developing and improving internal procedures, e.g. for the generation of new content, on adding new content and on dissemination and community building. Specifically, the following work has been conducted since the beginning of 2024:

- Deliverable 2.6, describing the platform as launched, was delivered.
- The PARCopedia editorial team was installed, a core team of T2.2 partners meeting weekly to discuss necessary changes and improvements.
- Detailed internal procedures, e.g. for processing new wiki articles, were developed.
- Three focus group sessions were conducted between March and April 2024, to gain a deeper understanding of the PARCopedia user experience, and how to best meet their needs and desires for this platform by developing informed strategies for the whole CRA. Three main future lines of actions were defined: 1.) formulation and implementation of a communication strategy, 2.) provision of guidance and tools to PARCopedia users and 3.) conceptual considerations regarding the PARCopedia WIKI.
- FAQs and support pages on how to best use PARCopedia and on how to share knowledge on PARCopedia through wiki articles were developed and made available online. Pages providing more details on who is behind PARCopedia and on the PARCopedia community itself were also published.
- The first PARCopedia webinar was held on 28 June 2024 providing a detailed overview of the platform and addressing key functionalities of PARCopedia. More than 300 people participated in the webinar. In addition, individual user support was provided to newly founded user groups on the PARCopedia's social media part, e.g. the PARC junior community.
- The PARCopedia landing page "My Dashboard" was overhauled to include frequently updated news items, events, job offers as well as a public stream from PARCopedia's social network component. The original central PARCopedia search engine was replaced with a new one which is now able to return search results from all parts of the platform, including the social network part.
- A new section on "resources" was developed and published in October 2024, providing links to databases, tools and training materials relevant for the PARCopedia community.
- The first newsletter of PARCopedia was developed and sent in October 2024.

At the end of September 2024, PARCopedia had almost 900 registered users and – projecting past developments into the future – stands a real chance of welcoming its 1.000th user before the end of the year. It currently (late September 2024) features 20 discussion groups with 35 topics in 10 discussion fora, 63 PARCopedia wiki articles, 311 published posts (news, job opportunities, announcements) and 74 featured events. While numbers on PARCopedia seem to be encouraging, more work will be needed to populate the platform with more content and to engage users to use PARCopedia platform more often.

Partners involved: ANSES, AUTH, BfR (co-leader), ENSP, GCSL, ILVO, INSA (co-leader), JSI, MU, SOM, UBA, UOB, UKON

AUTH is in charge of developing and maintaining the IT infrastructure. BfR has led and coordinated the work with the support of INSA.

Within the PARCopedia editorial team, UOB assists with the coordination of content creation and the related internal procedures. MU and UBA are substantially supporting the community management and communication part of PARCopedia. BfR, INSA, MU and UBA actively and substantially contribute content to PARCopedia. ANSES provides the link with the coordination team, the MB and the rest of the PARC partners. Further partners have contributed to the editorial team's work.

Dissemination efforts included presentations at numerous meetings including PARC MB, GB, SF, WP NH and Consortium meetings, conferences such as EUROTOX 2023 in Ljubljana and 2024 in Copenhagen, ESTIV 2024 in Prague, or the SOT meeting 2024 in Salt Lake City (USA), the meeting of the WHO Chemical RA network in December 2023, various OECD working groups (planned for October 2024), other EU project meetings (RISK-HUNT3R, ASPIS cluster), the first EU Commission roadmap workshop (cf. next section) as well as numerous webinars, inter alia the EMA 3Rs Stakeholder Meeting and a number of German 3R-related webinars.

➤ A2.2.2. PARCroute

In PARC Y3, T2.2 under its activity NGRAroute collaborated with the EU Commission for the organisation of the first workshop on “The Roadmap Towards Phasing Out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments” and participated by providing presentations on PARC and on PARC T2.2 activities. An entire session of the workshop was dedicated to the discussion of a set of draft guiding principles for the development of a future NGRA framework. These principles, along with identified work streams and important tasks to consider under the further roadmap work were also circulated for commenting to a broad network of stakeholders within and outside of PARC after the workshop. More than 1.500 comments were received and addressed, resulting in an updated version of the principles integrating the feedback received. This revised version then formed the core of the additional deliverable AD2.1 “NGRAroute: 2nd interim report”, which was submitted to the EU portal at the beginning of October 2024, after undergoing a second commenting round, again including a broad circle of stakeholders and receiving another 600+ comments which were all addressed individually. Throughout the year, ongoing collaborations with the EU Commission's roadmap work were maintained, and T2.2 members participated in dedicated working groups on Human Health (BfR) and Environment (EAA, UBA). Task 2.2 will also be represented in the third WG on Change management (by UOB), once this activity will officially kick off. The main findings of AD2.1 “NGRAroute: 2nd interim report” and the status of the NGRAroute activity and principles were also reported at the second workshop on the COM's “Roadmap towards phasing out animal testing for chemical safety assessments” on 25 October.

Partners involved: ANSES, BfR (co-lead), CEFAS-DEFRA, EAA, EEA, ENSP, GCSL, INSA (co-lead), ISS, MU, NILU, SOM, STAMI, UBA, UOB

BfR is leading and coordinating the work with the support of INSA. BfR also coordinated the development and finalisation of the NGRAroute guiding principles and the relevant network of people to involve in the commenting rounds. EAA is conducting extensive literature and project mapping work and – together with UBA - has created a tool to systematically search the compiled database of NGRA-related literature that serves as the background to develop the roadmap. UOB is conducting similar work on the side of legislation. All other task partners have provided substantial inputs to the work and to the documents developed. In addition, specifically WP leads of PARC WPs 4, 5 and 6 have significantly contributed during the commenting rounds and as reviewers of the additional Deliverable AD2.1.

Publications

Aside from presentations at numerous meetings (cf. previous sections), the following articles have been published or submitted by Task 2.2 in 2024 to promote NGRAroute:

- Liebmann L et al. (2024): Europäische Partnerschaft zur Bewertung von Risiken durch Chemikalien (PARC) – Deutschlands Beitrag im Überblick / European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) – Germany’s contribution at a glance, UMID 2024:37-49. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/umid-012024>
- Fabbri M et al. (2024): Report of the European Commission Workshop on “The Roadmap Towards Phasing Out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments”, Brussels, 11-12 December 2023. Submitted for publication to Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology
- Herzler M et al. (2024): The European Partnership PARC’s Role in Actively Promoting the Uptake of New Approach Methodologies and Next-Generation RA into Regulatory RA Practice. Submitted for publication to Current Opinion in Toxicology
- Herzler M et al. (2024): Food for thought ... first steps towards an overarching Next-Generation RA (NGRA) framework to support the phasing out of animal testing in chemical risk assess (working title), planned for submission to ALTEX in October 2024.

NGRAroute has also been acknowledged in two documents published by the European Commission in 2024:

- European Commission (2024): Proposal to establish a Subgroup on Test Methods in CARACAL. In 52nd Meeting of the Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (CARACAL). <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/a0b483a2-4c05-4058-addf-2a4de71b9a98/library/4fa23357-4bbb-4f8f-a46b-fa9b784a7300/details>
- European Commission, Cronin M (2024): Report of the European Commission workshop on “The Roadmap Towards Phasing Out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments” – Brussels, 11-12 December 2023. Edited by: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2873/34576>

➤ A2.2.3. CLs and MLs

The Deliverable D2.8 (CLs and MLs – Annual work report) was finalized and submitted. Following the discussions at the joint GB/MB meeting in November 2023, it was decided to prioritize nanomaterials, microplastics and new generation environmental RA and to have chemical and methodology leaders for these chemicals and methodology. As such, a new open call was set up and disseminated among the PARC partner institutions for applications to the roles of the CLs and MLs for the chemicals and methodologies agreed on by the MB. The applications received were evaluated and the results of the evaluation were presented to the MB. The list of newly selected CLs and MLs was approved by the MB. A meeting with the CLs (15/04/2024) and a meeting with the MLs (26/04/2024) were organized to go over the roles and responsibilities of CLs and MLs and to discuss the future activities. Individual meetings with the CLs and MLs for the preparation of individual annual work plans were organized. Annual work plans for Y4 were prepared. Groups in PARCopedia were established for EDCs and nanomaterials and PARCopedia wiki articles prepared for the chemicals and methodologies. Regular meetings were planned and the first regular meeting took place. Deliverable 2.10 (2nd CLs and MLs Annual work report) was prepared.

INSA has led and coordinated this activity, with the support of BfR, both co-leaders of this Task.

Partners involved (institutions of CLs and MLs): UBA, NKUA, Fraunhofer ITEM, UKHSA, AUTH, IISPV, UI, IMR/EFSA.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D2.6	PARCopedia	BfR	M18	M21	The launch of the platform happened later than planned, which delayed the submission of the deliverable
D2.8	1st Annual CL/ML reports' coordination and submission	INSA	M21	M24	Short delay in the process of review
AD2.1	Status report on NGRAroute	BfR	M24 (postponed M29)	M29	AD2.1 was delayed until M29. The reason for the delay is that events regarding the COM roadmap have unfolded more slowly than originally anticipated. An additional reason is given by the fact that in total more than 1000 written comments on the guiding principles and work streams were received, with a large majority in the affirmative. Many important additional ideas/suggestions were provided but to do them justice with only limited resources available took more time than expected.

1.2.2.3 Task 2.3. Sustainability

Leader: INSERM (FR), NCPHP⁴ (HU)

Participants: DOMG (BE)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

⁴ AMD-101057014-80: The Beneficiary 'Nemzeti Népegészségügyi Központ' (abbreviation in Hungarian: NNK; full name in English: National Public Health Center; abbreviation in English: NPHC) was changed to 'Nemzeti Népegészségügyi és Gyógyszerészeti Központ' (abbreviation in Hungarian: NNGYK; full name in English: National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy; abbreviation in English: NCPHP) as of 1st August 2023. The acronym NPHC was replaced by NCPHP in the WPs where they are contributors.

The 2nd survey on national needs was developed and launched in February 2024 to (i) gather information on the current needs and expectations of the NHs themselves, (ii) collect good practices, (iii) gain insight into national success stories, and (iv) monitor NH activities. The results of the survey were analysed and presented to, as well as discussed with, the NHCPs during the NHCP meetings held in Hall in Tirol, Austria and Brussels, Belgium in May and June 2024, respectively. Twenty-seven out of the 28 NHCPs completed the survey. The results clearly show the development of the NHs: the number of organisations involved in the NH network grew to 430; more than half of the NHs included scientists, regulators, and policymakers beyond the PARC members and new representatives from industry, consumer associations, trade unions and other Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) were engaged; almost all NHs covered the expertise of PARC topics (except for FAIR data) by the end of 2023. NHCPs reported difficulties such as (i) limited resources for activities beyond organising NH meetings, (ii) challenges in reaching non-scientific NH members and gathering partners physically for meetings, (iii) difficulties in engaging NH members and maintaining their interest, (iv) expanding the NH, and (v) securing co-funding for HBM studies. Almost half of the NHCPs shared good practices regarding stakeholder engagement, organising meetings and other NHCP actions, providing support to those still facing some challenges. Furthermore, several national success stories were also reported and published on the PARC website in collaboration with T3.2. The survey was also used to collect data for output indicators on the performance of the NHs.

To facilitate the exchange among the NHCPs, a PARCopedia group has been created.

The 3rd survey, prepared by T2,3 partners in collaboration with the NHCs and the NHCPs in 2024, will be launched in January 2025.

Partners involved in the activities: NCPHP (leading), INSERM, NHCs (UKHSA, SZU), ANSES, UBA, BfR, FMUL, INSA, MU, NIOM in collaboration with the WP co-leaders.

A survey had been sent to the national hubs on the exit strategy in 2023. During the first months of 2024, the survey was analyzed. A deliverable D2.9 (1st PARC Exit Strategy Plan and sustainability report) was written and submitted in May 2024. This deliverable was accepted. The survey outcomes are that the following activities need to be sustainable after PARC: HBM, toxicology, environmental monitoring, access to data and safe by design. It was also clear that our conclusions should be further developed in light of the “one substance, one assessment” legislative proposals of the Commission, which address a number of activities of PARC. The deliverable also included a number of suggestions on the most relevant frameworks to ensure the sustainability of those different activities; for example, concerning HBM it is suggested that the precise framework could be embedded in the legislation (for example, within the legislative proposals on “one substance, one assessment” put forward by the Commission) and a central coordination at the EU level by an EU agency would be optimal. For the other activities, a central coordination at the EU level was also found to be needed. Those conclusions were shared with the NH (NH meeting) and with the MB and GB of PARC. Since the acceptance of the deliverables, meetings were held or planned with the different task and WP leaders to discuss exit strategies in their fields. It was agreed that those meetings should prepare for a physical meeting between task 2.3 partners and WP and task leaders in early 2025.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

Concerning the exit strategy, the only problem was that several NH stated that they were not ready in 2023 to answer some of the questions. We therefore consider the outcomes of the survey as “qualitative” and not necessarily representative of the opinions of all NH. This was clearly stated in the deliverable 2.9.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D2.9	1st PARC Exit Strategy Plan and sustainability report	INSERM	M24	M25	

1.2.3 Work package 3. Synergies, collaborations and awareness

1.2.3.1 Task 3.1. Building effective interactions

Leader: EAA (AT), AUTH (EL)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AGES (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), IUSS (IT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), NIB (SI), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), GCSL (EL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

➤ A3.1.1. Establishment and running the SF

Since January 2024, the Terms of Reference for the SF were adopted and a shorter memorandum of understanding was shared and agreed upon by the members of the SF. One of the two initially elected Co-chairs of the SF has withdrawn from her role. The SF continues to run with only one Chair until another member of the SF shows availability to commit to the role. Under the leadership of EAA, several online meetings were organized among the Task 3.1.1 partners (GCSL, INSA, APA, FMUL, STAMI, NIB, UBA, UOC, EEA, NKUA) to prepare for the third hybrid SF meeting. In a preparatory meeting for the third SF, SF members expressed their needs for the SF and were introduced to PARCs' RRM by the EEA. The hybrid meeting was held back-to-back with the consortium meeting on 15th May 2024 in Hall in Tyrol, Austria. The SF members were asked to join the discussion on PARC science-to-policy activities towards a NGRA through interaction with WP2.2. leaders. Furthermore, response to the SF members' initial interest in activities in occupational health projects in PARC was provided by presentations and interactions with PARC WP6 and WP4 project leaders on occupational studies as well as on chemical mixtures. Another virtual SF meeting in 2024 was just preliminary to the consultation process on PARC future activities and SF members were encouraged and informed to participate in an online survey and consolidation meeting during the summer/autumn period of Y3. Also, AUTH had the opportunity to present developments for the SSbD toolbox to the SF and announce a workshop to discuss the SSbD toolbox. Under the leadership of EAA, several online meetings were organized among the Task 3.1.1 partners (GCSL, INSA, APA, FMUL, STAMI, NIB, UBA, UOC, EEA, ANSES, NKUA) to discuss the work ahead in the consultation process for PARC future activities and the further establishment of PARCopedia SF members groups to allow internal SF

and PARC related information flows. EAA and partners continued to interact and cooperate with the nominated SF Co-chair and to seek opportunities for effective collaboration between the SF and the PARC consortium.

➤ A3.1.2 Establishment and running of the IB

Strategies to manage the expectations from PARC and the IB members and maximise their inputs were discussed with the Task 3.1.2 partners (AUTH, ANSES, AGES, UBA, IUSS, LNS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, APA, NIB, NKUA, UOC, GCSL), in order to be presented and discussed at the forthcoming IB meetings of 2024. The 2nd IB meeting was held on 15/5/2024 in Hall in Tyrol, Austria. Key topics that were discussed included (a) the prioritization needs for AOPs development, (b) the perspectives on chemical mixtures RA, (c) the FAIRification of data in PARC to support transparency in chemical RA, and (d) the CRA methods to support EWS for chemicals. Highlighted points included (a) the importance of science-to-policy debates and ensuring input into current processes to inform policy performance, (b) ensuring two-way communication between policy stakeholders and collecting information on policymakers' challenges and concerns and (c) to emphasize the link between WP2 (science-to-policy interface) and WP5 (hazard assessment) for the uptake of NAMs in regulatory frameworks. Meeting minutes have been prepared (AUTH) and distributed.

The 3rd IB meeting was held online on 23/09/2024 (AUTH). The main discussion topic was the future needs for PARC (AUTH, ANSES, AGES, EEA, UBA, IUSS, LNS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, APA, NIB, NKUA, UOC, GCSL). In this direction, there was a short presentation on the scope of the future prioritization needs by the PARC CT, and the key outcomes so far. The IB brought the international experience from similar activities, while several members proposed more generic recommendations on the scientific directions of PARC. A key recommendation that was suggested and accepted, was to narrow down focus areas, starting with a top 10 list to target more specific needs and actions. These focus areas will be continuously refined throughout the duration of the project to reflect feedback from the GB. International cross-agency collaborations of PARC were recommended, as well as collaboration with non-chemical-specific initiatives, such as the exposome, was also highlighted as potentially beneficial. Finally, the need for an exit strategy and the overall longevity of PARC was raised as it will be crucial to identify the sustainability of the NAMs, databases, etc., that result from PARC. Meeting minutes have been prepared (AUTH) and distributed.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.3.2 Task 3.2. Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Leader: EEA (EU), NCPHP (HU)

Participants: ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), UMIT (AT), VITO (BE), DOMG (BE), CIPH (CR), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), HB (EE), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), UI (IS), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UNINA (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), SZU (SK), JSI (SI),

NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), ISCI III (ES), KEMI (SE), SLV (SE), FOPH (CH), UKHSA (UK), UOB (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

The PARC website (<https://www.eu-parc.eu>) has been continuously maintained, developed and populated with new content by NCPHP and EEA in 2024. Frequent meetings were organised between the EEA, NCPHP, and service providers (graphic design company and website developer). The following developments were completed in 2024: visualisation of (i) research projects, (ii) HBM laboratories on an interactive map, (iii) output indicators, and (iv) opportunities. In addition, a new functionality was added to the website for the direct creation of surveys. This functionality was used to create the form for expressions of interest in SYNnet. The PARC leaflet that was created by EEA, NCPHP, INSA and GCSL was translated into national languages by the NHCPs and uploaded to the PARC website.

The official PARC social media channels on LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram and X (formerly Twitter) were regularly updated with new content, including progress updates, interviews and results. The social media and website content management group (EEA, NCPHP, BPI, EFET, GCSL, INSA, NIJZ and NKUA) held weekly meetings to discuss the latest news and events based on inputs received from other WPs and the CT. The tasks of the group members included editing or preparing news items for the website and updating social media channels. WP nominated contact points for WP3 (ANSES, BfR, UBA, SpF, AUTH, RIVM, KEMI, UoB, MU, ISCI III) are providing information on the latest news and events from their respective WP and content for the thematic areas. New social media campaigns were launched in 2024, including a series of posts on the implementation of HBM studies within the Aligned Studies, as well as short interviews with key PARC actors.

To increase the impact of scientific publications, the Science Digest newsletter, featuring the latest PARC publications, was published eight times in 2024 by NCPHP, EEA and GCSL. The key scientific and regulatory messages provided by the corresponding authors were reviewed, and the PARC community on Zenodo, an open data repository, was maintained by GCSL. The PARC general newsletter called PARC Sampler including the latest news, interviews and science impact among other themes was published in Spring/Summer and Autumn/Winter 2024 by EEA and NCPHP in collaboration with the social media and website content management group (BPI, EFET, GCSL, INSA, NIJZ and NKUA).

An exhibition titled “Healthy Horizons: Our Journey to Create a Safer Chemical World” was organised by EEA and NCPHP during the PARC Consortium meeting, held between 13-16 May 2024 in Hall in Tyrol, Austria. The exhibition featured a series of informative displays, various types of postcards promoting PARC scientific publications, the European HBM Laboratory Network and PARCopedia. Touch screens showcased the work being undertaken by PARC, including various research projects. Microscopic images demonstrating the work and findings of PARC researchers were displayed on a screen. One highlight was an interactive installation titled “Visualising Your Opinion on Chemicals”, where participants were asked to answer questions by weaving their choices around different options. Additionally, a survey with 10 questions was presented, among others, to better understand how to improve certain aspects, such as identifying challenges in translating research into policy, and to explore the daily attitudes of scientists.

The procurement process for implementing the representative citizen survey was carried out by NCPHP. NHCPs were asked to translate the final version of the survey to national languages.

The first focus groups on citizens' perspectives and concerns about chemicals in daily used products were organised in Finland (TTL), Latvia (RSU), the United Kingdom (UKHSA), Portugal (FMUL, ENSP) and Sweden (RISE), based on the design developed by FMUL, NCPHP, INSA, EEA and ENSP, with training provided by FMUL. The transcripts have been prepared, and the data analysis has begun.

The survey mapping the risk perception of different stakeholders regarding risk communication was conducted in Greece and Slovenia by EFET and NIJZ, respectively. The results of the survey have been analysed and a report has been prepared. A concept for a series of webinars on risk communication was developed by ENSP, FMUL, EFET and NIJZ.

Efforts to map stakeholder surveys, already completed or in progress by the various PARC projects/activities, started by reviewing the information available in the annual work plans and the 1st periodic report (GCSL, UOC, INSA, NCPHP). Extensive rounds of consultations with the GB, GSB, IB and SF were run by the CT and WP2 in order to provide input to priorities for the MB. Industrial stakeholders outside the SF were also consulted in the area of SSbD by WP8 and through several case studies in WP6. A trilateral meeting between the CT, WP2 and WP3 was held to discuss areas for targeted consultation with regulators and policy makers (outside the GB/GBS) to design an appropriate survey.

The bibliometric analysis for the period from May 2022 to December 2023 has been prepared by UOC. T1.3 was supported by NCPHP and EEA in developing the visualization of output indicators, particularly those to be presented on the PARC website. Indicator values related to communication and dissemination were provided to T1.3.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

Many countries expressed interest in organizing the first round of focus groups and an internal call had to be launched for the selection which delayed the downstream process. This delay was predicted in AWPY3 and therefore the D3.5 was planned for M32 instead of M28.

Due to the transformation of NCPHP, the procurement process for the citizen's survey took longer than initially planned and the results of the survey will be analysed in 2025.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D3.5	1st Report on citizen's perception and concern: results of the surveys and focus groups	EEA	M28 (postponed M32)		D3.5 is delayed to M32. Many countries expressed interest in organizing the first round of focus groups and an internal call had to be launched for the selection which delayed the downstream process. Due to the transformation of NCPHP, the procurement process took longer than initially planned. Since the survey will cover all PARC countries, identifying

No	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
					potential service providers was also time-consuming.

1.2.3.3 Task 3.3. Networking and Synergies

Leader: INSA (PT), NKUA (EL)

Participants: ANSES (FR), MU (CZ), UBA (DE), FMUL (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), EFET (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Work on expanding the synergies network to include new Partnerships, projects, etc. and respond to PARC demands for synergies was continued (NKUA, INSA, ANSES, MU, UBA, FMUL, APA, ENSP, UAVR, JSI, NIB, NIC, NIJZ, EFET, UOC, BPI, GCSL). The interaction strategy between SYNnet and WPs in order to identify and address internal needs and gaps was revised (BPI, ENSP, NKUA, GCSL, INSA, UBA).

Exchanges with WP/Task/Project leaders took place to identify external scientific activities that are relevant to PARC and promote the idea of transforming existing interactions into formal synergies (all partners).

The form to collect expressions of interest from external projects and activities was embedded in PARC's website (NKUA, INSA). Expressions of interest from further external activities and projects were received and forwarded to the relevant WPs/Task co-leaders for evaluation. In the cases where there was interest in establishing synergies, dedicated meetings between PARC and the external activities and projects were organized. The file with data on the external projects/activities who have expressed interest in establishing synergies with PARC was updated. Information on the status of the requests was registered in the file (NKUA, INSA).

A collaboration agreement between PARC and the NORMAN Association has been developed by the CT with the support of Task 3.3 (NKUA, INSA).

The first SYNnet Forum was organized back-to-back with the SETAC annual meeting that took place in Spain in May 2024 and the second SYNnet Forum was organized back-to-back with the 52nd European Environmental Mutagenesis and Genomics Society Meeting that took place in Rovinj, Croatia in September 2024 (INSA, NKUA). The third SYNnet Forum taking place within the EUROTOX 2025 conference in Athens in September 2025 started to be organized. Information on the SYNnet Forums was announced in PARC's website and social media channels (NKUA, INSA, UOC, BPI, GCSL, EFET).

A "Workshop on Synergies with External Initiatives" was organized at the Consortium Meeting in Hall in Tyrol on the 15th May 2024. Several external projects participated in this workshop and presented their activities, namely Biodiversa+, ASPIS Cluster, NORMAN Association and EURION Cluster (NKUA, INSA). A Second Workshop on Synergies with External Initiatives was organized on 27th November 2024 and had the participation of projects from the ENKORE and the Green Deal Clusters (NKUA, INSA).

Input on synergies and collaborations has been given to Task 1.3 for the production of the respective indicators and the leaflets produced for the key performance indicators related to the synergies were reviewed (NKUA, INSA).

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

Although there are many collaborations between PARC and external initiatives it is challenging to conclude them as formal synergies.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.4 Work package 4. Monitoring and Exposure

1.2.4.1 Task 4.1. HBM

Leader: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AU-PH (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEA (FR), CSIC (ES), EAA (AT), EHESP (FR), FFA (FI), TTL (FI), FISABIO (ES), FOPH (CH), HSE (UK), KI (SE), IMROH (HR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), INSST (ES), IOM (UK), KUM (DE), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), KU Leuven (BE), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MOH (IL), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), MUW (AT), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), NPHSL (LT), ONIRIS (FR), UKHSA (UK), PIH (BE), REGIONH-RH (DK), RSU (LV), SRU (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), STAMI (NO), SZU-CZ (CZ), SZU-SK (SK), THL (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UGent (BE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), ULFFA (SI), ULPGC (ES), ULUND (SE), UMU (SE), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), UNIVIE (AT), UNN (NO), UOULU (FI), UOC (EL), UPV/EHU (ES), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WULS-SGGW (PL), CIPH (HR), SHSO (CY), SDU (DK), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), UFZ (DE), NCPHP (HU), UI (IS), VSCHT (CZ), EASP (ES), SECO (CH)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Overall coordination of T4.1. i.e., participation in bi-weekly follow-up meetings with task co-leads to coordinate the progress of the task. Participation in monthly Task force meetings with WPLs and other WP4 TLs. Preparation and participation in the annual WP4 meeting (08-09/10/2024 Berlin), 8-weekly follow-up meeting with T4.1 project and activity leads [VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES)]. Task 4.1 leaders (VITO, ISCIII), have also been involved in the working group created in PARC by Task 2.1 to address the request submitted by the European Environmental Agency (EEA) & the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) to the CT with the objective of identifying the sources and extent of human exposures to DnHexP and/or MnHexP. Among the actions taken were the gathering of information on availability of already existing data and/or biobanked samples for future analysis from T4.1 partners; the analysis of the information to identify laboratories that analyse the biomarkers; contacting laboratories to gather information on prices, capacities etc. for analysis and the potential reintegration of earlier analyses; and evaluation on method development or harmonisation activities in PARC.

- A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies

S4.1.1.1. Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct

No projects were planned since it is a transversal activity.

Partners involved in this transversal activity: CIPH (Croatia), EAA (AT), EASP (ES), Fraunhofer (DE), FOPH (CH), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), INSA (PT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), JSI (SL), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-IL (IL), MUW (AT), NIJZ (SL), NIOM (PL), PIH (BE), RSU (LV), SpF (FR), STAMI (NO), SZU-CZ (CZ), THL (FI), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UMU (SE), UPV-EHU (ES), VITO (BE)

In the context of this initiative, our primary goal was to review and enhance the existing HBM4EU resources and develop a toolkit to support the launch of the PARC general survey. We have established working groups, each dedicated to a specific set of materials:

- Documents concerning ethical considerations and informed consent (UPV/EHU, ISCIII, INSA, ISS, EAA, SZU-CZ)
- Protocols and guidelines for sample collection, handling, and storage (Fraunhofer, ISCIII, ISS, EAA, UPV/EHU, JSI, RSU, SZU-CZ, UBA, LNS)
- Survey questionnaires for gathering information on demographics, lifestyle factors, health status and potential sources of chemical exposures (SpF, FOPH, Fraunhofer, EASP, IDAEA-CSIC, INSA, ISCIII, JSI, LNS, LSMU, NIJZ, NIOM, PIH, RSU, STAMI, THL, UBA, UMU, SZU-CZ), and
- Solutions for digitalizing the survey (ISCIII, CIPH, EASP, INSA, JSI, NIJZ, LNS, MOH-IL, MUW, PIH, SpF, UBA, UMU)

Within each working group, partners contributed their insights and expertise, resulting in suggested modifications and adaptations. The review process was coordinated through multiple online meetings and involved consultation and collaboration with various PARC project partners including P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO, A4.1.4-Data management and analysis, P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO, S4.1.1.4 Occupational surveys, WP3, and other stakeholders such as JRC.

Recent decisions have been made regarding the digitalization solutions (INSA, ISCIII, SpF, PIH, VITO), and the surveys' questionnaires are implemented in REDCap (INSA).

In 2024, the activity produced the Material and Data Transfer Agreement (MDTA). This document was prepared under the leadership of Fraunhofer and other partners (ISCIII, ISS, EAA, EPV/EHU, JSI, RSU, SZU-CZ, UBA, LNS), coordinated by SpF. The MDTA was reviewed by the Data Protection Officers (DPOs) of SpF and UBA before validation. Each partner will be able to adapt it according to the laws of their respective country. Finally, the MDTA could not be included as an annex to AD4.1 because the AD had already been submitted to HaDEA. Therefore, it is available in a specific folder on the [Sharepoint](#).

S4.1.1.2. General population survey

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP)

- **P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO [M1-M81]**

Partners involved in this project: [AUTH (EL), EAA (AT), EASP (ES), INSA (PT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SL), NIJZ (SL), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY / SGL (CY), MOH-IL (IL), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), RegionH-RH (DK), RSU (LV), SpF (FR), SZU-CZ (CZ), SZU-SK (SK), UI (IS), UKHSA (UK), UT (EE), HB (EE), UPV/EHU (ES), UBA (DE), VITO (BE), PIH (BE), WULS-SGGW (PL), KI (SE), ULUND (SE), UMU (SE), UDC⁵ (IE)].

⁵ AMD-101057014-118: The University College Dublin – PARC acronym “UCD”, PIC number 999974359 entered as new Beneficiary in PARC as of 01/10/2024 with the agreement that the ‘Environment Protection Agency’ – PARC acronym “EPA” remains the only member of the Grant Signatory Board and takes over responsibility for coordinating Ireland’s engagement in PARC in the same way as other grant signatories with AE do. The starting date for the eligibility of the costs for UCD is on

General Coordination of the project [VITO (BE)] including, organization of an online project meeting 18 June 2024 [VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), INSA (PT)] and a physical meeting back-to-back with the WP4 meeting in Berlin (07/10 and 10/10 2024) [VITO (BE)], Overall coordination and communication with project partners (e.g., development of online surveys to collect input), interaction with S4.1.1.1 on development of supporting materials for the project, exchange with T4.2 (P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU) and T4.3 (P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Complementary_developments_JSI/UAntwerpen) to prepare the development of add-ons concerning collection of personal environmental samples and application of NTS methods in a subset of studies as proof-of-concept, exchange with P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth to prepare a proposal for implementation of effect biomarkers in a subset of the studies (regular online progress meetings), interaction with 4.1.2 on the progress of PARC QA/QC and subsequent sample analysis [VITO (BE)]. Selection of studies (Milestone MS10) has been updated: addition of Sweden to the aligned studies with three collaborating partners KI (SE), UMU (SE), ULUND (SE)- effective January 8 2024.

Regular online meetings with core group partners [VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), UBA (DE), SpF (FR)] to prepare an ethics template, initiate a communication plan, etc.

Participation in online meeting (18/06/2024) [VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), UCD (IE), NIPH (NO), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), ISS (IT), LNS (LU), SZU-SK (SK), ISSeP (BE), MOH-IL (IL), RSU (LV), LSMU (LT), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), SpF (FR)].

Participation in Physical meeting in Berlin (07 and 10/10/2024) [VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), NIPH (NO), MoH-CY/SGL (CY), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), LNS (LU), UI (ISL), SZU-SK, ISSeP (BE) MOH-IL, RSU (LV), LSMU (LT), NIJZ (SL), UPV/EHU, NIOM (PL), PIH (BE), SpF (FR)].

All partners performed the necessary study preparation (e.g., prepare national/regional adaptations of supporting materials, prepare and submit ethical dossier, etc..) according to their (national/regional level) timeline for:

- studies in children [AUTH (EL), EAA (AT), INSA (PT), ISCIII (ES), JSI (SL), LNS (LU), MOH-CY / SGL (CY), NCPHP (HU), NIJZ (SI), RegionH-RH (DK), RSU (LV), SpF (FR), SZU-CZ (CZ), UBA (DE), UKHSA (UK), University Tartu / Health board (EE), WULS (PL)];
- studies in teenagers [AUTH (EL), INSA (PT), JSI (SL), NIPH (NO), NIJZ (SL), NIOM (PL), Region-H (DK), RSU (LV), SpF (FR), UBA (DE), UKHSA (UK), VITO (BE), PIH (BE), KI (SE), UMU (SE), ULUND (SE)];
- studies in adults [AUTH (EL), EASP (ES), INSA (PT), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY / SGL (CY), MOH-IL (IL), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), RSU (LV), SpF (FR), SZU-CZ (CZ), UBA (DE), UI (IS), UKHSA (UK), UT / HB (EE), UPV/EHU (ES)].

Table 2: Implementation of a general population HBM survey:

Time Period: M21–M32

Age Group	Recruitment and Sample Collection (Status)	Participants
Children (6–11 years)	Started	WULS-SGGW (PL), RegionH-RH (DK)
	Continued	JSI (SI), NIJZ (SI)
	Finalized	None

01/10/2024 and UCD specifically contributes as partner in the PARC Aligned Studies under WP4 (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO).

Teenagers (12–18 years)	Started	VITO (BE), PIH (BE), NIPH (NO), RegionH-RH (DK), NIOM (PL)
	Continued	JSI (SI), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL)
	Finalized	None
Adults (19–39 years)	Started	NIPH (NO), ISSeP (BE), NIOM (PL), MOH-IL (IL), UPV/EHU (ES)
	Continued	None
	Finalized	UBA (DE)

S4.1.1.3. Targeted Surveys

Participation in online meetings to discuss and agree on criteria for the evaluation of proposals for targeted surveys [VITO (BE), UBA (DE), SpF (FR), ISCIII (ES)]. Providing support to partners who are developing a proposal for a targeted study in PARC [VITO (BE)]. It was decided to postpone the start of projects within the targeted studies starting from Y4. Project Proposals have been elaborated and submitted for review.

S4.1.1.4. Occupational surveys

- **P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL [M1-M29] (The project has been extended from M18 to M29) and is now ended.**

Partners involved in this project: TTL (FI), SpF (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), LSMU (LT).

Cd, PAHs, Cr and BPA were selected as priority substances for this study. General population surveys which have collected data on these substances were identified and, in the end, altogether 7 studies were available for the study. Since most of the selected studies did not include detailed ISCO coding for occupations and this additional coding were made by study owners, and completed datasets were transferred to PEH database and were shared to TTL for data analyses. These data analyses are made in October-November 2024 and the results communicated in the end of November in D4.8 (Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies). This project ended in September 2024 (M29).

- **P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven [M1-M36]**

Partners involved in this project: [KUL, INSA, MU, UGR, AU, LNS, SRU, DPH-UNINA, SpF, BPI].

In the recent online meeting with partners in occupational studies, discussions centered around potential chemical compounds to be included in the Sentinel Surveillance project. Following this, a survey was conducted to assess the preferences of the partner countries concerning chemical compounds for occupational exposure surveillance. The survey results highlighted two key compounds of interest: PFAS and Mycotoxins.

In response to these findings, a new mapping exercise has been initiated and is currently underway. This exercise aims to prioritize the chemicals of focus and assess the capacity of participating institutions to contribute to the project, either through sample collection or via questionnaire-based data gathering. So far, KUL, INSA, MU, UGR, AU, LNS, SRU, DPH-UNINA, SpF, and BPI have actively participated in the exercise. The outcome of this mapping activity will help identify the relevant chemicals, potential occupational exposures, and target workplaces or companies for focused surveillance. However, there have been slight delays in completing the mapping exercise. As a result, an additional 6-month extension has been requested to ensure

the successful completion of the protocol development. Due to several unresolved challenges regarding participant selection, sample representativeness, and cross-country data comparability, it was decided not to extend the project beyond three years. Concerns regarding quality assurance in recruitment, sample collection, and laboratory analyses also remain unaddressed. A six-month extension would not suffice to overcome these issues, making it necessary to end the project as planned.

- **P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU [M1-M48]**

Partners involved in this project: TTL, SRU, MU, INSST, UGR, INRS, ISS, UMIL, UNINA, UNIPD, RSU, LNS, HSE, IOM, INSA

The outline of the occupational healthcare project was defined together with TTL, MU, ENSP, INRS, LNS, SRU, ISS, UNINA, UMIL, UNIPD, RSU, SGGW, IOM, identifying the aims and scope of the project. The project will focus on hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anesthetics and disinfection/cleaning products (ethanol and isopropyl alcohol). Study protocols, selection of target groups and substances, SOPs, information leaflets and informed consent forms have been finalized (TTL, SRU, MU, INSST, UGR, INRS, ISS, UMIL, UNINA, UNIPD, RSU, LNS, SGGW, ENSP, HSE, IOM, INSA). Also training videos for collecting samples have been prepared during autumn 2024. Workshop among study partners was organized in parallel to the WP4 meeting in Berlin (and online) on Oct 7th, 2024 to discuss on the first experiences hgfton the sampling campaigns and remaining open issues.

Specific substances covered in the study include 12 cytotoxics, 4 anesthetic substances and 2 disinfectants. These exposures will primarily be studied in hospital settings in 11 countries (SRU, UNINA, UMIL, UNIPD, INRS, INSST, LNS, TTL, RSU, HSE, MU, UGR, INSA, STAMI). Biomarkers of exposure and effects and supporting external exposure measurements were identified during the Y2 of PARC and laboratories able to analyse these biomarkers have been selected by TTL and SRU. Since the biomarkers covered in this study are generally not included in G-EQUAS, small-scale customized interlaboratory comparisons have been planned (by TTL, SRU, HSE, MU, UMIL) for those biomarkers which are analysed by several laboratories and are conducted during Y3 of PARC.

Interested hospitals have been already contacted in several countries. The aim is to recruit at least two hospitals per country. All partners have already submitted their ethical application and by October 2024 ethical permission was already granted for several partners (TTL, MU, RSU, UNINA/ISS, INSST, UGR). Samplings will start in the end of 2024-beginning of 2025 after ethical approvals.

- **P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL [M1-M48]**

Partners involved in this project: TTL, ENSP, STAMI, KUL, LNS, UniSante, NIOM, WULS, AU, MOH-CY, ULUND, DPH-UNINA, ISS, UMIL, UNIPD, INSA, UGR, AUTH, HSE and IOM.

The outline of the occupational waste management project was defined with the partners involved (LNS, TTL, ENSP, STAMI, KUL, NIOM, WULS, AU, MOH-CY, ULUND, DPH, ISS, UMIL, UNIPD, INSA, AUTH, Unisante, HSE and IOM). Study protocols, selection of target groups and substances, and SOPs, information materials and informed consent forms and other supporting materials including training videos for samplings have been finalized (LNS, TTL, ENSP, STAMI, KUL, AU, MOH-CY, ULUND, INSA, AUTH, Unisante, HSE and IOM). All partners have submitted ethical applications and the majority of partners (ENSP, UNINA/ISS, WULS, ULUND, STAMI, AUTH, TTL, NIM, MOH-CY, KUL, HSE) have already received ethical permission for the study by the beginning of October 2024. A workshop among study partners was organized in parallel with

the WP4 meeting in Berlin (and online) on Oct 7th, 2024 to discuss the first experiences on the sampling campaigns and remaining open issues. Analysing laboratories for various biomarkers (including exposure and effect markers) and external exposure analyses have been selected by TTL and ENSP.

Exposures will be studied in 13 countries and partners have identified and approached waste management companies interested in participating in the study in their countries (ENSP, STAMI, ULUND, DPH, ISS, KUL, UMIL, UNIPD, LNS, AUTH, TTL, AU, NIOM, WULS, MOH-CY, HSE, UniSante). Sampling campaigns have already started in some countries (FI/TTL, GR/AUTH, PT/ENSP, SE/ULUND, BE/KUL, PL/WULS) during the summer 2024 and in remaining countries samplings will start in the end of 2024 or in the beginning of 2025.

S4.1.1.5. Implementation of innovative methods

No project submitted at present

Following T4.1 partners are contributing to the overarching T4.1-T4.3 working group [VITO (BE), LNS (LU)]. Discussions on innovative methods are ongoing and integrated in T4.3 projects and in the T4.1 occupational surveys.

➤ A4.1.2 Supporting activities progress: Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

No projects were planned since it is a transversal activity.

S4.1.2.1. Define the best suited exposure biomarkers (matrix/chemical) and analytical methods for the specific HBM studies addressed in PARC

Under this sub-activity further refinement of the prioritization of exposure biomarkers (matrix/chemical) for the Occupational Studies has taken place after the information collected from different laboratories on the technical feasibility and analytical methods has been updated. The status of harmonization of the analytical methods for the selected compounds has also been revised and updated.

No work has taken place with regard to the PARC HBM Targeted Studies as it was agreed at WP4 level that the proposals would be submitted for Y4.

S4.1.2.2. Ensure the quality and comparability of the analytical HBM data through a flexible Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/QC) programme to cover the needs of the specific HBM studies addressed in PARC

The final selection of biomarkers of exposure for the PARC Aligned Studies has been done, the document was made available in February 2024 with the final update 1st March 2024 by email to study owners and laboratories in the HBM laboratory network as well as in the PARC webpage (available in the T4.1 VITO SharePoint as well as in the WP4 folder at the PARC-ANSES SharePoint). This document presents the levels finally defined, the PARC Aligned Studies scope and the PARC Discovery scope and provides additional information on QA/QC aspects and analytical guidelines.

In the case of the Occupational Studies, the activities have involved a further evaluation of the QA/QC approaches (LNS, TTL, ENSP, SRU, ISCI) in collaboration with T9.3 (online meeting 3rd September 2024). A document on planned analyses and QA/QC actions has been prepared describing the alignment with G-EQUAS for the analyses of biological samples for exposure assessment in the waste management survey and plans for alternative approaches for QA/QC of biomarkers in biological samples in the healthcare study and for the occupational hygiene samples in both studies.

The PARC QA/QC programme has aligned with the G-EQUAS scheme for most of the biomarkers of exposure included in the Aligned Studies and the Occupational Studies and there is a specific proficiency test (PT) for total mercury in hair organized by ISCIII. The programme started in spring 2024, round 1 of the PARC QA/QC programme, and laboratories received their results in July 2024. The second round is now taking place and results will be available in January (for the mercury PT) and February 2025 (for G-EQUAS). Therefore, it is expected that the first list of candidate laboratories for chemical analysis in the HBM studies in PARC is available in March 2025. There has been excellent coordination between the G-EQUAS organisers and ISCIII, supported also by T9.3 (online meeting 12th February 2024).

We are currently evaluating the participation in the first round for which we have received information from 43 laboratories of the 46 that registered in the G-EQUAS scheme in relation to PARC and 30 laboratories in the mercury in hair PT from 18 and 22 European countries, respectively. The results were presented at the WP4 Annual Meeting in October 2024.

S4.1.2.3. Explore new QA/QC approaches to support the use of innovative techniques in HBM surveys in PARC

No further activities have taken place in Y3 as these depend on the further development of the add-ons in the Aligned Studies and other HBM surveys and further identification and alignment of needs and coordination with T4.3 and T9.3.

S4.1.2.4. Harmonise analytical methods across laboratories and define reference analytical methods when possible

The activities on the development of an inventory concept to identify needs and knowledge gaps (key contributor NIPH; other contributors: ISCIII, ISS, LNS, MUI, SCIENSANO, UAntwerpen, ULUND, UNIEVE, UOC) have continued during Y3 with information updates. One working meeting was held (all partners in the subtask listed above; 25th April 2024).

In addition, two new activities on method harmonization have been designed:

- Monitoring urinary mono-n-hexyl phthalate and its secondary metabolites. Coordinated by NIPH; partners: UAntwerpen, RegionH, ULUND, and LNS. Dr. Holger Koch (Institute of the Ruhr-University Bochum, IPA) was invited as an external expert as he has profound experience with HBM of MnHexP and its secondary metabolites through past activities in HBM4EU. Several meetings have been held to plan this activity further (27th May 2024, 25th September 2024 and November 2024).
- PFAS in human samples. Coordinated by NIPH; partners: UAntwerpen, ISS, ULUND, and LNS. Several meetings are held to further plan the activity (19th September 2024, 18th October 2024 and November/December 2024).

S4.1.2.5. Analyse the exposure biomarkers in the samples emerging from HBM task

The chemical analysis plan has been updated (key contributor SCIENSANO; other contributors: ISCIII, MU, ULUND, UGR, UAntwerpen, RSU, AUTH, KUM). The templates for collecting information from laboratories and to monitor the progress of chemical analyses are being updated to accommodate new information needs in the PARC Aligned and Occupational Studies and to harmonise the data with that from other WP, such as WP9, as well as to meet the requirements of WP7. A specific folder in the T4.1 SharePoint has been created as a first step to track the status of the chemical analyses.

A working meeting (all partners in the subactivity listed above; 23rd January 2023) has been held. In addition, coordination meetings with the T4.1 and WP7/9 have also been held (26/09/2024, November 2024).

S4.1.2.6. Analyse effect biomarkers in samples emerging from the HBM task

The activities and planning of the monitoring of the effect biomarker analysis (UGR, ISCIII, VITO), are being done in collaboration with T4.1.3 as the implementation of effect biomarkers will take place under P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO. In the context of this collaboration, the final implementation plan for effect biomarkers and health outcomes in PARC Aligned Studies has been prepared. Specific meetings on effect biomarkers QA/QC aspects in PARC were held on 23rd February 2024 and 12th September 2024.

- A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

S4.1.3.1. Propose health-based HBM guidance values

- **P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_Derivation of HBM-GVs_UBA [M1-M81] (The project has been extended from M36 to M81):**

Partners involved in this project: ANSES, AUTH, LNS, MOH-IL, NIJZ, NIPH, SRU, SECO, TTL, Unisante, UBA, UOULU.

Within the framework of PARC project 4.1.3.1.a, eleven substance dossiers as basis for the derivation of HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs) or HBM Exposure Equivalents for Cancer Risk (HBM-EECR) have been drafted by project month 30, respectively for DHHB (diethylamino hydroxybenzoyl hexyl benzoate, Uvinul® A plus), (gamma/lambda) cyhalothrin, benzophenone-3, diisononyl phthalate (DiNP), diethylhexyl terephthalate (DEHTP), aluminium, nickel, chromium VI, mercury, acetamiprid, imidacloprid (deadline for submission of the respective final reports M36).

Proposals for guide values were/are first discussed within the project and then forwarded to the national hubs for further comments and approval. All partners were/are involved in discussing the proposals for the guide value derivations and answering specific questions, some of the partners have taken the lead for individual substances and their guide value derivation.

UBA has the lead responsibility for the HBM-GV derivation for seven substances with reference to the general population, namely for DHHB, (gamma/lambda) cyhalothrin, benzophenone-3, DiNP, DEHTP, Acetamiprid and Imidacloprid. The PARC NHCP consultation has been finalised for all substances and the corresponding HBM-GVs, except for imidacloprid, which will be included in the consultation shortly.

ANSES is the lead organisation for the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers for aluminium and its compounds, also for the derivation of HBM guide values for the general population and for workers for arsenic and the derivation of HBM-GVs for the pyrethroid metabolites cis and trans DCCA for the general population and for workers. So far, HBM-GVs for aluminium and its compounds have been derived and the consultation within PARC has been completed; work is still ongoing to derive the guide values for Arsenic and the pyrethroid metabolites, but it is already clear that the work on pyrethroids cannot be completed until year 4.

The Finish Institute of Occupational Health (TTL) is in charge of a substance dossier on nickel and the derivation of the associated HBM-GV. Following consultation with the PARC national hubs and final consideration of the comments received this task has already been completed.

A working group consisting of SRU, TTL, Unisante, SECO and partly ANSES was set up to derive further HBM-EECR values for chromium VI. As the HBM-EECR already derived within the framework of HBM4EU is not compatible with the current EU protection objectives, a short document has been prepared with reference to HBM4EU Deliverable D5.12. The supplementary derivations correspond to the cancer risk levels 4/1000, 4/10000, and 4/100000 and use the same approach as for the HBM4EU guide value, i.e. correlation between biomonitoring results and air concentrations. The new values are intended for workers in the chrome-plating sector and for welders. The substance report and the derived HBM-EECRs have already been submitted to the national hubs for expert comment and are now being finalized.

NIPH and TTL are working on the derivation of HBM guidance values for mercury, first drafts are already available and need to be discussed at project level. MOH-IL and LNS are working on the PFAS, a scoping document has been drafted, and literature research and -evaluation of individual PFAS have also already been carried out. The results obtained so far will be discussed further within project 4.1.3.1.a. 6.2.3 (case study mixture RA).

Table 3: Status P4.1.3.1.a Reports -18.10.2024

Project report number	Title	Achievement date	Partner(s) in charge of the project report	Status	Comments (Confidentiality)
Report 1; AD 4.3, part I	Substance dossier on the UV filter Uvinul A plus (DHHB) and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	M36	UBA	Consultation carried out (via PARC National Hubs). Final processing is underway.	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 2; AD 4.3, part II	Substance dossier on the pyrethroid (gamma-, lambda-) cyhalothrin and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	M36	UBA, Unisante	Consultation carried out (via PARC National Hubs). PBPK modelling and, if possible, HBM-GV derivation for workers will be done as requested during consultation	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 3; AD 4.3,	Chromium VI - Derivation of	M36	TTL, SRU, Unisante,	Consultation carried out	Confidential until publication

part III	further HBM-EECRs		SECO	(via PARC National Hubs). Final processing is underway.	in a scientific journal
Report 4; AD 4.3, part IV	Substance dossier on nickel and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers	M36	TTL	Consultation carried out (via PARC National Hubs). Completed after final processing.	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 5; AD 4.3, part V	Substance dossier on DEHP and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	M36	UBA	Consultation carried out (via PARC National Hubs). Final processing is underway.	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 6; AD 4.3, part VI	Substance dossier on DINP and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	M36	UBA	Consultation carried out (via PARC National Hubs). Final processing is underway. Possible addition of HBM-GV for workers.	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 7; AD 4.3, part VII	Substance dossier on aluminium and compounds and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers	M36	ANSES	Consultation carried out (via PARC National Hubs). Final processing is underway.	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 8; AD 4.3, part VIII	Substance dossier on benzophenone-3 and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	M36	UBA	Consultation carried out (via PARC National Hubs). Final processing is underway.	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 9; AD 4.3, part IX	Substance dossier on acetamiprid and derivation of	M36	UBA	Consultation carried out (via PARC	Confidential until publication

	HBM-GVs for the general population			National Hubs). Final processing is underway.	in a scientific journal
Report 10; AD 4.3, part X	Substance dossier on imidacloprid and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	M36	UBA	Report is available in draft form. Consultation will start soon	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 11; AD 4.3, part XI	Update mercury – HBM-GVs	M36	NIPH-FHI, TTL	Ongoing, first draft available	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 12; AD 4.3, part XII	PFAS - scoping review, HBM-GVs for individual PFAS, if applicable	M36	MOH-IL, NIPH-FHI, LNS	Ongoing, draft of scoping document available	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 13; AD 4.3, part XIII	Substance dossier on arsenic and derivation of HBM guide values for the general population and for workers	M36	ANSES	Ongoing	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal
Report 14; AD 4.3, part XIV	Derivation of HBM-GVs for the pyrethroid metabolites cis and trans DCCA for the general population and for workers		ANSES	Postponed to year 4 of PARC.	Confidential until publication in a scientific journal

S4.1.3.2. Identify effect biomarkers for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes

No project submitted at present

The work developed under this sub-activity is described in the project P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO

S4.1.3.3. Link HBM studies to health examination and dietary surveys

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP)

- **P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO [M1-M52]**

VITO and SpF coordinated P4.1.3.3.a, in which VITO is leading the part on implementation of effect biomarkers in PARC surveys, and SpF the part on health outcomes.

Part 1: Health outcomes

Partners involved in this part of the project: [SpF (lead), BPI, IDAEA-CSIC, EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer-IBMT, INSST, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, UKHSA, RSU, TTL, UBA, UPV/EHU, VITO].

A comprehensive mapping exercise and literature review were conducted to assess the current state of knowledge regarding exposure markers, effect biomarkers and associated health effects for prioritized substances in PARC (SpF, EAA, UKHSA, TTL, KU Leuven, INSST, RSU, JSI UBA, Fraunhofer-IBMT, EHESP, LNS, JSI and NIJZ). Based on the insights gathered, SpF was able to propose a set of health measurements to be conducted in various age groups, and specific health outcome questions that were incorporated in the health part of survey questionnaires - S4.1.1.1. Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct (SpF).

During the year, several objectives were addressed as part of the feasibility study. An open call was launched among the project partners (KU LEUVEN, VITO, BPI, EPV/EHU, LNS, RSU, UKHSA) to identify interested HES cohorts. So far, two cohorts have been responded: 3xG (VITO, BE) and INMA (UPV/EHU, ES). For the studies included, SpF have prepared some documents to describe the feasibility study and collect several information about the cohorts (biomarkers, health outcomes data, bio banked samples, etc..). Two bilateral meetings were organized with VITO to discuss the progress of the project in June and October. A new and last open call was launched during the WP4 meeting (October 2024). The available data are currently being compiled and a statistical analysis plan is being developed by SpF and studies involved (VITO, EPV/EHU) to explore the links between past exposures and health effects. Once the data are collected and the statistical plan is finalized, collaboration with T4.1.4 and WP7 will be established.

Part 2: Identification of effect biomarkers

Partners involved in this part of the project: Core partners: VITO (lead), SpF, AU, AUTH, EAA, INRS, INSA, Inserm, ISCIII, JSI, LNS, MU, SECO, TTL, UGR; Additional partners: BPI, CEA, IDAEA-CSIC, KU Leuven, LSMU, NIJZ, NIOM, NLZOH, UKHSA, SRU, Sciensano, STAMI, UGent, ULPGC, UNINA, UNIPD, UOC, UOULU, USI, WULS-SGGW

In year 3, the final effect biomarker & health outcome implementation plan for the PARC Aligned Studies was submitted (M22). In M26, implementation was further discussed with the studies in an online meeting. VITO has made an overview on which studies will measure which biomarkers of effect and on the health outcomes that will be assessed. Based on that, the research questions were formulated. Concerning health outcomes, VITO has been translating the tools identified for health outcome assessment (R-RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth.1) into concrete guidance for the aligned studies in order to be able to pool the data as much as possible for statistical analyses. To collect information on asthma, allergy, and asthma, this has been based on the validated questionnaire of the Global Asthma Network. With respect to neurological outcomes, consensus on which tool to use was not reached. Since some studies are already in implementation phase, VITO made a proposal to what extent harmonization of the collected info is still possible, in agreement with the involved partners. Furthermore, VITO was actively involved in the OECD initiative aimed to develop guidelines for the use of effect biomarkers in HBM settings. Concerning the QA/QC program of the effect biomarkers, UGR together with ISCIII and VITO drafted the document "Design and implementation of a QA/QC laboratory program for the implementation of effect biomarkers" (M32).

➤ A4.1.4 Data management and analysis

Involved partners for this transversal activity [AU-PH (DK), INSA (PT), JSI (SI), MU (CZ), NIPH (NO), PIH (BE), SpF (FR), LNS (LU), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UH (BE), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE)].

S4.1.4.1. Data management

No project submitted at present

Regarding data management, the following activities have been performed: Further evaluation and adaptation of HBM4EU basic data format [VITO]. Evaluation and adaptation of scripts to perform QC of the data, to calculate additional data and to calculate aggregated data from the individual data templates [VITO]. Development of web application (tools) to perform these scripts locally [VITO]. Further maintenance of the European HBM dashboard and PEH data platform [VITO]. Further elaboration and validation of the biomarker list [VITO, MU]. Maintenance of a website to host HBM related activities [VITO]. Support for the questionnaire codebook for the PARC Aligned Studies [PIH, VITO]. Supporting occupational studies in codebook development and data harmonization [TTL, VITO, LNS]. Input and review with regard to HBM metadata [MU, SpF, UBA, TTL, PIH, VITO] to be collected. Feedback and review on the tools, codebooks, dashboard and the website [MU, SpF, UBA, TTL, PIH]. Supporting studies in data management issues [VITO].

S4.1.4.2. Data analysis

The statistical analysis plan for the T4.1 projects is further elaborated [AU-PH, INRAE, INSA, JSI, MU, NIPH, SpF, TTL, UBA, UH, UU-IRAS, VITO]. Two students of UH evaluated the approach to statistically derive European exposure values [UH, VITO]. Support/advice was given to research partners in performing statistical analyses [JSI, NIPH, UU-IRAS, VITO]. Members of the statistical working group participated in specific project meetings for statistical advice [INRAE, JSI, MU, NIPH, UU-IRAS, VITO].

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP)

- **P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO [M1-M48] (The project has been extended from M36 to M48)**

Partners involved in this project: [AU-PH (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), EASP (ES), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), ISCI (ES), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), Sciensano (BE), SpF (FR), SZU-SK (SK), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE)].

Some additional and revised data requests for data access to the individual data are submitted to the PEH data platform for each of the lead partners to get approval for data use of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies [EASP, MU]. For the exposure-effect analyses of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, the manuscript on “Associations between urinary phthalate metabolites with BDNF and behavioral function among European children from five HBM4EU aligned studies” was published in TOXICS [UGR], the manuscript on “Association of environmental pollutants with asthma and allergy, and the mediating role of oxidative stress and immune markers” was published in Environmental Research [VITO]. The main analysis of the research question on “Association between UV filters, acrylamide and non-persistent pesticides and body mass index among adult population” lead by INRAE is finished, sensitivity and stratification analysis will be conducted during the next months with the first draft manuscript proposal”. For the remaining Risk Quotients (RQs), the statistical analyses are being finalized and the manuscripts are being drafted [AU-PH, AUTH, EASP, INRAE, NIPH, SPF, UGR, VITO]. For the geospatial analyses of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, a tool was developed to retrieve geospatial variables from the geocoordinates of participants in collaboration with the P7.2.2b_HBMdatasets project (JSI). Data owners were instructed to derive these geospatial variables and to upload these data to the PEH Data Platform (JSI, VITO). The working group decided on which variables to be of relevance for the substance groups studied

(JSI, MU, VITO). For the occupational and SPECIMEn studies, statistical analyses were initiated (TTL, UU-IRAS, LNS).

A hybrid project group meeting was organized in Granada March 18-19, 2024 (UGR, VITO) and the following partners participated physically: AU-PH, EASP, INRAE, ISCIII, JSI, LNS, NIJZ, NIPH, MU, Sciensano, SpF, SZU-SK, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO. Some other partners joined only online: AUTH, INSA, LSMU, TTL and UBA. Multiple online meetings were organized for the specific studies or research questions (JSI, NIPH, TTL, AUTH, UU-IRAS), with participation of all project partners (AU-PH, AUTH, BPI, EASP, INRAE, INRS, INSA, ISCIII, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, Sciensano, SpF, SZU-SK, TTL, UBA, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO). A core group online meeting was held August 28, 2024 (AUTH, JSI, TTL, VITO).

➤ A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO [M1-M66]**

Project activities have started from M9.

Partners involved in this project [VITO (BE), SpF (FR), ISCIII (ES), LSMU (LT), NIPH (NO), UBA (DE), INSA (PT), LNS (LU), FOPH (CH), MOH-CY].

Organization of project meetings and overall coordination of the project [VITO (BE), SpF (FR)].
Providing input for the PARC feedback to One Substance One Assessment (OSOA) reform proposal [VITO (BE), SpF (FR)]

Development of a document with testimonials on policy uptake of HBM data/results [VITO (BE)]
Initiation of the assessment report of existing monitoring systems in HBM (e.g. WHO mother milk survey) or other domains such as food/feed and assessment of existing international HBM programs and European HBM programs/studies [VITO (BE)]. All partners will contribute to complete the report.

Participation in online project meetings (14.01.2024) [VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), LSMU (LT), NIPH (NO), UBA (DE), INSA (PT), LNS (LU), SpF (FR), FOPH (CH), MOH-CY].

Participation in online inter-task meeting with T1.3 and T2.3 on sustainability (20.09.2024) [SpF (FR), VITO (BE)].

Presentation of project at GB in Hall Tirol (16.05.2024) [SpF (FR), VITO (BE)].

Organization/participation of second meet-up with international experts in HBM at ISES 2024 (Montreal-21-24.10.2024 28.09.2023) [VITO (BE), UBA (DE), FOPH (CH)].

Participation in hybrid meeting (Berlin - 07/10/2024) physical [VITO (BE), UBA (DE), LSMU (LT), SpF (FR), NIPH (NO), ISCIII (ES), MOH-CY (CY), INSA (PT)], online [LNS (LU), FOPH (CH), DOMG (BE), ANSES (FR)]

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

Project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO: The contribution of RSU in Year 3 (Y3) and presumably in Year 4 is and will be lower than planned due to the HBM survey involving children and teenagers being put on hold. This delay is attributed to challenges in obtaining the necessary ethical approval, caused by the absence of a national biomonitoring law. The adoption of the law has experienced repeated delays resulting in unexpected hurdles, including the need to establish a Central Medical Ethics Committee for projects involving children. Until this law is adopted, RSU does not have the required legal structure to proceed with such evaluations, which has led to a temporary pause for their participation in the survey for minors.

For the project P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO, an extension of one year was requested for the following reasons: For the further analyses of the HBM4EU MoM-study, the SPECIMEn study and the HBM4EU occupational studies, a delay was caused in the initiation of the statistical analysis, due to capacity issues at the involved partners' institute. For the geospatial analysis of the HBM4EU aligned studies, it took some time to come up with the best technical solution to derive geospatial variables from the geolocation of the participants, and for the development of this tool. And now some time will be needed to allow the data owners to train themselves and implement the tool. For the exposure-effect analyses of the HBM4EU aligned studies, the approval of the data requests took longer than anticipated.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD4.8	Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies	TTL	M18 (postponed M29)		AD4.8 is delayed to M29 due to requested delay for the related project P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL

1.2.4.2 Task 4.2. Environmental and multisource monitoring

Leader: INERIS (FR), AU (DK)

Participants: ANSES (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CNRS (FR), CNR-IRSA (IT), CSIC (ES), CSTB (FR), EA (UK), EAWAG (CH), EFET (EL), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), FISABIO (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), NKUA (EL), OFB (FR), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SYKE (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCLM (PT), UFZ (DE), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UniLU (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), ISCIII (ES), VUA (NL), NILU (NO), UKCEH (UK), BPI (EL), NMBU (NO), SpF (FR), DCU⁶ (IE)

⁶ AMD-101057014-118: Dublin City University – PARC acronym “DCU”, PIC number 999892588 entered as new Beneficiary in PARC as of 01/10/2024 with the agreement that the ‘Environment Protection Agency’ (EPA) remains the only member of the Grant Signatory Board and takes over responsibility for coordinating Ireland’s engagement in PARC in the same way as other grant signatories with AE do. The starting date for the eligibility of the costs for DCU was on 01/10/2024 and DCU will contribute under T4.2.

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU [M1-M42] (The project has been extended from M36 to M42)**

This pilot project consists of six steps, which are intended to form the backbone of all environmental and multisource projects in T4.2. PFAS and EDCs were selected for the pilot project according to the following overall plan:

- EDCs are analysed in air, water, soil and biota (fish), using a combination of bioassays, target analyses and suspect screening (ideally covering the full EDC list).
- PFAS are studied in two complementary approaches: A baseline study using existing monitoring data on diffuse PFAS contamination, and a series of case studies focusing on the transport and transformation of PFAS from known sources to aquatic recipients.

After the completion of the second step (4.2.2 Review of existing knowledge) and the third step (4.2.3 Design of the monitoring campaign) in 2023, the work in 2024 focused on the operational activities for the setup of the monitoring campaigns (EDCs and PFAS case studies), the collection of existing monitoring data (PFAS baseline) (both under 4.2.4 Monitoring activities) and the organization of the data flow and transfer and statistical data analysis (4.2.5 Data analysis and transfer). Documents produced in this phase and minutes of meetings in subgroups are available on the T4.2 section of the PARC SharePoint site.

4.2.4 Monitoring activities

EDCs

More than 200 samples were collected throughout the EU covering 4 matrices and different scenarios and reference sites. During the operational phase, the project partners organized their work into four working groups: Sampling and sample preparation, Target analysis, Suspect screening, and Bioassays. The working group partners met weekly, while project leaders' meetings were held biweekly to ensure all activities were well aligned.

SOPs for sampling and sample storage were developed for each matrix (water: INERIS, IVL; soil: SLU, OVAM, INERIS; biota: NKUA, ONIRIS, IVL, INERIS; air: IVL, INERIS) as well as extraction protocols (generic protocol for bioassay and suspect screening and specific protocols for target analysis).

The Bioassay WG (INERIS, BfG, INSERM, UFZ) established a battery of bioassays which were accompanied by guidelines and SOPs to ensure a harmonised approach.

The Target Analysis WG dedicated significant effort to prioritising substances for target analysis versus suspect screening, starting with a list of 7300 compounds (list which was then curated in collaboration with NORMAN and published in Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944199>). Priority for target analysis was given to compounds with the highest evidence of ED-activity according to existing experimental and predicted data, high relevance for the selected bioassays and scarce environmental monitoring data. A list of substances fulfilling these criteria was proposed to the analytical laboratories. The final choice was determined as the best compromise between the selected criteria and the analytical capacity of the laboratories. 8 laboratories (Water: BRGM, IDAEA-CSIC, ISSeP, SLU, SYKE, UFZ, VSCHT; Air: IDAEA-CSIC, ISS, RECETOX, NILU, NKUA; Soil: BfG, IDAEA-CSIC, ISS, ISSeP, RECETOX, SLU; Fish: IDAEA-CSIC, ISS, ONIRIS) engaged for the analysis of a total of 260 compounds in water, 350 in air, 200 in soil and 200 in biota.

The Suspect Screening WG developed dedicated SOPs and selected three sub-lists of ED-suspects for different matrices: 3203 for water, 261 for air, 2690 for soil, and 2070 for biota. This resulted in a total of 3868 unique substances, which were assigned to the appointed expert

laboratories (Water: AU, BfG, BRGM, INERIS, UFZ; Air: AU, Fisabio; Soil: BfG, NKUA; Fish: NKUA, ONIRIS).

The EDC monitoring campaign was launched at the end of 2023 for fish, followed by the other matrices (water, soil and air) in winter-spring 2024. The work involved sampling (Water: BfG, IDAEA-CSIC, INERIS, ISSeP, IVL, JSI, OVAM, UG-PL; Soil: IDAEA-CSIC, INRAE, ISSeP, IVL, RECETOX, OVAM, UG-PL; Air: Fisabio, IDAEA-CSIC, ISSeP, IVL, RECETOX, NILU; Fish: IDAEA-CSIC, ISSeP, IVL, NKUA, SYKE, UG-PL, UL), coordinating laboratories (Water: IVL, INERIS, UG-PL, JSI; Air: RECETOX; Fish: NKUA; Soil: SLU) responsible for collecting and forwarding samples to analytical labs, and analyzing laboratories selected based on their expertise and resources for the project. The Project Leading Team established dedicated procedures to ensure that all steps of the process were carried out in a coordinated and harmonised way. SOPs describing the different steps of the processes (sampling, preparation, intended analyses) were produced for each matrix. Tracking and data collection files were shared and filled in at each step of the sampling and analytical work to ensure the traceability of the samples, to keep record of any deviations from the SOPs and to facilitate sample processing and planning.

It is expected that the data collection work will be finalised in 2024.

PFAS baseline

The work for the derivation of baseline values for PFAS (co-leaders: CNR-IRSA, OVAM) in the different countries is ongoing and considers different land uses. A total of nine partners (CNR-IRSA, OVAM, BRGM, ISSeP, Sciensano, SLU, SYKE, UBA, UL) are actively involved in this process, which has facilitated the identification of datasets from at least ten European countries and for different matrices. Data covering up to 70 different PFAS (depending on the dataset) is currently being collected in a harmonised protocol (checked for FAIR principles by WP7) and transferred as described under “Data analysis and transfer” below. In parallel, a plan for statistical analysis of the data has been initiated and will be pursued further as described in “Data analysis and transfer”. At least six WG meetings were organized in 2024 with the partners involved.

PFAS Case studies

In parallel to the PFAS baseline, a series of PFAS case studies were launched with a complementary character to the PFAS baseline study. While the PFAS baseline study addresses diffuse PFAS contamination in the environment, the PFAS case studies focus on PFAS emission sources and subsequent pathways to the aquatic environment, with particular interest in the role of precursors. This activity is co-led by SLU and OVAM and addresses a common set of five research questions using a combination of methodological approaches such as target analysis, suspect screening, non-target analysis, and determinations of PFAS Total, such as EOF and TOPA. In total, 19 distinct case studies have been developed in eleven EU countries (by SLU, OVAM, SYKE, UAntwerpen, VSCHT, INRAE, EAWAG, UKEA, CNR-IRSA, UBA, IDAEA-CSIC, AU, BRGM). The environmental compartments include biota, soil, groundwater, surface water, marine/brackish water, wastewater, sludge and solid particulate matter. In 2024, the partners involved worked on sample collection and analysis.

Four WG meetings were organized in 2024 with the partners involved. An in-person workshop is being planned for early 2025 to bring the individual case studies together in a combined approach to the defined research question.

4.2.5 Data analysis and transfer

The fifth step in the pilot project, the data analysis and transfer, started with a definition of the data flow plan at the end of 2023, in collaboration with WP7 and in line with the whole PARC DMP, and is currently being consolidated.

A new project leading team (DATA Group) (RECETOX, UFZ, INERIS, AU, OVAM and CNR-IRSA) was appointed for this task in January 2024. The partners have defined a workflow covering all aspects related to QA/QC of the sampling and analytical data provided by the laboratories, data transfer to the database before statistical analysis and interpretation. Various meetings were held in order to ensure a smooth handover of tasks from 4.2.3 to 4.2.5. This occurred while the analytical work (in 4.2.4) was ongoing, so both project leading teams worked on this part, approaching it from the organisation of the analyses and the data processing, respectively. This also included further developments of initial considerations for the analysis of the PFAS baseline data, which include the retrospective addition of information on land uses for all sampling points, the verification of the minimum requirements for data acceptability based on QA/QC criteria set in this project phase, the handling of values below detection limits etc.

All data collected and generated in the different parts of the project will be uploaded in a protected area of the NORMAN EMPODAT Database to facilitate data processing during the project, which had been decided together with WP7 in earlier phases of the project. This data transfer has included multiple meetings with NORMAN representatives on optimized data collection templates for this project. All data will be made available in IPCHEM at the end of the project.

For both EDCs and PFAS, a pan-European approach has been chosen corresponding to the European regions covered in T4.1. The design of the monitoring campaign (without the detailed monitoring plan) has been described in AD4.5 finalized 19.9.2023.

- **P4.2.b Y2 Monitoringframe [M13-M36] (The project has been extended from M30 to M36)** (including preparatory transversal work in Y1):

The project leaders for this ongoing project are UBA, OVAM, INERIS and AU. Following the comprehensive review in 2023 of scientifically established prioritization schemes and approaches documented in the peer-reviewed literature, along with a series of workshops and project meetings, the project partners reached a consensus on a prioritization concept that meets the needs of T4.2. The result (described in D4.1, February 2024) is a conceptual framework where; to answer a given research/regulatory question, the users will be able to build their own “filter” (by selecting and combining multiple criteria and associated indicators), resulting in a categorisation of the substances matching the given research/regulatory question. Subsequently, the substances can be ranked within each category. The activities in 2024 focused on the next steps in dedicated working groups, addressing “Data sources and evaluation”, “IT infrastructure” and testing of the tool in selected “Case studies”. The WG “IT infrastructure” (NKUA, UBA, OVAM, INERIS, AU) has been in charge of converting the approved prioritization concept into an operational and automated tool. The prototype was discussed with partners at various meetings and was gradually improved based on their feedback. In parallel, the task of the WG “Data sources and data evaluation” (OVAM, INERIS, UBA, AU, CNR-IRSA, ISSeP, UKCEH, INRAE, NKUA, NILU, SYKE, Sciensano, IVL, BRGM) has been to provide an overview of indicators and their corresponding databases and/or models for retrieving substance-specific information.

Since accessible data for a wide spectrum of indicators is a cornerstone in the prioritisation framework, various databases have been identified that could feed into the prioritisation scheme but need to be maintained and updated.

Particular attention was also devoted to collaboration with the development of the EWS in T8.2 which had also identified the prioritization of signals as a central step in an EWS. A joint workshop was held on 4-5 June 2024 at the University of Athens to develop this topic further, both separately for T4.2/T8.2 and jointly (Examples of questions that were addressed in the breakout sessions

during the workshop: i) How can the prioritisation scheme in T4.2 accommodate early warning? ii) Sharing of models and computational tools; iii) Possibilities of sharing models and computational tools, infrastructure, platforms between EWS in T8.2 and the prioritization framework in T4.2; iv) Case studies linking T4.2 and T8.2).

Several partners (AU, INERIS, BRGM, CNR-IRSA, CNRS, CSTB, EAWAG, FISABIO, IDAEA-CSIC, INRAE, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, OVAM, NKUA, Sciensano, SLU, SYKE, UA, UBA, UG-PL, UKCEH, UL FFA) have signed up for contributing in the WG "Case studies". Their development started at the workshop in Athens (project meeting organized back-to-back to the workshop) (Participants in the workshop: NKUA, SLU, INERIS, AU, OVAM, CNR-IRSA, UBA, UKCEH, UL FFA, SYKE, Sciensano, IVL, Fraunhofer) with a shortlist of relevant case studies. To be able to finalize the case studies and evaluate the outcome the projects have been extended and will now end M36 instead of M30.

A collaboration is envisaged with the NORMAN network.

- **P4.2.c_Y3_Human Exposure_INERIS_AU [M25-M72]**

This project was initiated in 2024 in collaboration with T4.1 as it connects with the HBM General Survey under the responsibility of T4.1. The purpose is to i) generate personal environmental exposure data for the participants in the General Survey and ii) to generate knowledge of environmental non-food exposure sources to chemicals, focusing on the indoor environment, drinking water and soil (mainly related to homegrown vegetables). A project leading team has been established (AU, INERIS, LNS, CSTB, NILU) and the additional project participants have been preliminarily identified (VITO, MU, ISCIII, IDAEA-CSIC, ISSeP, IVL, JSI, NKUA, OVAM, UAntwerpen, UBA, UniLU, VSCHT, UL, UPV/EHU, ISS, AUTH, MO-CY/SGL, RSU). As this required some budget transfers, the list still needs final consolidation.

The project was kicked off at a hybrid workshop at LNS in Luxembourg (30th May 2024), with the following participants: AU, AUTH, CSTB, IDAEA-CSIC, INERIS, ISS, ISSeP, IVL, JSI, LNS, LU, MOH-CY/SGL, MU, NILU, OVAM, RSU, UAntwerpen, UBA, UniLU, UPV/EHU, VITO.

At the workshop, the objectives of the projects were discussed and adopted. Other topics were the alignment with the T4.1 activities, external links to other initiatives in the field and the establishment of Working Groups addressing specific aspects of the projects. The workshop concluded on a need for Terms of References of each WG, ensuring complementarity and links to the overall T4.2 project steps as tested in the P4.2.a_Y1 project.

Subsequently, WG leaders have been defined and started the work in the following WGs: WP1: Prioritization of substances; WG2: Harmonized methodology for sampling; WG3: Chemical analysis; WG4: Existing samples and contextual information; WG5: Data management and statistics. WG-specific meetings are held regularly, in addition to project leader meetings on a bi-weekly basis. A hybrid meeting of the whole project group took place in Berlin on 10th October 2024, as a satellite event of the WP4 meeting.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

- **P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU**

A 6-month extension was requested for this project. The justification is related to the high level of complexity of the project involving several parts (EDCs and PFAS), each including several complex activities, such as a comprehensive EU-wide sampling campaign for the EDCs and 19 monitoring studies for PFAS in different European countries. There were slight delays in each of these activities, particularly related to sampling logistics. In addition, the use of different

monitoring tools, e.g. bioassays and target analysis, requires more time to ensure a rigorous interpretation of the data and to exploit all possibilities of an integrated data analysis. Finally, the third part of the project (extensive collection of existing PFAS data to establish a European baseline) has been more time consuming than expected due to curation work on heterogeneous data sets.

- **P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe**

A deviation from the original time plan was identified as regards the achievement of Landmark 2 (“Launch of the online operational tool for prioritization of environmental multi-source monitoring” M24). The development of the IT-infrastructure could start only in January 2024 and not in May-June 2023 as originally planned. The preparatory tasks outlined in the work plan, which were necessary before embarking on the development of the prioritisation framework, encountered delays compared to the original schedule.

The working group comprised participants with varying experiences and perspectives. While this diversity was enriching, the working group took more time than anticipated to align with the concept of prioritisation, to agree on common terminology, and establish a common understanding.

This delay has impacted the achievement Landmark 3 (Results of Case studies M28) and Landmark 4 (Results of first implementation of the online tool M28).

For these reasons an extension of the project to M36 has been accepted. With the new Gantt Chart Landmark 3 is now planned for M32 and Landmark 4 for M34).

A third workshop (to be held in person in Athens on 4-5 June 2024) was organized in collaboration with T8.2. While this collaboration was included in the original project description, no dedicated workshop had been assigned to it. The idea of this joint workshop was brought up by T8.2 at an in-person meeting in May 2023 and welcomed by T4.2 as a promising collaborative initiative.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D4.1	Description of a mechanism for selection of chemicals / matrices / endpoints for projects	INERIS	M20	M25	Delays due to multiple exchanges between reviewers and authors

1.2.4.3 Task 4.3. Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Leader: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INERIS (FR), INRS (FR), , IRFM (IT), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), ONIRIS (FR), ORU (SE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE),

UBAH (UK), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UGR (ES), UniLU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), AUTH (EL), BPI (GR), CNR-IRSA (IT), EV-ILVO (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), IVL (SE), JU (CZ), KUM (DE), LNE (FR), NIB (SI), NIJZ (SI), NILU (NO), NIOM (PL), OFB (FR), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), SYKE (FI), THL (FI), TNO (NL), UG-AT (AT), UG-PL (PL), UKCEH (UK), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UNIADBN (UK), VSCHT (CZ), WULS-SGGW (PL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Six Height projects have been elaborated in year 1 were conducted during the reporting period, in line with the roadmap established for task 4.3., which were primarily designed by the co-lead teams. These projects were then all progressed globally as planned, under the lead of the respectively appointed project leader teams.

➤ A4.3.1 Transversal actions

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC_WR [M1 - M60] (The project has been extended from M36 to M60)**

This project relates to definition and harmonisation of QA/QC Issues for SS/NTS/EDA approaches.

Lead: WR, Partners involved: INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AU), ONIRIS (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), AUTH (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), LNE (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL).

As a starting point, an inventory was made on existing QA/QC procedures, guidelines, and proposals regarding the application of SS/NTS approached in the food, environmental and HBM domains, with contributions from all partners. In Y2 In order to avoid any duplication of already existing resources, a gap analysis was performed from the previous inventory that led to a content refinement for the present project, to focus on two important but still underconsidered aspects then selected to be specifically addressed in this project for future usage of SS/NTS/EDA data for in a context of RA/regulatory purposes. These worklines included (1) the harmonization of the way by which the chemical coverage of each method is evaluated and reported, and (2) how to make the output better suited not only for qualitative but also (semi) quantitative exposure pattern comparison. Two working groups have been established to focus on these key aspects. Working group 1 started on the development of a common QA/QC marker mix for analytical method QA/QC and chemical space coverage reporting. Working group 2 has initiated an inventory of existing strategies for semi-quantification or normalization of SS/NTS results. The current status and next steps are presented and discussed during the annual WP4 meeting in Oct 2024.

- **P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03-EWStools_SLU [M1 - M60]**

This project relates to relevant contribution to EWS (WP8.2).

Lead: SLU, Partners involved: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), ORU-MTM (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), AUTH (EL), ISS (IT), NILU (NO).

This project consists of multiple steps, with the first one focusing on reviewing existing information related to (self-)sampling, suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as early warning monitoring tools and secondly formulate criteria for the categorization of annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format. These activities have been summarized in a perspective article on innovative approaches as a contribution to an EWS which is planned to be submitted in December 2024. This project is in close collaboration with Task 4.2 focusing on environmental samples for analysis of PFAS from source to recipients using target, suspect and NTS approaches and in close collaboration with Task 8.2 focusing on environmental samples (e.g. solid particular matter (SPM), wastewater, fish) using target, suspect, NTS and EDA approaches.

- **P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP [M1 - M60]**

This project relates to the elaboration of integrated Data Processing Workflow.

Lead: EHESP (FR), Participants: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), MU (CE), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), WR (NL)

Following our workplan, we have launched in 2023 our data preprocessing collaborative trial using HBM/food/environmental datasets in order to 1) identify and select the most appropriate data preprocessing tools to implement in the Galaxy Workflow (in terms of performance and interoperability between tools) and 2) test the different QA/QC we proposed to assess the performance of the data preprocessing step in different real life situations (these QA/QC will be used to generate automatic reports). 15 partners have agreed to participate; the trial was launched in March 2023, ended in August and we are currently collecting the different results.

In Y3, we also progressed on the generation of new tools to automatize the suspect screening process within the Galaxy workflow. We are developing a tool that will automatically build or update suspect screening libraries from PubChem, this tool will be highly interoperable with the Scannotation tool that generate automatic pre-annotation of experimental HRMS datasets with different scoring. This new tool will be presented to the partners and validated before implementation in the workflow.

We have also progressed on the Galaxy domain that will host the HRMS exposomics workflow (ie RECETOX domain).

- A4.3.2 Human samples-based proof-of-concepts

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP)

- **P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE [M1 - M48]**

This project relates to a first proof-of-concept application focused on perinatal exposure

Lead: INRAE (FR); Participants: EHESP (FR), CEA (FR), VUA (NL), KUM (DE), UNIVIE (AT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), UAntwerpen (BE), UGR (ES), AU (DK), UniLU (LU), LNS (LU), UNIABDN (UK), MU (CZ), ISPV (ES), VSCHT (CZ), BPI (EL), VITO (BE), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (SP), SU (SE), AUTH (EL)

The actions run within this project during the considered reporting period were conducted in alignment with the previously established roadmap. The achieved activities are summarized as follows:

1st Pillar: A round of SS/NTS was conducted on urine, serum, and maternal milk samples collected from 30 pregnant women and across different analytical platforms. Fourteen partners

applied their in-house workflows to analyze the samples. A harmonized reporting template was elaborated and provided to all participating partners. The results from a general profiling of the chemical exposure of these women were collected and compared across the different samples (urine, serum, milk) and between the various labs. These results demonstrate the partners' capability to perform exposomic profiling on different human matrices. Importantly, they represent a first new experimental dataset documenting the presence of chemicals of emerging concern and real-life chemical mixtures present in such human samples.

2nd Pillar: Harmonizing SS-NTS analysis across the EU is crucial for large-scale application. As a first step toward harmonization, a mixture of 50 QA/QC markers was established and prepared, covering a wide range of chemicals in terms of physicochemical properties and usage. Using this mixture, an inter-lab assay was conducted with fourteen partners across three different matrices (serum, urine, and maternal milk). Each partner used their own SS-NTS workflows, allowing for a comparison of different approaches in terms of chemical coverage and sensitivity. The link between the observed chemical coverage and each individual method technical details is ongoing as a matter of deeper critical analysis and possible methodological recommendations or reference SOPs.

3rd Pillar: This pillar focuses on both innovative sampling methods and innovative sampling matrices. Two working groups, involving partners from WP 4.1-4.3, were formed, and two literature reviews were initiated, focusing on the use of silicone wristbands (SWB) and dried blood spots (DBS) for HBM. In parallel with the bibliographic work, a testing phase is being prepared to evaluate how these new types of sampling supports are influenced by analytical treatments when applied in the context of SS/NTS chemical profiling for HBM.

A physical meeting was held in Nantes, France, on April 15th and 16th, regrouping all the H01 partners, with representatives from both H02 and H03. During the meeting, the results from the chemical profiling of the 30 pregnant women and the inter-lab study were presented and discussed. Future actions were also defined during this meeting.

- **P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS/LNS [M13 - M60]**

This project relates to a second proof-of-concept application focused on occupational exposure.

Lead: INRS (FR), LNS (LU), Participants: WULS-SGGW (PL), INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UGR (ES), STAMI (NO), UAntwerpen (BE), TTL (FI), UEF⁷ (FI), MU (CZ), JSI (SI), WR (NL), BPI (GR), AUTH (GR).

The H02-Occupational Project began with the Drafting and Presentation of the Project Proposal. This phase involved a comprehensive review and finalization of the proposal by all partners in a dedicated kick-off meeting where the proposal was formally presented and discussed [October 2023; key partners: INRS, LNS, help from all partners]

- **Sample Sourcing and SOP Development:** this task entailed identifying sources for SWB, dried DBS, and conventional samples, and drafting SOPs for sample collection. The development of these SOPs was conducted in collaboration with the 4.1.1.4 "Occupational

⁷ AMD-101057014-118: The University of Eastern Finland - PARC acronym "UEF", PIC number 991207984, entered in PARC as new affiliated entity as of 01/05/2024 with the Finnish Institute of Occupational Health - PARC acronym "TTL", acting as Beneficiary. The starting date for the eligibility of the costs for UEF was on 01/05/2024. UEF contributes in the project P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure of the WP4 (task 4.3), by providing innovative nontargeted screening approach for analysis of conventional blood samples by non-targeted UHPLC-MS method and in task 9.4 with their participation in the mapping of existing training, and in the outline of PARC training plan.

surveys". As a result, SOPs for SWB and DBS samples were finalized, and revisions were made to the SOPs for urine and blood sampling [February 2024; all partners]. Additionally, a training session video and a Q&A session were produced following the SWB and DBS SOPs [March to September 2024; key partners: INRS, LNS, WULS].

- **Sample Storage and Shipment:** efforts were directed toward identifying laboratories capable of receiving, storing, and distributing samples collected under WP4.1 to the 4.3 partners for analysis. Three laboratories have been identified, INRS for urine and DBS samples, LNS for dust and SWB samples and UUF/TTL for blood samples. Currently, the sampling under WP4.1 is ongoing, with no device testing conducted yet. The next step involves receiving samples from the 4.1 projects.
- **Methodological Testing for SWB and DBS:** two reviews were initiated in collaboration with the H01 project to evaluate the methodological aspects of using SWB and DBS samples [key partners: EHESP (FR, H01), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), LNS (LU), TTL (FI) and other partners will join during Y4].
- **Activity Repartition and Analytical Capabilities:** a dedicated Excel file was created in collaboration with H01 to inventory the innovative methods developed by all partners [all H01 and H02 partners, June 2023]. Furthermore, confirmation of analytical capabilities was gathered from all H02 partners [February 2024, all partners].
 - **Interlaboratory Assay for SS/NTS:** an interlaboratory assay based on the H01 PILAR 2 results from the H01 project is ongoing, in collaboration with H01/H03 projects. This assay will use an expanded list of QA/QC mix to cover a broader range of substances. The list of QA/QC mix has been adjusted and communicated to all partners [key partners: INRS (FR), INRAE (FR), JSI (SI), AUTH (GR), UGR (ES); Jun 2024]. Urine and plasma samples for the assay have been provided by INRS (FR), AUTH (GR), and JSI (SI). The next steps include preparing QA/QC samples in October 2024, shipping samples under the MTA to all involved partners in November 2024 and completing analysis and results reporting by February 2025. [February 2025; all partners]
- **P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementary developments_JSI/UAntwerpen [M25 - M72]:**

This project marks the third proof-of-concept application aimed at expanding the chemical space covered by NTS/SS analyses.

Lead: JSI (SI), UAntwerpen (BE), Participants: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEA (FR), IISPV (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), VUA (NL), WR (NL), WULS-SGGW (PL), INRAE (FR), CNRS (FR), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), AU (DK)

The project officially started in M25 and will last for 48 months. The actions run within this project during the considered reporting period were conducted in alignment with the previously established roadmap. The ongoing and achieved activities are summarized as follows:

- In the frame of Project co-building phase (M25-M31), the project kick-off meeting was held on June 12, 2024, with 41 attendees representing most partner institutions. Key objectives, methodologies, and project directions were outlined, focusing on:
 - Alternative sample matrices (e.g., saliva, hair)
 - Enhanced sample preparation methods (e.g., deconjugation, phospholipid removal)
 - Orthogonal LC separation techniques like HILIC chromatography and IM-MS.

The project's timeline was established, including a 1.25-year co-building phase, followed by planning and sourcing (0.5 years), laboratory analysis (1.25 years), and final evaluation (1.25 years). Partners provided input on research interests, potential student cohorts, and experimental setups. Further, the attendees were asked to take an active role in answering polls on their particular research interests, decisions were taken regarding the preparation of a research perspective paper, initiation of the PhD cohort interactions and PhD exchange, plans about finalizing the extended QA/QC list for the interlab study, as well as regarding setting up two working groups for initial lab experiments with the interested participants:

- Group 1: HILIC and add-on separations (IM-MS)
- Group 2: alternative matrices (hair, saliva)
- Other collaborative efforts are linked with project 4.3.2.b_H02 to extend the QA/QC list for an upcoming interlaboratory study, and with 4.1 Gen Survey for sample sharing discussions. Meetings were also held with ISS (IT) to coordinate a 2025 student exchange.
- In the frame of Initial investigations phase (M25-M40) experiments were conducted to evaluate HILIC's role in expanding the chemical space for polar components in human matrices. Initial results from a study on ovarian cancer patients versus healthy controls demonstrated HILIC's value in identifying exposure biomarkers potentially linked to ovarian cancer. A research paper on these findings is in progress.

The second main line in the initial investigations phase deals with the potential of hair as a matrix to provide complementary information on human exposure. To this end we began testing a multi-residue analysis method for hair samples, aiming to consolidate a broad range of exposure biomarkers into a single HPLC-MS workflow. Future stages will transition this method to an NTS/SS approach.

➤ A4.3.3 Environment samples-based proof-of-concepts

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP)

- **P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH [M1 - M48] (The project has been extended from M36 to M48)**

This project relates to wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) and mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for environmental exposure assessment.

Lead: UFZ (DE) & UBATH (UK), Participants: MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), IRFM (IT), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), ISS (SP), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), UL-FFA (SI), BRGM (FR), JU (CZ), MU (CZ), INRAE (FR), OFB (FR), UL (LV), UG (PL), VITO (BE)

Ongoing activities in Y3:

Focal point of the project is a Pan-European Study which should demonstrate the application of the developed approaches both for WBE and environmental exposure assessment on a representative dataset involving multiple laboratories and complementary analytical methods.

To this end, a set of developed suspect and non-target screening methods for Wastewater-Based Epidemiology (WBE) was established at six different laboratories, which will be benchmarked against targeted methods. Regarding environmental assessment, a combination of complementary GC-HRMS and LC-HRMS methods and bioassays covering a range of relevant endpoints were established, which aim at a comprehensive toxicological and chemical

fingerprinting of wastewater and allow a prioritisation of samples for subsequent EDA. As a basis, a machine learning-based model was developed from a data set of 105 (raw) wastewater samples stemming from different sources to identify source-specific features and compound fingerprints. This is currently validated against a novel dataset of 30 samples and will be combined with a classification and prioritization of potentially toxic compounds from mass spectra-derived molecular fingerprints using tandem mass spectrometry.

The current state and potential of high-throughput EDA was reviewed (peer-reviewed paper published: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-024-05424-4>) and a HT-EDA method was developed which allowed the identification of drivers of androgenicity in hospital wastewater conducted, combining high-throughput fractionation, non-target screening and toxicity prediction (manuscript currently under review).

The Pan-European Study covers influent and effluent samples from 30 WWTPs across Europe (one large Wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) with mixed wastewater input and one small WWTP with mainly domestic inputs in each of 15 countries), where samples were taken between June and September 2024 and are currently processed and sent out for analysis in November 2024.

- **P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS [M13 - M60]**

This project relates to sentinel animal species as EWS for detecting emerging chemicals

Lead: ONIRIS (FR), Participants: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), Eawag (CH), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), INRAE (FR), JSI (SI), OFB (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), UG-AT (AT), VUA (NL).

The project has been sub-divided in 3 Actions. Action 1 on aquatic invertebrates (mussel/gammarids) is led by SU (SE) and ONIRIS (FR). Within this Action, the listing of all sample sets that would be available is on-going. Action 2 on bees and bees products is led by JSI (SI) and ANSES (FR). Within this Action, a PhD project has been defined between the two Action leaders and a PhD-candidate recruited as of October 1st. Other partners are interested in this Action and discussions are on-going to determine how to aggregate them on the PhD-project. Action 3 is led by ONIRIS (FR), with support from OFB (FR). It relates to the drafting of a systematic review article on animal sentinel species for chemical hazards in the environment and food. A scope and plan proposal is under drafting. A potential Action 4 on earthworm (with possible connection to the future project on soil) is on hold and will be reconsidered next year depending on the remaining resources.

- A4.3.4 Food samples-based proof-of-concepts

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02-Food item exposure_ANSES [M13 - M48]**

This project relates to the application of SS/NTS to food products.

Lead: ANSES (FR). Participants: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), BfG (DE), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UL-FFA (SL), VSCHT (CZ), WR (NL), WULS (PL), EV-ILVO (BEL), GCSL (EL).

The online Kick-off meeting (KoM) with all interested participants was held on 22 February 2024. Participants who were interested in participating to the first action consisting in an interlaboratory exercise confirmed their participation (CEA, ISS, JSI, MUI, ONIRIS, VSCHT, WR, WULS-SGGW,

GSCL, EV-ILVO, ANSES-Fougères, ANSES –MA). The experimental design for this interlab assay was finalized by project leaders according to discussions with partners (number of samples, matrices of interest, levels of concentration, etc.). The selection of two relevant food items to be considered in the project has been fixed based on concerted discussions performed on Y2 and the beginning of year 3. Baby food and honey will be the matrices of interest in the interlaboratory trial. A list of 30 relevant chemical substances was defined to be used as QAQC markers in baby food and honey positive control samples. From these 30 substances, the identity of only 10 of them will be communicated to the partners. At this stage, samples and substance standards were acquired. The preparation of the samples by project leaders and their dispatch to the participating partners has been scheduled for October 2024. From this date, the participants will begin to prepare and analyse the samples using their own SS/NTS analytical methodologies based on LC-HRMS for global profiling.

Concerning the method development component of the project, in January 2023, the work on the development of an SS/NTS method based on LC-HRMS was started (PhD thesis co-financed in half by PARC), in order to complete the panel of investigated substances by all partners. The development of SS method of about 70 biocidal substances in milk and chicken muscle has been realized. The target screening methodology has been validated, and the validation of the workflow for the SS is ongoing.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.5 Work package 5. Hazard Assessment

1.2.5.1 Task 5.1. Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern

Leader: NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), BPI (EL)

Participants:

Activity 5.1.1: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), BfR (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), IMR (NO), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIPH (NO), NVI (NO), Sciensano (BE), STAMI (NO), TTL (FI), ULFFA (SI), UMIL (IT), UNAV (ES), UNIVIE (AT), WU-TOX (NL)

Activity 5.1.2: BfG (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), IEP-NRI (PL), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGent (BE), UPO (ES), UU (SE)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

- A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P5.1.1a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVE [M1-M48] (project extended from M36 to M48)**

In this project, data gaps on the mycotoxins (*Alternaria* and enniatins toxins) for human health are being closed by generating data on relevant toxicological endpoints.

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

Sourcing of test items:

- Finalization of the public tender: all test items from the public tender (BEA, ALT, ATX-I, TEN) were delivered to the partners [BfR (DE)]
- Synthesis of enniatin A, A1, B and B1 and of AME by chemical synthesis and delivery to partners [TUB (DE), BfR (DE)]; the synthesis of AOH is still pending due to unexpected difficulties with the selected synthesis strategy, which are aimed to be solved by the end of year 3, but is clearly associated with substantial delays in the *in vitro* testing. So far, inclusion of AOH was only possible with compound individually purchased by different groups, originating from *Alternaria* cultivation upon purification, thus not necessarily chemically pure as to be expected from chemically synthesized compound as planned in WP5.1.1a
- Characterization of the enniatins, BEA and AME [NVI (NO), UNIVIE (AT)]

Ongoing work of *in vitro* assays to close data gaps:

- Genotoxicity:
 - Finalization of SOS/umu testing for ENN A, A1, B and B1. Results of the assays with all enniatins were negative in the presence and the absence of S9 [UNAV (ES)]
 - Ames assay: completed testing for TeA. TeA did not induce mutagenic effect in TA98 and TA100 (+/- S9); preliminary testing for TEN and ALT on strains TA97a, TA98, TA100 and TA1535; toxicity testing for ENN A, A1, B and B1 in TA98 finalized [BfR (DE), NIB (SI)]
 - yH2Ax assay: completed for Enniatin A, A1, B, B1, BEA and ATX-I, AME, ALT, TeA and TEN, no induction of yH2Ax after 24h incubation in HepaRG cells [BfR (DE)]
 - Micronucleus Test: completed testing for ENN A, A1, B and B1.
 - All tested enniatins were negative after 3h and 24h of incubation in TK6 cells with and without S9. Positive for TeA, ATX-I, AME and AOH after 24h exposure without S9. Negative for ALT and TEN after 24h exposure without S9. Positive for AME after 3h exposure with S9 and negative for TeA and ATX-I after 3h with S9. Negative for TeA after 3h without S9 [Sciensano (BE)]
 - Regarding TeA, long exposure (48 h) to 1, 10, 50, and 75 µM revealed a significant increase in MN frequency in HepG2 cells at concentrations above 50 µM, as compared to non-exposed cells, while short exposure (3 h) caused a significant increase in MN above 75 µM [INSA (PT)].
 - Regarding AME, 3 h exposure to 1, 5, 10, 20 and 30 µM did not result in a significant increase in the MN frequency. However, after 48 h exposure, there was a significant increase in MN frequency at concentrations of 20 µM and 30 µM, as compared to non-exposed cells. All experiments were performed without S9 [INSA (PT)].
 - EFSA has published the opinion “Genotoxicity of beauvericin” in October 2024, and this document is being taken into consideration for future activities.
- Endocrine effects:
 - H295R steroidogenesis assay acc. OECD456: start of the assay was delayed due to a delivery problem of the Nu-serum; cytotoxicity testing for ENN A, A1, B and B1 is finished [ISS (IT)]
 - Preliminary experiments with positive and negative controls for AR STTA (OECD TG 458) have started [BPI (EL)]

- Completed testing of ER STTA (OECD TG 455) for ENN A, A1, B and B1, AME, TeA and BEA. The enniatins, BEA and TeA showed no agonistic or antagonistic effect. AME showed no antagonistic but an agonistic effect [INRS (FR)]
- Preliminary experiments with positive and negative controls for E-screen assay in MCF-7 cells have started [BPI (EL)]
- Ongoing work on Thyroid-related MIEs with enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins [BfR (DE)]
- Immunotoxicity:
 - THP-1-Lucia NF-kB reporter system Enniatins A, A1, B, B1, *Alternaria* toxins TeA, ATX-1, AOH and AME tested in THP1-Lucia monocytes. TeA, enniatins A, A1, B, B1 do not affect the LPS-induced induction of NFkB-activation in THP-1 monocytes in non-cytotoxic concentrations. ATX-1, AOH, AME showed a concentration dependent suppression of LPS-induced induction of NFkB-activation in THP-1 monocytes [UNIVIE (AT)]
 - TLR and Dectin reporter assay AOH and AME show some reduction of LPS-induced TLR-NFkB signal, while ATX-1 increased the TLR-NFkB signal in the absence of LPS. ALT, TeA and TEN did not significantly impact the TLR-NFkB signal alone or in combination with LPS [STAMI (NO)].
 - PBMC viability, cytokine profiles and immunophenotyping in male and females [NIPH (NO)]
- Additional activities:
 - Absorption and metabolism of enniatins [ANSES (FR), NVI (NO)]
 - Kinetic of AOH glucuronidation for PBPK modeling in WP5.3.4 [UNIVIE (AT)]

Project meetings:

- Preparation of monthly project meetings [BfR (DE), UNIVIE (AT)] with participants [NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), ANSES (FR), WU-TOX (NL), STAMI (NO), NIB (SI), UNAV (ES), BPI (EL), Fraunhofer (DE), ISS (IT), NVI (NO), Sciensano (BE), INSA (FR), INRS (FR)]
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (27-29 May 2024, Lisbon, Portugal)
 - Accelerating the identification of enniatins and related metabolites [NVI (NO) - Poster]
 - Effects of enniatins and *Alternaria* mycotoxins toxins on a human intestinal model [NVI (NO) - Poster]
 - Genotoxicity assessment of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins with the *in vitro* micronucleus assay [Sciensano (BE) - Poster]

Conferences:

- NSFT Winter meeting 2024 (25-28 January 2024, Beitostølenm, Norway):
 - Innate immune responses of *Alternaria* toxins *in vitro*: Receptor activation, inflammation induction, and signal transduction [STAMI (NO) - Poster]
 - Closing data gaps on natural toxins effect on human health: Immunotoxic effects of *Alternaria* toxins using a co-culture lung exposure model [STAMI (NO) - Poster]
- EUROTOX 2024 (8-11 September 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark):
 - Steroidogenesis assay (OECD TG 456) to fill data gap on BPA alternatives and on the natural mycotoxins enniatins and beauvericin: preliminary results from two PARC projects [ISS (IT) - Poster]
 - Metabolism of enniatin B in primary mouse, rat and human hepatocytes [ANSES (FR), NVI (NO) - Poster]
 - Investigating the genotoxic effects of the *Alternaria* toxin Tenuazonic Acid in human liver cells [INSA (PT) - Poster]
- EEMGS/ICAW2024 (23-27 September 2024, Rovinj, Croatia):
 - Genotoxicity assessment of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins with the *in vitro*

- micronucleus assay and the SOS/umu test [Sciensano (BE), UNAV (ES) - Poster]
- Closing regulatory data gaps on the genotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis of natural toxins and bisphenols [INSA (PT), BfR (DE), UNIVIE (AT), NIPH (NO) - Oral presentation]
- 45th Mycotoxin Workshop (2-5 June 2024, Vienna, Austria):
 - Immunomodulating effects of *Alternaria* toxins activation on the toll like receptor – NFkB/AP-1 signalling pathway [STAMI (NO) - Poster]
- 4th HBM Workshop (19 April 2024, Lisbon, Portugal):
 - Contribution to the characterisation of *Alternaria* toxins' genotoxicity in human liver cells [INSA (PT) - Poster]

Deliverables and publications:

- Crudo et al. Discovery of the *Alternaria* mycotoxins alterperyleneol and altertoxin I as novel immunosuppressive and antiestrogenic compounds *in vitro*, Archives of Toxicology, submitted in June 2024, published in October 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-024-03877-1> [UNIVIE (AT)]
- Finalization of a review paper to enniatins and BEA [BfR (DE), NVI (NO), UNAV (ES), INSA (PT), BPI (EL), Sciensano (BE), ANSES (FR), ISS (IT), UNIVIE (AT), NIPH (NO), IMR (NO), INRS (FR), NIB (SI)]
 - **P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_Human tox_BfR [M1-M54] (project extended from M36 to M54)**

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

Substance Testing and SOP Development:

- Solubility studies were completed for all prioritized BPA alternatives (listed below) to determine substance stability and bioavailability. [ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), ISCII (ES), LIH (LU), MUI (AT)]
- Prioritized BPA alternatives numbered 0 to 8: 0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, 3-BPS-MAE, 4-Pergafast 201, 5-BPP, 6-BPAP, 7-TCBPA, 8-TBBPA.
- A living SOP document was prepared and distributed for substance testing. It is continuously updated by WP5 partners, incorporating the solubility and bioavailability data for the BPA alternatives. [INSA (PT), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), TTL (FL), ULFFA (SI), ISCIII (ES), LIH (LU), NILU (NO), MUI (AT)].

In Vitro assays to close data gaps:

Metabolism – Biotransformation [Leaders: INRAE (FR), ISS (IT)]

- As needed for regulatory purposes, the purity of all prioritized BPA Alt CHIRON batch has been confirmed using HPLC-UV and H-NMR in the 8 prioritized substances and BPA that is use as reference chemical.
Our prioritized BPA Alternatives are also available as radio-labelled molecules except for 3-BPS MAE. In addition to our listed substances, we will study: 10-BPS, 11-BADGE and BPB.
- Cytotoxicity assays were completed in HepaRG cells as well as HepG2 cells for all substances (CHIRON's list of 21 molecules)- Metabolic fate/biotransformation studies: pilot radio-HPLC profiling in HepaRG cells completed for 0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, 4-PF-201, 5-BPP, 6-BPAP.
- Ongoing: all other radio-labelled molecules. Next steps: mass balance (³H or ¹⁴C) studies. 4-Pergafast 201 and 5-BPP are the only prioritized BPA alternatives not planned to be tested in Y4.
- Isoform specific metabolism study ISS (IT) has been carried out on BPZ. No reliable data were obtained due to stability problem of test item in the incubation buffer and its low solubility in

MeOH (unique solvent which is use for the stock solution preparation using recombinant enzymes and Human liver microsomes). Next step will be to use BPE as test item which shows a higher solubility in water matrix.

- An HPLC-Diode array method has been set up to detect and quantify the BPA alternatives: BPZ, BPP, BPE, BPAP, BPS-MAE and TCBPA.
- The developed HPLC-Diode array method has been applied in preliminary biokinetic study analyzing samples of Jurkat cells used in some Immunotox experiments [ISS, (IT)].
- An SOP for sample preparation and biokinetic analysis was prepared and uploaded in the sharepoint to apply the same methods to the cell systems used by other groups [INSA (PT), ISS (IS)].

Endocrine disruption [Leaders: ISS (IT), INRAE (FR)]

- H295R steroidogenesis (OECD TG 456) by [ISS (IT)]
 - 7 out of 8 prioritized BPA Alternatives were tested using 0-BPA as reference chemical.
 - Substances tested: 0- BPA; 1- BPZ; 2- BPE; 3- BPS-MAE; 5- BPP; 6- BPAP; 7- TCBPA; 8- TBBPA.
 - Relative cytotoxicity potency: BPP > BPZ > BPAP > BPS-MAE > BPA, BPE
- *In vitro* test (under consideration by EURL ECVAM) by [ISCI (ES)]

Substances, experiments performed, n numbers of replicates:

- T3 transport inhibition/IC50 by: 0-BPA (n=6), 1-BPZ (n=3), 2-BPE (n=4), 3-BPS-MAE (n=3), 4-Pergafast 201 (n=3), 5-BPP (n=3), 6-BPAP (n=3), 7-TCBPA (n=3); 8-TBBPA (n=5) EXTRA // 9-BPH (n=4), 10-BPS (n=3), 11-bagde (n=3), 12- trans CBDO (n=3) and Controls (Silychristin n=10)
- I- transport inhibition/IC50 by: 0-BPA (n=2), 8-TBBPA (n=2) and Controls (ClO₄⁻ n=4)

Carcinogenicity [Leader: INSA (PT)]

The three experimental approaches planned to assess genotoxic and genotoxic carcinogenicity were developed as follows:

- Battery of genotoxicity tests (as defined by EFSA) – bacterial gene mutation test (Ames test) and *in vitro* micronucleus assay in mammalian cells
 - Ames test was completed for two BPA alternatives: 2-BPE and 5-BPP, with and without metabolic activation [ISS (IT)].
 - SOP completed and test procedure standardized for the micronucleus assay.
 - Dose-finding experiments (MTT, CBPI) completed and preliminary results of the micronucleus assay obtained for five compounds: 2-BPE n=2, 5-BPP n=1 [ISS (IT), INSA (PT)];
- Micronucleus, comet and transcriptomic assays in 2D and 3D HepG2 cells
 - SOPs were completed for assays in 2D and 3D HepG2 (Comet Assay and MN Assay) [Fraunhofer (DE), NILU (NO), INSA (PL)].
 - Dose- range finding based on cytotoxicity testing was completed for six of the 8 prioritized BPA alternatives, BPA as control and 13-BPG as additional test substance (0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, 5-BPP, 6-BPAP, 7-TCBPA, 8-TCBBPA) [Fraunhofer (DE)].
 - Implementation of the micronucleus and comet assays in 3D HepG2 cultures started [Fraunhofer (DE), NILU (NO)]
- Bhas 42 cell transformation assay
 - SOPs were prepared and Test procedure (initiation and promotion) agreed [INSA (PT), NILU (NO), TTL (FL), INRS (FR)].
 - Preliminary inter-lab comparison using controls, and a 0-BPA dose-range was carried out and results compared and discussed to assess the performance of the laboratories

involved and agree on critical points of the assay [INSA (PT), NILU (NO), TTL (FL), INRS (FR)].

- Dose-range finding (based on cytotoxicity assay) was performed for prioritized BPA Alt: 0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, 3-PBS-MAE, 5-BPP, 6-BPAP, 7-TCBPACompounds and preliminary data has been produced for CTA assay for three of the selected compounds [INSA (PT), NILU (NO), TTL (FL), INRS (PT)].

Developmental Neurotoxicity [Leader: CNRS (FR)]

- Adverse cognitive effects - *In vitro* screening of cellular effects of BPA alternatives [CNRS (FR)]
 - Assessment of gene expression for markers of pluripotency and differentiation into hippocampal progenitors and mature neurons to validate the protocol derive hippocampal neurons from human induced pluripotent stem cells.
 - Assessment of gene expression for sex steroid and thyroid hormone (TH) receptors. Tests of cellular viability following exposure to 0-BPA, 1- BPZ, 2-BPE, 6-BPAP.
 - Cellular effects of BPA alternatives on neuronal network formation, synaptogenesis. Collection of samples for:
 - methylation studies [LIH (LU)]
 - TH signaling studies [INRAE (FR)]
- Molecular and epigenetic analyses for the identification of relevant biomarkers [CNRS (FR) and LIH (LU)]
 - Started the analyses for exposure to 0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, 6-BPAP.

Immunotoxicity [Leader: UMIL(IT)]

- Identification of immune cell targets and effects of bisphenols on immune functions [UMIL (IT)]
 - Studied the impact of BPA and its analogues (0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, 3-BPS-MAE, 6-BPAP, 7-TCBPA // EXTRA: BPP) on T independent antibodies production using an *in vitro* human model (PBMC)
- Inflammation-induced tryptophan breakdown and related immunobiochemical pathways [MUI (AT)]
 - Immunometabolism markers
 - Model: human PBMC and/or relevant human monocyte-derived cell lines measured together with standard proliferation assays
 - Preliminary information on cytotoxicity and cell viability has been shared.
 - Reporter gene activation, in combination with metabolite measurements will provide deeper insights into the modulation of immunobiochemical pathways such as inflammation-induced tryptophan breakdown.
 - Investigation in a lung epithelial model will be performed in a limited set of compounds.
- Investigation of the relationship between bisphenols' immunotoxicity and their effect on the glucocorticoid system [ULFFA (SI)]
 - *In silico* screening with Endocrine Disruptome; effects of bisphenols on the release of cytokines from THP-1 macrophages and Jurkat cells.
 - 0- BPA; 1- BPZ; 2- BPE; 3- BPS-MAE; 5- BPP; 6- BPAP; 8- TBBPA
- To provide new mechanistic data for AOP development, the effects of BPA analogs on the intracellular calcium homeostasis of both resting and stimulated immune cells will be evaluated
 - Dose-finding experiments for 1-BPZ (trypan blue, Jurkat cells, media with and without proteins).
 - Acute and long-term (24h) effects of 1-BPZ on both resting and stimulated intracellular

calcium levels.

Meetings:

- Internal project meetings:
 - Ongoing with the Task/Activity Leaders 5.1.1, Project Managers, Endpoint leaders and partners. Our project reviewers are mostly experts from ECHA and to have a better overview and understanding of our work they are joining our monthly meetings. The participants are as follow:
 - Regulatory Agencies: ECHA, EFSA, EEA are welcome to join. So far, only experts from ECHA have joined our monthly meetings. A5.1.1 Activity Leaders [NIPH and INSA]
 - Project Manager [BfR (DE)]; P5.1.1.b Endpoint Leaders: Metabolism - Biotransformation [INRAE (FR), UMIL (IT)]; Endocrine disruption [ISS (IT), INRAE (FR)]; Carcinogenicity [INSA (PT)]; Developmental Neurotoxicity [CNRS (FR)]; Immunotoxicity [UMIL (IT)]
 - Partners joining the specific Endpoint meetings: [NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), ISS (IT), TTL (FL), ULFFA (SI), ISCII (ES), INRS (FR), Fraunhofer (DE), LIH (LU), NILU (NO), MUI (AT)].
 - At the same time, each Endpoint Leader set up a minimum of 4 meetings with their partners.
 - e.g. carcinogenicity meeting: Regular meetings were organized both with all partners involved in this specific endpoint and with partners involved in each of the 3 more specific activities described below, in order to plan the work and agree on critical issues related to experimental procedures and planning (INSA (PT), BfR (DE), Fraunhofer (DE), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INRS (FR)).
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (Lisbon, Portugal: 27-29 May 2024):
 - Cellular and molecular effects of exposure to BPA alternatives in hippocampal neurons derived from human induced pluripotent cells [CNRS (FR), LIH (LU), INRAE (FR) - poster]
 - *In vitro* effects of BPA analogues on the immunoglobulin production [UMIL (IT) - poster]

Conferences:

- SOT 63rd Annual Meeting and ToxExpo (10-14 March 2024, Salt Lake City, USA):
 - *In vitro* effects of bisphenol A analogues on human B and T lymphocytes activation [UMIL (IT) - poster, immunotoxicity (PARC registration number 151)]
 - Opportunities within the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) for Respiratory Sensitization [LIH (LU) - Immunotoxicity (PARC registration number 185)]
- 4th HBM Workshop (19 April 2024, Lisbon, Portugal):
 - Contribution to the hazard assessment of substances alternative to bisphenol A: genotoxic and carcinogenic effects in mammalian cells [INSA (PT) - poster, carcinogenicity (PARC registration number 218)]
- 16th Conference of the International Society of Tryptophan Research (ISTRY) (24-26 April 2024, Jena, Germany):
 - IDO-1 activation is a key event, driving immunotoxicity [MUI (AT) - Immunotoxicity (PARC registration number 162)]
- ITCASS / ERGECD meeting 2024 (12-14 June 2024, Liverpool, UK):
 - *In vitro* effects of BPA and its analogues on antibody production [UMIL (IT) - presentation, carcinogenicity (PARC registration number 269)]
- EUROTOX 2024 (8-11 September 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark):

- Steroidogenesis assay (OECD TG 456) to fill data gap on BPA alternatives and on the natural mycotoxins Enniatins and Beauvericin: preliminary results from two PARC projects [ISS (IT) - Poster, Endocrine disruption (PARC registration number 208)]
- *In vitro* evaluation of immunotoxicity of bisphenol A substitutes using THP-1 cell line [Immunotoxicity]
- SNE annual meeting (16-19 September 2024, Nice, France):
 - Cellular and molecular effects of exposure to BPA alternatives in hippocampal neurons derived from human induced pluripotent cells [CNRS (FR) - poster, developmental neurotoxicology]
- EEMGS/ICAW2024 (23-27 September 2024, Rovinj, Croatia):
 - Genotoxicity assessment of BPA alternatives [Carcinogenicity]
- NanoTox2024 (23-25 September 2024, Venice, Italy):
 - Which *in vitro* liver model suits best for predictive toxicological research: A comparison [Fraunhofer (DE) - poster, carcinogenicity (PARC registration number 255)]

Deliverables and publications:

- Mhaouty-Kodja et al. A critical review to identify data gaps and improve RA of bisphenol A alternatives for human health. *Critical Reviews in Toxicology*, Submitted in May 2024, accepted in July 2024, DOI: 10.1080/10408444.2024.2388712. [NIPH (DK), INSA (PT), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), ULFFA (SL), ISCIII (ES) IBMT, LIH (LU), NILU, BfR (DE)]
- Closing regulatory data gaps on the genotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis of natural toxins and bisphenols [INSA, BfR, UNIVIE, NIPH] (invited communication, carcinogenicity).
- Franko N, et al. Adverse outcomes of the newly emerging bisphenol A substitutes. *Chemosphere*, Submitted in May 2024, published in August 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2024.143147>

- **P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES [M25-M60]**

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32

Substances:

The enniatin B1 synthesis was initiated in 2024, and purity of the substance will be checked (TUB (DE)).

The public tender has been published to subcontract the 14-day and TG408 studies under GLP, and the CRO is being selected. [ANSES (FR)]

As this project is based on a data gap identified by EFSA, a dialogue with them has been ongoing since the beginning of the project.

Project meetings:

- Several meetings took place at ANSES to discuss the administrative process of the public tender [ANSES (FR)]:
 - A meeting took place with ECHA to discuss their interest in the project, specifically the use of transcriptomics in chemical hazard assessment (11/03/2024) [ANSES (FR)]
 - Two meetings with EFSA were organized when setting up the project, and to keep them updated on its status [ANSES (FR)]
 - Four meetings were organized with WP5 partners of this project to discuss the analyzes they plan on performing and set up the experimental aspects of the project. [ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), TUB (DE), UNAV (ES), NGERE-INSERM (FR), WU-

TOX (NL), NVI (NO)]

- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (27-29 May 2024, Lisbon, Portugal): ANSES (1 poster)
- PARC consortium meeting (16-18 May 2024, Tirol, Austria): ANSES (1 poster)

Participants: [ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), NIPH, INSA (PT), TUB, UNAV, NGERE-INSERM (FR), WU-TOX (NL), WR (NL), NVI (NO)]

➤ A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment)

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

• **P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_Ugent [M1-M36]**

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

Mixtures of natural toxins, including both cyanotoxins and mycotoxins, have been tested during Y3. Selection of mixtures was based on results of the toxicity testing with single compounds carried out in Y1 and Y2.

Detailed descriptions of the assays that are being conducted to close the data gaps:

- Mixture tests of PSP producers (saxitoxin) and microcystin LR producers with copepods and daphnia following OECD TG211 and ISO guidelines for marine copepods. Results of both tests will be compared to understand differences between marine and freshwater species in terms of sensitivity. Both Ugent & UoB will do the same experiments with daphnia to allow interlaboratory comparison but also the collection of biological material for sufficient omics analysis if relevant in a later PARC follow up action. [UGent (BE), UoB (UK)]
- Mixture tests of combinations of mycotoxins that have been detected in effluent sewage and surface waters. Based on results from toxicity tests of single compounds of zearalenon, deoxynivalenol and enniatins on *L. stagnalis* embryos, exposure to mixtures at environmental relevant concentrations will be assessed on adult *L. stagnalis* reproduction according to OECD TG243. [SLU (SE)]
- Mixture tests of combinations of different chemicals with MC-LR (Microcystin-LR) in exposure to algae (OECD TG201): Terbutylazine (TBA) and cadmium as well as with cylindrospermopsin: TBA and cadmium. As can be seen, it was decided to apply a full factorial approach to test the same chemicals with the two cyanotoxins initially selected within M6 as this would allow a comparison between all combinations. [UAVR (PT)]

All partners are on track to finish the work in the allocated timeframe of three years.

Meetings:

- A short in person meeting was held at the SETAC Europe 34th Annual Meeting (5-9 May 2024, Seville, Spain) (all partners).
- WP5 meeting in Lisbon (27-29 May 2024, Lisbon, Portugal) [UGent (BE), UAVR (PT)] where [UAVR, (PT)] presented the results.
- Short meetings between [UoB, (UK)] and [Ugent, (BE)] were held via Teams regarding the joint experimental setup over the summer.

Conferences:

- SETAC Europe 34th Annual Meeting (5-9 May 2024, Seville, Spain):
 - Influence of Temperature on Acute and Chronic Toxicity of Marine Algal Toxins — A Case Study with Copepod *Nitokra spinipes* [UGent, (BE) - Poster]

- Acute Toxicity of Harmful Algae on Marine Zooplankton in the Context of Climate Change [UGent, (BE) - Poster]

Deliverables and publications:

- Liu W. et al. Temperature dependent sensitivity of the harpacticoid copepod *Nitokra spinipes* to marine algal toxins. Chemosphere, submitted in June 2024, published September 2024 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2024.143420> [UGent (BE)]
- Pinto A. et al. A short-term exposure to saxitoxin triggers a multitude of deleterious effects in *Daphnia magna* at levels deemed safe for human health. Science of the Total Environment, submitted in June 2024, published in August 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.175431> [UGent (BE), UAVR (PT)]

- **P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU [M1-M48] (project extended from M42 to M48)**

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

In Y3, experimental work (tests with individual compounds) and the development of analytical methods is ongoing. Parameters being tested include mortality, reproduction, endocrine effects, regeneration, oxidative stress, behavior, growth, DNT, development, cytotoxicity, genotoxicity.

In summary the prioritized BPA alternatives for Environmental Health are:

Table 4: prioritized BPA alternatives for Environmental Health

List of compounds – based on workshop outcome (for Environment):	
1-BPZ	2,4'-DIHYDROXYDIPHENYL SULFONE
2-BPE	trans-2,2,4,4-Tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobu-tanediol
3-BPS-MAE	Benzyl 4-hydroxybenzoate
4-Pergafast 201	4,4'-bis(N-carbamoyl-4- methylbenzenesulfonamide)diphenyl-
5-BPP	methane
6-BPAP	4-hydroxyphenyl 4-isoprooxyphenylsul-fone
7- TCBPA	Methyl bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetate
BPPH	4,4'-Thiodiphenol
BPS-MPE	Urea-urethane Compound
Substances that are frequently identified in environmental compartments (e.g. surface water, soil, sediment):	
BPB, BPF, BPS, BPAF, BADGE	

Activity i: investigation of the adverse effects (e.g. apical endpoints such as mortality, effects related to the anticipated mode of action or MIE, effects on reproduction) of BPA alternatives on organisms belonging to different taxa.

- **Aquatic invertebrates** [BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), IEP-NRI (PL), UG-PL (PL), UAVR (PT), SU (SE), INERIS (FR), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), Cefas (UK), UFZ(DE)]
 - Regeneration assay – freshwater planarian *Girardia tigrina* (BPE, BPS MAE, BPZ): Head Regeneration assays with the planaria *Girardia tigrina* were performed with BPA and assays testing for effects of BPZ, and BPE, BPAF are currently ongoing. Additional endpoints (biochemical markers, behaviour and reproduction) will be initiated soon with BPA and the most/least toxic BPA alternatives [UAVR (PT)].
 - Acute toxicity test on *Daphnia magna* (TG 202) (BPP, BPAP, BPS MAE, Pergafast 201, BPAF, BPB, BPF, BPS, BPZ, BPF, BPS, BPZ, BPPH, BPBP, BPE, BPA, BADGE, BPB,

BPZ)

- Tests of single BPS, BPF, BPB and BPAF completed [BPI (EL)]
 - Testing started with a delay due to procedures for purchasing chemical reagents and the need to ensure compliance with national legislation [IEP-NRI (PL)].
 - Acute toxicity tests in *Daphnia magna* were carried out with Bisphenol S and food limitation. Eight concentrations of BPS were tested with and without food stress. 21-day *Daphnia* survival and reproduction were recorded as endpoint. The experiment was repeated three times, providing 65 replicates per concentration. Results showed that sensitivity dramatically increases, 6-fold at LC50 range and 70 fold at LC10 range of concentrations. The BPS effect concentration with low food at LC10 was 3.8µg/L. These combined effects can be predicted by Stress Addition model (SAM, Liess et al 2016), not by Effects Addition Model (EA, Bliss et al., 1939). Next plans include Testing BP mixtures in combination with natural stressors and using SAM approach for the prediction of mixture and multiple stress effects [UFZ (DE)].
 - Experimental work with toxicity assessment of single compounds BPE, BPZ, BPF is completed. The calculations of endpoints based on nominal concentrations are performed. Analytical methods have been developed and fully validated. The calculations of endpoints based on measured concentrations is on-going and measured concentrations is on-going. Moreover, a machine learning approach was developed to investigate the structural relationships of bisphenols and their alternatives to identify the most important structural properties combined with logD that directly affect toxicity to *Daphnia magna* according to the procedure Test No. 202: *Daphnia* sp. Acute Immobilisation Test. To confirm the model's reliability and accuracy, the experimental validation of is now being performed. [UG-PL (PL)].
 - BPA, BPF, BPS, and 3 additional bisphenol substitutes not yet assessed [INERIS (FR)].
 - 48-hour acute toxicity tests on *Daphnia magna* with single compounds BPA, BPAF, BPE, BPF, BPS, and BPZ have been completed. Previous experimental data for BPB are also available and will be processed. 24-h and 48-h LC50/LC10 values were determined based on the nominal concentrations. Our results indicated the following toxicity order for the bisphenols: BPZ > BPAF > BPA > BPE > BPF > BPS [SU (SE)].
 - *Daphnia magna* reproduction test (TG 211) (BPS, BPA, BPF, BPZ)
 - Testing started with a delay due to procedures for purchasing chemical reagents and the need to ensure compliance with national legislation [IEP-NRI (PL)].
 - Testing effects of BPF on the somatic growth and reproduction of *Daphnia magna* has been completed following 7-day and 21-day exposures, respectively, using the calculated 48-h LC5 concentration of BPF. In addition, data on 21-d OECD Reproduction test for BPA and BPS are available and being processed [SU (SE)].
 - Short term juvenile hormone activity screening assay (JIHASA, OECD proposal) (BPF, BPS, BPE, BPB, BPA, BPZ): Not yet assessed [INERIS (FR), UAVR (PT)]
 - *Lymnaea stagnalis* reproduction test (TG 243) (BPZ, BPA, BPS MAE, BPAP, BPE)
 - Tests completed for BPA, BPZ and BPS-MAE [SLU (SE)].
 - Tests completed for BPE and BPAP. BPS-MAE to come. *L. stagnalis* embryo exposure completed for BPE and BPAP, both with and without maternal exposure [SDU (DK)].
 - *Hyalella Azteca* chronic toxicity test (BPZ, BPA, BPAF, BPAP): tests completed [Cefas (UK)]
 - *Arenicola* marine toxicity test (BPZ, BPA, BPAF, BPAP): tests completed [Cefas (UK)]
- **Algae/aquatic plants** [IISPV (ES), IEP-NRI (PL), BPI (EL), UG-PL (PL), SU (SE)]

- Algae growth inhibition test (TG 201) BPZ, BPB, BPF, BPS, BPE, BPAP, BPS MAE, BPPH, Pergafast 201, BPP)
 - Tests on BPS, BPF and BPB completed [BPI (EL)]
 - Algal growth inhibition test (*Pseudokirchyniella subcapitata*) with single compounds for BPA, BPS, and BPF has been completed [SU (SE)].
- Lemna sp Growth inhibition test (TG 221) (BPE, BPP, BPZ, BPE, BPA, BPAF, BAGDE, BPS MAE, NPB, BPC, BPF, BPS)
 - Analytical methods for determining individual bisphenols (BPE, BPP, BPZ) in SIS medium were developed, tests were carried out on individual substances, test end points were determined [IEP-NRI (PL)].
 - Experimental work with toxicity assessment of single compounds BPS, BPE, BPA, BPF is completed. The calculations of endpoints based on nominal concentrations are performed. Analytical methods have been developed and fully validated. The calculations of endpoints based on measured concentrations are on-going and measured concentrations are on-going [UG-PL (PL)].
 - Growth inhibition tests with Lemna minor (freshwater) and Ceramium tenuicorne (brackishwater, marine) for BPA, BPS and BPF have been completed [SU (SE)].
- **Zebrafish** [INERIS (FR), UAVR (PT), SDU (DK), BPI (EL), NIB (SI)]
 - Fish embryo acute toxicity test (TG 236) (BPAF, BPC, BPB, BPF, BPS, BPAP, BPPH, BPS MPE, BPE, TCB PA, BPS MAE, BPZ)
 - Tests on BPS, BPF and BPB completed [BPI (EL)]
 - Tests on BPA, BPAF, BPPH and BPAP completed [NIB (SI)]
 - Tests have been completed for BPA, BPAF, and BPZ. Additional endpoints, including behavior and a set of biochemical markers, were also assessed. Data analysis for these three bisphenols and BPS-MAE testing is currently ongoing [UAVR (PT)].
 - Tests on BPA, BPAF, BPB, BPC, BPC-Cl, BPF, BPS, BPS-MAE, BPS-MPE and TCBPA completed [INERIS (FR)].
 - EASZY assay: detection of substances acting through estrogen receptors using transgenic CYP19A1B GFP zebrafish embryos (TG 250): tests on BPA, BPAF, BPB, BPC, BPC-Cl, BPF, BPS, BPS-MAE, BPS-MPE and TCBPA completed. Tests on other bisphenol substitutes (BPE, BPZ, BPAP, BPP) still on going [INERIS (FR)].
 - Effect of bisphenol on metabolism in tg (cyp3a65:GFP) zebrafish embryos (no OECD TG associated with this assay): tests on BPA, BPAF, BPB, BPC, BPC-Cl, BPF, BPS, BPS-MAE, BPS-MPE and TCBPA completed [INERIS (FR)].
- **Amphibians** (BPE, BPS MAE, BPZ) [UAVR (PT)]: *In vitro* toxicity of single BPA, BPZ, BPS-MAE and BPE, for amphibian cell lines is almost finished, only BPAF still needs to be tested. *In vivo* assays with amphibians are still running with some delays due to the need to repeat some assays. Data for BPS-MAE and BPAF is already available.
- **Soil organisms** [BPI (EL), IISPV (ES)]
 - earthworm reproduction test (TG 222) (BPE, BPF): definitive test is completed for BPZ and on-going for BPE [BPI (EL)].
 - reproduction test on *Caenorhabditis elegans* (ISO 10872) (BPE, BPF): range finding tests are ongoing [IISPV (ES)].
 - Effects on soil microorganisms: carbon transformation test (TG 217 and ISO 11274) (BPAF, BPB, BPS MAE, BPF, BPS, BPC, BPS MPE): range finding tests are ongoing [IISPV (ES)].
 - Effects on soil microorganisms: nitrogen transformation test (TG 216) (BPAF, BPB, BPS

MAE, BPF, BPS, BPC, BPS MPE): range finding tests are ongoing [IISPV (ES)].

- **In vitro / high throughput assays** [BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), IEP-NRI (PL), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), EAWAG (CH)]
 - Fish cell line acute toxicity – the RTgillW1 cell line assay (TG 249): Experimental work with 14 single compounds (BPA, BPS, BPB, BPSMPE4, BPS-MAE, BPAP, BPAF, BPZ, BPP, TBBPA, BPF, BPE, BPPH, TCBPA) with the “Fish Cell Line Acute Toxicity: The RTgill-W1 cell line assay” according to OECD TG249 is completed. Analytical verification of the concentrations of tested substances at start and end of exposure duration from samples taken directly out of the well plates is completed (no analytical verification was possible for BPSMPE4, BPP and TCBPA) [EAWAG (CH)].
 - Microtox® acute toxicity test (some tests will have to be repeated due to solubility issues) (BPE, BPS-MAE, Pergafast 201, BPS-MPE, BPAP, BPZ, BPP, BPPH/BPAF, BPF)
 - Tests (*Vibrio fischeri*) have been completed for BPE, BPAP, BPS-MAE, Pergafast 201, BPZ, BPP, BPPH and BPS. Quantification of BPA alternatives is not done yet [IISPV (ES)].
 - Tests (*Vibrio fischeri*) have been completed for PF, BPE, BPAP, BPAF, BPS-MAE, Pergafast 201, BPS-MPE4, BPZ, BPP and BPPH [BPI (EL)].
 - YES assay, *in vitro* screen and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (BPS, BPG, BPAP, BPE, BPA, BPZ, BPAF): the assay was carried out as a screening tool with BPA and several BPA alternatives. Results are ready.
 - Reporter gene assays and mammalian cell models for high-throughput screening (BPS, 2,4-BPS, Bz, BPF, BPS-MAE, D8, BPE, BPT, BPA, BzPB, BPAF, BADGE, BPB, BPS-MPE, Pergafast 201, BPAP, BPZ, BP-MIBK, BTUM, BPG, BPP, TCBPA, BPPH, TBBPA, Racemic TCMD, Trans TCMD): BPA and 26 alternatives were assessed in eight *in vitro* bioassays for cytotoxicity, endocrine disruption, xenobiotic metabolism, adaptive stress responses, mitochondrial toxicity, and neurotoxicity. Several alternatives showed even more potent ER α activity than BPA, and PPAR γ was significantly activated by previously inactive compounds, including TCBPA, TBBPA, and BPS-MPE. Simulated phase I metabolism reduced cytotoxicity for BPPH but increased it for BTUM. Estrogenic activity remained unchanged for all except BPG, which showed a decrease. Only trans-TMCD and racemic TMCD were less toxic and inactive in all assays, indicating their potential as safer alternatives.

Activity ii: Investigation of the effects of “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on the endocrine system [Leader: UFZ (DE), participants: BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), IEP-NRI (PL), UAVR (PT), EAWAG (CH)]

Mixture working group: agreed on the approach that will be followed for the specific mixtures to be tested in different organisms. Representatives from all partners involved in experiments with mixtures participate in this working group. The working group has been meeting regularly since the summer of 2023, most recently in April 2024, to discuss the design of the mixture experiments. The goal is to have a clear hypothesis for mixture testing with the aim of publishing one joint paper on mixtures. The proposed mixture design is based on equipotent mixtures to test mixture hypotheses and concentration ratios of environmental occurrence (water and sediment).

12 BPs are included in the Adamovsky review (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108728>) for European waters:

- 4 were never detected (BADGE, BPZ, BPAB, TBBPA)
- 1 was rarely detected (BPG)
- The remaining 7 with good exposure data are BPA, BPS, BPF, BPE, BPB, BPC and BPAF

- Group 1 with abundant occurrence and bioassay data, group 2 with occurrence and limited toxicity data and group 3 with no occurrence data:
 - Group 1 (water and sediment exposure data): BPA, BPS, BPF, BPAF
 - Group 2 (sediment exposure data): BPE, BPB, BPC
 - Group 3 (no exposure data): BPZ, BPAP, BPPH, BPS-MAE

Meetings:

- Internal project meeting activities i & ii (23 April 2024, Teams) [all participants]. The agenda of the meeting was: 1. General issues; 2. Update on the progress of the experimental work; 3. Discussion on planning of the experiments with mixtures.
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (Lisbon, Portugal: 27-29 May 2024):
 - PS effects at field relevant concentrations when combined stressors are considered [UFZ (DE) - poster]
 - Bisphenol E reduces swimming performance in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). Can it be related to Thyroid Hormone System (THS) sensitive endpoints? [SDU (DK) - poster]
 - Assessment of oestrogenic and metabolic activities of bisphenols, alone or in mixture, using transgenic zebrafish embryo based-bioassays [INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR)]

Conferences:

- SETAC Europe 34th Annual Meeting (5-9 May 2024, Seville, Spain):
 - Bisphenol A alternatives alters Thyroid Hormone System (THS) sensitive endpoints in zebrafish - are they safer alternatives? [SDU (DK), PARC registration number 222]

Deliverables and publications:

- Adamovsky O, et al. Exploring BPA alternatives – Environmental levels and toxicity review, Environment International, submitted in February 2024, published in June 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108728> (PARC registration number 158)

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

P5.1.1.b BPA_ Human Tox_ BfR

The endocrine disruption is one of the endpoints of more interest when filling up data gaps of BPA Alternatives, since ED in BPA is one of the main concerns of the partners. Unfortunately, three of the five assays planned for this endpoint cannot be performed regardless of the experts' efforts:

- The proposed Transcriptional activation assay AR STTA (TG 455 and TG458) was suspended in Y2, the partners [ISS (IT), INRAE (FR), ISCIII (ES)] decided to commit to other activities and transfer their PMs accordingly. The endpoint leader has been actively searching for new partners to perform these assays without success.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.5.2 Task 5.2. Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

Leader: DTU FOOD (DK), VUB (BE); 5.2.2: MU (CZ)

Participants:

Activity 5.2.1: AIT (AT), ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), DTU (DK), IfaDo (DE), INRAE (FR), INSA (FR), INSERM (FR), IRAS (NL), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), IUF (DE), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NMBU (NO), NCPHP (HU), RIVM (NL), SDU (DK), TiHo (DE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UIBK⁸ (AT), UKHSA (UK), RPTU(DE), UKON (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), ULFFA (SI), UNAV (ES), UU (SE); VUA (NL), VUB (BE), WSFR (NL)

Activity 5.2.2: BfG (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), IEP-NRI (PL), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGent (BE), UPO (ES), UU (SE)

Dissemination activities, Transversal for Task 5.2

Current Opinion in Toxicology (Position paper on validation) PARC registration number 292

Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design conference, Switzerland [UFZ (DE)],
<https://www.empa.ch/web/s506/ssbd24>, PARC registration number 279

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

- A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTX_BfR [M1-M60]**

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

During the first year of the project, all available assays and cellular models at the different partners' laboratories were identified and the most suitable assays to be conducted were defined notably to avoid redundancy between laboratories. The list of assays performed by each partner is included in the AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints, submitted in M12.

First, a set of reference chemicals has been established:

- positive controls (Griseofulvin, As₂O₃, CdCl₂, Ochratoxin A, Ethanol, DEHP, Phenobarbital, TCDD, 17β-estradiol, Cyclosporin A)
 - negative controls (Tunicamycin, Nutlin-3, Aflatoxin B2, Benzo(e)pyrene, Ampicillin, Mannitol)
- that provide information on the applicability of the different methods to identify non genotoxic carcinogens (NGTxC) or distinguish NGTxC from genotoxic compounds. These compounds were, depending on the status of the method for each partner, tested and the results presented at a face-to-face meeting in Toulouse in March 2023 (M11).

During this meeting partners also agreed to focus future work on five key aspects of cancer development that are also referred to as "hallmarks of cancer", in particular oxidative stress, nuclear receptor activation (focus on estrogen and AhR receptors), proliferation, inflammation and Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition-migration (EMT). For each of these aspects of cancer development between 5 and 10 additional reference compounds were identified. At least two of

⁸ AMD-101057014-118: Professor Dr Kathrin Thedieck, who was the main scientific contact involved in the activities of PARC WP5 for the Austrian affiliated entity University of Innsbruck - PARC acronym "UIBK", left the University of Innsbruck and started working for the University of Duisburg-Essen in Germany - PARC acronym "UDE", on 01/04/2024. Consequently, UIBK withdrew from PARC on 01/04/2024 and UDE entered in PARC as affiliated entity of UBA on 01/04/2024.

these compounds per “hallmark” are to be tested by the partners to develop a database that allows a direct comparison of the complementarity of the different methods and technologies. First results were discussed in a face-to-face meeting in Berlin 2024 (M23). The concept of the work has been published in *Frontiers in Toxicology* in M15, “New approach methodologies to facilitate and improve the hazard assessment of non-genotoxic carcinogens—a PARC project”, doi 10.3389/ftox.2023.1220998). (<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/ftox.2023.1220998/>).

In year 2 and 3, all partners have tested the first set of reference chemicals whereas the testing of the “hallmark” specific testing is still ongoing in some labs, although there is a need for more discussion on the definition of physiological/biological relevant thresholds to distinguish positive from negative results. An excel table has been created to keep track of all selected chemicals, including additional substances for partners performing high-throughput approaches, and which chemical has already been tested by each partner. In addition, a template has been developed to describe the experimental setup and results in sufficient detail for each chemical and method to allow a thorough analysis of the sensitivity and reliability of each assay in respect to the respective MoA. The results will be discussed in detail at the next internal project annual meeting (March 2025, Madrid, Spain) to start with the selection of potential complementary and predictive testing batteries.

The contribution made by each partner is described in more detail below:

- Validation on 2D HepaRG cells with an HCA (α -Hexylcinnamaldehyde) of the positive and negative compound for different endpoints (cytotoxicity, oxidative stress, AhR activation, and steatosis). Establishment of a 3D model of hepatocytes and a multicellular model including hepatocytes, stellate cells and Kupffer cells [ANSES (FR)].
- Testing of 74 reference chemicals in the E-Morph assay and in the cell painting approach as well as for gH2Ax induction in MCF7 cells. Cell painting data analysed applying a newly developed Knime-based automatic analysis workflow. In addition, the development of new multicellular liver model has been initiated that included endothelial cells as well as the evaluation of the HepaRG model for the detection of “Hallmark” effects [BfR (DE)].
- Performed real-time monitoring of changes in proliferation, morphology, and/or migratory capacity in MCF7 breast cancer cells co-cultured in the presence of human preadipocytes (hMADS) using XCelligence technology. Development of a test strategy to better understand modulations in cell index upon exposure to the compounds. In the case of a decreased cell index, a caspase 3/7 test is performed to explore a potential effect of the compounds on cell death. In the case of increased cell index, cell count is conducted to evaluate modulation in proliferation rate and cytoskeleton staining will explore a possible epithelial-mesenchymal transition, the first step of metastasis [INSERM (FR)].
- Testing of a large number of compounds in the 2D Model that is since 2023 part of an OECD project with the aim to develop a new test guideline. Multi-tissue liver spheroids containing stellate and Kupffer cells have been established and are currently being tested with the reference compounds. Other markers (oxidative stress and inflammation) are being developed [INRAE (FR)].
- Results obtained by applying 18 already available VEGA QSAR models (<https://www.vegahub.eu/>), more specific for NGTXCs (e.g. Nuclear Receptor-Mediated Endocrine Activity models) were analysed in detail, with a focus on the statistical analysis of the “important positive controls” “NGTXC_MoA oxidative stress” and “NGTXC_MoA NR activation” datasets. A large amount of data related to the different modes of action related to carcinogenicity, such as the Key Characteristics of Carcinogens (KCC) datasets available on the ICE platform from the Network Time Protocol (NTP) website (<https://ice.ntp.niehs.nih.gov/Search>) were analysed and, in addition a search for additional

- NGTXCs (from ECVAM genotox databases and IARC classification data from ICE) performed. After data curation, three of the KCC datasets (KCC 4 - Epigenetic Alterations, KCC 3 - Alteration of DNA Repair/Genomic Stability and KCC 5 - Oxidative Stress) with the larger set of NGTXCs were compared and analysed for correlation. Furthermore, by applying SARPy (SAR in python) software to the KCC 4 and KCC 3 datasets, specific rules related to these different modes of action have been extracted. It is planned to extract rules from the KCC 5 dataset, to analyse and compare the results, to explore the AC50 continuous values to evaluate the possibility of regression models in addition to the classification ones [IRFM (IT)].
- Finalizing experiments on the first 8 selected compounds, which included flow cytometry and gene expression analysis by qPCR on 3D HepG2 cell models (spheroids) at two different timepoints (24h and 96h). Utilizing flow cytometry, four different endpoints were analysed: proliferation (Ki67 antibody), mitotic cell formation (pH3 antibody), DNA double strand break formation (γH2AX antibody) and cell cycle distribution (Hoechst 33258 stain). By qPCR, the impact gene expression on several different mechanisms (proliferation, cell cycle regulation, oxidative stress response, apoptosis, epigenetic changes, DNA damage response and oncogenesis) was analysed. Additionally, cytotoxicity (MTS assay) assessment and flow cytometry experiments on 6 new chemicals (Diethyl maleate, Potassium bromate, Diuron, FICZ, Phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate and Nicotine) with 3 distinguished modes of action: oxidative stress, nuclear receptor activation and proliferation-mitogenic signalling [NIB (SI)].
 - Testing two cell lines representing distinct breast cancer subtypes; JIMT-1 and T-47D, to establish 2D and 3D multicellular aggregates as described by [Buocikova et al., 2022](#). Both cells were successfully cultivated in 2D and 3D cells and exposed to the eight-reference control substances (4 positives and 4 negatives) and the cytotoxic potential expressed as metabolic activity of the cells was investigated using the alamarBlue assay as described by [Longhin, et al., 2022](#). Both JIMT-1 and T-47D cells exhibited expected similar responses to the four tested negative controls. While in response to the four positive controls tested, the response in JIMT-1 aggregate 3D model to the positive controls was more pronounced than in T-47D mammosphere by decreasing the cell viability suggesting that JIMT-1 3D spheroid models are most appropriate for further studying the MoA of these 8 compounds using additional endpoints related to the cancer hallmarks [NILU (NO)].
 - Completed evaluation of the effects of eight out of 16 selected reference compounds in WB-F344 cells, establishing effective concentrations for GJIC, cell density and viability. Experiments with the other eight reference compounds are in progress and should be completed in the Year 3. Testing of additional compounds representing carcinogens with specific modes of action has been also initiated [MU (CZ)].
 - Testing of reference substances for proliferation, cell viability/cytotoxicity, ROS formation/oxidative stress, EMT and DNA damage/genomic instability is ongoing. Reference compounds from the first list have already been studied. To assess proliferation, a flow cytometry-based EdU incorporation assay was established and used for the reference compounds in both cell models. Furthermore, experiments with repeated exposure have been started using reference compounds [RPTU (DE)].
 - First set of reference compounds have been tested in zebrafish for induction of oxidative stress applying a specific fluorescent dye with different protocols to optimize the protocols and identify most suitable timepoints of analysis. Additional testing is ongoing [RIVM (NL)].
 - Various hiPSC reporter were applied for testing of reference compounds focusing on reporter cell lines addressing proliferation /cell cycle and oxidative stress. In addition, 3 D mammary-like organoids as well as a 3D liver model are being developed from the iPSC cells and evaluated. In particular hiPSC adaptive stress response reporter lines in hepatocyte-like cells (HLCs) and other lineages were analyzed. HLCs derived from endogenously tagged SRXN1-GFP oxidative stress response reporter hiPSCs were exposed to 40 compounds of interest, including known liver carcinogens and endpoint-specific controls, for high-content microscopy

analysis of reporter activation. In addition, the use of FUCCI cell cycle reporter HLCs to monitor mitogenic effects upon exposure to the non-genotoxic carcinogenic phorbol ester PMA were explored. For the differentiation into progenitors of mammary gland epithelial cells, the protocol was further optimized for the generation of mammary gland organoids that reproducibly show the expression of relevant markers, including prolactin induction of milk protein. In addition, pooled targeted transcriptomics showed activation of mammary morphogenesis pathways. To evaluate their response to non-genotoxic carcinogens with estrogenic activities, we exposed the mammary gland organoids to estradiol (E2) and collected samples for single cell sequencing. Furthermore, the tumor suppressor gene TP53 was deleted to explore if cancer-relevant genetic alterations affect the response of mammary gland and liver progenitor cells to non-genotoxic carcinogens [UL-LACDR (NL)].

- Toxicity testing of the selected compounds in HepG2 cells using the MTT assay after 3 and 24 hours of treatment completed. The genotoxicity of the same compounds was assessed using the standard and Fpg-modified comet assay after 3 hours in the same experimental model. The tested concentrations were calculated based on the toxicity data obtained after 24 hours of treatment. Moreover, CTA and detection of histone H2AX and H3 phosphorylation is being set up [UNAV (ES)].

Meetings:

- P5.2.1.a_NGTxCs Annual Meeting (25-26 March 2024, Berlin, Germany). Participants: ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), MU (CZ), RIVM (NL), RPTU (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UNAV (ES).
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (27-29 May 2024, Lisbon, Portugal):
 - *In vitro* phenotypic screening to establish predictive profiling of non-genotoxic carcinogens [BfR (DE) - poster]
 - Establishment of an *in vitro* co-culture model representing the human liver to investigate non-genotoxic carcinogens [BfR (DE) - poster]
- During the summer 2024, PMs have performed bilateral online meetings with each partner to discuss the current status of their activities and the next steps.

Conferences:

- Gen2Bio 2024 (14-15 March 2024, Saint-Malo, France):
 - *In vitro* based testing strategy for the identification of non-genotoxic carcinogens (NGTxC) [ANSES (FR) - Poster]
- 34th Meeting of the German Society for Environmental Mutation Research (GUM) (20-22 March 2024, Kaiserslautern, Germany):
 - Establishment of an *in vitro* Test Battery to Identify Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens in Human Colon Cell Models [RPTU (DE) - Poster]
- 2024 Summer Immersion on Innovative Approaches in Science (30 May – 1 June 2024, Washington DC, USA):
 - *In silico* models apply for "non-genotoxic carcinogenic compounds" [IRFM (IT) - Poster]
- 22nd International Congress of the European Society of Toxicology *In Vitro* (ESTIV 2024) (3-6 June 2024, Prague, Czech Republic)
 - *In vitro* based testing strategy for the identification of non - genotoxic carcinogens (NGTxC) [ANSES (FR) - Poster]
- EUSAAT (European Society for Alternatives to Animal testing) 2024 congress (18-20 September 2024 Linz, Austria):
 - HepG2 spheroids: A new testing approach for the determination of adverse effects of chemicals [NIB (SI), INRAE (FR) - Poster]
 - Towards the validation of an *in vitro* assay for gap junctional intercellular

- communication to identify non-genotoxic carcinogens [MU (CZ) - Poster]
- 52nd European Environmental Mutagenesis and Genomics society (EEMGS) meeting and 15th International Comet Assay Workshops (ICAWG) (23-24 September, Rovinj, Croatia):
 - Cyclosporin A, a non-genotoxic carcinogen – its possible mechanisms of action [NIB (SI), INRAE (FR) - Poster]
 - Adverse (geno)toxic effects of bisphenol A and its analogues BPS, BPAP, BPAF, BPFL, and BPC in a 3D HepG2 cell model [NIB (SI) - Poster]
 - New approach methodologies to facilitate and improve the hazard assessment of non-genotoxic carcinogens [INRAE (FR), BfR (DE) - Presentation]
 - Set up of a human 3D multi-cellular liver model for non-genotoxic chemical carcinogen detection [INRAE (FR) - Presentation]

Deliverables and publications:

- Contribution to D5.3 “report on AOPs”, submitted June 2024 (M26) (all partners)
 - **P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR [M1-M48 (project extended from M36 to M48)]**

The management of this project has been updated from September 2024 on (M29), with a new expert from BfR joining and continuing the in-kind contribution by INRAE.

In this project, a battery of metabolic disrupting chemicals (MDC)-specific NAMs based on human as well as non-human models have been developed.

Partners are testing the BPA-alternatives prioritized in PARC WP5: 0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, 3-BPS-MAE, 4-Pergafast 201, 5-BPP, 6-BPAP, 7-TCBPA, 8-TBBPA.

The WP5 experts agreed on using 0-BPA as a reference substance and for metabolism halogenated analogues as 7- TBBPA and 4- Pergafast 201. More substances will be tested as reference chemicals to set up the assays (detailed per activity).

Synergies with ongoing projects such as the EURION cluster have been identified, the spectrum of MDC has been extended and there was active participation in the selection process of PARC priority-listed families of substances by [INRAE (FR), BfR (DE), INSERM (FR), Ifado (DE), currently University Duisburg-Essen (UDE), previously by IUBK (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), UAntwerpen (BE), UU (SE), UFZ (DE)].

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

Action 1: Functional and structural characterization of Nuclear Receptors (NR and bisphenols interactions) [INSERM (FR)].

Using stable reporter cell lines (HeLa, U2OS), 23 bisphenols or bisphenol A alternatives were characterized for their capacity to activate or inhibit estrogen receptors α and β (ER α and β), androgen receptor (AR), mineralocorticoid receptor (MR), progesterone receptor (PR), constitutive activated receptor (CAR), pregnane X receptor (PXR) and peroxisome proliferator activated receptor γ . Several bisphenols alternatives have been identified for the first time as PPAR γ activators. They have been crystallized and their 3D structure determined. These bisphenols were also characterized by UU for their ability to induce differentiation on human pre-adipocytes.

The results concerning the PPAR γ activity of bisphenols should be published in the first trimester of 2025 in an article associating INSERM and UU-IRAS.

Several bisphenols alternatives, including BPA, were also characterized as PXR activators and their 3D structure has been established by crystallization. The article is due to be published in the first trimester of 2025.

Further work will be carried out during years M37 to M48 (May 2025 to April 2026) to better understand the effect of bisphenols and their alternative products on steroid receptors and the CAR (see the annual work plan for year 4).

Action 2: *In vitro* assays for screening MBD

2.1 The Mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) activity is being addressed by quantitative high-resolution mass spectrometry (HR-MS) and immune assays [currently University Duisburg-Essen UDE (DE), previously by IUBK (AT)].

During 2024, this action has been transferred from UIBK to UDE. The lab led by Kathrin Thedieck now forms part of the newly founded Research Center One Health Ruhr (RCOHR) of the Ruhr Alliance (<https://www.uaruhr.de/researchallianceruhr/onehealthruhr.html.de>). The RCOHR mission is closely linked to the PARC aims. The RCOHR aims to understand human health in the context of the environment. Specifically, the RCOHR links the interdisciplinary foci of (1) environmental research, (2) oncology and (3) neuroscience.

The budget transfer has already been arranged with the PARC CT. All budget that has not been used by UIBK until March 2024 has been transferred in its entirety to UDE. The hiring of personnel at UDE is ongoing, and the new PhD started in October 2024.

The PhD has been focusing on translating the assays from UIBK to the new facility at the UDE. Specifically, the re-establishment of the HepG2 and HepaRG cell culture systems and cytotoxicity assays for MD response screening.

Due to the transfer, the progress is slower than anticipated and the work will need to be continued after year 4.

Two PARC-related manuscripts have been published during the reporting period, details can be found below in Dissemination activities.

2.2 High-throughput screening assay for phospholipidosis in human liver cells [BfR (DE)]

The planned phospholipidosis assay is established using HepaRG cells and LipidTOX™ Red Phospholipidosis Detection Reagent. For an in-house validation of the phospholipidosis assay, a screening has been done with 36 substances (chosen from literature; see list below) that are known to induce or not induce phospholipidosis *in vivo*. Compounds were initially tested regarding their cytotoxicity, and phospholipidosis induction in HepaRG cells was compared to *in vivo* data to assess the assay performance. In addition, BPA and three of its alternatives (selected jointly with the partners; see list below) were tested.

Table 5: Screening of 36 substances

Aberration	Substance name	CAS number	Biological replicates
AMO	Amiodarone HCl	19774-82-4	3
AAP	Acetaminophen	103-90-2	3
KTC	Ketoconazole	65277-42	3
TCY	Tetracycline HCl	64-75-5	3
KTC	Ketoconazole	65277-42	3
CQ	Chloroquine diphosphate	50-63-5	3
RIF	Rifampicine	13292-46-1	3
GM	Gentamicin sulfate	<u>1405-41-0</u>	3

PL	Propranolol	318-98-9	3
TAM	Tamoxifen	10540-29-1	3
CAF	Caffeine	58-08-2	3
IPM	Imipramine HCl	113-52-0	3
MPY	Methapyrilene HCl	135-23-9	3
CSA	Cyclosporine A	59865-13-3	3
MED	Menadione	58-27-5	3
CPM	Chlorpromazine HCl	69-09-0	3
CZP	Clozapine	5786-21-0	3
DPY	Disopyramide	3737-09-5	3
FXT	Fluoxetine HCl	56296-78-7	3
TLO	Tilorone 2HCl	27591-69-1	3
DXM	Dexamethasone	50-02-2	3
AMY	Amitriptyline HCl	549-18-8	3
AKA	Amikacin	37517-28-5	3
HLP	Haloperidol	52-86-8	3
HYZ	Hydroxyzine 2HCl	2192-20-3	3
MRT	Maprotiline HCl	10347-81-6	3
STL	Sotalol	959-24-0	3
TIR	Thioridazine	130-61-0	3
CAB	Carbamazepine	298-46-4	3
COP	Clomipramine HCl	17321-77-6	3
EYT	Erythromycin	114-07-8	3
DCF	Diclofenac	15307-86-5	3
DXC	Doxycycline H ₂ O	17086-28-1	3
OFX	Ofloxacin HCl	118120-51-7	3
TIP	Triparanol	78-41-1	3
PCA	Procainamide HCl	614-39-1	3
BPA	Bisphenol A	80-05-7	3
BPS	Bisphenol S	80-09-1	3
BPF	Bisphenol F	620-92-8	3
TCBPA	3,3,5,5-Tetrachlorobisphenol A	79-95-8	3

Comparison with *in vivo*, *in vitro* and *in silico* data is currently ongoing and the respective publication is in preparation.

For establishing the phospholipidosis assay in a 3D liver model, suitable co-culture media compositions were tested for cultivation of HepaRG (hepatocytes), HHSteC/LX-2 (stellate cells), THP-1 (macrophage cells) and HUVEC (endothelial cells). HUVEC cells were replaced by the cell line HMEC-1 due to cultivation issues, and suitability of HMEC-1 cultivation with chosen co-culture media is ongoing. Specific protein (IHC) and gene expression (qPCR) markers for each cell type (in 2D) are currently investigated, as well as different spheroid sizes and compositions.

2.3 Test system for pancreatic beta cell signaling and function disruption by MDCs [BfR (DE)]

Due to the crucial role of pancreatic beta cells in glucose homeostasis, the cellular test system endoc- β H1 and endoc- β H5 were selected to gain more toxicological insight into possible mechanisms of metabolic disruption. Endoc- β H1 and endoc- β H5 are based on human-derived β -cells capable of secreting insulin in response to glucose. As such they are an ideal starting point. However, the ordering process for the endoc- β H1 was very long and complex. The initiation of the process started on M10 (23.02.2023) and the cells arrived on M19 (23.11.2023). The pharmaceutical controls and chemicals to test were also ordered and most of the substances have arrived. The testing phase of the cells are expected to be ready by December 2024.

2.4 Development and optimization of adipocyte models to study adipocyte differentiation and response to test chemicals [UU-IRAS (NL)]

We have developed a robust and efficient 96-well plated method for adipogenic differentiation of human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs) derived from a previous and well established 24-well plate model. For this we used a range of concentrations of model chemicals including ROSI, MEHP, TPP, TBT, 8-TBBPA and fludioxinil. This 96-well plate method allowed us to screen for their adipogenic potential five new bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives (BPG, BPT, BPTUM, BPS 4AE and BPS 4BE) in addition to the six previously screened BPA alternatives (0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, BPS, BPPH, 4-Pergafast 201 and 6-BPAP).

To further characterize the adipogenic properties of hMSCs, we conducted a time course experiment to elucidate the role of leptin signalling in this process. We measured leptin levels as well as expression of key adipogenic genes during different timepoints in the differentiation period.

Additionally, we transferred the assay to serum-free conditions for a more animal free alternative and avoid batch to batch variation of Fetal Calf Serum (FCS). We established the culture method and optimized and characterized the cells in comparison to the assay with FCS. In addition to the 2D adipogenesis model, we established a 3D model of adipogenic differentiation in serum free conditions. All the experiments were performed in triplicates with three independent replicates.

Currently, there are no delays encountered, and we are on track to complete our tasks as scheduled.

2.5 Unravel the molecular consequences of BPA alternatives exposure in adipocytes [UFZ (DE)]

An assay was developed to investigate adipogenesis using SGBS preadipocytes that are sensitive to PPAR γ activation. Effects of BPA alternatives on cell viability was assessed in both preadipocytes and adipocytes, and effects on lipid accumulation was measured in mature adipocytes using different concentrations ranging from environmental relevant to potentially accumulated in tissues. The assay can be used in 96-, 48-, 24- or 6-well format. So far, 0-BPA, BPP, BADGE, 8-TBBPA, 7-TCBPA and TBBPS were tested for their cytotoxic and adipogenic potential in concentrations in 4 replicates. As a side activity, we established metabolomics as NAM to study adipogenic effects (doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2024.118847) and performed a molecular profiling of human and murine adipogenesis to define relevant processes that can be targeted by metabolic disruption (doi: 10.1016/j.isci.2024.109711). Besides, we established thermal

proteome profiling to identify molecular initiation events which we have applied to determine cellular target proteins of BPA and halogenated alternatives. A global proteomic approach was performed to identify the signalling pathways influenced by the BPA and halogenated alternatives.

2.6 Development of an in vitro methodology and phenotoxicity score for safety assessment based on cell profiling of compounds using the Cell Painting protocol [IfADo (DE)]

Progress has been achieved that allowed to substantially improve the differentiation of stem cell (hiPSC) derived human hepatocyte-like cells for toxicity testing in vitro. Specifically, a technique was established to downregulate the transcriptional control factor CDX2. Too high CDX2 expression is responsible for the so far incomplete differentiation; due to high CDX2 activity, the stem cell derived hepatocyte-like cells express intestinal gene clusters. Titrating CDX2 to optimal levels reduced RNA levels of intestinal gene clusters and intestinal functional features (particularly intestine-specific enzyme activities). A manuscript describing the key role of CDX2 in hepatocyte differentiation is in preparation.

A set of 14 substances (known hepatotoxic and non-hepatotoxic compounds) is currently analyzed in primary human hepatocytes and in hiPSC derived hepatocyte-like cells to understand how closely the latter resemble “real” (primary) human hepatocytes.

Action 3. Whole organism

3.1 Development of early life stage zebrafish metabolic disruption test [UAntwerpen (BE)]

After developing a zebrafish larval metabolic disruption assay in Y1-2, UAntwerpen has investigated to what extent metabolic disruption can be observed using a zebrafish embryo (NAM, non-protected life stage in the EU) test. A zebrafish embryo assay with aquatic exposure to the well-known metabolic disruptor rosiglitazone, the PPAR γ antagonist T0070907 and BPA as an environmentally relevant metabolic disruptor has been performed. Physiological and morphological effects (swimming activity, respiration, yolk size, growth, and morphological abnormalities) were investigated together with lipid peroxidation levels and transcript level analysis of genes involved in lipid signaling, transport, and catabolism. Increased yolk size compared to controls together with changes in the levels of transcripts coding for apolipoproteins suggested disrupted lipid transport and use from the yolk. This was accompanied by reduced swimming activity. Overall, the study showed how exposure to MDCs can influence biochemical and molecular processes involved in early lipid metabolism and may lead to adverse outcomes in the earliest life stages of fish. This work was published in Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (doi: 10.1002/etc.5930).

Meetings:

- Internal project meetings: monthly online meetings continued where partners share preliminary results and refine the reports. PhDs students are joining the monthly meetings replacing their dedicated monthly meetings.
- All partners shared information regarding the NAMs being developed in this project in the Periodic Technical Report, PARC MB meeting and PARC WP5 Annual meeting in Lisbon this May 2024 (M25).
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (Lisbon, Portugal: 27-29 May 2024):
 - Functional and structural characterization of the interactions of Bisphenol-A and its substitutes with nuclear receptors [INSERM (FR) - poster]
 - Functional and structural characterization of the interactions of Bisphenol-A and its substitutes with nuclear receptors [BfR (DE) - poster]

Conferences:

- Environmental Endocrine Disruptors - Gordon Research Conference (23-28 June 2024, Lucca, Italy):
 - Metabolic disruption of lipid metabolism in human liver cells [BfR (DE) - poster, action 2.2, PARC registration number 240]
 - Development of a Phospholipidosis Assay with Human Liver Cells using High-Throughput Fluorescence Microscopy [BfR (DE) - poster, action 2.2, PARC registration number 251]
- Annual meeting Dutch Society of Toxicology (18-19 June 2024, De Reehorst, the Netherlands):
 - Screening of PFAS for obesogenic effects with an optimized 96-well high-throughput assay for adipogenesis in human mesenchymal stem cells [UU-IRAS (NL) - poster, action 2.4, PARC registration number 257]
 - Development of a human *in vitro* adipogenesis assay with serum-free conditions [UU-IRAS (NL) - poster, action 2.4, PARC registration number 258]

Deliverables and publications

- Kipura T, et al. Automated Liquid Handling Extraction and Rapid Quantification of Underivatized Amino Acids and Tryptophan Metabolites from Human Serum and Plasma Using Dual-Column U(H)PLC-MRM-MS and Its Application to Prostate Cancer Study. Metabolites. Submitted in May 2024, published in June 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo14070370> [UDE (DE) action 2.1]
 - Galhuber M, et al. ODE-based models of signaling networks in autophagy. Current Opinion in Systems Biology. Submitted in May 2024, published in December 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coisb.2024.100519> [UDE (DE) action 2.1]
 - Goerdeler C, et al. Metabolomics in human SGBS cells as new approach method for studying adipogenic effects: Analysis of the effects of DINCH and MINCH on central carbon metabolism. Environmental Research. Published in April 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2024.118847 [UFZ (DE) action 2.5 - PARC registration number 228]
 - Aldehoff AS, et al. Molecular profiling of human and murine adipogenesis to define relevant processes that can be targeted by metabolic disruption. IScience. Published in April 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.isci.2024.109711 [UFZ (DE) action 2.5]
 - Aldehoff AS, et al. Unveiling the dynamics of acetylation and phosphorylation in SGBS and 3T3-L1 adipogenesis. IScience. Published in April 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.isci.2024.109711 [UFZ (DE) action 2.5 - PARC registration number 32]
 - Seal S, et al. From pixels to phenotypes: Integrating image-based profiling with cell health data as BioMorph features improves interpretability. Molecular Biology of the Cell. Submitted in August 2023, published in March 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1091/mbc.E23-08-0298> [UU (SE) action 2.6]
 - van den Boom R, et al. Effects of Metabolic Disruption on Lipid Metabolism and Yolk Retention in Zebrafish Embryos. Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry. Published in June 2024. doi:10.1002/etc.5930 [UAntwerpen (BE) action 3.1]
- **P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU [M1-M48]**

In this project we develop and improve new approach test methods to detect thyroid hormone (TH) system disrupting chemicals. The project includes complex human-based *in vitro* assays, *in*

silico predictions, multi-organ toxicogenomics, non-mammalian vertebrate test species and cross-species extrapolations to improve on human-health relevant RA of TH system disrupting compounds.

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

Action 1: Mapping of the activities of the different groups to the existing THSD AOP network [All partners]

Mapping of all partner activities has been completed, and a project article has been published (Ramhøj et al., 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3389/ftox.2023.1189303>).

Action 2: Characterization of evolutionary conservation of the TH-axis [UAntwerpen (BE)]

A case study to compare fish and mammalian data on Thyroid Hormone System Disruption (THSD) for model compounds propylthiouracil, methimazole, iopanoic acid and perchlorate has been conducted. The data was mapped to the THSD AOP network and Key event and adverse outcome with a high potential for cross-species extrapolation were pinpointed. Data gaps were identified, and further work in year 3 will explore qualitative assessment and possibilities for adapting quantitative assessment to accommodate the lack of data on certain aspects such as thyroid hormone levels in fish.

Action 3: Optimization and characterization of assays to develop more extensive test batteries of NAMs

3.1 Screening assays for thyroid hormone (TH) disruption for early-phase liver developmental toxicity (2D) [VUB (BE)]

A comparison of stemness properties between 2D monolayer and 3D reaggregate hSKP cultures, based on 3 independent biological replicates using qRT-PCR and immunofluorescence, indicated higher expression of the hepatic markers AFP and CYP1B1 in the 3D condition. Experiments were initiated to investigate TH signaling in hSKP-HPC cultures following supplementation with T3, T4, or both. While the cell viability of differentiating hSKP-HPC exposed to T3 alone was negatively impacted (and for which new experiments are being performed), hSKP-HPC formation in the presence of T4 alone or in combination with T3 showed a tendency to increase the expression of TH receptors, deiodinases and TH membrane transporters. RNA of those samples was collected and sent to INSERM for BRBseq transcriptomic analysis.

3.2 Overexpressing cell lines for thyroid hormone transporters OATP1C1 and OAT4 (2D) [VUA (NL)]

An LC/MS based protocol for TH uptake inhibition experiments in the overexpressing cells is established. An overexpression model is currently being established of the thyroid hormone transmembrane transporters (THTMT) OATP3A1 in HEK293 cells. Three HEK293 cell lines have been obtained that each overexpress one isoform of OATP3A1. Currently, the uptake protocol is being optimized in terms of TH concentration and uptake duration.

3.3 Integrated model for measuring thyroid hormone transport inhibition across the blood-cerebrospinal fluid barrier (3D) [VUA (NL)]

A stem-cell based 3D choroid plexus organoid model has been established and characterized in terms of THTMTs and deiodinase expression. An LC/MS based protocol for measurements of TH uptake inhibition in the choroid plexus organoids has been developed. First uptake experiments have been performed to establish a timeline of T4 uptake and deiodination. Furthermore, the effect of several compounds, such as the positive control compound, Silychristin, have been tested.

3.4 Thyroid follicle model for identification of TH biosynthesis disruption (3D) [BfR (DE)]

Establishment of an *in vitro/ex vivo* culture of pig slaughterhouse by-product thyroid glands. The model reflects the complete, sequential process of thyroid hormone production in the mature organ with several molecular initiating events interacting concurrently. Progress has been made in the characterization of the model by establishing RT-qPCR and imaging workflows. Furthermore, the potential of the model's ability to identify THSDs was shown by exposing the culture to reference inhibitors propylthiouracil (PTU), methimazole (MMI), and sodium perchlorate. The main readout of chemical testing was established to be integrative ELISA measurements of the culturing medium at certain time points after chemical exposure. General functionality of the system was shown by responsiveness to thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), iodide and reference inhibitors leading to decreased hormone levels in the medium, but the method suffers from high variation and issues in reproducibility. Recently, performance was enhanced by depleting hormonal background in medium. First evidence has been gathered that this will lead to clearer results in the hormone measurements and reduced variability. Also, positional effects and replication issues were addressed.

3.5 Identifying inhibitors of thyroperoxidase, deiodinase type 1,2,3 and dehalogenase as potentially relevant MIE of TH pre-receptor control (*In vitro* & *In chemico* assay) [BfR (DE)]

Perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) and tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA) have been tested in the full suite of assays in collaboration with other PARC subtasks. Also, thyroid and liver samples from the rat *in vivo* (action 5.1) have been tested – this data showed a complex TH system disruption in both dams and offspring.

3.6 *In silico* models for TH system disrupting properties [DTU QSAR (DK)]

Data curation and development of quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models for 3 endpoints within the TH system: MCT8 inhibition, transthyretin (TTR) binding and thyrotropin releasing hormone receptor (TRHR) inhibition. Data and structure curation is finished for MCT8 and preliminary models optimized for sensitivity, specificity and balanced accuracy + domain size performed well, final modeling in updated QSAR software ongoing. Initial models for TTR based on data from Timo Hamers et al. (VU, NL) and curated (resulting in N=209 substances) by DTU were made in the beginning of 2024, showing good performance, and later this year updated with ToxCast data (resulting in N=606). The preliminary new models show good performance and final modeling is ongoing. A preliminary model with good performance has also been made for TRHR inhibition based on Tox21 data, and final modeling scheduled for 2025.

Action 4: Communication / Deliverables / outputs (Details below after Action 6)

Expected outcome 4: Disseminated results and knowledge in and outside PARC network

Action 5: Whole organism model: zebrafish larvae and embryo & *In vivo* rat study

5.1 *In vivo* rat data (studying TBBPA and PFOS substances) [DTU (DK), INSERM (FR)]

In order to elaborate on mechanisms and downstream effects of Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors (THSD), Data and samples from the rodent reproductive toxicity study with the model compounds PFOS and TBBPA performed in Y1 and Y2 was analysed. A method for quantification of TBBPA by LC/MS was developed (manuscript in preparation) and internal concentrations of PFOS and TBBPA measured in pregnant dams, fetuses and pups. A collaboration for obtaining measurements of TH by LC/MS has been established and samples shipped. PFOS and TBBPA caused minor apical effects – yet TH system disruption has been identified. Data analysis of the multi-organ transcriptomics data is ongoing – PFOS and TBBPA caused drastic and complex molecular changes in the developing animals.

5.2 Zebrafish and snail (*L. Stagnalis*) assay with metformin and bisphenol E (BPE) [SDU (DK)]

Characterisation of the evolutionary conservation of the Thyroid Hormone (TH) system in relation to invertebrates and non-mammalian vertebrates. This could pave the way for testing of TH

system disrupting properties, also in other species and is supported by experimental work performed in other PARC tasks and projects. Development of analytical test methods to detect TH system sensitive endpoints in zebrafish e.g., inflation of the posterior swimbladder chamber and eye morphology including retinal pigmentary epithelium (RPE) layer and in *L. stagnalis* investigating morphological endpoints during development, analysis of potential TH found in *L. stagnalis* at different life-stages.

Developmental neurotoxicity related endpoints in zebrafish larvae e.g., developmental brain morphology and swimming behavioral changes in a light/dark transition test have been studied. This experimental work will be used to support the research in P5.2.1.e.

5.3 Comparative assessment of thyroid hormone system disruption in mammals and fish [UAntwerpen (BE)]

The use of zebrafish embryo tests as NAMs for extrapolation to mammals including humans using an adverse outcome pathway (AOP) network approach has been analysed. An extensive literature review and data synthesis has been performed for four data-rich model compounds (MMI, PTU, iopanoic acid, perchlorate) to collect data from fish and rodent studies. Responses are compared between fish and rodents at the level of the Molecular Initiating Events (MIEs), Key Events (KEs) and Adverse Outcomes (AOs) that are part of the THSD AOP network. Specific attention is going to a comparison of baseline TH levels, and directionality as well as the extent of the changes in response to the model compounds.

5.4 Zebrafish embryo and larvae assay [ISCI (ES)]

Development of an *in vivo* zebrafish embryo model to investigate potential disruptors of thyroid function, with a specific focus on iodine accumulation and thyroid hormone transport across the organism. To quantify iodide and thyroid hormone levels, a non-radioactive Sandell-Kolthoff (S-K) method was employed. Reference inhibitors for iodine transport (perchlorate, ClO_4^-), thyroid hormone (T3/T4) transport (silychristin and bromosulphophthalein, BSP), and thyroid function (methimazole, MMI) were tested. Unexpectedly, the presence of these inhibitors resulted in increased levels of iodide and thyroid hormones (TH) in the whole body, contrary to anticipated outcomes. The results were also verified by total T3 levels in the ZFe with ELISA assays.

Use of radioisotopes to enhance the sensitivity of the assay and to distinguish between endogenous and exogenous iodine/thyroid hormones. Development of a panel of thyroid-related genes, whose expression will be analyzed using quantitative PCR (qPCR) in zebrafish embryos exposed to the reference inhibitors as well as known endocrine disruptors, including BPA, TBBPA, and tetrachlorobisphenol A (TCBPA).

Action 6: Data Analyses - Provide a framework for interpretation of *in vitro* and molecular data [INSERM (FR)]

Data from a large animal study comprising the complexity of developmental thyroid system disruption by several mechanisms has been harnessed. The dataset includes 7 tissues, 2 developmental stages (fetal and 16 days old) for both PFOS and TBBPA. There are approximately 8000 genes affected.

Action 4: Communication / Deliverables / outputs

Meetings:

- During M21-M32 the project organized a 2-day workshop at DTU (Copenhagen) to discuss and disseminate our work [Participants: DTU (DK), VUB (BE), VUA (NL), BfR (DE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), ISCI (ES), INSERM (FR)].
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (Lisbon, Portugal: 27-29 May 2024)

Conferences:

- SOT 63rd Annual Meeting and ToxExpo (10-14 March 2024, Salt Lake City, USA):
 - Effects of PFOS and TBBPA exposure on the reproductive and thyroid hormone system in the developing rat [DTU (DK) - Poster]
- 9th German Pharm-Tox Summit 2024 (13-15 March 2024, Munich, Germany):
 - Porcine thyroid follicles as an *in vitro* tool in chemical testing for thyroid hormone system disruptors [BfR (DE) - Presentation]
- SETAC Europe 34th Annual Meeting (5-9 May 2024, Seville, Spain):
 - The Cross-Species Applicability of the Thyroid Hormone System Disruption (THSD) AOP Network and it's Utilisation in Cross-species Extrapolations [UAntwerpen (BE) - Presentation]
 - SDU (DK) - 2 Posters
- 22nd International Congress of the European Society of Toxicology *In Vitro* (ESTIV 2024) (3-6 June 2024, Prague, Czech Republic):
 - Development of a human stem cell-based *in vitro* model to assess developmental liver toxicity induced by thyroid hormone disruptors [VUB (BE) - Poster]
 - Human based brain barrier models for studying thyroid hormone transport [VUA (NL) - Presentation]
- Gordon Research Conference on Endocrine Disruptors 2024 (23-28 June 2024, Lucca, Italy):
 - From fish to mammals: a cross species AOP network approach for extrapolation of thyroid hormone system disruption effects [UAntwerpen (BE) - Poster]
- 44th International Symposium on Halogenated Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) (29 September – 4 October 2024, Singapore):
 - DTU (DK) - Poster
- 7th IC-3Rs Symposium 2024 (19 September 2024, Brussel, Belgium):
 - VUB (BE) - Poster

- **P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_INSERTM [M1-M48] (project extended from M36 to M48)**

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

In general, during Y3, the pre-selected methods from Y2 have been further developed. The partners have tested and/or optimized their methods applying their reference chemicals (see table). Also, some mechanistical analyses have been performed to better understand the answer of the models to the immunotoxicants, and to likely refine the methods for specific endpoints. Currently the project has led to at least 16 NAMs under development. Some laboratories have estimated the Test Readiness Criteria (TRC) of their method(s) using the ReadEDTest (Pepper platform) even though the questionnaire is devoted to ED and not immunotoxicants [NIPH (NO), UFZ (DE), ULFFA (SI), UMIL (IT)]. All partners contributed to a review paper published in *Frontiers in Toxicology*, doi: 10.3389/ftox.2024.1339104.

The main compounds used to develop the NAMs within this project are:

Biocides	chloramine-T, piperazine
BPA alternatives	BPA, BPS-MAE, BPZ, BPB, TCBPA, BPAP, Bis-Z, BPPH, BPG, BPS-MPE, PF201, BTUM, BPE, BPP

(Myco)toxins	Deoxynivalenol, fumonisin B1, aflatoxin B1, enniatin A, A1, B, B1, ochratoxin A, zearalenone, alternariol, tenuazonic acid, tentoxin
Therapeutic substances	dexamethasone, chloroquine, sirulimus (rapamycin), cyclosporine A, tacrolimus (FK506), doramapimod, Hydrocortisone, dapsone
Perfluorinated substances	PFOA, PFOS, PFDA, PFNA, PFHxS, PFUnDA and mixture
Other	BP3, MIKB, B[a]P, TCDD,

Given the large panel of immunological key characteristics that might be impaired by toxics, discussions are ongoing to define reference compound lists for specific immunotoxic endpoints.

Action 1: Respiratory sensitizer [MUI (AT), RIVM (NL), LIST (LU), NCPHP (HU), UMIL (IT)].

The group still explored their NAM using mainly two reference compounds (Chloramine-T, Piperazine). UMIL also works on bisphenols and alternatives. The current practical work of the respiratory sensitization group includes different models: air liquid interface (ALI) cultured Calu-3 cells [RIVM]; tetra-culture model consisting of ALI cultured alveolar type II epithelial cells (A549), endothelial cells (EA.hy926), macrophage-like cells (PMA-differentiated THP-1), and dendritic-like cells (non-differentiated THP-1) (ALIsens®) [LIST]; coculture model consisting of BCi and THP-1 [MUI]; co-culture model consisting of BEAS-2B cells (or EVs) and THP-1 cells [NCPHP]. Current readouts include barrier function, viability/cytotoxicity measurements, gene expression, cytokine secretion, cell surface marker expression, and characteristics of extracellular vesicles (EVs). Some models respond differently to the two reference compounds (e.g.: the ALI model of lung bronchial epithelial cells (Calu-3) reacts to piperazine, cytokine release, but not to chloramine-T) [RIVM]. Comparisons between laboratories have also been carried out. A sensitization of mice (C57Bl/6 and BALB) with 100 ug chloramine-T has also been performed. The concentration of EVs from treated mice were increased indicating that sensitization impacts EV production of lung cells. This supports the experiments performed *in vitro* on EVs to validate the NAM model [NCPHP].

The common work of this sub-group leads to a publication on respiratory sensitization mechanisms, *in vitro* assays and AOP: (Hargitai and Parráková et al., <https://doi.org/10.3389/ftox.2024.1331803>)

Action 2: Immunosuppression [INSERM (FR), NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), UU-IRAS (NL), ULFFA (SI), UFZ (DE), UMIL (IT), WR (NL)]

In this sub-project NAMs are developed using PBMCs [INSERM, NIPH, LIH, UFZ, UMIL]) and some established cell lines such as THP-1, Jurkat or Namalwa [INSERM, INSA, IRAS, ULFFA, WR]. Two laboratories work on co-culture such as Caco-2/Macrophages [INSA, ULFFA]). The main reference compounds used are PFAS [INSERM, NIPH, UMIL]), bisphenols and alternatives [linked to WP5.1.1b; UU-IRAS, UFZ, ULFFA, INSA, UMIL], and other compounds such as mycotoxins or antibiotics [WR, ULFFA]. *In vitro*, cytotoxicity analyses, quantification of production of cytokines (several methods of quantification), immunoglobulins, surface markers, determination of gene cluster, characterization of EVs (quantity, type, content) have been performed.

In vivo, experiments have been carried out to optimize vaccination parameters and determine the answer of the mice to the influenza antigen [INSERM] before the main experiments with a PFAS exposure.

The study carried out in parallel to associate the quantification of PFAS in human serum and the response to vaccination against COVID began in October [NIPH, next year for INSERM].

Action 3: Immunostimulation [UFZ (DE), WR (NL), INSA (PT), UU-IRAS (NL)]

Most of the models and endpoints (thus the methodology) are common with action 2.

Specific work investigated the microbiota response to pollutants (BPX, PFAS) and the changes in the immunostimulatory potential of exposed microbes using a co-culture system with human Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells (PBMCs).

Meetings:

- MUI organized an in-person meeting as part of Action 1 with RIVM and NCPHP partners within the MUI lecture series, a program for continuing education.
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (Lisbon, Portugal: 27-29 May 2024):
 - Respiratory sensitization: development of new approach methodologies, adverse outcome pathways and identification of effect markers [NCPHP (HU), MUI (AT), UMIL (IT), INSERM (FR), RIVM (NL), LIST (LU) - Poster]
- Since April 2024, the whole group started again regular online meetings on a monthly basis (except July). From September 2024, ECHA members participated to these meetings. A hybrid meeting has also taken place during the WP5 Lisbon Meeting. From October, two laboratories presented their results during those meetings. The respiratory group (action 1) have also specific regular meetings on a monthly basis. They (MUI, NCPHP, RIVM) meet also physically in MUI to discuss their experiments, harmonization of work, applied laboratory methods, possible collaborations and future plans.
- On March 1st and 4th 2024 (two half days), a joint meeting related to developmental immunotoxicology (DIT) has been organized with Dr Fenna Sillé from the Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing (CAAT) at the John Hopkins University, Environmental Health and Engineering department. Several informal meetings occurred to organize this workshop. During these two sessions, ECHA, EFSA and JRC have presented the regulator point of view about DIT (gaps, needs, schedule, prioritization). Seven talks were given by researchers outside of PARC, three talks were given by WP5.2.1d partners (UMIL, RIVM, UFZ). Two Breakout sessions (2 in parallels, twice) were organized on major immunotoxicological issues.

Conferences:

- SOT 63rd Annual Meeting and ToxExpo (10-14 March 2024, Salt Lake City, USA):
 - UMIL poster
 - Modeling the human immune system *in vitro*: Opportunities for discovery and refinement of adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) for immunotoxicity [RIVM (NL) - Presentation]
- French Assemblée Nationale (March 2024, Paris, France): Round table at French about PFAS [INSERM]
- 22nd International Congress of the European Society of Toxicology *In Vitro* (ESTIV 2024) (3-6 June 2024, Prague, Czech Republic): poster [UFZ (best poster)]
- Dutch Society of Toxicology Annual Meeting (18-19 June, Ede, the Netherlands):
 - Development of a trained immunity model in THP-1 cells and the assessment of BPA on trained immunity [UU-IRAS (NL)]
- Joint ITCASS/ERGECD meeting (Liverpool, UK, June 2024): conference ([UMIL])
- EUROTOX 2024 (8-11 September 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark):

- Chemical respiratory sensitization: status, challenges, and future opportunities [MUI, NCPHP, LIST - common poster]
- UFZ poster
- EUSAAT (European Society for Alternatives to Animal testing) 2024 congress (18-20 September 2024 Linz, Austria):
 - Coculture of Jurkat and THP-1 cell lines as a model for the evaluation of immunosuppressive properties of chemical [UL-FFA - Poster]

Deliverables and publications:

- Hargitai R., Parráková L. et al., Chemical respiratory sensitization current status of mechanistic understanding, knowledge gaps and possible identification methods of sensitizer. *Frontiers Toxicology*, submitted in November 2023, published in May 2024, 6:1331803. doi: 10.3389/ftox.2024.1331803 [MUI, RIVM, LIST, NCPHP, UMIL]
- Snapkow I. et al. New approach methodologies to enhance human health RA of immunotoxic properties of chemicals - a PARC (Partnership for the Assessment of Risk from Chemicals) project. *Frontiers Toxicology*. Submitted in November 2023, published in March 2024, 6:1339104. doi: 10.3389/ftox.2024.1339104 [all partners]
- Jaylet T. et al. Comprehensive mapping of the AOP-Wiki database: identifying biological and disease gaps. *Frontiers Toxicology*, submitted in August 2023, published in February 2024, 6:1285768. doi: 10.3389/ftox.2024.1285768 [MUI, NIPH]
- Pierzchalski A. et al. A comprehensive battery of flow cytometric immunoassays for the *in vitro* testing of chemical effects in human blood cells. *Front Immunol*. Submitted in October 2023, published in January 2024, 14:1327960. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2023.1327960 [UFZ]
- Fischer F et al. Single and mixture effects of bisphenol A and benzophenone-3 on *in vitro* T helper cell differentiation. *Chem Biol Interact*. Submitted in January 2024, published in April 2024, 25;395:111011. doi: 10.1016/j.cbi.2024.111011 [UFZ]
- Fischer F, et al. An *in vitro* model system for testing chemical effects on microbiome-immune interactions - examples with BPX and PFAS mixtures. *Front Immunol*. Submitted in September 2023, published in June 2024, 15:1298971. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2024.1298971 [UFZ]
- Franko N and Sollner-Dolenc M. Evaluation of THP-1 and Jurkat Cell Lines Coculture for the *In Vitro* Assessment of the Effects of Immunosuppressive Substances. *Toxics*, submitted in July 2024, published in August 2024, 12(8), 607; <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics12080607> [ULFFA]

Interaction with other PARC projects:

P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm: SG1 - AOP immunotox [NIPH, INSERM, NCPHP, MUI, WR]

P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm: SG4 – Effect markers group [INSERM, NCPHP, MUI, WR]

P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR: BPA alternatives [INSA, UMIL]

P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR: Systems Toxicology [NCPHP, INSERM]

P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_NIPH: PFAS mixtures in collaboration with Oddvar Myhre and Tamara Tal

- **P5.2.1.e_Y1_Neurotox_UFZ_IUF_NIPH [M1-M48] (project extended from M36 to M48)**

Goal - Relevance (Regulatory and Scientific): Regulatory testing for ANT and DNT is currently performed in mammals (e.g., OECD TG #424, 426). We seek to develop, evaluate, and

implement NAMs for DNT or ANT that, based on the mode of action of toxicants, inform on safe chemical concentrations. P 5.2.1e focuses on the development of new assays that fill critical gaps in the existing DNT *in vitro* test battery (DNT-IVB version 1.0) and development of a first version of the ANT IVB.

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

All partners agreed upon 96 reference chemicals test set and coordinated procurement with the JRC, led by [IUF (DE) and UFZ (DE)]. While we hoped to obtain the reference chemicals in Y3, procurement is ongoing. We predict that the chemicals will be shipped in February 2025. A list of test chemicals is provided below. For completed NAMs, chemicals will be evaluated in Y4.

Action 1: Fill existing gaps in the DNT IVB. Gaps will be filled by assays predictive of, for example, myelination, synaptogenesis, neuronal network formation, neuron-specific signaling, higher-level CNS behavioral/cognitive endpoints, and epigenetically- and ED-induced DNT. Readiness levels, performance parameters and applicability domains will be determined and probed in case studies on pathway-specific model compounds. Toxicological information for improved prediction of risk of selected high-priority compounds will be provided.

Action 1.1 Refine existing NAMs to reduce cost and increase throughput

1.1.1 Human Neuronal Network Formation (hNNF) assay [IUF (DE)]

- Gap closure DNT IVB: Since the hNNF assay (human neural network formation assay), based on commercially available cells is very expensive and thus limits the testing of a large number of chemicals, we have developed a refinement strategy aimed at replacing the commercially available cells with in-house generated hiPSC-based neuronal cell lines. We successfully established a transfection protocol for the integration of an Ngn2 expression cassette into the IMR9 hiPSC line using the PiggyBac-Transposon system. Furthermore, the subsequent selection and neuronal induction was effective. First co-cultures of excitatory (Ngn2) neurons and primary human astrocytes yielded morphologically mature neural networks. This protocol is currently being adapted for the generation of inhibitory Ascl1/Dlx2 neurons.
- The biostatistical pipelining for the hNNF assay was further refined to accelerate the evaluation process.

1.1.2 Human synaptogenesis NAM [NIPH (NO)]

- For further characterization in relation to closing gaps in DNT IVB, RNAseq analysis has been performed in 2D hNPCs “synaptogenesis” assay (NIPH) compared to 3D hNPCs (IUF) (both derived from hiPSC) undergoing differentiation for 3, 14 and 21 days.
- For refinement of human synaptogenesis in the DNT IVB, acrylamide and glycidamide have been used as stressors in hNPC undergoing differentiation for 3, 14, 21 and 28 days. RNAseq analyses have been completed, which will be compared with high content imaging covering quantification of maturing and synaptogenesis (ongoing).
- Refinement of maturing and synaptogenesis assay in hNPCs undergoing differentiation for 3, 14, 21 days exposed to human relevant PFAS compounds and their mixture. Six PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA and their mixture) were selected based on human blood concentrations in Scandinavian populations. Selected gene expression predicting synaptogenesis, differentiation, neurite outgrowth, and neuronal subtype characterization after exposure to 0.5, 1, 100 and 1000 x human blood concentration is

ongoing, high content imaging of the same PFAS and their mixture for maturing and synaptogenesis (for comparison with gene expression) is planned spring 2025.

- Testing of positive controls including chlorpyrifos, chlorpyrifos-oxon (5 concentrations ranging from cord blood concentrations to toxic levels) in hNPC undergoing differentiation for 3, 14, 21, 28 days, RNAseq completed (analysis ongoing), high content imaging covering maturing and synaptogenesis ongoing. Expected completion of analysis early spring 2025.

1.1.3 Automated cellular neurotoxicity assays for fast screening of chemicals and sample extracts (complex mixtures) [UFZ (DE), UKON (DE)]

- The high-throughput cell assay for neurotoxicity was planned to be multiplexed with mitochondrial toxicity using the MMP-I indicator. To complement the existing *in vitro* battery (IVB) for not only testing individual chemicals but also hundreds of environmental samples. However, the detectability of the mitochondria was not good enough in the differentiated SH-SY5Y cells, therefore AREc32 cells were used, and mitochondrial toxicity was multiplexed with activation of oxidative stress response, both of which are also relevant for DNT (Lee et al. 10.1021/acs.est.3c09844). Both assays have also been applied to extracts from human serum and cord blood (in preparation) and mixture experiments were performed with mixtures of up to 75 active neurotoxicants, profiled in the HTS neurite outgrowth inhibition assays and in mixed in concentrations as detected in human serum samples (Braun et al. 10.1126/science.adq0336). Both assays have already been applied to 24 BPA substitutes in the BPA case study in P5.1.2.b and will be used for the BPA mixture study in Y4.
- Most cell lines and most primary cells or stem cell-derived cells can compensate mitotoxicity by increasing the glycolytic flux. For some cell types, it is possible to prevent this response by removing glucose from the culture medium, blocking the glucose transporter or substituting galactose for glucose. All these approaches were tested on neural crest cells, LUHMES cells and iPSC-derived peripheral neurons, i.e. the test systems used for UKN2, UKN4 and UKN5. For UKN4, all approaches worked, for UKN2 and UKN5 the substitute of galactose for glucose was best tolerated. Under this condition, all cells maintained their normal viability, functionality and ATP content. However, they became more sensitive to mitochondrial toxicants. A manuscript is in preparation to describe the Mitotox variant of UKN5. Over 20 toxicants have been screened. The Mitotox variant of UKN2 has been used in a case study on strobilurins, which was presented at Eurotox2024. The Mitotox variant of UKN4 is at present used to generate data that are used as input of a quantitative AOP.

1.1.4 Introducing cell painting to detect early sub-cellular changes in exposed *in vitro* models for DNT/ANT in 2D and 3D BrainSpheres by [UU (SE), IUF (DE)]

- Optimization of methods and cell lines for Cell Painting in 2D for DNT continued, and a new method for 3D cell painting continued (manuscript in preparation). A method for increasing the interpretability of AI modeling on Cell Painting data was published (Seal et al. Mol Biol Cell. 35, 3, 2024) [UU (SE)]

Action 1.2 Build NAMs that cover battery gaps

1.2.1 Behavior-based battery, including learning and memory by [UFZ (DE)]

- A paper adding the visual startle response to the zebrafish light-dark transition test was recently published (<https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP13667>)

- UFZ developed a new approach method called the Visual and Acoustic Motor Response (VAMR) NAM that detects effects on learning and memory-related endpoints in early life stage zebrafish. It was preprinted (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.09.25.613874>) and has been submitted for peer review to Environmental Health Perspectives.
- In a separate study, using the VAMR NAM, we evaluated 63 reference chemicals with known modes of action, including five predicted negatives and 5 environmental chemicals predicted to disrupt GABA receptor-dependent signaling. This paper is in preparation and will be submitted to Environment International in November 2024 (Herold et al).
- The zebrafish assay work is on time, without delays.

1.2.2 Neural tube closure 1.2.2 by [UKON (DE)]

- The UKN1/RoFA assay was modified to allow a higher throughput. It was applied to three case studies: (i) various retinoids were tested and it was found that the response correlated well with transcriptional activity on retinoid response genes; (ii) various valproic acid derivatives were tested. The RoFA outcome correlated well with the *in vivo* potency of the compounds concerning failure of neural tube closure. (iii) A series of developmental toxicants (human drugs) and non-toxicants was tested.
- The assay reached a predictive accuracy > 80%. Notably, all readouts were obtained in a culture phase, when no test compound was present to directly affect the cells. Test compounds were only present during the first 4 days, while the RoFA was measured after 12-15 days (i.e. a long washout period).

1.2.3 Seizures by [INSERM-UBX (FR)]

- Development, optimization, and pre-validation of a new NAM, named Electric Field Pulse Motor Response Test (EFP MRT) have been performed. This is an innovative high throughput system which enables direct stimulation of the zebrafish pre-feeding larvae motor system via the activation of reticulospinal neurons independently of sensory processing. EFP MRT is used for the quantitative assessment of induced neuronal and/or neuro-muscular functionality disruption and epileptic-like seizures, in an *in vivo* context, after exposure to molecules alone or in mixtures. A refinement of the EFP MRT protocol, in order to higher the robustness and reproducibility of the test method, was obtained. An increase in the number of end-point criteria analysed, in order to describe as precisely as possible, the changes in locomotor behaviour induced after Electric Field Pulse (EFP) stimulation following chemical exposure, was carried out. EFP MRT endpoints used are: latency of reaction, total distance moved, speed during swim, tail beat number, bend amplitude, bending speed as well as balance loss.
- A software tool called of DanioTracker™ was developed, which allows the processing of the large quantity of quantitative data generated by the EFP MRT. This makes it possible to obtain the data from the experiments in an automated and very fast way in order to increase the productivity and the transferability of the method. DanioTracker™ is an automatic multi-object detection and tracking program based on artificial intelligence by deep learning applied to the analysis of videos of groups of zebrafish pre-feeding larvae, including a large panel automatic stroke analysis and an ergonomic graphical user interface. The pre-validated EFP MRT including DanioTracker™, optimized within the framework of this work, is a robust and transferable NAM which have the potential to move towards OECD validation. A manuscript will be submitted about EFP MRT and DanioTracker™ (Mercé T, Al Kassir S, Bourcier LM, Dubrana LE, Soares M, Knoll-Gellida A, and Babin PJ. High-throughput assessment of neuromuscular functionality disruption in zebrafish larvae for toxicological and medical applications).

- The numerical simulation of the EFP-induced escape response of zebrafish pre-feeding larva was carried out by combining experimental imaging of body deformations with Navier-Stokes numerical simulations. Our aim was to quantify energetic parameters associated to EFP-induced fast-starts. The energy endpoints obtained are complementary to those directly accessible via DanioTracker™. Simulations based on swims recorded in different swimming media show that the power output during swims remains unchanged as fluid viscosity increases, while the cost of transport is linearly correlated to viscosity. This modeling method revealed neuromuscular energetic constraints in the EFPMRT and an effective adaptability of the neuromuscular system responsible for escape swims, which allows an optimal exploitation of available muscular power in healthy animals independently from external constraints. This method can be used to identify any factors inducing a decrease or increase in neuromuscular energetic performance, including neuromuscular toxicants. A manuscript is submitted about the method and the conclusions reached (Ravel G, Bergmann M, Knoll-Gellida A, Mercé T, Bouharguane A, Al Kassir S, Iollo A, and Babin PJ. Modeling zebrafish electric field pulse-induced escape response reveals neuromuscular energetic constraints and efficient body deformation adaptation to high-viscosity fluids).
- The evaluation of some selected PARC chemicals of interest for DNT and ANT has been started. Analyses focuses on certain neurotoxic organophosphorus (OPs) compounds, used as proof of concept. EFPMRT will be integrated in a battery of zebrafish embryo/eleuthero-embryo neurobehavioral tests to screen and assess the mode of action (MOA) of neurotoxicants and to feed a decision tree for regulatory purposes. As a consequence, an established neurobehavioral test was used, the Visual Motor Response Test (VMRT), complementary to EFPMRT, to assess potential induction of sensory and motor disorders. In addition, the levels of neurotoxicity-related enzymatic activities (e.g., acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and Neuropathy Target Esterase (NTE)) were measured to correlate with identified locomotor defects and therefore increase mechanistic knowledge. It is demonstrated that parent compounds and metabolites exhibited different OP-specific neurotoxicity potentials in five days post-fertilization pre-feeding larvae. Overall, the results strongly suggest the need to 1) take into account the metabolic conversion rate when assessing the MOA of a toxicant in the used experimental models, and 2) assess both parent compounds and their metabolites in order to provide a comprehensive overview of the effect of tested compounds when developing regulatory frameworks for chemical RA. A manuscript will be submitted about the conclusions reached on the neurotoxicity of parent OPs molecules and their known associated metabolites (Mercé T, Al Kassir S, Bourcier LM, Dubrana LE, Soares M, Knoll-Gellida A, and Babin PJ. Comparative assessment of cholinergic and non-cholinergic locomotor disorders induced by organophosphorus compounds and their metabolites in zebrafish eleutheroembryos). We are waiting for the JRC to provide us with the molecules selected by the consortium, so that we can continue screening their effects using the tools and test methods we have developed. This will increase the information available in a database we are developing of multi-assay signatures/fingerprints of known toxicants using EFPMRT, VMRT and enzymatic assay endpoints.

1.2.4 Thigmotaxis by [ISCIII (ES)]

- A Thigmotaxis Assay using zebrafish embryos (120 hours post-fertilization, hpf) has been successfully developed to assess anxiety-like behaviors in response to both visual and acoustic stimuli within the ANT mode: 1 h of acute exposure. The assessment of anxiety is conducted using the Noldus Daniovision system, with a duration of approximately 30 minutes per plate per stimulus and an experimental setup involving 24 embryos per

substance concentration and 12 embryos per control, with 6 concentrations, 2 positive controls (anxiogenic: valerianic acid/tofisopam and anxiolytic: diazepam) and 2 negative controls (DMSO and saccharine).

- After conducting trials with various anxiogenic/anxiolytic positive and negative controls (diazepam, alprazolam, tofisopam, valerianic acid, caffeine, ethanol, etc.), it has been determined that 96 square well plates perform equally well or better compared to 24 round well plates, leading to their adoption for further assays.
- The drafting of the standard operating procedure for this assay was completed.
- Ongoing work in the process of developing an R-based application for the automation of behavioural data curation and pre-analysis steps, particularly prior to Benchmark Response (BMR) calculations.
- Initiated the testing of self-sourced reference chemicals under the ANT mode and are currently awaiting the supply of additional compounds from the JRC.
- Furthermore, the process of identifying appropriate positive and negative controls (anxiogenic and anxiolytic agents) has begun for use in the DNT mode, specifically optimized for the 96-well plate format.

1.2.5 Zebrafish motor neuron toxicity by [RIVM (NL)]

- Ongoing work on the development of a medium-throughput NAM for motor neuron toxicity. The NAM is based on a transgenic model with fluorescently labelled motor neurons. Using automated imaging (VAST BioImager) we imaged zebrafish embryo's following developmental exposure to concentration ranges of known motor neuron toxicants to optimize fluorescence detection. This involves the testing of various imaging strategies to capture motor neuron density and branching. Currently, the approach is tested for reproducibility and biological variation. It is foreseen that testing of other compounds can start early 2025.

1.2.6 Zebrafish DNT persistence by [RIVM (NL)]

- Project revolves around the persistence of DNT effects observed at 5 days post fertilization (dpf) using the L/D transition test. Within this project we exposed zebrafish embryos to a set of four different psychoactive substances with two different MOAs, known to induce DNT in humans, during several time periods until 14 dpf. All fish were subjected to the L/D transition test at three subsequent timepoints: 5 dpf, 10 dpf and 14 dpf. The resulting dataset is being analyzed using a broad approach, considering all relevant endpoints that can be derived or calculated from the output data of the Zebrabox. In addition, samples have been taken to measure internal concentrations on all timepoints of behaviour assessment.

1.2.7 Zebrafish Neurospheres (Started Y3, M25, May 2024) [BfR (DE)]

- Start of the establishment of an *in vitro* method for DNT toxicity testing based on zebrafish (ZF) neural tissue. The initial time point 48 hpf has been proven to be suitable for obtaining the neural tissue of the ZF. 20 ZF brains were pooled for one dissociation. For the neurosphere preparation, two different protocols were tested, using either Accumax or DNase/Papain for the digestion step. We discovered that the protocol using DNase/Papain is best suited to dissociate ZF neural tissue.
- Determined the most suitable medium composition for proliferation by increasing the cell viability.
- Currently, on going work on optimizing the migration assay using two different cell attachment matrices (ECL – entactin, collagen IV, laminin; or Poly-D-Lysin/Laminin).

Progress made on the staining protocol, unravelling β III-tubulin+ cells in the migration area. Further work will come on astrocyte and oligodendrocyte differentiation assays.

- Progress has been delayed due to recruitment delay for the Ph.D. position. The Ph.D. candidate Indigo Brakus supervised by Dr. Britta Kühne und Prof. Marta Barenys started in June 2024.

Action 1.3 Build confidence that NAMs cover key modes of action (ED, epigenomic)

1.3.1 Epigenomic changes as early markers for DNT [Leader: UU (SE), partners providing the models: NIPH (NO), NMBU (NO), AIT (AT), IUF (DE), UG-PL (PL)]

Including epigenetic endpoints into DNT assays.

- The first proof of concept study in collaboration with NIPH (and IUF) is ongoing. The aim is to identify epigenetic endpoints in DNT assays using Illumina EPIC bead array and GBS-MeDIP, a method developed at UU. GBS-MeDIP has the advantage of being cheaper and not dependent on the producer (Illumina) of the bead arrays. One aspect of this proof-of-concept study is to compare the two methods for genome-wide methylation analyses and evaluate if GBS-MeDIP is sensitive enough for identifying relevant epigenetic patterns. The study is conducted in hNPCs that underwent differentiation for 3, 14 and 21 days (compared with time 0; neural stem cells) with acrylamide and its metabolite glycidamide as positive controls (based on interesting findings by RNAseq analysis).
- Samples for GBS-MeDIP were shipped to UU. UU optimised the GBS-MeDIP protocol for these cells and has prepared the samples for sequencing. Data (and publication) is expected by the end of 2024 [UU (SE) with NIPH (NO)].
- For establishing human relevance of the identified epigenetic markers, it is planned to compare results to human data. During Y3, UU has been involved in the generation and analysis of a genome-wide epigenetic dataset in the SELMA (Swedish Environmental Longitudinal, Mother and child, Asthma and allergy) study, a population-based mother-child cohort where epigenetic patterns in children aged 7 and 15 years can be linked to both prenatal chemical exposures and neurodevelopmental outcomes [UU (SE)].
- Developed and tested the method to measure hormone and neurotransmitter concentrations (ACh, cortisol, adrenaline) by use of high-resolution LC-MS technology in the larval zebrafish brain after exposure to PFAS and control substances (cortisol, carbamazepine) under DNT test scheme (master thesis in prep.). PFAS compounds were tested (PFOA, PFHxS, and PFOS and plan to test a PFAS mixture, PFNA, PFUnDA, and PFDA in Y4). All compounds will undergo further evaluations according to points 2-5. We plan to use this method to test other hormones (gap closure DNT) after exposures to neuroactive compounds [NMBU (NO)] .
- HTP and fluorescence imaging for DNT was completed in the AB wild-type strain and in in part (1.) the PFAS exposed transgenic mpeg1:gfp zebrafish (expresses GFP+ under the control of the macrophage-expressed gene (mpeg) promoter in microglial cells) embryos up to 5 dpf. Histopathological analyses and IHC analyses are in progress. Results of the HTP imaging and oxidative stress were presented at Eurotox 2024 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2024.07.461> (Nilsen et al, manuscript in prep). In Y4 we plan to use advanced detailed imaging of cellular and subcellular structures [NMBU (NO)].
- As further development of a NAM for neurotoxicity, it was screened the potency of selected contaminants to cause changes in cellular oxidative stress parameters such as cellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation including locomotor response (LMR) larval behaviour (Noldus DanioVision, Wageningen, the Netherlands). These screening tests are still ongoing for further PFASs exposures and controls [NMBU (NO)].

- The use of different probes for ROS assessment has been evaluated, including positive and negative controls for induction of ROS. Due to the extensive amount of laboratory work of the newly hired PARC PhD student and planned PARC mobility, the manuscript about the conclusions reached is postponed to Y4 [NMBU (NO)] .
- To build confidence that NAMs address potential neurotoxic modes of action (MoA) for the neurodevelopmental adverse outcomes (AOs), it has been sampled PFAS exposed embryonic and larval stages (3-120 hpf) of ABwt and transgenic zebrafish for RNA-seq and further OMICS (including epigenetics) analyses, which will take place in Y4 [NMBU (NO)].
- Transfer of the hiPSC-differentiation process from 6-well to 24-well format for a higher throughput and testing the effects of selected hormone receptor agonists and antagonists (applied during the differentiation process) on cell viability (MTT) and resulting barrier integrity (TEER), the effects of a mixture of six PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA), which were selected based on human blood concentrations in Scandinavian populations (collaboration with NIPH) was assessed. Interestingly, highest concentrations increased cell viability (MTT) and affected resulting transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER). High-throughput qPCR of hiPSC-brain endothelial-like cells revealed significant differences of Blood Brain Barrier (BBB) markers [AIT (AT)].
- A study relevant for reproducibility and robustness of the hiPSC-differentiation protocol about the influence of phenol-red in the cell culture media was finished. Next to barrier integrity changes also bulk RNAseq was conducted and showed significant differences in marker expression and pathway regulation dependent on basal media differences [AIT (AT)].
- A systematic review was conducted for *in silico* models to predict KE in AOPs for DNT induced by thyroid disruption, established in Y2. The available knowledge was summarized, and gaps were identified. Furthermore, each of the models was assessed according to OECD criteria. Manuscript in preparation [UG-PL (PL)].

1.3.2 Endocrine Disruption Analyse RNAseq data [NIPH (NO), IUF (DE), NMBU (NO)]

To build confidence that NAMs cover endocrine disruption modes of action (MoA) (and for further characterization in relation to closing gaps in DNT IVB), RNAseq analysis has been performed in 2D hNPCs “synaptogenesis” assay (NIPH) compared to 3D hNPCs [NIPH (NO) with IUF (DE)] (both derived from hiPSC) undergoing differentiation for 3, 14 and 21 days (*submitted*).

1.3.3 Endocrine Disruption single-cell sequencing (Started Y3, M25, May 2024, actively involved since 11/2023) [UoB (UK)]

- Identification of the source of origin of adverse outcome pathways in the central nervous system (brain and spinal cord) upon chemical exposure. Pilot studies with fluoxetine were carried out, a representative compound for developmental neurotoxicity in zebrafish larvae by single cell transcriptomics using the 10X genomic technology. Fluoxetine is known to have wide range of effects: in neuroendocrine signalling, synaptogenesis and disruption of lipid metabolism and nervous system and heart development. Computational analysis was carried out to generate cell clusters for each treated and controls sample and their replicates and identified their cell types by intersection with the Daniocell single cell atlas (<https://daniocell.nichd.nih.gov/>) as reference. Confounding effects of ambient RNA primarily from muscle/mesodermal cells were identified, which interfered with clustering and downstream differential gene expression analyses. However, removal of ambient RNA and subsequent removal of features/genes which were most likely originating from ambient RNA, i.e. not reported to be expressed in neuronal cells resulted in marked improvement in clustering of the neuronal cell populations and increased the accuracy in detection of

differentially expressed genes in the pseudo-bulk analyses. Thus, it was possible to cluster and identify neural cell types representing brain and spinal cord tissues and associate gene expression changes upon fluoxetine treatment.

1.3.4 Identification of AOP markers and cis-regulatory elements (enhancers) for use in NAMS assay development. (Started Y3, M25, May 2024, actively involved since 11/2023) [UoB (UK)]

- Identification of AOP markers and cis-regulatory elements (enhancers) for use in NAMS assay development. The computational analysis of the above experiments to seek AOP markers identified differentially regulated genes involved in dopaminergic and glucocorticoid signalling and comparison of fold changes between the bulk (data analysed without cell information) and pseudo-bulk (neuronal cell clusters) demonstrated the substantially higher sensitivity of the single cell approach in detecting changes in genes expressed in subset of cells. This revealed misregulation of specific neuroactive ligand-receptor, dopaminergic, steroid hormone signalling pathways in line with some reported effects of fluoxetine in zebrafish consistent with previous findings in bulk transcriptomic assays. The misregulated genes represent AOP marker candidates.
- Delays: not possible yet to identify cis-regulatory elements for use in NAMS as the single cell assay for transposase accessible chromatin with high-throughput sequencing (ATAC-seq) experiments have been delayed due to suboptimal nuclear preps from the zebrafish larval brains. In the meantime, we optimised nuclear preparations and will carry out single cell ATAC experiments for cis-regulatory element identification in Y4.

Action 2: Development of NAMs relevant for the detection of ANT. Readiness levels, performance parameters and applicability domains will be determined and probed in case studies on pathway-specific model compounds. An overall testing strategy including an ANT IVB will be proposed.

Action 2 seeks to fill gaps in the existing DNT *in vitro* test battery (DNT IVB). Here, information on the partners' DNT assays and readiness levels has been collected. The assay list is being used to design a comparative study on performance, sensitivity, specificity and redundancy of DNT test methods. For chemical selection, candidate model compound lists from consortium member projects and via interaction with ASPIS cluster EU projects have been assembled and a semi-automatic workflow was prepared to compile candidate compounds with physicochemical, structural and toxicological properties.

Action 2.1 New Cellular NAMs

2.1.1 Human Multi-Neurotransmitter Receptor (hMNR) [IUF(DE)]

- The human Multi-Neurotransmitter Receptor Assay (hMNR) evaluates substance effects on matured human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC)- derived BrainSpheres that undergo three weeks of 3D differentiation, followed by four weeks in 2D on a 96-well multielectrode array (MEA). Afterwards, adult neurotoxicity MoA can be assessed in acute or chronic exposure scenarios. Corresponding to this assay workflow, RNA sequencing samples (in triplicate) were collected at six stages: post-thaw (passage 0), passage 2, after 21 days of 3D, and at 14, 21, and 28 days of 2D differentiation. Early analysis confirms advanced network maturation by week 4, with late-stage genes (synapse organization, neurotransmitter storage/release) showing strong differential expression between weeks 3 and 4 of 2D differentiation.
- In addition, the biostatistical analysis and automated evaluation workflow of the hMNR assay were further improved enabling faster handling of generated data sets. This

includes the improvement of data evaluation procedure (workflow, tables, R-code) and the determination of cutoff-values.

2.1.2 Peripheral myelin toxicity [TiHo (DE)] (project started 08/23)

- The development of motor neuron and Schwann cell cocultures has been established in both 2D and 3D. Initial analyses of myelin expression in these models—specifically Myelin Protein Zero (MPZ) and Myelin Basic Protein (MBP) compared to panneuronal marker class III β -tubulin (TUJ1), quantified according to Chesnut et al. (2021) doi: [10.3390/ijms22157929](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22157929) and Pamies et al. (2021) revealed lower myelin expression in 3D cultures compared to 2D cultures (with no MBP expression and low MPZ expression). Additionally, electron microscopic analysis confirmed these findings. However, myelin expression in 2D cultures was also too low to directly proceed with demyelination assessments.
- To address this, work on optimizing myelination *in vitro* was initiated. The goal is to establish a sensitive demyelination assay by enhancing myelination in 2D cultures over a six-week period before transitioning to the 3D cultures. Various factors are being added to the culture medium to maximize myelination. This work on *in vitro* myelination is expected to be published in 2025 (Adams-Niedergeses et al.).
- Additionally, a Master's student, Julia Spänle, has contributed to the project by testing different xeno-free extracellular matrices to optimize stem cell cultures and neural differentiation, aiming to eliminate the need for Matrigel or animal-derived laminin. A review on the relevance of these xeno-free matrices for regulatory testing is scheduled for submission in October (Spänle et al.). Further, recombinant antibodies have been obtained
- Progress has been delayed due to significant recruitment challenges for both the Ph.D. stipend and postdoctoral positions. One candidate for the Ph.D. stipend, who was set to start in January 2024, quit after one week. A new Ph.D. student, Cody Adams-Niedergeses, began in June 2024. The postdoctoral position, initially held by Britta Kühne, Ph.D. (08/23–10/23), was filled by Dr. Lisa Haiber in January 2024. These delays, along with the additional step of optimizing myelination in the models, have necessitated an extension of the project timeline.

2.1.3 Blood-brain barrier integrity [AIT (AT)]

- A set-up with sampling at early time-points to determine the compound permeability across the hiPSC-based BBB model was successfully established and integrated into the test procedure. HPLC analysis was established for the five compounds and permeability coefficients were determined showing significant different permeation rates, which could be used for pharmacokinetic modelling.
- After successful assessment of the effects of the compounds on cell viability (MTT) on a differentiated model of neuronal SH-SY5Y cells, co-culture models have been set-up with brain endothelial cells in order to test if permeated compounds might influence underlying cells of the CNS. Standard brain endothelial cell line hCMEC/D3 was co-cultured either with astrocytoma or SH-SY5Y cells in Transwell models and effects of apically added compounds on TEER and cell viability (MTT) of hCMEC/D3 and astrocytoma or SH-SY5Y were tested after 72h of incubation. Results confirmed that the longer incubation time induced moderate effects detectable by TEER. Additional work on optimization of the SH-SY5Y differentiation protocol is ongoing.
- For ANT, ongoing work with five compounds (Capsaicin, Carbaryl, Diazinon, Brucin, Ibuprofen) to be tested considering different target receptors and easy-to-establish HPLC

analytical methods. First, the hiPSC-derived BBB model was exposed to these compounds at five concentrations for 24 hours and effects on barrier integrity (measurement of transendothelial electrical resistance = TEER) was assessed, and cell viability (MTT) and toxicity (LDH) measurement within the same assay as read-outs were successfully implemented. Although effects on cell viability were found, only small effects have been detected in TEER data. Since TEER is considered as an important read-out, next experiments with prolonged incubation times longer than 24h will be tested.

Action 3 originally contained all zebrafish work. Because zebrafish assays were designed to fulfill ANT and DNT testing aims, they were condensed into action items 1-2 in a previous version of the planning document.

Meetings:

- Internal project meetings: they take place the second Thursday of each month and include all partners (beneficiaries). In addition, regulatory partners from ECHA, EFSA, and the JRC participate to ensure that our products meet regulatory needs.
- Internal meetings of Action 1.3.1 Epigenomic changes as early markers for DNT (Work to include epigenetic endpoints into DNT assays). The subgroup on epigenetics has continued with meetings to update on proof-of-concept studies.
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (Lisbon, Portugal: 27-29 May 2024):
 - Establishment of a zebrafish neural tissue *in vitro* culture for DNT testing [BfR (DE) - poster]
 - Development of a High Throughput Thigmotaxis Assay to evaluate Neurotoxicity in Zebrafish Embryos [ISCI (ES) - poster]
 - Towards closing the gap of BBB data for neurotoxicity assessment: Establishment of human BBB *in vitro* models for adult and developmental neurotoxicity testing [AIT (AT)]
 - Next-generation NAM for neurotoxicity testing [UFZ (DE) - poster]
 - Innovative methods for regulatory developmental and adult neurotoxicity testing *in vitro* [IUF (DE) - poster]

Conferences:

- Norwegian Society for Pharmacology and Toxicology winter meeting (25-28 January 2024, Beitostølen, Norway):
 - Evaluation of developmental neurotoxicity induced by pesticides in human iPSC-derived neural stem cells undergoing differentiation towards neuronal and glial cells [NIPH (NO) - PARC registration number 140]
 - Transcriptomic characterization of 2D and 3D human induced pluripotent stem cell based *in vitro* New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for developmental neurotoxicity testing [NIPH (NO) - PARC registration number 148]
 - Developmental neurotoxicity of acrylamide and its metabolite glycidamide in a human mixed culture of neurons and astrocytes undergoing differentiation – a RNA sequencing study” [NIPH (NO)]
- European Congress on Alternatives to Animal Testing (EUSAAT) (18-20 September 2024, Linz, Austria):
 - Myelin matters: Development of a human stem cell-based peripheral myelin toxicity assay for regulatory testing [IUF (DE) - poster, PARC registration number 301]
- 5th International Conference on Developmental Neurotoxicity Testing (DNT) (7 - 10 April 2024, Konstanz, Germany):

- It was organized and used for refining future strategies concerning a regulatory implementation of the developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) *in vitro* test battery (DNT-IVB), also considering the important input from PARC. The outcome has been summarized in two manuscripts, which will be submitted in 2024 [UKON (DE)].
- PFAS and their mixtures as risk factor for neurodevelopmental disorders based on New Approach Methodologies and epidemiological studies [NIPH (NO)]
- Work from 5.2.1e was presented at the DNT5 meeting, SETAC, Society of Toxicology Annual Meeting, Eurotoxicology Annual Meeting, and the International Zebrafish Meeting.
- ISCI: Findings disseminated in a poster presentation at the 34th SETAC meeting and during the WP5 annual meeting in Lisbon.

Deliverables and publications:

- Cöllen E, et al. Elements and development processes for test methods in toxicology and human health-relevant life science research. *Altex*. Published in January 2024. <https://doi.org/10.14573/altex.2401041> [UKON (DE) - PARC registration number 154] (all actions)
- Brüll M, et al. Preparation of Viable Human Neurites for Neurobiological and Neurodegeneration Studies. *Cells*. Submitted in December 2023, published in January 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells13030242> [UKON (DE) - PARC registration number 155] (all actions)
- Suciú I, et al. Definition of the neurotoxicity-associated metabolic signature triggered by berberine and other respiratory chain inhibitors. *Antioxidants*. Submitted in December 2023, published in February 2024. doi: 10.3390/antiox13010049 [UKON (DE) - PARC registration number 156] (all actions)
- Tal T, et al. New approach methods to assess developmental and adult neurotoxicity for regulatory use: a PARC work package 5 project. *Frontiers in Toxicology*. Submitted in December 2023, published in April 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ftox.2024.1359507> [UFZ (DE), IUf (DE), NIPH (NO), UU (SE), ECHA, BfR (DE), INSERM (FR), RIVM (NL), UoB (UK), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), TihO (DE), UKON (DE), AIT (AT), ISCI (ES)] (all actions)
- Smirnova L, et al. Revolutionizing developmental neurotoxicity testing – a journey from animal models to advance *in vitro* systems. *Altex*. Published in April 2024. <https://doi.org/10.14573/altex.2403281> [UKON (DE)] (all actions)
- Leist M, et al. Controversy on health-based guidance values for bisphenol A - the need of criteria for studies that serve as a basis for RA. *Archives of Toxicology*. Published in May 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-024-03778-3> [UKON (DE) - PARC registration number 204] (all actions)
- Pamies D, et al. Recommendation on fit-for-purpose criteria to establish quality management for Microphysiological Systems (MPS) and for monitoring of their reproducibility. *Stem Cell Reports*. Published in May 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stemcr.2024.03.009> [UKON (DE) - PARC registration number 247] (all actions)
- Renner N, et al. Modeling ferroptosis in human dopaminergic neurons: Pitfalls and opportunities for neurodegeneration research. *Redox Biology*. Submitted in December 2023, published in July 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2024.103165> [UKON (DE) - PARC registration number 183] (all actions)
- Seal S, et al. From pixels to phenotypes: Integrating image-based profiling with cell health data as BioMorph features improves interpretability. *Molecular Biology of the Cell*. Published in February 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1091/mbc.E23-08-0298> [UU (SE)] (action 1.1.4)
- Gutsfeld S, et al. Investigation of Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Genes as Requirements for Visual Startle Response Hyperactivity in Larval Zebrafish Exposed to

- Structurally Similar Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS). Research. Published in July 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP13667> [UFZ (DE)] (action 1.2.1)
- Seltenrich N. Neurotox Screen? Zebrafish Study Points to PFOS Early-Life Exposure Effects. Science Selection. Published in August 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP1546> [UFZ (DE)] (action 1.2.1)
 - Leuthold D, et al. Multi-behavioral phenotyping in zebrafish identifies a novel disruptor of non-associative learning with environmental and human relevance. BioRxiv – preprint. Published in October 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.09.25.613874> [UFZ (DE), IUF (DE)] (action 1.2.1: development of the Visual and Acoustic Motor Response (VAMR) assay in 5 dpf zebrafish embryos using a 96 well plate format. This assay battery returns quantitative data on 16 endpoints including baseline activity, visual startle responses, visual motor responses, acoustic startle responses, acoustic startle habituation, potentiation of habituation, and memory retention)
 - Mercé T, et al. High-throughput assessment of neuromuscular functionality disruption in zebrafish larvae for toxicological and medical applications. In preparation. [INSERM-UBX (FR)] (action 1.2.3)
 - Ravel G, et al. Modelling zebrafish electric field pulse-induced escape response reveals neuromuscular energetic constraints and efficient body deformation adaptation to high-viscosity fluids. Submitted. [INSERM-UBX (FR)] (action 1.2.3)
 - Mercé T, et al. Comparative assessment of cholinergic and non-cholinergic locomotor disorders induced by organophosphorus compounds and their metabolites in zebrafish eleutheroembryos. In preparation. [INSERM-UBX (FR)] (action 1.2.3)
 - Lislien M, et al. Transcriptomic characterization of 2D and 3D human induced pluripotent stem cell-based *in vitro* models as New Approach Methodologies for developmental neurotoxicity testing (submitted) [NIPH (NO)] (action 1.3.2)

Table 6: DNT Chemical test set

Chemicals selected by 5.2.1e, in collaboration with JRC. Chemicals will be procured and distributed by the JRC in Y4 for testing in completed NAMs.

No	Compound	Comptox ID	CAS RN
1	Trichlorfon	DTXSID0021389	52-68-6
2	5,5-Diphenylhydantoin	DTXSID8020541	57-41-0
3	Tebuconazole	DTXSID9032113	107534-96-3
4	Hexachlorophene	DTXSID6020690	70-30-4
5	Triethyl-tin bromide	DTXSID1032226	2767-54-6
6	PFOA	DTXSID40892486	335-67-1
7	all-trans Retinoic acid	DTXSID7021239	302-79-4
8	Haloperidol	DTXSID4034150	52-86-8
9	Kainic acid	DTXSID7040526	487-79-6
10	PBDE 47	DTXSID3030056	5436-43-1
11	PBDE 99	DTXSID9030048	60348-60-9
12	Deltamethrin	DTXSID8020381	52918-63-5
13	Methylmercury chloride	DTXSID2031615	115-09-3

14	Nicotine	DTXSID1020930	54-11-5
15	Chlorpyrifos-oxon	DTXSID1038666	5598-15-2
16	Acrylamide	DTXSID5020027	79-06-1
17	Dexamethasone	DTXSID3020384	50-02-2
18	Sodium valproate	DTXSID6023733	1069-66-5
19	Tributyltin chloride	DTXSID0040709	1461-22-9
21	Chlorpromazine	DTXSID0022808	69-09-0
23	2(4-morpholinyl)benzothiazole	DTXSID90891505	4225-26-7
24	Narciclasine	DTXSID70183677	29477-83-6
25	Acetamiprid	DTXSID0034300	160430-64-8
26	Paraoxon (Parathion-oxon)	DTXSID6024046	311-45-5
27	Carbamazepine	DTXSID4022731	298-46-4
28	Imidacloprid	DTXSID5032442	138261-41-3
29	Rotenone	DTXSID6021248	83-79-4
30	Ethylenethiourea	DTXSID5020601	96-45-7
31	Fipronil	DTXSID4034609	120068-37-3
32	Thiamethoxam	DTXSID2034962	153719-23-4
33	Azoxystrobin	DTXSID0032520	131860-33-8
34	Camptothecin	DTXSID0030956	7689-03-4
35	Tetraethylthiuram disulfide	DTXSID1021322	97-77-8
36	Mebendazole	DTXSID4040682	31431-39-7
37	Citalopram	DTXSID8022826	59729-33-8
38	Lidocaine	DTXSID1045166	137-58-6
39	Cyclophosphamide	DTXSID5020364	50-18-0
40	Propylthiouracil	DTXSID5021209	51-52-5
41	Methotrexate	DTXSID4020822	59-05-2
42	Methimazole	DTXSID4020820	60-56-0
43	Azacytidine	DTXSID9020116	320-67-2
44	Cytosinearabioside	DTXSID3022877	147-94-4
45	Hydroxyurea	DTXSID6025438	127-07-1
46	Bromodeoxyuridine	DTXSID7033105	59-14-3
47	Colchicine	DTXSID5024845	64-86-8
48	Aspartame	DTXSID0020107	22839-47-0
49	5-Fluorouracil	DTXSID2020634	51-21-8

51	Limonin	DTXSID8045985	1180-71-8
53	ANA-12	DTXSID501045818	219766-25-3
54	Dorsomorphin	DTXSID401006988	866405-64-3
55	Diacylglycerol (1,2-Diastearin)	DTXSID20147249	10567-21-2
58	Digoxin	DTXSID5022934	20830-75-5
59	Manganese (II) chloride	DTXSID9040681	7773-01-5
62	Nocodazole	DTXSID9031800	31430-18-9
63	Mevastatin	DTXSID4040684	73573-88-3
64	Caffeine	DTXSID0020232	58-08-2
65	GABA	DTXSID6035106	56-12-2
66	Picrotoxin	DTXSID7045605	124-87-8
67	Bicuculline	DTXSID3042687	485-49-4
68	Glutamate	DTXSID5020659	56-86-0
69	DL-2-amino-5-phosphonovaleric acid (AP5)	DTXSID90893701	76326-31-3
70	NBQX disodium salt	DTXSID701019087	479347-86-9
71	Dopamine	DTXSID7020550	62-31-7
72	Buspirone hydrochloride	DTXSID1037193	33386-08-2
73	Carbaryl	DTXSID9020247	63-25-2
74	Trimethyltin chloride	DTXSID6042496	1066-45-1
75	Emamectine benzoate	DTXSID0034566	155569-91-8
77	Fluoxetine	DTXSID7023067	54910-89-3
78	Glycine	DTXSID9020667	56-40-6
79	Strychnine	DTXSID6023600	57-24-9
80	Lead (II) acetate trihydrate	DTXSID3031521	6080-56-4
81	Purmorphamine	DTXSID20415293	483367-10-8
82	Cyclopamine	DTXSID6043709	4449-51-8
83	Flavopiridol	DTXSID20904970	146426-40-6
84	Maneb	DTXSID9020794	12427-38-2
85	Bis-I (bisindolylmaleimide1)	DTXSID50157932	133052-90-1
86	Fulvestrant	DTXSID4022369	129453-61-8
88	Hydroxyflutamide	DTXSID8033562	52806-53-8
89	17-beta-estradiol	DTXSID0020573	50-28-2
90	Perfluorohexanesulfonate (PFHxS)	DTXSID3037709	3871-99-6

91	Bisphenol A	DTXSID7020182	80-05-7
92	Cuprizone	DTXSID30861909	370-81-0
95	Nomifensine	DTXSID0023377	24526-64-5
N1	Acetaminophen	<u>DTXSID2020006</u>	103-90-2
N2	Amoxicillin	<u>DTXSID3037044</u>	26787-78-0
N4	Chlorpheniramine maleate	<u>DTXSID4020321</u>	113-92-8
N5	Diethylene glycol	DTXSID8020462	111-46-6
N6	D-Mannitol	DTXSID30858955	87-78-5
N7	Doxylamine succinate	DTXSID7020552	562-10-7
N8	Famotidine	DTXSID5023039	76824-35-6
N9	Ibuprofen	DTXSID5020732	15687-27-1
N10	Metoprolol	DTXSID2023309	51384-51-1
N13	Warfarin	DTXSID5023742	81-81-2
N14	Dinotefuran	DTXSID7034549	165252-70-0
N15	Glycerol	DTXSID9020663	56-81-5
N16	Omeprazole	DTXSID6021080	73590-58-6
N17	Selegiline hydrochloride	DTXSID9044584	14611-52-0

➤ A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

Activity 5.2.2. operates under the project P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU, that has two main activities, one focuses on filling data gaps (A5.1.2) and another one on NAMs development (A5.2.2). These two activities cooperate on this project as both are focused on environmental aspects and investigate the BPA alternatives as horizontal PARC priority substances.

During Y1, information on NAMs was collected and discussed during an on-line workshop that took place in M7 to identify potential synergies and overlaps between the partners participating in the project. In order to identify the BPA alternatives that will be suitable for the development of specific NAMs, the participants have been successfully working on a review summarizing the occurrence and biological activity of the BPA alternatives identified from the BPA alternatives priority list (AD5.1, submitted in M10).

- **A5.2.2 Joint project: P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU [M1-M48] (project extended from M42 to M48)**

During months M21 to M32, subtask 5.2.2 continued in project activities, communicating with partners and focusing on the progress of the partners. The subtask's primary focus was on managing the project "BPA alternatives" to develop NAMs using BPA alternatives as model chemicals. This period also saw various collaborative and communication efforts across partners and work packages within the PARC framework.

The main 5.2.2. subtask meeting is regularly held in the spring of each year. In March 2024 (M23), an online “progress check” meeting was organized during this period, bringing together 46 participants from 16 partners involved in the project. The meeting focused on gathering updates on progress, identifying challenges, and fostering collaboration among partners.

The key information from the Progress Meeting indicating the status for Y3:

- **Project Schedule:** 65% of the partners are on schedule. The primary delay encountered was due to issues related to the standard delivery of BPA alternatives.
- **Obstacles:** 47% of partners reported no significant obstacles, with the main challenge being recruitment delays.
- **Budget Issues:** 79% of the partners did not face budgetary constraints. Budget issues were noted at the national level for a few partners.
- **Contribution Changes:** 80% of the partners reported no changes in their contributions to the project.

In summary, it is expected that the vast majority of partners will deliver their contribution as described in the project proposal, in spite of human resources challenges, or minor financial challenges.

Communication and Partner Engagement (Y3)

Subtask 5.2.2 leaders established and used bilateral communication with partners to ensure progress and overcome any unforeseen issues. The task leader [MU (CZ)] visited partner EAWAG (CH), to provide support and align on project objectives. In general, the main topics of discussion during these visits and bilateral communications and online meetings were the unforeseen challenges encountered by partners, the prioritization of tasks within the PARC project, data reporting strategies, and the future project opportunities within PARC.

Collaboration and Cross-Work Package Interaction (Y3)

Subtask 5.2.2 had active interaction with WP7 concerning data reporting strategy and related issues. Additionally, the subtask contributed to the development and commentary on the Priority Setting Document prepared by Task 2.1 within the PARC project, which is central to determining the project’s focus areas and future directions. Subtask leaders also attended the WP5 meeting in Lisbon to ensure synergies and report the project progress.

Publications and Knowledge Sharing (Y3)

The project's activities, in addition to partner-specific publications, resulted in three notable publications (extensive reviews and EPAA report) that summarized the biological activity of BPA alternatives and reported the PARC position in the field of alternatives to animal testing within the EU.

1. **Human Health:** A collaborative effort with Activity 5.1.2 resulted in a paper summarizing the biological activity of BPA alternatives on human health, currently in press (DOI: 10.1080/10408444.2024.2388712).
2. **Environmental Impact:** Another publication focusing on the environmental implications of BPA alternatives was released (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2024.108728).
3. **Regulatory Toxicology:** Subtask 5.2.2 also contributed to a manuscript ready for submission to *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, discussing the use of alternatives to animal testing for environmental safety assessment.

Sharing standard operating procedures (SOPs)

Subtask 5.2.2 leaders-initiated discussions on publishing SOPs related to NAM development, concluding with a recommendation to make them available on Zenodo and ANSES SharePoint for broader accessibility.

During months M21-M32, Subtask 5.2.2 made considerable progress on key projects, particularly in the development of NAMs through the “BPA alternatives” project. The subtask fostered extensive communication with partners, contributed to publications, and began planning for future initiatives in line with PARC priorities.

BPA Alternatives Project and NAMs Development

The primary activity of the subtask was the ongoing "BPA alternatives" project (**project P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU**), where BPA alternatives are used as model chemicals to advance NAMs. This project is vital in developing new, innovative approaches that reduce reliance on traditional animal testing methods.

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

Note that actions i and ii correspond to A5.1.2 and are described in their corresponding section.

Activity III. – In Silico Approaches

- *In silico* models for toxicological assessment of BPA alternatives. Identified gaps in current models and emphasized the need for improved tools. Continued development of specific models for BPA alternatives with new experimental data [NIC (SI)].
- TK-TD models from exposure dose to molecular and population-level responses. Focused on BPA alternatives (BPS and BPF) using zebrafish and stickleback. Data already produced. Continued work on extrapolation of organisms' responses to population levels [INERIS (FR)].
- Combined experimental and computational studies on BPA alternatives in *Daphnia magna*. Continued work on experimental validation of the developed models [UG-PL (PL)].
- Predicting aquatic neurotoxicity through machine learning. Compared sensitivity of daphnids and fish for neurotoxic and non-neurotoxic chemicals. Continued work on a model that predicts the neurotoxic potential of a chemical [EAWAG (CH), MUI (AT)].
- Advancing work on data and model harmonisation of *in silico* predictive modeling, grouping and uncertainty analysis with case studies from environmental domain [IISPV (ES)].
- Harmonization of data reporting template for computational effects assessment toolbox [NIVA (NO)].
- high-content screening of chemicals in the zebrafish embryo assay -12 BPA alternatives were tested to identify activities. Integrated new endpoints in high-content screening (e.g. cardiovascular) and work on extended QSAR models. Work on 28 BPA alternatives testing in in-vitro test batteries (ongoing). Investigated synergies of BPA alternatives effect and the additional stress of pesticides and food limitation (*Daphnia* model) [UFZ (DE)].

Activity IV. – Invertebrate Models

- Refinement and screening toolbox for molting disruptors using the *Daphnia* model. Initial screening of BPA alternatives was performed for molting disruption, including characterization of the mode of action [NIVA (NO)].
- Assessment of neurotoxicity, oxidative stress, and other endpoints in invertebrates. Continuous work on testing on *Daphnia* and *Artemia* to develop the methodological approach for the determination of specific enzymes' activity in tested organisms [UG-PL (PL)].

- Developed toxicity assessment methods using mollusk models. Embryotoxicity test developed employing transcriptomics. Continued work on the investigation of biomarker genes and the establishment of behavior methodologies [SLU (SE)].
- Developed an assay to assess endocrine effects in insects, focusing on the ecdysis process. Optimized SOPs for transcriptomics and protein extraction. Continued work on exposure design and methods for hormone analysis [BPI (EL)].
- Developed endocrine-disruptive endpoints using *Caenorhabditis elegans*. Continued work on finalizing RNA sequencing workflow, optimization, and validation of test protocol for *C. elegans* in liquid medium and validation of developed methods [BfG (DE)].
- Investigated endocrine-disruptive endpoints in snail model *Lymnaea stagnalis*. Metformin exposure and data analysis finalized in embryos. For selected BPA alternatives, exposure was finalized in embryos and adults (TG 243). Continued work on molecular endpoints and thyroid hormone analysis [SDU (DK)].
- Continued work on assessing obesity, oxidative stress, and neurotoxicity in model organism *C. elegans*. Data collected for several strains [UPO (ES)].
- Continued work on high throughput metabolomics in aquatic periphyton. Optimization of periphyton quantity, miniaturization and automatization of the assays [INRAE (FR)].
- Optimized a new high throughput behavioral vertical cuvette-oriented device able to monitor both vertical and horizontal swimming trajectories of *Daphnia magna* [CSIC (ES)].

Activity V. – Vertebrate Models

- Studied neurotoxic effects in zebrafish using five chemicals, including BPA. Completed behavioral assays, with data analysis of omics samples ongoing [EAWAG (CH), MUI (AT)].
- Progress was put on hold for vertebrate models due to external factors [BfG (DE)].
- Conducted zebrafish embryo tests for developmental neurotoxicity, focusing on thyroid-disrupting chemicals. Continued work on BPA alternatives and a broader spectrum of the visualization methods [UAntwerpen (BE)].
- Established a 3D *Zebrafish liver* (ZFL) model for genotoxicity evaluation. Continued work on toxicogenomic analysis and expanded assays for genotoxicity markers [NIB (SI)].
- Work on *Xenopus laevis* embryonic assay with an early exposure and short and late effects assays. Continued work on an endocrine disruption analysis [CNRS (FR)].
- Continued work on the multi-omics and cross-species, cross-omics data-based comparative pathway analysis using zebrafish models; the fish embryo test, incorporating automated morphology and behavioral assessments; and an automated content screening in zebrafish, including morphology assessment, behavioral analysis, and heart rate monitoring [UFZ (DE)].
- Continued work on optimization of assays focused on zebrafish development, endocrine disruption, and behavioral changes [SDU (DK)].
- Obtained all necessary approval at the national level for zebrafish experiments. Optimized chemical analysis for determination of BPA alternatives in tissues. Refinement of exposure conditions. Continued work on bioinformatic pipelines to determine the impact of chemicals on the intestinal microbiome [MU (CZ)].
- Developed and validated zebrafish embryo assay for identifying neurotoxic chemicals (ataxic gait assay). Compilation of a list of transcriptomic biomarkers for endocrine disruption in zebrafish embryos. Data was collected from zebrafish liver spheroids to determine toxicity and metabolic disrupting activity [CSIC (ES)].

Meetings

- Annual meeting A5.2.2. (13 March 2024, online) [all partners]

- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (Lisbon, Portugal: 27-29 May 2024):
 - Zebrafish embryo comparative high content assessment of BPA and substitution compounds [UFZ (DE) - poster]
 - Development of a multi-endpoint Data Reporting Format (DRF) for FAIRification of (eco)toxicity data [NIVA (NO) - poster]
 - Characterization of molting disruptors using AOP- informed screening tests in Crustaceans [NIVA (NO) - poster]
 - New approach methodologies with invertebrates for the identification of adverse environmental effects like endocrine-disruption – Pros and cons of *C. elegans* for testing BPA alternatives [BfG (DE) - poster]
 - Exploring the Molecular Basis of Transient versus Persistent Neurotoxic Effects Using a Multi-Omics Approach in the Zebrafish Model [EAWAG (CH) - poster]

Conferences

- Norwegian Society for Pharmacology and Toxicology winter meeting (25-28 January 2024, Beitostølen, Norway):
 - Linking chemical disruption of molting processes to survival of crustaceans [NIVA (NO)]
- 5th International Conference on Developmental Neurotoxicity Testing (DNT) (7-10 April 2024, Konstanz, Germany):
 - Exploring the Molecular Basis of Transient versus Persistent Neurotoxic Effects Using a Multi-Omics Approach in the Zebrafish Model [EAWAG (CH) - poster]
- 22nd International Congress of the European Society of Toxicology *In Vitro* (ESTIV 2024) (3-6 June 2024, Prague, Czech Republic):
 - Ecotoxicological Evaluation of Bisphenol A and alternatives: A Comprehensive *in silico* Modelling Approach [NIC (SI)]
- 7th IC-3Rs Symposium 2024 (19 September 2024, Brussel, Belgium):
 - Impact of endocrine disruption on the number of hair cells in neuromasts of the lateral line organ of zebrafish larvae [UAntwerpen (BE)]
 - Advancing the understanding of the life-stage specific impact of thyroid hormone system disruption in the zebrafish embryo model [UAntwerpen (BE)]
- IX Spanish Worm Meeting (24-25 October 2024, Seville, Spain):
 - Comparative toxicity of plastic related chemicals on *Caenorhabditis elegans*: bisphenol A and two caprolactones [UPO (ES) - poster]

Deliverables and publications

- Gasser L, et al. Machine learning-based prediction of fish acute mortality: implementation, interpretation, and regulatory relevance, *Environ. Sci. Adv.* Submitted in March 2024, published in June 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4VA00072B>
- Adamovsky O, et al. Exploring BPA alternatives – Environmental levels and toxicity review, *Environment International*, submitted in February 2024, published in June 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108728>
- Stevanovic M, et al. Zebra-K, a kinematic analysis automated platform for assessing the sensitivity, habituation and prepulse inhibition of acoustic startle in adult zebrafish. *International Journal of Molecular Science*, submitted in September 2024, published in October 2024. doi: 10.20944/preprints202409.0525.v1
- Vracko M, et al. Clustering of Bisphenols Based on Toxicity Predictions for Key Aquatic Species: *Daphnia Magna*, Fathead Minnow, and Fish. *Aquatic toxicology*. 2024. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4942077>

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D5.1	1st New approach methodologies report	BfR	M18 (postponed M20)	M23	Delayed to include a section on: readiness for regulatory (Position paper)

1.2.5.3 Task 5.3. Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs

Leader: UL-LACDR (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), INSERM (FR), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE)

Participants:

Activity 5.3.1: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), KIT (DE), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), Sciensano (BE), UFZ (DE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIABDN (UK), WSFR (NL)

Activity 5.3.2: ACES/SU(SE), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BfG (DE), BPI (EL), DTU (DK), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KIT (DE), KU Leuven (BE), MUI (AT), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), Sciensano (BE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIVIE (AT), WSFR (NL)

Activity 5.3.3: ANSES (FR), ETHZ (CZ), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), NVI (NO), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UNIVIE (AT); WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

- A5.3.1 Prioritised NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterisation and A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology (Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment).

These two activities were combined in a single project for coherence purposes:

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR [M1-M48] (project extended from M36 to M48)**

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

In this reporting period the project continued working on the identified Case Studies (CS).

CS1: Application of transcriptomics for read across and grouping approaches [leading: Sciensano (BE), UFZ (DE); contributing: IISPV (ES), ISCIII (ES), UG-PL (PL), AUTH (EL), IRFM (IT)]. The overall objective of the case study is to compare different methodologies of grouping

based on chemical properties and grouping based on mode of action data (e.g. omics). This CS is working closely in collaboration with ECHA. The different methods have been applied to existing datasets of BPA and BPA alternatives. During Y3, CS1 evaluated more chemical fingerprinting methods. This CS highlighted how different methodologies as well different sources of data resulted in different grouping results.

CS2: Application of transcriptomics for *ab initio* hazard characterization and RA [leading: UL-LACDR (NL), KIT (DE); contributing: Sciensano (BE), UGent (BE), AUTH (EL)]. This case study aims at investigating the application of different systems toxicology methods available at case study partners for an *ab initio* approach for hazard assessment. We have applied different methods including gene set enrichment analysis, Weighted Gene Correlation Analysis (WGCNA), genotoxicity biomarkers sets and subsequently different benchmark dose response analysis methods. We have worked on a dataset of kidney cells (RPTEC-TERT1) and primary human proximal tubule cells) exposed to several doses of cisplatin at different time points. UL-LACDR has developed an automated and interactive report for systems tox *ab initio* assessment, that is currently being tested by the other partners. This CS is currently consolidating the findings in a publication, and a draft is expected to be completed by the end of Y3.

CS3: Assessment of temporal transcriptomics responses and the impact on hazard identification in safety assessment [leading: INSERM (FR); contributing: IISPV (ES)]. In this case study, different computational approaches and protocols developed by the partners in PARC are applied and the outcome will propose best practices for time course experiments in systems toxicology.

In Y3 this CS has worked on an *in vivo* transcriptomics dataset of rat exposed to 3 chemicals (diclofenac, naproxen, diuron and the mixture of the 3 of them) at 6 time points and 5 concentrations. An *in vitro* dataset has also been analyzed, including liver spheroids exposed to cyclosporin A and Phenytoin at different concentrations and time points. CS3 has included a comparison with the existing *in vivo* data in TG-GATEs with similar concentration and time point profiles. All 3 CS have tested the implementation of the OECD Reporting Transcriptomic Framework (<https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/testing/omics.htm>). In particular, CS2 have used the reporting structure to highlight analysis differences and indicated areas of unclear or missing information. Regulatory agencies showed interest in this project activities via CS specific activities and deliverables and are regularly participating in update meetings (ECHA and FDA).

Human translation of toxicogenomics data [leading and contributing: UL-LACDR (NL)]. In parallel to the above case studies UL-LACDR has also worked on the translation of toxicogenomics data to human *in vivo* responses. UL-LACDR has constructed a gene co-expression model (WGCNA) for a dataset of human kidney biopsy samples (>650) with diverse pathologies. The generated modules were validated using predefined gene sets from the MMDx database, confirming the relevance of our modules. Using gene sets from the MMDx database, we identified modules linked to cell-type specific transcripts and validated them with deconvolution from single cell sequencing data. Expression profiles from human *in vivo* settings were compared with those from an *in vitro* human RPTEC/TERT1 cell line: 43% of the human kidney modules were found to be preserved in the *in vitro* cell line. This result is remarkably good, especially considering the large differences in physiology between a 2D cell line of immortalized human proximal tubule cells and a section of human whole kidney.

Meetings:

- Project annual meeting (10-11 April 2024, Leiden, the Netherlands): UL-LACDR (NL) hosted a workshop with all partners to report on CS progress and finalize the next steps and publication strategy. Participants were: Sciensano (BE), INSERM (FR), UFZ (DE), IRFM (IT), UGent (BE), KIT (DE), AUTH (EL).
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (27-29 May 2024, Lisbon, Portugal):

- Translation of *in vitro* models to human data: systems toxicology approaches for renal toxicity assessment [UL-LACDR (NL) - poster]
- Bringing systems toxicology into RA: learnings from the read-across, ab-initio and temporal data and human translation case studies [UL-LACDR (NL), UFZ (DE), UHC (DE), Sciensano (BE), INSERM (FR) - poster]

Conferences:

- XVII Congreso Español y VII Iberoamericano de Salud Ambiental (15-17 May 2024, Malaga, Spain):
 - Toxicological and epidemiological approach for estimating the health impact of atmospheric pollutant [ISCI (ES) - presentation]
- EuroTox2024 (08-11 September 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark): NCPHP, MUI, RIVM and LIST (1 joint poster), AUTH, IISPV, INSERM, IRSN, NIPH, UG-PL, UMIL (1 joint poster), UGent (1 poster)

Publications and deliverables

- AD5.7 “Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms” have been submitted the 02/02/2024 (M22).
- Canzler S, et al. Evaluating the performance of multi-omics integration - a thyroid toxicity case study. Archives of Toxicology. Under review, submitted in September 2024.

➤ A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_INSERM [M1-M48] (project extended from M36 to M48)**

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

In year 3, all groups continued their activities: the core group (CG) with expertise in methods for AOP development, the three specialty groups (SG1: immunotoxicity and NGTxC; SG2: endocrine disruption; SG3: neurotoxicity) and the effect markers group (EMG including subgroups corresponding to the 3 SGs and a subgroup on epigenetics). The SGs and EMG finalized the inventory on the available AOPs and/or effect markers in their own fields and identified the AOPs that they considered to be their priorities for further development or for build-up.

Work of the CG, the SGs and the EMG is detailed below:

CG – Core group Leads: [INSERM (FR), AUTH (EL) and Sciensano (BE)]

FAIR tools linking chemicals to AOP events based on text mining and AI methodologies are under development in collaboration with WP8 (e.g., AOP-helpFinder v3 should be released soon). The CG supported the work of the SGs, and organized meetings with other WPs (e.g. WP6, WP7 and WP8).

SG1 – Immunotoxicology and Non-Genotoxic Carcinogenesis Leads: [NIPH (NO) and MUI (AT)]; Partners: [AUTH (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), KIT (DE), NCPHP (HU), UMIL (IT), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL), LIST (LU), UL-LACDR (NL), RIVM (NL), Sciensano (BE)].

SG1 has been further subdivided in 3 workings groups:

- **Respiratory sensitisation group** [MUI (AT), NCPHP (HU), LIST (LU), UMIL (IT), RIVM (NL), INSERM (FR)]: A list of literature-characterized and officially categorized respiratory sensitizers was prepared and an inventory of AOP/KE and NAMS (potentially) applicable to respiratory sensitization was created and published together with a summary on the current status of mechanistic understanding of respiratory sensitization, including newly suggested KEs and a critical discussion of knowledge gaps in the field of respiratory sensitization. All groups contributed to the review (Hargitai R, et al., 2024, doi: 10.3389/ftox.2024.1331803), which is a joint initiative with WP5.2. MUI, LIST and RIVM also participated in the OECD DRP writing group. Air-Liquid Interface (ALI) exposures on the two prioritised chemicals were performed in a dose-response manner (RIVM).
- **Immunosuppression group** [NIPH (NO), WR (NL), UNIVIE (AT), INSERM (FR), IISPV (ES), RIVM (NL), AUTH (EL)]: All partners in the immunosuppression working group participated in the further development of the AOP 14 (GR Activation leading to Increased Disease Susceptibility), including AI-assisted literature searches (AOP-helpFinder 2.0). In collaboration with WP7.3.3 partners IISPV (ES), the WG is engaged in an AOPbot case-study based on the AOP 14 work. Part of the work was written up as a master thesis and successfully defended in June 2024.
- **Non-genotoxic carcinogenesis (NGTxC) group** [NIPH (NO), INSERM (FR), KIT (DE), ISS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL)]: All the partners in the NGTxC group took part in the discussions concerning the development of 3 AOPs: (i) AOP 439 (<https://aopwiki.org/aops/439>), which links AhR activation to breast cancer tumor formation, and (ii) the 2 AOPs 474 and 534 (<https://aopwiki.org/aops/474/> <https://aopwiki.org/aops/534/>), which link succinate dehydrogenase inhibition to tumour formation. AO 439 is the subject of a scientific publication (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107323>) and has undergone an internal review by the OECD, a process that has now been finalised. It has been sent for external review and we are awaiting feedback.

SG2 – Endocrine and metabolic disruption [Leads: UAntwerpen (BE), SDU (DK)]; Partners: [AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BfG (DE), BPI (EL), DTU (DK), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KU Leuven (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL), Cefas-Defra (UK), MU (CZ)].

SG2 has three main activities:

- **Thyroid hormone system disruption** [Lead: UAntwerpen (BE), partners: ISS (IT), AUTH (EL), UG-PL (PL), BPI (EL), SDU (DK),]: Work on the following priorities has been performed: Develop MIE Monocarboxylate Transporter 8 (MCT8)inhibition (UAntwerpen), Develop paths leading to AOs (e.g. impairment of motor activity and/or social responses or other behavioural endpoints) via hypothalamus disruption (ISS, AUTH), Develop sex applicability domain descriptions (ISS), Investigate whether KEs and KERs linking THSD to DNT in mammals are also applicable to fish (UAntwerpen, UG-PL, BPI, AUTH), Implement tDOA study results from ERGO in AOP-Wiki (UAntwerpen), Explore linkages between THSD and metabolic disruption with human relevance (AUTH, ISS), Explore mechanisms initiated by thyroid receptor (TR) antagonism (Cefas-Defra), Initiate AOP development for invertebrates (SDU), Explore potential disruption of the thyroid system by PFAS (UG-PL), Explore cross talk between TR antagonism during development and reproduction focusing on DNT endpoints (Cefas-Defra).
- **(Anti-)androgen and (anti-)estrogen disruption** [Lead: KI (SE), partners: AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), BfG (DE), Cefas-Defra (UK), UNIVIE (AT)]: Work on the following priorities has been performed: Development of an AOP describing perturbation of androgen receptor activity leading to reduced fetal growth (AU, BPI, BfG, AUTH, KI), Development of an AOP for Androgen receptor agonism leading to reproductive dysfunction (in annual-

spawning fish) (Cefas-Defra), Exploring molecular mechanism of a crosstalk between estrogen and AhR signaling pathways leading to immunosuppression (UNIVIE, KI).

- **Metabolic disruption** [Lead: INSERM (FR)]: Work on the following priority has been performed: AhR activation leading to liver fibrosis.

SG3 – Neurodevelopment [Leads: NIPH (NO), AUTH (EL), and UMIL (IT), partners: BfR (DE), BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), UG-PL (PL), UAntwerpen (BE), UHC (DE), NILU (NO)]. The SG3 has divided its activities into two subtasks: adult neurotoxicity (ANT) and developmental neurotoxicity (DNT).

- **ANT** [Lead: UMIL (IT), partners: AUTH (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRSN (FR), NIPH (NO), UG-PL (PL)]: ANT/SG3 initiated the development on an AOP network to investigate the potential correlation between the dysregulation of clinically recognized biological markers of Alzheimer Disease and exposure to stressors such as Organochlorines (OC) and Organophosphorus (OP) pesticides. The strategy adopted is to design an a priori protocol (ALL PARTNERS), to develop an AI tool for KEs prioritization, literature screening and data extraction (AUTH, IISPV, INSERM, NIPH), complemented by an expert knowledge-based approach (ALL PARTNERS), and to carry out a systematic review process by experts using the RAYYAN tool to also screen the literature and complement the Key Event Relationship (KER) (ALL PARTNERS led by UG-PL).
- **DNT** [Lead: AUTH (EL), partners: INSERM (FR), NIPH (NO), BfR (DE), UG-PL (PL), UAntwerpen (BE), BPI (EL), UNIVIE(AT)]: Four priorities were identified by the DNT SG3 subgroup: (i) development an AOP that will provide evidence for the dysregulation of glycolysis after early developmental stages exposure to EDCs” (AUTH, NIPH, UNIBAS, INSERM); (ii) development of an AOP that will provide evidence for the dysregulation of the tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA) cycle after early developmental stages exposure to EDCs (AUTH, NIPH, UNIBAS, INSERM), (iii) investigation on whether KEs and KERs linking THSD to DNT in mammals are also applicable to fish (UAntwerpen, AUTH, BPI, UG-PL) and (iv) the development of an AOP for toxicants (e.g. L-BMAA) resembling natural amino acids” (AUTH, NIPH, BfR, UG-PL).

EMG – Effect markers [Leads: AU (SE) and KU Leuven (BE), partners: BPI (EL), INSERM (FR), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), UG-PL (PO), UGent (BE), AUTH (EL), MUI (AT), IISPV (ES), UHC (DE)]

- **Endocrine disruption** (AU): Search of effect markers for estrogen-, androgen-, and thyroid-related AOPs. The results of androgen and thyroid were included in D5.3, and manuscript writing is planned. Search on the estrogen related markers is ongoing.
- **Immunotoxicity & NGTxC** (NIPH, NCPHP, MUI, UGent): Search of effect markers for respiratory sensitization (NCPHP, MUI), immunosuppression (NIPH, UGent) and NGTxC-related AOPs. For respiratory sensitization, several effect markers including both omics and physiological effects markers were identified eg. bronchial provocation test, basophil activation test, eosinophil-derived neurotoxin level, exhalome analysis, miRNA ratios in blood or breath, serum cytokine level. Probably a single test will not be sufficient for a specific and sensitive assessment, but a combination of suitable assays (a battery of tests of several KEs) could be used in an integrated testing strategy. A PubMed search (NIPH) for potential markers of immune suppression / immune function has been performed. At least one of the identified markers will be tested in a human cohort to assess its predictive value in epidemiological studies (Y3/4). The literature review for the identification of effects markers for immunosuppression also included a specific search for the effects of marine toxins using AOP helpfinder as well as a search on the NCBI database for gene expression data (UGent). For 2 marine toxins the mode-of-action and immunomodulating effects were

explored using *in vitro* human cell line models in order to experimentally validate some of the effect markers.

- Metabolism (INSERM): Search on effect markers for metabolism-related AOPs.
- Neurotoxicity (AUTH): Finalization of the identification of effect markers for neurotoxicity related-AOPs (DNT & ANT) retrieved from the AOP-wiki. For all MIEs, KEs, and AOs with no effect markers, an initial literature review on potential biomarkers that could be used to assess the impact of various neurotoxic agents on neurodevelopmental processes was conducted. Comprehensive literature reviews, mainly targeting MIEs, KEs, and AOs that lack identified effect markers for DNT and ANT were initiated.
- Epigenetic effects (KU Leuven, UG-PL, IISPV, UGR, BPI, UHC): Search on epigenetic effects markers. Continuation of the work on one human data set, including exposure-outcome correlation analyses. Potential interactions or confounding factors (age, lifestyle, BMI, patient status, ...) to avoid inaccurate results were explored. Data analyses are ongoing with a focus on epigenetic changes in the germ line, and environmental chemicals, including organophosphate esters (OPEs) (from flame retardants and/or plasticizers), as environmental chemicals of interest.

Meetings:

- Organisation of an online Developmental immunotoxicity (DIT) workshop (two half-days, 1st & 4th of March 2024) with a broad representation of WP5 partners, regulatory agencies and potential US collaborators.
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (27-29 May 2024, Lisbon, Portugal):
 - Development of new and existing Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) linked to developmental neurotoxicity [AUTH (EL), NIPH (NO), BfR (DE), UG-PL (PL), INSERM (FR), UAntwerpen (BE), UMIL (IT) - poster]
 - Strengthening Chemical RA through the Development of Adverse Outcome Pathways for Immunotoxicity Endpoints [UNIVIE (AT), NIPH (NO), RIVM (NL), WR (NL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), KIT (DE), ISS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL) - poster]
 - Designing a putative AOP for identifying substances potentially associated with Alzheimer's disease [UMIL (IT), NIPH (NO), INSERM (FR), AUTH (EL), CNRS (FR), UG-PL (PL), IISPV (ES) - poster]
 - Intergenerational chemical RA in humans using epigenetic epidemiology studies and machine learning approaches [KU Leuven (DE), IISPV (ES), UHC (DE), UG-PL (PL), BPI (EL) - poster]

Conferences:

- EuroTox2024 (08-11 September 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark):
 - Artificial intelligence for the development of Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) to assess neurodegenerative disorders following ionizing radiation exposure [AUTH (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FE), IRSN (FR), NIPH (NO), UG-PL (PL), UMIL (IT) - poster]
 - Designing a putative AOP for identifying substances potentially associated with Alzheimer's disease [UMIL (IT), NIPH (NO), INSERM (FR), AUTH (EL), CNRS (FR), UG-PL (PL), IISPV (ES) - poster]
 - NCPHP, MUI, RIVM and LIST (1 joint poster)
 - UGent (1 poster)
- Lung *In Vitro* Event (20-21 June 2024, Nice, France): RIVM (1 poster)
- 63rd Annual Meeting and ToxExpo of the Society of Toxicology (SOT) (10-14 March 2024, Salt Lake City, USA):
 - RIVM (invited lecture) + poster

- AUTH, IISPV, INSERM, IRSN, NIPH, UG-PL, UMIL (1 joint poster)

Publications and deliverables

- D5.3 “report on AOPs”, submitted June 2024 (M26) [all partners]. This document gives an overview of the AOPs that are being developed as part of Project 5.3.2a (AOP development) and Task 6.1 (IATAs development), their development status, and follow up actions for regulatory acceptance of those AOPs. In addition, an update on the work of the EMG is provided in the present deliverable as well.
- Jaylet T, et al. Comprehensive mapping of the AOP-Wiki database: identifying biological and disease gaps. *Front Toxicol*. Submitted in August 2023, published in March 2024, 8;6:1285768. doi: 10.3389/ftox.2024.1285768. PMID: 38523647; PMCID: PMC10958381. This publication was the result of a collaborative effort among all SG regarding the case studies, culminating in a thorough analysis and mapping of the AOP-Wiki database to identify (biological and disease) gaps.
- Hargitai R, et al. Chemical respiratory sensitization-Current status of mechanistic understanding, knowledge gaps and possible identification methods of sensitizers. *Front Toxicol*. Submitted in November 2023, published in July 2024, 29;6:1331803. doi: 10.3389/ftox.2024.1331803. eCollection 2024. PMID: 39135743
- Nurettin Y, et al. AOP-networkFinder - A versatile tool for FAIR reconstruction of Adverse Outcome Pathway networks from AOP-Wiki. *Bioinformatics and bioRxiv*, published in April 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11068434

➤ A5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology

Projects progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology_Fraunhofer [M1-M48] (project extended from M36 to M48)**

In Y1, seven different case studies were defined to address knowledge as well as conceptual gaps in IVIVE-PBK models. By this activity we will ensure that the PBK models developed in this project will be useful for the development of quantitative AOPs (a close link to A5.3.2) and also for *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolations (a close link to T6.1).

The core group comprises experts in PBK modelling and/or *in vitro* ADME models (P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer) and coordinates the selection of case study compounds according to the identified data and conceptual knowledge gaps. The core group also coordinates the cooperation with other tasks like T5.3, T5.2 and WP6 to finally generate a harmonised framework for kinetic modelling.

Detailed description of the actions carried out M21-M32:

The experimental testing of *in vitro* ADME input data is ongoing in the different case studies:

Case study 01a: 01_a_human_microbiome [Lead: ETHZ (CH), participants: WR (NL), UNIVIE (AT), IISPV (ES)]

This case study focuses on developing and evaluating *in vitro* tools to measure gut microbial metabolism kinetics as well as *in silico* strategies to accurately incorporate such results into gut competent PBK models. As a second step, these will be applied to generate data for PARC priority chemicals.

Until now, the following progress has been achieved:

- A joint review on gut competent PBPK modeling was published to provide a comprehensive

assessment of the methodological status quo of microbiome incorporation in PBK models (Stevanoska M, et al. 2024). - Anaerobic fermentation experiments using human samples were conducted to compare the impact of different sampling and fermentation conditions on chemical biotransformation. To that end, the degradation kinetics of a set of chemical probes that represent the metabolic capacity of the gut microbiome was followed by LC-MS/MS. Results show significant interindividual differences, as well as significant effects of media composition and feces dilution on microbiome's biotransformation capacity. However, freezing and storage of fecal samples did not affect microbial metabolism. A research paper compiling these data in concrete recommendations for the design of future test systems is in preparation.

- Ongoing work on a QSAR tool to quantitatively predict enterohepatic recirculation of glucuronides. First results were shown as a poster at EUROTOX 2024 [ETHZ (CH)].
- Collaboration on the assessment of gut microbial metabolism of three chemicals of interest [ETHZ (CH), IISPV (ES)].

Case study 01b: 01_b_CS_zebrafish_microbiome [Lead: UFZ (DE), participant: ETHZ (CH)]

This CS is on hold due to a budget reallocation at the UFZ (DE).

Case study 02: PBK models for PFAS compounds [Lead: IISPV (ES), participants: WR (NL), UNISANTE (CH), WU-TOX (NL)]

Until now for PFAS compounds, the mechanistic aspect i.e., the enterohepatic recirculation, liver transporters, and kidney transporters like organic anion transporting polypeptides (OATP) which has been observed in rats and mice, is lacking. In addition, during the literature review of existing data, IISPV also observed some drastic differences in mechanism related to PFOS and PFOA for rat and human in published PBK models, making extrapolation from one species to another extremely difficult. Considering all these modeling gaps, a strategy was built to develop an advanced generic PBK model for 4 PFAS compounds by joint effort from IISPV and WR. Additionally, to account for sex related differences in the elimination of these compounds advanced model will help in bridging the gaps as separate models were built for male and female. The work of this case study has been combined with the case study of PFAS PBK modelling in WP6.2.2 and the partners listed therein.

- An advanced generic PBK model for 4 PFAS compounds considering OECD PBK reporting template and criterion in rat has been developed.
- Ongoing work on extrapolation of the rat PFOS and PFOA PBK model to human and on the validation for different exposure scenarios.
- For PFNA and PFHxS, rat PBK model validation is ongoing, and some significant sex related differences were observed.
- In-vitro permeation and enterohepatic recirculation (EHR) data from different cell lines have been extracted for PFAS compounds and IVIVE approach is being used to include it in the PFAS NAM based model. Few results of the model were shown as a poster in Eurotox 2024.
- Newly developed PFAS PBPK model has been used to simulate blood concentrations and compare these with experimental blood concentrations from the general population provided by the Swiss Federal Office of Public Health (UNISANTE).

Case study 03: Isoform metabolism [ISS (IT), WU-Tox (NL), Fraunhofer (DE), INERIS (FR), UNIVIE (AT), UNISANTE (CH)]

Since the isoform specific metabolism and the involvement of specific transporters has been considered by EFSA as one of the crucial data to evaluate human variability related to kinetics differences (Testai et al, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.7033>), the case study aims to include this kind of data into PBK models, thus enhancing their predictability of the internal dose possibly tailored for the different population groups. For this reasons data rich model compounds (e.g. organophosphorothionate or pyrethroid pesticides or pharmaceutical such as irinotecan) as well other compounds for which data will be experimentally produced within PARC (e.g. BPA alternatives or natural toxins such as Alternaria toxins) were selected.

- Data on isoform specific metabolism of 5 OPT compounds catalysed by CYP and PON have been collected together with *in vivo* data and existing information on PBK models available. In addition, relative expression of CYP and PON isoforms in different life stages were also collected in order to see the contribution of metabolism in the age-specific toxicity of OPTs. (ISS) Data are ready to be transferred to modelers (Fraunhofer).
- Data on isoform specific metabolism of 8 Pyrethroids (PYR) catalysed by CYP and carboxylesterases (CE) have been collected together with *in vivo* data and existing information on PBK models available. In addition, relative expressions of CYP and CE isoforms in different life stages were also collected in order to see the contribution of metabolism in the age-specific toxicity of PYR (ISS). Data have been transferred to modelers (INERIS), who started to model the data after collecting information on *in vivo* exposure as well as on existing information on PBK models (INERIS).
- Data gap for PYR have been detected and CYPs and CEs isoform specific metabolism will be carried out on Cypermethrin, fenpropratin and tau fluvalinate. The biological material has been already purchased. The experiments will start as soon as the chemical standards will be delivered. The data delays from other 5.1.1 projects (bisphenols), regarding isoform specific metabolism, persist for solubility problem of the test items (as indicated in the specific section).

Case study 04: Tiered testing strategy for inhalation PBK modelling [Lead: INERIS (FR), participants: Fraunhofer (DE), STAMI (NO), AUTH (EL)]

In the first 18 months of the project five case study compounds (thymol, propanolol, hippuric acid, mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate and Sumatriptan) which differ with regard to the absorption kinetics have been selected by INERIS and Fraunhofer. SOPs have been agreed and shared within partners in the beginning of the testing procedure. Partners are involved in different steps:

- Develop combined *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches to estimate the absorption of inhaled environmental contaminants. This includes stability testing in cell free environment, binding to plastics and binding to biological matrices (INERIS); passive absorption using the PAMPA assay (Fraunhofer); assessment of permeability through three different barrier models (INERIS, ITEM, STAMI).
- Address the *in vitro* kinetics of the compound at the air-liquid interface and compare the observations with the predictions of current *in silico* models (INERIS).
- Evaluate the impact of relevant *in vitro* ADME parameters to further develop or improve PBK models (Fraunhofer, INERIS).
- The analytical work is done at AUTH.

The *in vitro* model used by STAMi showed a very high permeability. In fact, HBEC-3KT in normal culture medium (LCH-9) does not give very high TEER measurements. Therefore, this model is not suitable for studying the kinetics of the test compounds.

The characterisation of the test compounds in the test systems, including polymer binding, abiotic degradation, binding to biological matrices (cells and FBS), was carried out to determine more accurately the actual exposure of the cells to the compounds (thymol, propanolol, hippuric acid,

mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate and sumatriptan). Some results are still pending as the bioanalysis phase has not been completed.

All permeability tests were performed on the compounds tested. Fraunhofer performed PAMPA and Calu-3 cells for liquid-liquid interface permeability assays, Ineris performed Calu-3, hAelvi cells for air-liquid interface permeability assays. Permeability results are pending.

Once the data is available, biokinetic and PBK models will be developed.

Posters of this work were presented at the annual PARC meeting and at the meeting of the French "Groupe de Métabolisme et Pharmacocinétique -GMP-".

Case study 05: Integrate models addressing the transport via the blood brain barrier (BBB) [Lead: IISPV (ES), participant: UNISANTE (CH)]

The objective of this case study is to evaluate the neurotoxicokinetic for multiple priority chemicals like PFAS groups, bisphenols and organophosphate pesticides by conducting *in vitro* studies for data-deficient chemicals and developing PBK models considering BBB transport. The first year was dedicated by IISPV to conduct literature search for finding the relevant data to be used in developing a brain specific PBPK model and identify data gaps. To fill data gaps, *in vitro* study was conducted with Human BBB cell lines (HCMEC/D3) for multiple chemicals like PFOS, PFOA, chlorpyrifos, permethrin and cyfluthrin. Experiments were performed to evaluate cell viability, passive diffusion and active transport at three different concentrations (high, medium and low) for each chemical. Quantitative analysis was performed using LC-MS technique.

Data was analyzed considering permeability equations with the application to use it further for PBK modeling.

Parallely, IISPV has also been working on the feasibility of extending the existing PBPK model to include mechanistic BBB and brain-specific compartments. Permeability-limited equations have been included in the existing PBPK model for BBB and brain-specific compartments.

The validation of the toxicokinetics in multiple brain-sub compartments for different chemicals and the evaluation of the models has been done for PFAS chemicals.

This case study is also collaborating with other brain disorders related projects in WP5 and WP6 to showcase the application of more advanced PBPK models. A successful application of this *in vitro-in silico* pipeline shows the feasibility of reducing the usage of animal studies and developing a harmonized approach for integrating BBB *in vitro* data in PBK models.

Case study 06: *Alternaria* toxins [Lead: UNIVIE (AT), participants: ETHZ (CH), IISPV (ES), NVI (NO), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)]

The objective of this CS is to establish a PBK model for selected *Alternaria* toxins based on *in vitro* assessments of intestinal absorption and hepatic metabolism. This model will be used to predict tissue concentrations at relevant exposure doses to facilitate QIVIVE. Alternariol (AOH) was previously selected as the first compound for a PBK model as it is the most data rich compound among the targets.

To fill the data gap regarding the kinetics of the phase II hepatic metabolism of AOH, UNIVIE conducted *in vitro* glucuronidation studies of this compound with both rat and human liver S9 fractions. Extreme delivery problems of the commercial cofactor kit from the only supplier in year 2 and reoccurring problems with the available UHPLC-MS/MS instrument at UNIVIE in year 3, delayed the provision of experimental data. However, in year 3 the *in vitro* experimental data in rat liver S9 fraction were finalized, and the corresponding kinetic constants were calculated. In addition, preliminary tests were performed on human liver S9 fraction, for which the acquired samples need to be measured and finalized. Therefore, the delay in the *in vitro* data collection hampered the modeling of ETHZ, which indicates the need to extend this CS for Y4.

Case study 07: Enniatins [Lead: ANSES (FR), participants: NVI (NO), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)]

The aim of this CS is to fill in data gaps, to build and test the predictive ability of PBK models in animals before extrapolation in human for these emerging mycotoxins (Enns A, A1, B, B1) that could be of help to reach a RA according to EFSA. After a late start in 2023 due to the need to synthesize toxins for the experiments and to set up protocols (analytical, *in vitro*, etc.), the following progresses were made in 2024 (This CS07 will continue in 2025, on Y4):

- EnnB
 - Validated quantitative LC-HRMS method for ENNB in different matrices. Analysis of samples from *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies at ANSES. HRMS method for accelerated detection of ENNB metabolites (NVI).
 - Non-linear mixed effect modeling of IV/oral cross over plasma TK experiment on Sprague Dawley rats for EnnB with the simultaneous determination of clearance, volume of distribution, oral bioavailability and absorption rate as a result. QIVIVE of *in vitro* clearance on EnnB determined on rat and human hepatocytes (ANSES).
 - Intestinal S9 incubation (pilot and clearance (triplicates) for human and rat to obtain *in vitro* intestinal clearance data – only successful for human, rat showed hardly any metabolism in the pilot study and was therefore not included in the clearance study (WR).
- EnnB1
 - LC-HRMS analytical method (plasma, medium, buffer) development and validation for rapid equilibrium dialysis to determine binding of EnnB1 to inactivated hepatocytes and plasma of rat and human. *In vitro* clearance on EnnB1 determined on rat and human hepatocytes. Authorisation of ethical committee for animal experiment for IV/oral cross over plasma TK experiment on Sprague Dawley rats for EnnB1 with long delays due to stricter regulatory rules on housing catheterised rats (ANSES).
 - Hosting PhD student from ANSES. Validated quantitative LC-HRMS method for ENNB1 in different matrices. Analysis of samples from *in vitro* studies at ANSES. HRMS method for accelerated detection of ENNB1 metabolites (NVI).
 - Liver S9 incubations (pilot and clearance (triplicates)) for human, rat and pig to obtain *in vitro* hepatic clearance data – succeeded for all species. Intestinal S9 incubation (pilot and clearance (triplicates) for human and rat to obtain *in vitro* intestinal clearance data – only successful for human, rat showed hardly any metabolism in the pilot study and was therefore not included in the clearance study (WR).
- EnnA1
 - Liver S9 incubations (pilot and clearance (in triplo) for human and rat to obtain *in vitro* hepatic clearance data – succeeded for both species (WR).
- Enn B, B1, A, A1
 - Four enniatins (A, A1, B and B1) an LCMS-method were already available at the institute and used for the quantification of the substrate depletion in the *in vitro* clearance studies (WU-TOX). All obtained *in vitro* clearance data can be incorporated in the PBK-models that will be developed (WR).
 - Rapid equilibrium dialysis (RED) methods were developed for all four enniatins (A, A1, B, B1) together with an extraction and analytical method to determine concentrations in protein and serum-supplemented cell culture medium. Results indicate that the non-specific binding of the chemicals and the apparent time-dependent loss of the chemicals in the RED make this method for the determination of plasma protein binding (PPB) unreliable. It is suggested to test for the PPB of enniatins using alternative approaches, like solid phase microextraction (SPME) and/or ultracentrifugation (WU-Tox).

Case study 09: PBK model for metabolic disruption [UDE (DE), Fraunhofer (DE)]

During 2024, this action has been transferred from UIBK (AT) to UDE (DE). The lab led by Kathrin Thedieck now forms part of the newly founded Research Center One Health Ruhr (RCOHR) of the Ruhr Alliance (<https://www.uaruhr.de/researchallianceruhr/onehealthruhr.html.de>). The RCOHR mission is closely linked to the PARC aims. The RCOHR aims to understand human health in the context of the environment. Specifically the RCOHR links the interdisciplinary foci of (1) environmental research, (2) oncology and (3) neuroscience. The PhD has been focusing on translating the assays from UIBK to the new facility at the UDE. Specifically, the re-establishment of the HepG2 and HepaRG cell culture systems and cytotoxicity assays for MD response screening. Due to the transfer, the progress is delayed and the work will need to be continued after year 4.

Meetings:

- Monthly meetings, update of case studies [all partners].
- PARC WP5 Annual meeting (27-29 May 2024, Lisbon, Portugal)
 - o Accelerating the identification of enniatins and related metabolites [NVI (NO) - poster]
 - o Development of a Tiered Testing and Assessment Strategy to Address the Absorption Rate of Inhalable Compounds using CaCo-2, Calu3 and PAMPA assays for three model compounds Propranolol, Sumatriptan, and Hippuric acid [Fraunhofer (DE), AUTH (EL), INERIS (FR) - poster].
 - o Optimization and evaluation of gut microbial metabolism testing for use in PBK modeling [ETHZ (CH) - poster]
 - o Advancing New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for RA with Open-sourced Harmonized physiologically based Kinetic (PBK) models (cross cutting activities of WP5, 6, 7 and 8) [IISPV (ES) - poster]

Conferences:

- EuroTox2024 (08-11 September 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark):
 - o Refining toxicokinetic models for enterohepatic recirculation of toxins undergoing hepatic glucuronidation [ETHZ (CH) - poster]
 - o Developing an open-source harmonized PBK Model for 4 PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, and PFHxS) to assess the toxicological profile of forever chemicals [IISPV (ES), WR (NL) - poster]

Deliverables and publications

- Stevanoska M, et al. Physiologically based kinetic (PBK) modeling as a new approach methodology (NAM) for predicting systemic levels of gut microbial metabolites. Toxicology Letters. Submitted in January 2024, published in April 2024, 396:94-112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2024.04.013>

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D5.3	1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	M26	
AD5.7	Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms	UL-LACDR, SCIENS ANO	M12 (postponed M18)	M22	The delay is a consequence of the "workshop on systems toxicology: data requirement and strategy" being moved from December to January. This workshop was essential for gathering information and executing the AD. Its purpose was to discuss relevant datasets and case studies. Based on the requirements of three identified case studies, there was an additional search need in the public domain for relevant omics datasets

1.2.6 Work package 6. Innovation in RA

During the reporting period, a joint WP6 workshop with WP and task leaders, partners, and relevant stakeholders was organized at Karolinska Institute, Stockholm, Sweden on April 22-24, 2024 (M24). Besides project updates, guided discussions on how to meet the regulatory challenges and to identify opportunities for increased collaboration advancing regulatory science, was an important part of the workshop. Dedicated discussions on specific topics of joint interest across the WP included promoting the regulatory use of NAMs and how such methods can be practically implemented in regulatory decision-making processes, structured evaluation and weight-of-evidence (WoE) approaches and enhancing transparency in assessing human relevance and data integration, and regulatory needs related to the RA of chemical mixtures, including the need to consider socio-economic and health impacts of exposure. The Coordination team as well as other PARC WPs were represented at the workshop [KEMI (SE), RIVM (NL), KI (SE), all WP6 partners].

Prior to the workshop, an online meeting was organised where the respective views on research needs and priorities were presented by DG Sante, DG ENV, JRC, EFSA, and ECHA.

1.2.6.1 Task 6.1. Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

The projects described below are aimed at the development of IATAs for three different health effects, *i.e.* genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity. In conjunction, in a fourth project, a workflow for the assessment of human relevance is being developed. Each of the four projects

in T6.1 covers work related to A6.1.1, A6.1.2, and A6.1.3. Therefore, the achievements of all four projects are summarized under each of the activities within T6.1. Many project team members participated in the WP6 workshop held in Stockholm (SE) in April 2024 (M24). This allowed for detailed discussions on progress made, next steps as well as relevant linkages to other projects and tasks within PARC, including common themes such as weight of evidence analysis or endocrine disruption.

➤ A6.1.1: Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

• **P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM [M1 - M36]**

The project, led by RIVM (NL) and AUTH (EL), aims to establish a workflow for the assessment of human relevance of both AOPs and NAMs related to the key events or key event relationships of the pathway under study. A project team was established at the beginning of the project (M1). During the reporting period, all project partners participated in recurring (at least once a month, often more frequently) online meetings that were organized during the reporting period by RIVM and AUTH [partners involved: AUTH (EL); RIVM (NL); ENSP (PT); BPI (EL); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); IISPV (ES); LIST (LU)].

The previously established case study teams have successfully completed application of the biological considerations of the workflow to each of the case studies: AOP#162 [partners involved: RIVM, AUTH, ENSP, STAMI, ISS, LIST, NIPH], and AOP#54 [partners involved: AUTH, RIVM, BPI, WU-TOX, IISPV, IRSN]. Following application, the biological considerations were discussed and evaluated in detail through multiple online meetings, both per case study team and in a plenary setting. This foundational work has resulted in a refined definition of the biological considerations and improved templates.

During the period, we advanced this work by focusing on the empirical considerations for the workflow. Building on the completed biological assessment, the project team conducted thorough evaluations of the empirical evidence, further refining the workflow. The empirical considerations involved close collaboration with the case study teams and led to improvements in how empirical data are integrated into the workflow. Once both the biological and empirical aspects were finalized, the team moved forward with initiating comprehensive WoE assessments. This phase, now in progress, is focused on combining the biological and empirical evidence into a structured, transparent WoE evaluation. The approach for this assessment has been carefully shaped by expert consultations and workshops, ensuring that it meets both scientific and regulatory standards [partners involved: AUTH (EL); RIVM (NL); ENSP (PT); BPI (EL); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); IISPV (ES); LIST (LU)]. Throughout the reporting period, stakeholder engagement remained a priority. Dedicated meetings between the project managers and representatives of ECHA and EFSA were held on a regular basis. Furthermore, a webinar was held on April 11, 2024, to update stakeholders on the project's progress and to collect feedback. In the WP6 workshop (April 22-24, Stockholm), a half-day session was dedicated to principles and best practices with regard to WoE, covering not only IATAs but also human relevance. These interactions have been vital for gathering feedback and ensuring that our approach remains aligned with broader community expectations. The outcomes of the work conducted in the project, including the biological and empirical assessments and the ongoing WoE evaluation, are being compiled into a manuscript (in preparation). This document will comprehensively detail the workflow, the case study results and the methodologies applied, providing valuable insights for future human relevance assessments.

Next steps involve finalizing the WoE assessments, reviewing the outcomes for consistency and completing/submitting the manuscript. The team will continue stakeholder engagement and explore workflow automation with WP7 to improve efficiency. In a follow-up project, additional case studies may be conducted to further test and refine the workflow, ensuring its robustness across different contexts. This phase may also expand the workflow's application to new AOPs and NAMs, while maintaining alignment with regulatory needs and scientific advancements.

Meetings

Recurring meetings were held at least every month with all project partners. Where appropriate, additional and/or longer meetings were held, to allow for dedicated discussions on the case studies, e.g. in breakout groups. Starting in summer 2024, a core team of five persons has held additional meetings about every month, to prepare for a scientific manuscript on the work done. The draft manuscript has been shared with the project team and will be discussed with all members late 2024. Furthermore, the progress made as well as next steps were discussed in periodic meetings with representatives from ECHA and from EFSA.

- **P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen [M1 - M36]**

The project, led by UAntwerpen (BE) and UKHSA (UK), aims to develop IATAs for identifying EDCs both in a human and environmental health context. All partners participated in online meetings every four months to discuss the general strategy within the project. These meetings were organized during the reporting period by UAntwerpen and UKHSA [partners involved: UAntwerpen (BE); UKHSA (UK); MU (CZ); AUTH (EL); UGent (BE); INSERM (FR); UL-LACDR (NL); RIVM (NL); ISS (IT); DTU (DK); SDU (DK); LIST (LU); BPI (EL); UG-PL (PL); IISPV (ES); STAMI (NO); KI (SE); IRFM (IT); ENSP (PT); SCIENSANO (BE); CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), UU-IRAS (NL), collaborating organisation: JRC (EU)].

The work was performed in two subgroups focusing on two areas for the development of AOP network-based approaches to incorporating NAMs in ED assessment. The two subgroups are 1) Thyroid hormone system disruption [core partners involved: UAntwerpen (BE); UKHSA (UK); MU (CZ); AUTH (EL); RIVM (NL); ISS (IT); SDU (DK); LIST (LU); UG-PL (PL); IRFM (IT); collaborating organisation: JRC (EU)] and 2) anti-androgenicity [core partners involved: KI (SE); UKHSA (UK), MU (CZ); INSERM (FR); DTU (DK); BPI (EL); IRFM (IT); CEFAS-DEFRA (UK); UAntwerpen (BE)]. The work in the subgroups is organized through two monthly meetings.

The two subgroups followed the same strategy in their specific ED area. As a basis for developing ED assessment strategies, an overview of all relevant AOPs, describing both human and environmental health effects, were organized in AOP networks that were evaluated (for example, in terms of taxonomic domain of applicability) and continuously updated. Key mechanisms and effects were identified from the AOP networks and organized in conceptual models. Relevant methods were identified and mapped to the AOP networks and the conceptual models.

The subgroups are preparing one manuscript each, that will provide an in-depth overview of the available methods linked to the mechanisms and effects described in the AOP networks, and a reflection on potential regulatory applications. Many of the methods for anti-androgenic effects are published Test Guidelines having readiness level A+. For the thyroid-related methods readiness assessment is primarily driven by the activities of the OECD Thyroid Disruption Method Expert Group (TDM EG). In collaboration with P6.3.2.h on hazard classes for ED and P6.1.1.a on human relevance, a third manuscript has been developed that provides a comprehensive inventory of all available test methods relevant to THSD, i.e., including methods that do not

directly map to the AOP network for THSD. Methods are categorized according to the levels of the OECD ED Conceptual Framework, with an assessment of the validation status of each method. In total the inventory counts 120 methods comprising established methods (e.g., OECD Test Guidelines) as well as citable methods including those that are under further development and in some cases are ready for validation or in the initial stages of validation. With this effort, we respond to an international need for a comprehensive reference list of methods that can be used for the evaluation of THSD.

Each of the different activities in the project are considering relevant information from related international efforts such as the work performed in the EURION cluster, at the OECD and the JRC. The project outcomes will be applicable to the REACH and CLP legislations as well as the Plant Protection Products Regulation (PPPR) and the Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR), by providing a framework for using *in silico*, *in vitro* and fish test data for THSDC identification. For REACH, regulatory uptake is anticipated in the upcoming REACH revision where data requirements can be updated, and consequently in the implementation of the new hazard classes in the CLP regulation. For example, in the medium term, new endpoints for THSD that are under validation for addition to fish Test Guidelines such as TG210 may be included in an update of the REACH requirements, which would result in the availability of data on the T-modality for the environment, also for CLP. As a longer-term perspective, the project contributes to the use of NAMs in regulatory testing. A series of specific case studies will be developed and executed in a follow-up project starting in PARC Y4 in collaboration with ECHA, EFSA and other stakeholders, generating new data and re-using existing data for chemicals that are relevant in the context of specific legislations.

- **P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano [M1 – M48], the project has been extended from M36 to M48**

The project, led by SCIENSANO (BE) and INRAE (FR), aims to develop an IATA for genetic toxicity, one of the health effects prioritized in the EU CSS [partners involved: BPI, EFSA, IBMT, INRAE, IRFM, IRSN, ISS, KWR, LIST, MUI, RIVM, NILU, NIPH, SCIENSANO, STAMI, UG-PL, UL-LACDR, VUB, WR, WU-TOX]. For this endpoint, various non-animal tools are available or under development, and some of them have been used for regulatory purposes for some time now. A draft AOP network was developed based on AOPs present in the AOP-Wiki or in literature and an inventory of non-animal methods for genotoxicity was compiled. During the reporting period, the partners continued their work in the three subgroups:

- Development of AOP networks [partners involved: SCIENSANO, NIPH, INRAE, STAMI, IBMT, UG-PL, VUB, ISS, IRSN, WR, LIST, NILU, RIVM]: the key events (KEs) and KE relationships (KERs) in the AOP, linking “Formation, bulky DNA adducts” to “Increase, Mutations” were selected for further characterization. As there is currently no strict guidance on how the information to characterize KE(R)s should be collected, especially in data-rich domains, a systematic search strategy to document KERs within the AOP network was first developed and now tested on the AOP for bulky DNA adduct formation. The lessons learned during this process will now be applied for the characterization of other KE(R)s in the AOP network.
- Development of quantitative AOPs (qAOPs) [partners involved: SCIENSANO, INRAE, KWR, UG-PL, VUB, UL-LACDR]: the AOP linking “Alkylation, DNA” to “Increase, Mutations” and “Increase, Structural chromosome aberrations”, containing KEs and KERs that are already well characterized, was selected for further quantitative development. To this extent, each KE of this AOP has been linked to an *in vitro* assay that can provide quantitative information on that specific event. Next, existing data on 2 known alkylating agents collected with the different assays were compiled through a large-scale systematic

literature search. Quantitative data from at least twenty studies have been extracted from the literature and compiled into a database together with data provided by internal and external (HESI-GTTC) partners. The preliminary analysis of these data is currently being done and demonstrates promising results, but the modelling is still ongoing. In addition, DNA adductomics experiments to collect information on the level of DNA alkylation after EMS exposure are being performed.

- Uncertainty analysis related to NAMs for genotoxicity [partners involved: MUI, SCIENSANO, INRAE, NIPH, IBMT, KWR, BPI, ISS, IRFM, NILU, RIVM, VUB, UG-PL]: a case study was initiated to collect more insights into the uncertainty associated with in vitro and in vivo genotoxicity tests, with an initial focus on the in vivo micronucleus test. All data 'relevant' or 'according' to the OECD TG 474 from the EFSA Pesticides Genotoxicity Database were extracted and a pilot study was performed with 13 active substances to assess the variability and uncertainty in the available in vivo micronucleus data. In addition, data available in the QSAR toolbox for these compounds were collected and evaluated as well.

In order to facilitate collaboration with other international scientists and supported by the positive advice of the OECD ESCA (June 2023), a Standard Project Submission Form (SPSF) on the AOP network for genotoxicity was prepared, and after revision, approved by the OECD for inclusion in the OECD work plan. Finally, discussions with regulators (EFSA, ECHA and JRC) have started to formulate the regulatory problems that need to be addressed with our IATA.

Meetings

- Recurring meetings (initially every month; since April 2024 reduced frequency as most work is done in the subgroups) with all project partners and open to representatives of regulatory agencies (BPI, EFSA, IBMT, INRAE, IRFM, IRSN, ISS, KWR, LIST, MUI, RIVM, NILU, NIPH, SCIENSANO, STAMI, UG-PL, UL-LACDR, VUB, WR, WU-TOX).
- Recurring meetings of the three subgroups i.e. a) development of AOP networks (partners involved: SCIENSANO, NIPH, INRAE, STAMI, IBMT, UG-PL, VUB, ISS, IRSN, WR, LIST, NILU, RIVM); b) development of quantitative AOPs (qAOPs) [partners involved: SCIENSANO, INRAE, KWR, UG-PL, VUB, UL-LACDR]; and c) uncertainty analysis related to NAMs for genotoxicity [partners involved: MUI, SCIENSANO, INRAE, NIPH, IBMT, KWR, BPI, ISS, IRFM, NILU, RIVM, VUB, UG-PL].
- Presentation and discussion of the draft AOP network for permanent DNA damage during the BO 'New approaches for the characterisation of genotoxic effects based on in vitro and in silico data' at the BfR International symposium 'RA of Genotoxic Compounds – Challenges and Future Perspectives' (Berlin, Germany, February 2024, SCIENSANO & INRAE), the HESI-GTTC meeting 2024 (Washington DC, US, 14-16 April 2024, SCIENSANO), the ESCA meeting 2024 (online, 27th of June 2024, SCIENSANO), the OECD genotoxicity expert group meeting (online, 5th of September 2024, INRAE) and the SKIG meeting (online, 18th of September, SCIENSANO).

Conferences

- PARC SYNnet session during the EEMGS 2024 meeting (Rovinj, Croatia, 23-26 September 2024). Sciensano (1 oral presentation) and UL-LACDR (1 oral presentation).
 - Demuyneck E, Thienpont A, Van Goethem F, Rogiers V, Vanhaecke T, Winkelman LMT, Olsen AK, Svendsen C, Arnesdotter E, Gutleb AC, Stępnik M, Wyrzykowska E, Adam-Guillermin C, Bossa C, Marcon F, Wik L, Soop GL, Mollerup S, Narui S, Nikolopoulou D, Hatzi VI, Machera K, Huliganga E, Mufara K, Yauk C, Audebert M

and Mertens B. Development of an AOP-based IATA for Genotoxicity: Building an AOP network for genotoxic events leading to permanent DNA damage. Oral presentation by E. Demuynck at the EEMGS 2024 meeting.

- Winkelman LMT, Demuynck E, Stepnik M, Thienpont A, Majid S, Audebert M, Mertens B, and Beltman JB. Meta-analysis for quantifying a genotoxicity AOP linking DNA alkylation to increase in mutations and chromosomal aberrations. Oral presentation by L. Winkelman at the EEMGS 2024 meeting.
- EMGS 2024 meeting (Palm Springs, US, 7-11 September 2024). Organisation of a session entitled 'Towards the development of a global genotoxicity AOP network' (INRAE, SCIENSANO) including one oral presentation (Sciensano).
- Mertens B, Demuynck E and Audebert M. Towards a global AOP network for permanent DNA damage Invited lecture by B. Mertens during EMGS meeting 2024. EUROTOX 2024 meeting (Copenhagen, Denmark, 7-11 September 2024). NILU - 1 oral presentation in a CEC course on a topic entitled "AOP development, the AOP wiki & the way to OECD endorsement".

- **P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR [M1 – M48], the project has been extended from M36 to M48**

The project, led by UL-LACDR (NL), is aimed at the development of an IATA for liver toxicity [partners involved: UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), AUTH (EL), MU (CZ), IISPV (ES), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), WR (NL)].

In earlier reporting years it had been decided to focus on liver toxicity, and liver fibrosis specifically to complement similar activities (external to PARC) that are mainly focused on liver cholestasis. AOPs related to this process within the AOP-Wiki were combined into an AOP network, and an initial case study was set up focusing on the initial key events. To this purpose, as a first step four liver cell test systems and three test chemicals had been selected to study the relevance of these cell systems for liver fibrosis.

In the current reporting period, the liver cell test systems were exposed to a wide concentration range of the 3 chemicals [partners involved: UL-LACDR (NL), INSERM (FR), MU (CZ), STAMI (NO), and RISK-HUNT3R partner KU-Leuven]. We established this range on the basis of pharmacokinetic models to calculate expectations from in vivo data (from the TG-GATES database), in collaboration with the Horizon 2020 project RISK-HUNT3R [partners involved: WU-TOX (NL), ISS (IT) and RISK-HUNT3R partner Certara]. The exposures for the different cell systems were done both in 2D and 3D spheroid set-ups, and evaluation was done at the time point 24h post exposure as this was expected to be sufficient for the first KE to take place (depending on metabolic activity within the various cell types). At this time point, we measured both cytotoxicity and created samples to measure the transcriptome. The samples were sent for TempoSeq sequencing to measure RNA expression. Initial analysis on the resulting sequencing data has been performed, showing substantial differences between the cell systems (and in 2D/3D) in baseline conditions and with respect to their responses to the selected chemicals. This analysis is currently ongoing and results will be used to determine the next case study to be executed. To also detect later key events in the future, NAMs with mixed cell systems are being developed [partner involved: STAMI (NO)]. Moreover, a collaboration with the FDA is being established in order to utilize their organ-on-a-chip system Emulate, which can employ up to 4 cell types (hepatocytes, Kupffer cells, endothelial cells and hepatic stellate cells).

Besides these experimental efforts, partners worked on refinement of the AOP network [partners involved: INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), MU (CZ), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), WR (NL)]. Specifically, focus has been on the role of the Aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AHR). Moreover, text mining approaches were developed and applied to find genes involved in fibrosis, with which existing AOPs can be refined. Finally, qAOP development was continued in collaboration with RISK-HUNT3R [partner involved: UL-LACDR (NL)]. To this purpose, first a general framework for qAOP development was established on the basis of dynamical mathematical models (ordinary differential equations). Second, existing in vivo data were analyzed in detail in order to map gene expression to specific key events on the basis of 'modules' established with co-regulated gene network analysis. Newly acquired NAM data will be compared to in vivo activity of these modules, which can only be done for the initial key event with the data generated in our first case study. Future data focusing on late key events, acquired in the next case study, will be included later.

Meetings

Recurring meetings were held every month with all project partners. Besides the partners, at least one representative from RISK-HUNT3R was usually present. Similarly, RISK-HUNT3R case study meetings were frequently attended by partner UL-LACDR. Recently, a representative from EFSA started joining our meetings, and a representative from ECHA will also start attending in the near future.

Disseminations

Poster presentation at EUROTOX 2024 (Copenhagen, 8-11 Sept 2024): Graciela López-Soop, Lina Wik, Shan Zienolddiny-Narui, Steen Mollerup. New Approach Methodologies for hepatotoxicity hazard assessment: development of an in vitro human liver fibrosis model (presenter: Graciela López-Soop).

Manuscript submitted to Computational Toxicology: Di Tillio F & Beltman JB. Developing Quantitative Adverse Outcome Pathways: An Ordinary Differential Equation-Based Computational Framework.

➤ A6.1.2: Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

The IATAs listed in A6.1.1 are being developed through various cycles of optimisation; (interim) evaluations are foreseen to be conducted through case studies. For the first round of case studies, criteria for suitable substances were developed and candidate substances have been identified. The actual design of the IATA case studies has been completed and case studies have been initiated. For the workflow for assessment of human relevance two case studies (one likely to be human relevant; one less likely to be human relevant) were selected in close collaboration with ECHA and EFSA (see also under A6.1.1); these will be completed in Y3. During the life of each of the T6.1 projects, results achieved and challenges encountered are discussed with stakeholders at regular intervals.

➤ A6.1.3: Stakeholder engagement

The work done in Task 6.1 is closely related to regulatory RA. Therefore, active involvement of regulatory partners is crucial to ensure that the outcomes will meet regulatory needs. In each project periodic meetings have been held between the project managers and representatives of ECHA, EFSA, and/or JRC. Dependent on the topic discussed, these meetings were either joint or separate for each of the agencies involved. Additionally, each of T6.1 project was presented in

a set of two dedicated half-day webinars preceding the WP6 workshop organized on 22-24 April 2024 (M24) in Stockholm. As a result, EFSA, ECHA, and JRC continued to actively contribute to the different T6.1 projects. Collaborations with other stakeholders were established during the reporting period, including OECD (especially in relation to the project on IATA for endocrine disruption and genotoxicity), the Health and Environmental Sciences Institute (HESI; project on IATA for genotoxicity) and ILMERAC (International Liaison group on Methods for RA of Chemicals in food; project on for human relevance). All the work done in A6.1.3 was (and will be) performed in close collaboration with WPs 2 and 3.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD6.1	Report on draft IATAs for selected endpoints (ED, genotoxicity and STOT) and recommendations/strategies for future IATA development for more complex endpoints.	UL-LACDR	M24 (postponed M32)		This AD replaces the AD6.2 initially planned Y1 and which was replaced by the milestone MS15 at M12 Proposal to merge AD6.1 with AD6.9 with a due date M32 accepted by the WP6 co-leaders in August 2024.

1.2.6.2 Task 6.2. Integrative exposure and RA

Leader: ANSES (FR), VITO (BE)

Participants: AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CSTB (FR), DTU FOOD (DK), EFSA (IT), EHESP (FR), ENSP (PT), FINBA (ES), TTL (FI), FMUL (PT), FOPH (CH), Fraunhofer (DE), GGeoSZ (SI), ICPS (IT), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), KI (SE), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), IUSS (IT), IVL (SE), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), ONIRIS (FR), RIVM (NL), SRU (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SECO (CH), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAVR (PT), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UG-PL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WR (NL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

T6.2 on integrative RA aims to support regulatory RA by providing methods, tools and concepts for integrative exposure, RA and HIA. Sixty institutes from twenty Member States join forces to improve risk models to account for chemical mixtures and the diversity of sources and routes. Four additional deliverables from the task T6.2 were published on the PARC website ([Deliverables page | Parc \(eu-parc.eu\)](#)). In year 3, we continued to work on the approaches, methods and tools developed in these additional deliverables and on their application to case studies. Results obtained during the year 3 and strengthened during the beginning of year 4 will be presented in four deliverables by month 36.

PARC news items describing the content and regulatory relevance of the four Task 6.2 deliverables were released in October 2023. The news items were reposted extensively on LinkedIn and other social media. In addition, output of the deliverables were communicated through several lecturers at national and international conferences.

In 2024, at the Member States levels, associated news items were released and lectures were provided. The deliverables and news items are being discussed in various regulatory environments such as the Standing Committee on Plant Animal Health, Food and Feed of DG SANTE and DG SANTE Committee on Industrial and Environmental Contaminants” and the CARACAL working group from DG GROW/DG SANTE, May 2024 a webinar was held for these working groups of the European Commission as well as for the PARC GB members. The webinar was well-attended by more than 100 regulators from 22 Member States.

Task 6.2 started to perform RA of mixtures on the basis of HBM data and projects to understand the sources and routes of exposure. The methods and data are in compliance with the EU Transparency Regulation and EFSA and OECD guidance on scientific grouping of chemicals into assessment groups. The model for RA is the MCRA model, which is validated against EFSA methods. Initial discussions with JRC on use of T6.2 mixture RA outcome for the developed on their CSS mixtures indicator for human health were held, in order to achieve the uptake of our scientific work in policy indicators. The outcome of burden of disease and health impact work done under Task 6.2 is shared with EEA and discussed with ECHA. In view of regulatory uptake of Task 6.2 work on aggregate exposure and PBPK models, initial contacts were held with the ExpoAdvance project, supporting EFSA’s roadmap for aggregate exposure.

T6.2 contributed to the strategic discussion of ECHA (KARC). Task 6.2 project leaders and task leaders had intensive contacts in year 3 with EFSA on how to work together on the EFSA Roadmap ExpoAdvance (strategic agenda until 2030 of EFSA).

Synergies between T6.2 projects across different activities under T6.2 was deployed. Hereto, a physical meeting in Brussels (2 April 2024) with participations of 40 experts (case study leaders and project leaders in T6.2) was organized. We discussed common studied endpoints, chemicals, harmonization, and use of tools (e.g., PBPK models), across cases studies. Further arrangements for practical collaboration across case studies from T6.2 projects were made.

T6.2 contributed to the discussion on the PARC future activities.

- [A6.2.1 Aggregated exposure assessment from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers](#)

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

This activity includes two projects.

- **P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO [M1 - M42], the project has been extended from M36 to M42**

Inventories have been made of realistic source-to-dose models for the general population to assess (i) direct exposure to chemicals released from consumer products and materials to the indoor environment, and (ii) direct and indirect exposure via release and transfer from the environment. Gaps (models and data), priority chemicals, products, and environmental sources for the project were defined. First steps were taken to generate a mechanistic understanding of source-to-dose exposure and to translate this into a conceptual model (including selection of models or model parts in view of research or regulatory questions to address in case studies).

Case studies were started. The case studies will be organized by around the chemicals and by type of environment (indoor and outdoor). Case studies for the outdoor environment (PFAS and at least metals) involve 1) case studies in hotspots in participating countries (hotspots, being complementary to general population background exposure for metals and PFAS covered in P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES), and 2) transfer-specific aspects for general population exposure (e.g. transfer from soil to crops and subsequent dietary exposure). Case studies for the indoor environment focus on model parameterization and validation for, phthalates and other plasticizers. The inventory of existing data to parametrise the conceptual model, in view of case studies, was initiated. One meeting for each environment (indoor/outdoor) was organized every two months. A joint physical meeting with P6.2.1b was organized in Luxembourg. This project participated to the development of the strategy, the model and data inventories, and selection of case studies presented in deliverable AD6.3 (M14) on the roadmap on aggregate exposure strategy through different sources and routes related to general and occupational environments [ANSES (FR), IVV (DE), CSTB (FR), IVL (SW), FOPH (CH)].

In year 3, within the case studies (see further) we elaborated further concepts and data for one or several aspects of the source to dose exposure chain in the outdoor and indoor environment. In the working group outdoor environment, we continued executing case studies started in Y2, i.e. exposure to Cadmium arising from fertilizer (source to dose) [ANSES], metal hotspot in Slovenia [ARSO, NIJZ, GeoZS]; PFAS hotspot in Flanders [VITO]; in year 3 the metals hotspot case study was extended with a case study in Belgium near an industrial site [VITO], and the PFAS hotspot case study was extended with several sites in the Walloon part of Belgium [ISSeP]. Additionally, we started new case studies focusing on a specific part of the source to dose chain, i.e., 1) exposure to lead from soils (using isotope Pb signature [ISSeP] and 2) the role of aerial deposition of PFAS on the environment and subsequent human exposure [VITO]. In year 3, we have set up collaboration with 6.2.2; i.e., PBPK models developed under 6.2.2 were applied in selected case studies under 6.2.1a (metals and PFAS).

The indoor group of this project worked in year 3 on several case studies, i.e. 1), exposure to lead via premise plumbing [KWR] 2) assessing the contribution of sources to indoor pollution, including the evaluation of indoor source to dose models for SVOCs (mainly plasticizers) with field study data [CSTB, LNS, IVL], and 3) a case study on suitability of the DustEx model to assess exposure to SVOCs in products that are released into the indoor environment, including indoor air, indoor surfaces and indoor dust [RIVM]. The indoor group elaborated a systematic review of plasticizer sources and concentrations in the European indoor environments [CSTB, LNS, RIVM, Unisante] which will be submitted for publication in Science of the Total Environment. This data inventory from this review will provide a base for future exposure assessments for the general population (see project 6.2.1b).

Conceptual framework and application in the PFAS hotspots case study was presented at the ISES Europe Workshop March 2024 in Berlin. Case study on sources of exposure to metals in

contaminated region in Slovenia is presented at the 2nd national Public Health Conference in Slovenia (October 2024). Case study on lead exposure arising from soils was published in Science of the Total Environment <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174763>) Manuscripts of other case studies are in the draft phase.

Overarching 6.2.1a project meetings were organized every 2 months with the entire project team, and ad hoc small project meetings within working groups and case studies took place in year 3.

Project lead: VITO (BE), LNS (LU)

contributors: CSTB (FR), ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH), IVL (SE), FOPH (CH) FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), ISSeP (BE), OVAM (BE), RIVM (NL), KWR (NL), NIJZ (SI), GeoZS (SI), ARSO (SI), UOB (UK)

- **P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES [M1 - M48]**

In this project, we started with an inventory of occupational and general life models to estimate aggregate exposure from various sources and routes of exposure as well as an inventory of available data. From the model inventory, we scored all the models and selected the relevant ones to be connected into the PARCToolBox to perform aggregate exposure for the prioritized case studies (PFAS, metals, pyrethroids and phthalates/plasticizers). During the year 3, with the help of T8.3, we developed a functional design to connect the selected models and started their implementation in the PARCToolBox (MCRA).

During the year 3, we continue to develop and to apply the strategy to aggregate exposure following the three points: 1/ a decision tree to decide on the need to aggregate sources and routes 2/ a population-based and a worker-based approach to aggregate exposure from general and occupational environments 3/ a procedure to link exposure model output in integrating variability and uncertainty. Partners with common interest were organised in working groups around case studies. For each case study, a deeper investigation of the available data and models was conducted. The relevant data and models were selected to be used in the different case studies. When needed a bibliographical research (ex: JEMS, monitoring data in sources, etc.) has been started to construct dedicated database (ex: PFAS and Cadmium in consumer products). The application of the proposed strategy started year 2 for the different case studies supported by specific developments such as the adaptation of occupational models to be linked with general life ones has continued during year 3 with the integration of more sources and routes. Sub-working group meetings were held online every two months for: WG Pyrethroids occupational environment, WG Metals Cd in consumer products, WG Metals Cd general environment, WG Metals occupational environment, WG PFAS general environment, WG PFAS occupational environment, WG PFAS consumer products, WG Plasticisers occupational environment, WG decision tree. For WG Model selection and description, 2 meetings were yield. For WG functional design, several meetings with fewer people were yield to organize the integration of models in the PARC toolbox. In addition, 8 information sessions to 6.2.1.b partners on exposure models for both general and occupational populations were yield. This project participated to the development of the strategy, the model and data inventories, the development of aggregation method and selection of case studies presented in the deliverable AD6.3, M14 on the roadmap on aggregate exposure strategy through different sources and routes related to general and occupational environments.

Project lead: ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH) Case study/method WG lead: ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH), WUR-BIOM (NL), TNO (NL), TTL (FI), IVL (SE), ISCI (ES), FOPH(CH) Contributors: CSTB (FR), INRS (FR), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), ENSP-UNL (PT), FMUL (PT), VITO (BE), ISSeP (BE), OVAM (BE), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), TNO (NL), SRU (NL), WR-

BIOM (NL), KWR (NL), MU/RECETOX (CZ), NIOM (PL), NIJZ (SI), GeoZS (SI), ARSO (SI), BPI (EL), AUTH (EL), UOB (UK), NIPH (NO), TTL (FI), EFSA (EU)..

➤ A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

• **P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS [M1 - M48]**

This project consists of the refinement and development of PBPK models for human RA and mixtures RA (in collaboration with activity 6.2.3). The aim is to provide PBPK models that address the sensitivity of different population sub-groups, the aggregation of multiple exposure routes, and the interpretation of HBM data and the mixtures of chemicals. Several prioritized chemical families are studied: PFAS, pesticides, metals, bisphenols and mycotoxins.

The first step was to inventory the human PBPK models available that were published or developed by partners since the review done in the HBM4EU project in 2019. For all chemical families, at least one new model was identified. The main characteristics of the models were gathered in a database (e.g., populations, the exposure and elimination routes, the organs included, and the language code). Each new model was described using the roadmap established in the HBM4EU project. This work is available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/10025624>, and will be updated throughout the project in creating new versions. This work is reported in the deliverable AD6.4 (M14) on the inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life.

The year 3 aims to expand for these compounds the parametrization of the PBPK models for identified gaps and needs for human lifelong exposure including sensitive populations: (i) description in physiology changes in the various developmental stages (article submitted in September), (ii) integration of gender-specific differences in physiology through life (article submitted in September), (iii) starting to describe the *in utero* exposure and the placental transfer process based on the physicochemical properties of the various compounds as well as the transfer across the blood-brain barrier, (iv) development and refinement PBPK models for priority compounds (e.g., PFAS), (v) harmonization and incorporation of aggregate exposure in PBPK models (articles in progress), and (vi) implementation of models in the integrative ParcToolBox in collaboration with T8.3 (in collaboration with T8.3 and WP7, a workshop was organized (7-8 October) for T6.2 partners on the implementation of FAIR PBK models in Systems Biology Markup Language (SBML) using Antimony). Connections with WP7 on ontology (IISPV) of PBPK models and accounting for uncertainty and variability (RECETOX) were established.

Several project working groups gathering a few partners were defined: one for each family (all partners involved), and one on the parametrization of physiology and anatomy and their dynamic evolution through life. One whole meeting was organized every 3 months, and one meeting on physiological parameters and one for each chemical group was done every 2 months.

[Partners involved: INERIS (FR), AUTH (EL), IISPV (ES), ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), SLU (SE), NIPH (NO), VITO (BE), WR-BIOM (NL), WR (NL), IRFM (IT), IVL (SE), TNO (NL), ONIRIS (FR), IUSS (IT), KWR (NL), UniSanté (CH)]

➤ A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and RA

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM [M1 - M48]**

We started to develop a strategy to perform RA for mixtures observed in real-life. The proposed strategy to perform mixture RA is based on applying HBM data, knowledge developed for mixtures in regulatory RA and in the field of toxicology, exposome and epidemiology (Section 2). This strategy is organised around three steps: 1) Prioritisation of mixtures, 2) Collection and organisation of HBM and hazard data (including toxicokinetic information), and 3) Mixture RA for prioritised mixtures and effects.

From PARC priorities and discussions with EU Agencies and Commission five case studies were started:

- pesticides causing brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition (CAG-NAN);
- pesticides causing functional alterations of the motor division (CAG-NAM);
- PFAS and immune effect;
- heavy metals and kidney effects;
- heavy metals and DNT (IQ loss);

HBM data from European studies have been listed in a data inventory. A process of harmonising and uploading in MCRA the data from these partner studies has been initiated under a data controller – data processor (DC_PC) agreement to comply with the GDPR regulation. Several HBM data sets from 10 Member States were harmonized in templates. HBM study owners used the same coding. During the year 3, the data were uploaded to the MCRA software enabling HBM study owners and cases study leaders to progress on case studies results in a harmonized manner. Hazard data such as internal (HBM-GV) or external (HBGV) reference values, external and internal toxicological points such No Observable Adverse Effect Level (NOAELs), relative potency factors etc. were collected, organized and uploaded in MCRA. From the PBK model inventory made in P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS, data gap was filled from literature review. Then a comparison of the model predictions obtained with generic vs. substance-specific models (acute and chronic exposure) was carried out to determine whether or not the generic model has similar performance than the specific-substance ones. Statistical analysis such as mixture identification, PBPK models, new risk metrics as well as adaptation to HBM data were implemented in MCRA in close collaborations with T8.3 to make it possible to apply the strategy in a harmonized way in each of the five case studies. During year 3, the strategy was applied to HBM dataset from 10 European Member States: 15 data sets for heavy metals and kidney effects, 15 data sets for heavy metals and DNT, 9 data sets for CAG NAM and CAG NAMS, 21 data sets for PFAS and immune effects. We also provided training to involved partners for the application in the cases studies and stakeholders. A training was held for the EFSA in March 2024 on the use of HBM data in the next generation mixture RA. This training was attended by 25 experts of EFSA. Other training was organized in close cooperation with PARC task 9.4. This focus of that training was on kinetic modelling. A first training was organized by MU. Experts from INERIS and RIVM contributed to the training by providing examples of kinetic models developed and/or applied in cases studies in task 6.2. A second training was held in October 2024 which focused on FAIR (Findable, Accessible and Interoperable) PBPK models⁹.

During the annual WP6 workshop (22-24 April 2024) risk managers were engaged, and progress are regularly discussed with DG SANTE, EFSA, ECHA, JRC with a focus on how risk managers can benefit from project outputs. During the workshop we discussed how to work with task 6.4 on

⁹ <https://www.eu-parc.eu/index.php/events/trainings/risk-assessment/workshop-implementation-fair-pbk-models-sbml-using-antimony?color=%23008475>

aggregated exposure and with WP4 representatives also working in task 6.2 how to align with PARC task 4.2.

Three project meetings were held. One in January, one in June and one in November. The meetings were attended by approximately 50-70 experts working on the project. Case study leaders showed their first results and explained how they harmonized the calculations methods. Project leaders explained the PARC review process and the need for synergies with the European Agencies. Furthermore, project leaders asked for carefully explaining the results in scientific articles being planned as part of the deliverable. This includes timely exchanges of draft publications with regulators and the EFSA. Furthermore, the project leaders and/or case study leaders started to engage EEA and ECHA throughout 2024. This resulted in planning follow-up actions on training and or links related to IPCHEM.

The project was disseminated to the PARC IB and to the PARC SF on 16 May 2024. Furthermore, the first project results were disseminated during the Eurotox 2024 conference held in Copenhagen¹⁰. EFSA and RIVM organised a dynamic session on integrative RA of real-life chemical mixtures using HBM data. The session showcased the models and tools developed by PARC to estimate risks from exposure to complex chemical mixtures. Four expert speakers from ANSES, BPI and WR shared insights on innovative strategies, case studies, and modelling approaches, as well as how we work together with European Agencies to enhance regulatory implementation. The four speakers represented the work of all experts from the institutes listed below.

Project lead : RIVM (NL), ANSES (FR) Case study and method WG lead : ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), BPI (GR), UGR (ES), VITO (BE) Contributors: Oniris/INRAE (FR), AUTH (GR), BPI (GR), DTU (DK), EHESP (FR), FINBA (ES) , IDAEA-CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), ISCIII (ES), LNS (BE), NIPH (NO), AU (DK), MU/RECTOX (CZ), RIVM (NL), SECO (CH), SLU, TNO (NL), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGR (ES), UNIVIE (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR-BIOM (NL), WR-WFSR (NL), EFSA, JSI (SI), INSERM (FR), STAMI (NO), ICPS (IT), UNIPD (IT), IRFM (IT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), EASP (ES).

➤ A6.2.4 Human HIA and risk indicators

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

In this task on EBD and HIA the project on case studies (P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_ UU-IRAS) functions currently as a central hub to which other projects (P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO; P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS; P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO) are linked (see Fig. 5). Starting from the case studies, data are gathered to perform EBD calculations, hurdles in the methodology are described and indicators are developed when finalizing the case studies.

¹⁰ <https://www.eu-parc.eu/news/tools-and-resources/parc-partners-lead-session-integrative-risk-assessment-chemical-mixtures>

Fig. 5: Links between the different projects in task 6.2.4 on EBD and HIA

This approach thus far (Y1-Y3), with the case studies being placed centrally and selected via a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) tool, led to several case studies being led by partners. During a physical 6.2.4 project meeting in Belgium (Antwerp 18-19 April 2024), results and approaches from several case studies were shared and discussed: discussions were also held regarding the balance between harmonization across case studies versus case study aspects (both in terms of methodology and data).

During year 3, some of selection criteria in the MCDA tool were modified to better adhere to the priorities within PARC; the renewed selection criteria involved: (i) EBD/HIA-estimation is prioritized (key selection criteria; this has been put forward explicitly as some proposals did not intend on providing any EBD/HIA-estimates), (ii) health costs and/or willingness to pay aspects are integrated, (iii) multiple health effects (if possible and/or relevant) instead of the classic one stressor – one health effect), and finally, (iv) case studies in which the PARC-prioritized health effects (endocrine disruption, neurotoxicity and immunotoxicity) are considered

It was decided in Y3 to have methodological case studies alongside the general case studies that focus on EBD/HIA-estimates for stressor – health outcome pair(s). The latter (stressor – outcome oriented) case studies will still be selected using the MCDA tool, whereas the former, newer case studies (focusing on methodological improvement) are selected by an expert panel using specific – a priori agreed upon – selection criteria that are expected to contribute the most the improvement of EBD/HIA-methodology.

- **P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO [M1 - M66]**

A concise inventory was made of the EBD and HIAs conducted for PARC priority chemicals and mixtures, based on expertise available among partners and a literature search. Available external and internal exposure data and exposure-effect functions were collected as well and an overview of availability, quality and accessibility of European and national health data registries was made. Starting from the case studies, exposure data, health data, exposure-response data were searched for. Additionally, it is tried to look for data on Socio-Economic Status (SES) to stratify results of the EBD assessments by SES. SES is a main influencer of health inequalities and reducing these inequalities is the first flagship under the Zero Pollution Ambition. Project lead: VITO/UU-IRAS Contributors: ANSES; AUTH; BPI; DTU; ENSP; FMUL; IISPV; INSA; ISSeP; IVL; KI; MU; NIJZ; NIPH; NLZOH; OI; RIVM; SRU; Sciansano; STAMI; UBA; USI; WR-BIOM.

- **P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS [M1 - M66]**

This project generated an inventory of methodologies and frameworks (including a glossary of definitions) for HIA and EBD calculations and associated uncertainties, which will form the basis for identification and planning of methodological improvements to be addressed in PARC 6.2.4. A manuscript on methodological challenges to address the EBD of chemicals was finalized in year 3. Project lead: UU-IRAS/UBA Contributors: ANSES; AUTH; BPI; DTU; ENSP; FMUL; IISPV; INSA; ISSeP; IVL; KI; MU; NIJZ; NIPH; NLZOH; OI; RIVM; SRU; Sciensano; STAMI; USI; VITO; WR-BIOM

- **P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS [M1 - M42]**

This project started with definition of a framework to complete the first activities of the project and the development by ANSES of a MCDA tool, The proposed set of criteria for prioritisation of case studies to start in year 2, were discussed with stakeholders, followed by a proof of concept in which the criteria were applied and a long list of case studies was proposed. Project lead: ANSES/VITO Contributors: ANSES, BPI, ENSP, DTU, FMUL, IISPV, IVL, KI, NIJZ, OI RIVM, SRU, Sciensano, STAMI,

Following case studies were initiated in year 1 or 2, and further elaborated or finalized in year 3:

- Pyrethroid exposure and association with ADHD (leading partner VITO; contributors: ANSES, BPI, DTU, IISPV, SRU, Sciensano). Accepted for publication in Environmental Health.
- EBD of a mixture of heavy metals on cancer and cardiovascular related mortality in adults living close to waste incinerators (leading partner FMUL; contributors: OI, IRAS, VITO)
- EBD of arsenic exposure and cancers (lung, bladder & skin) (leading partner Sciensano; contributors: ANSES, DTU, ENSP, VITO). Finalized in September 2024. Submission peer reviewed publication is foreseen in 2025.
- HIA of lead exposure and cardiovascular diseases and chronic kidney disease (leading partner DTU; contributors: ANSES, KI, IVL, STAMI, RIVM; Sciensano, VITO) Finalization for end of 2024 including publication in peer reviewed scientific literature.
- Influence of waste co-incineration in a cement plant on cancer burden (leading partner OI; contributors: FMUL, NIJZ)
- Lead (Pb) and methylmercury (meHg) and IQ loss in Children in Europe (Leading partner ANSES; contributors: ENSP, DTU, Sciensano, VITO)

New case studies will probably be initiated in Q4 of year 3 (after selection according to MCDA or expert panel):

- exposure to glyphosate and possible influence on diabetes
- EBD and probabilistic modeling
- Multi-metal-exposure and chronic kidney disease

Current discussions (Q3-Q4 in year 3) are ongoing on how to streamline all the different methodological approaches for performing an EBD/HIA, i.e., which method (comparative RA, ...) is best suited for which situation, which data are required for this method to be used, etc. This overarching methodological guidance will build further on the already existing working paper on methodological improvement referred to above and should allow partners to make a well-founded decision on which method to use, as well as support the ongoing efforts of making a built-in EBD/HIA-platform into the MCRA tool (in collaboration with T8.3).

- **P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO [M1 - M42]**

An inventory of existing types of risk and health impact indicators based on expertise available among partners, literature search, communication materials of (inter)national organizations, and stakeholder input (JRC and EEA for indicators related to the CSS and Farm to Fork Strategy) was made in Y1. Together with the case study prioritization, this was the basis for proposal for indicator development from year 2 onwards. Input was given to indicators developed by EEA for BPA and pesticides. Further, the case studies will form the basis to develop indicators in order to help translating science into policy and assist policymakers. Project lead: VITO/UU-IRAS Contributors: case study leaders ANSES, FMUL, Sciensano, DTU, OI, VITO.

Overarching project meetings were organized with all partners every 2 months, and each case study had a meeting roughly every 4/6 weeks.

A technical report 'data, methods, and indicators linked to EBD case studies for chemicals prioritized in PARC WP 6' was finalized and sent to T6.2 co leads (i.e. 30/04/2024).

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.6.3 Task 6.3. Review of RA methodologies

Leader: SU (SE), BPI (EL)

Participants: UCL (UK), INSA (PT), EAA (AT), EAWAG (CH), TTL (FI), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), INRAE (FR), IRFM (IT), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), LSMU (LT), REGIONH (DK), DTU (DK), UCPH (DK), RSU (LV), SCIENSANO (BE), STAMI (NO), NILU (NO), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), ULUND (SE), VUB (BE), UNIBAS (CH), KEMI (SE), SU (SE), UMIL (IT), UNIPD (IT), EFSA (EU), UT (EE).

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

The reviews of existing regulatory assessment systems performed in Task 6.3 are included in three projects organized under two activities.

Task project meetings were organized in M24 [SU (SE), BPI (EL), KEMI (SE), UCL (UK), INSA (PT), EAA (AT), EAWAG (CH), TTL (FI), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), LSMU (LT), MUI (AT), REGIONH (DK), DTU (DK), RSU (LV), SCIENSANO (BE), STAMI (NO), NILU (NO), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), ULUND (SE), VUB (BE), UNIBAS (CH)]. The focus of the meetings was to present and discuss the progress of the case studies under the respective projects, including regulatory context and relevance as well as stakeholder interactions. Representatives from ECHA, EFSA, EEA, and JRC were invited to the meetings for dissemination of results and to discuss regulatory relevance.

Case study-specific meetings for planning and progress updates have been organized by the case study leaders throughout the reporting period when needed.

➤ A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviews

Under activity A6.3.1, two projects have been pursued during the period: Case studies reviewing substance-specific RA depending on intended use (P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU; project leaders SU (SE) and UCL (UK)) and Case studies reviewing effect-specific RA (P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI; project leaders BPI (EL) and KEMI (SE)).

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP)

• **P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU [M1-M48]**

Three reviews (case studies) of substance-specific assessments depending on intended use have been pursued during the period. The case studies have been designed to evaluate and understand differences and similarities, and subsequent implications, across legislations. [SU (SE), UCL (UK), SCIENSANO (BE), IRFM (IT), KI (SE)].

CS12_MethodOSOA_SU [M1-M42], the CS has been extended from M36 to M42: We finalized a study that aimed to map out the scope of substances subject to assessment in multiple legal frameworks. The study also illustrated the importance of coordination and communication in the chemical assessment processes. In this study, we identified substances registered or authorised for the EU market and analysed their presence in different legal frameworks. Our findings showed that almost one-tenth of the substances identified were listed under more than one framework. However, there was a notable lack of coherent chemical identifiers available to accurately identify substances across the frameworks. The paper has been reviewed by WP2.1 and will be submitted for publication shortly. [SU (SE)].

CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL [M1-M36], the CS has been extended from M24 to M36: The 417 plastic additives identified by ECHA's plastic additives initiative, their respective function(s) and the type of polymer(s) they are associated with have been mapped against corresponding legislations contained in ECHA's EUCLEF. Collectively, a total of 37 pieces of legislation apply to these substances. The relevant associated regulatory annexes (lists of chemicals) have been downloaded and information related to classification CLP and status under REACH has been collated for each substance. This analysis discovered that EUCLEF only covers substances listed in annexes of specific pieces of legislation and that group of substances listed because a hazard classification, use or other common characteristics will be missed by interrogating EUCLEF. In order to complete our analysis of the collated data to discover patterns related to polymer type, specific function of the additive, hazard classification and regulatory coverage, we are currently first completing our dataset manually by analyzing all 70 pieces of legislation in EUCLEF. The data extraction from these individual pieces of legislation using the piloted template to collate information on RA, e.g., testing requirements, use and availability of modelling tools, weight-of-evidence approaches, and derivation of safety thresholds for each of the relevant pieces of legislation is advancing in parallel. This will be used to identify commonalities and differences in approaches to risk across at least 37 legislation and will inform OSOA. During year 3, the project "State-of-the-art review on hazardous substances in plastics" (PlastChem), funded by the Norwegian Research Council, has published a database of 16,000 chemicals associated with plastic (<https://plastchem-project.org/>). This forms the basis of a critical analysis of the representativeness of the list of 417 additives from ECHA's Plastic Initiative as well as the exploration of the feasible application of *in silico* tools to predict migration of chemicals from

polymers to their environment or their potential toxicity. Drafting of peer-reviewed publications is underway and now expected to continue during year 3 and may be completed during year 4 of PARC. [UCL (UK), SCIENSANO (BE), IRFM (IT)].

CS14 *BiocidesRA_SU* [M1-M24]: In this case study, finalised M24, we have analysed inconsistencies in the regulation of chemicals, as well as existing and missing links between different pieces of chemicals legislation. The overall aim was to (1) understand the interconnections between various pieces of EU chemicals legislation and (2) identify inconsistencies in the EU chemicals legislation, to strengthen the protection of human health and the environment. The work focused on the inconsistency in the regulation of antimicrobial substances when used in cosmetics and in biocidal products and whether the inconsistency was addressed through REACH. The results showed that the fact that substances not registered under REACH remain on the list of approved cosmetic preservatives, despite discontinued use on the EU market, indicates that the list is not up to date with which substances are currently used. In addition, classification as hazardous to the aquatic environment under the CLP is not sufficient to trigger any risk management measures under REACH. Since the CLP relies on other regulations, such as REACH, for regulatory measures such as prohibitions, there is a risk that substances classified as hazardous to the aquatic environment are overlooked by REACH. Further, the implications of the hazard classification under CLP in other regulations were examined, separately focusing on the regulatory implications for substances classified according to the criteria of the new CLP hazard classes for endocrine disruption for human health (ED HH), endocrine disruption for the environment (ED ENV), persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic, and very persistent and very bioaccumulative (PBT/vPvB), and persistent, mobile and toxic, and very persistent and very mobile (PMT/vPvM). The results showed that there are no regulations that specifically impose regulatory obligations for substances classified according to the new CLP criteria. However, six of the 53 examined regulations contained obligations aimed at all classified substances, meaning that these obligations will automatically apply to substances classified according to the new hazard classes under the CLP. Eight of 53 examined regulations had obligations for substances with endocrine-disrupting and PBT/vPvB properties. Overall, our findings indicate that pieces of legislation that rely on the CLP hazard classification for risk management will require revision to introduce the new hazard classes. The work has resulted in three publications. [SU (SE), KI (SE)].

- **P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI [M1-M48]**

Six reviews (case studies) of effect-specific assessments have been pursued during the period, including sensitization and developmental neurotoxicity as well as use of non-animal methods for identification of endocrine disruption, genotoxicity, and carcinogenicity. [REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH), VUB (BE), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT), BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), EAA (AT), UT (EE)].

CS9 *SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH* [M6-M54]: A paper has been written and submitted to a peer-reviewed scientific journal and a report has been delivered based on the following previous work: A mapping of current practices under different regulations (CLP, REACH, Cosmetic Products and Detergents, Biocidal, PPP and toys) concerning skin sensitizers were made within four areas: the goal, responsibilities, methods to assess skin sensitization, and mode of regulation. A questionnaire study was performed among representatives from competent authorities/regulators, Researchers/ clinicians, NGOs, and Industry concerning skin sensitization current practices and potential need for improvements. In total 109 participants answered the questionnaires [REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), UNIBAS (CH), IRFM (IT), SU (SE)]. This work has also been presented at The European Society of Contact Dermatitis Congress. A systematic

review focusing on the risk factors for skin sensitization from human experimental data has been initiated. A registration of the review in the International prospective register of systematic reviews, Prospero (PROSPERO) has been accepted and a risk of bias tool has been created [REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), UNIBAS (CH), IRFM (IT), SU (SE)]. This review is currently in the second screening phase [first and second screener REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO)] and is expected to be finished for submission later this year or at the beginning of next year.

CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB [M8-M42], the CS has been extended from M32 to M42: An evaluation of regulatory RA approaches used for cosmetic ingredients with ED concerns and the use of NAMs has been performed. 'Ab initio' NGRA for systemic toxicity of Benzophenone-4 and Octocrylene, both UV-filters present in the ED priority list. The NGRA of Benzophenone-4 was completed and discussed on M29 at a SCCS methodology meeting. From this work, a list of recommendations was extracted for further application. The 'ab initio' NGRA for Octocrylene could not be finished because of problems with PBPK modelling, and further efforts will be directed towards this. Between M21 and M32, several presentations have been given in national and international congresses and workshops with respect to the use of NAMs and NGRA in RA of cosmetic ingredients. Furthermore, in the period M21-32 the legislative changes at the EU level were followed up. Changes occurred in the EU cosmetic legislation as a consequence of the new categories introduced in CLP and REACH. [VUB (BE), INRAE (FR)].

CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS [M1-M48]: In this period, we have finalized the review and comparison of regulatory practices for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity classification and assessment. In particular, the analysis has been extended to also include pharmaceuticals [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT)] and a specific class of substances, i.e., nanomaterials [ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)]. The most relevant gaps and research needs have been analyzed and discussed. Short and long-term goals towards the improvement of human health protection and animal welfare through NAMs implementation have been identified [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)]. Concerning regulatory acceptability of QSAR approaches for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity, the OECD QSAR Assessment Framework (QAF) has been identified as a suitable tool for evaluating the models and their predictions (<https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/qsar-assessmentframework.pdf>) [ISS]. An inventory of NAMs for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment has been compiled and will be constantly updated, including NAMs under development within PARC. The current version of the NAMs list has been included in a publication (submitted). Useful information is being collected to assess their suitability to fill existing gaps and comply with the current legislations [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)]. Concerning the scoping study on the application of QSAR models, a list of substances known as human carcinogens (i.e., CLP class 1 A) has been drafted [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT)]. Collection of relevant chemical identifiers as well as cleaning and refinement of the list are ongoing. The Excel table mapping the relevant documentation for the case study topics is constantly updated and will be made available in the interim and/or final project report (e.g., as supplementary material). [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)].

Dissemination activities: EEMGS2024, Rovigno 23-27 September 2024, poster "Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations towards the regulatory implementation of NAMs" (C Bossa, CL Battistelli, M Dusinska, MJ Silva, attending). Paper on regulatory state of the art and NAMs for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment, in preparation. Initial case study discussion with ECHA (M20-M21). In contact with JRC to discuss and share ideas on the common relevant topics.

CS15_DNT_SU [M1-M48], the CS has been extended from M36 to M48: The collection of in vivo DNT study reports has been finalized. We have now available a collection of 54 guideline DNT study reports concerning 53 substances, of which 51 are pesticide active substances and 2

are other substances. To our knowledge, no further guideline DNT study reports are accessible to us under current legislation. The study reports were obtained by us in very different shape, ranging from scanned paper copies from the 1990ies with poor readability to reports where data could be directly extracted and pasted into Excel. We have identified a set of tools for a reliable data extraction and verification, which will be part of a scientific publication. The extraction of raw data for motor activity, as well as metadata and ancillary data, is currently ongoing and will likely be finalized by the end of this year (M32). We have developed initial ideas and methods for graphical and statistical analysis. [SU (SE)].

CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI [M1-M48], the CS has been extended from M36 to M48: The purpose of this CS is to develop scientific criteria for harmonised evaluation of reliability and relevance of data on endocrine parameters from non-guideline *in vitro* studies or data derived by studies conducted with non-validated protocols for use in weight of evidence assessments. A systematic literature search was performed using the AOP-helpFinder tool (V2) on keywords linking Adversity with Experimental method/model/tool. After discussion with partners and JRC, prioritization was given to standard *in vitro* test methods used in line with the EFSA/ECHA guidance to cover the gaps for endocrine adversity. For this purpose, a complementary literature search was also performed using more specific keywords. Currently, we are finalizing the description of reliability and relevance criteria for the evaluation of non-guideline transactivation assays using as basis the SciRAP tool. JRC, EFSA and ECHA have contributed with comments and discussions on the approach. A draft manuscript is under preparation. [BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR)].

CS18_ED-classes_BPI [M1-M48], the CS has been extended from M36 to M48: The purpose of this CS is to contribute to the harmonized implementation of the new CLP criteria on hazard classes for endocrine disruption taking into consideration currently available methods and tools. A systematic literature search was performed using the AOP-helpFinder tool (V2) to identify available *in vitro* test methods and *in silico* models/tools relevant for the assessment of endocrine disrupting chemicals with regard to Estrogen, Androgen, Steroidogenesis, and Thyroid (EATS) modalities. Prioritization was given to the literature retrieved for the T-modality with focus to (i) assessing the human relevance of thyroid effects in adults and (ii) assessing potential DNT effects in sensitive population. For this purpose, a complementary literature search was also performed using more specific keywords. Mapping of test methods relevant to thyroid hormone system disruption for human health and environmental regulatory hazard assessment was also performed in collaboration with Task 6.1 project on IATA development. Mapping of relevant read-across approaches has also been initiated. JRC, EFSA and ECHA have contributed with comments and discussions on the approach. A draft manuscript is under preparation on how to use the identified methods and tools for the implementation of the new CLP criteria on endocrine disruption. [BPI (EL), INSERM (FR), EAA (AT), IRFM (IT), VUB (BE), UT (EE)].

➤ A6.3.2 Use of tools, criteria, and methods

Under the activity, one project has been pursued during the period: Case studies reviewing tools, criteria, and methods used in regulatory RA (P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU; project leaders SYKE (FI) and SU (SE)).

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU [M1-M48]**

Nine reviews (case studies) on the use of tools, criteria, and methods in regulatory RA have been pursued during the period, including general aspects such as application of risk-based benchmarks and uncertainty analysis as well as aspects related to occupational RA and ERA. One additional case study (CS20) was initiated in M25. [SYKE (FI), ISSeP (BE), SU (SE), STAMI (NO), UBA (DE), JSI (SI), UCL (UK), TTL (FI), KI (SE), RSU (LV), INERIS (FR), KEMI (SE), ULUND (SE), BPI (EL), LSMU (LT), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), DTU (DK), UCPH (DK), ISS (IT), UNIMI (IT), UNIPD (IT), EFSA (EU)].

CS1_CARB_SYKE [M1-M48], the CS has been extended from M36 to M48: In M21-32, the comparative analysis focused on the European current and pending regulatory thresholds issued for PFAS in water bodies (Priority Substances Directive 2008/105/EC), drinking water (Drinking Water Directive (EU) 2020/2184), and certain foodstuffs (Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/2388), and the tolerable weekly intake value set by the EFSA. The results were published in Environment International (10.1016/j.envint.2024.108614), and then presented in the ENSOr conference in Brussels (M23), T6.3 meeting (M24), the NH Meeting in Belgium (M24), in the 3rd PFAS Congress in Paris (M26) and in the International CleanUp conference in Australia (M29). Planning of the next phase of the study initiated. [SYKE (FI), ISSeP (BE)].

CS2_RiskReduction_SU [M1-M36], the CS has been extended from M24 to M36: This study has been delayed due to difficulties recruiting and due to people on sick leave. The planned end-date has thus shifted from M24 to M36. During the reporting period, we have initiated a discussion on the development of the research questions and study design. [SU (SE), UCL (UK), UBA (DE), STAMI (NO), JSI (SI)].

CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND [M1-M48], the CS has been extended from M36 to M48: The description of generic components of uncertainty analyses for common and relevant types of assessment has been initiated. Typical sources of uncertainty have been identified, collected, and considered in a list of examples with applications of uncertainty analysis using a framework based on EFSA's Guidance on Uncertainty Analysis. Similar frameworks representing panel-based assessments using output from quantitative analysis done by other organizations will be added later. Interviews with uncertainty experts on their understanding and views on what it means to quantify uncertainty have started and will continue. Collection of information on practical challenges through a questionnaire with follow-up interviews is ongoing. [ULUND (SE), KI (SE), BPI (EL), UBA (DE)].

CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU [M13-M30], the CS has been extended from M24 to M30: Status of chemical data gap filling approaches across EU regulations has been analyzed, focusing on *in silico* methods such as QSARs. Current approaches listed by regulators as well as an overview of data requirements of five different regulations: REACH (1908/2006), CLP (1272/2008), PPP (1107/2009), FCM (1935/2004), and BP (528/2012) have been described. The REACH regulation was used as a baseline. Furthermore, a comparison of predictions of different QSARs models was conducted for three selected parameters within the categories physicochemical properties (*Kow*), environmental fate (BCF), and ecotoxicity (EC50; both acute and chronic effects). The models for the simplest parameter, *Kow*, had the overall best performance, followed by those for BCF. The analysis will be made available in the final project report. [DTU (DK), UCPH (DK), KEMI (SE), SU (SE)].

CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG [M1-M81], the CS has been extended from M36 to M81: A review regarding aquatic and sediment RA has been initiated, including identification of substances and mapping of topics for the identification of similarities and differences, and areas requiring further analysis of several different effect values. The first comparative analysis done for the active

substance imidacloprid has been complemented by a similar analysis for deltamethrin. RAs under Water Framework Directive (WFD), biocidal products regulation, plant protection products regulation, veterinary pharmaceutical regulation and REACH have been performed on the risks to aquatic life. REACH has been added upon suggestion by T2.1. Findings: Although number of effect data can differ considerably between regulations, ensuring that the most sensitive ecotoxicity study is included in the data set can lead to similar effect values (PNEC, RAC, EQS). Differences can still occur due to different expert judgment being taken. New information (e.g., updated knowledge on aquatic toxicity or the identification of unacceptable risks under one regulation) does not automatically lead to a re-evaluation under another regulation. A new assessment of studies has no consequences for the approval of active substances until the assessment of the entire dossier has been completed. Product extensions exceed the legally limited authorisation period of 10 years until the active substance is re-evaluated. Deltamethrin has been authorised as a PPP for 21 years through renewals and as a biocide for 11 years. The analytical detection limit for deltamethrin as a PPP (LoQ = 50,000 pg/l, RAR/B5/2018) was too high to measure the threshold value in the environment, (1.7 -50 pg/l) although this is required by law (Regulation (EC) 1107/2009, Art. 4). In the BPR dossier, the LoQ = 3,000 pg/l (RAR 2011). The results have been presented at SETAC conferences. Paper preparation is under way. [Eawag (CH), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), UBA (DE)].

CS20_PESTNAM_ISS [M25-M48]: In M25-32, interactions were established within PARC (WP2, WP5 and WP6) and outside PARC, e.g., other projects (CHANGE, EFSA Project ADME4NGRA) in areas relevant to the project. Through two meetings within the Project Group (PG) and EFSA, as an external scientific advisory entity, as well as information exchange via written procedure, the work plan and methodology were refined: a definition of the term NAM was agreed for the scope of the study and as a basis for the mapping exercise within Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009 for the authorization of active substances used in PPPs, linked to specific case studies, which will be found during the search and data extraction of actual NAM implementation, within EFSA's; the results from the data extraction should be compared with the existing legislation and data/information requirements; the retrieved NAMs should be classified as information, to support data waiving or used to modify/refine the final RA. The extraction of available documents from relevant websites/platforms (EU COM pest database, EFSA, Open EFSA) was performed, presented and discussed within the PG, together with the prepared template for data extraction. The Project Managers disseminated the description and main aims of the Project in different initiatives with relevant stakeholders (e.g. EFSA; EURL_ECVAM). (ISS (IT), UNIMI (IT), UNIPD (IT), BPI (EL), EFSA (EU)).

CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS [M2-M48], the CS has been extended from M38 to M48: The main legislations considered under this study, i.e., chemical regulations REACH, PPP, and BPR, which already have a clear framework for secondary poisoning assessment, and the WFD, which also gives provisions for secondary poisoning, have been analyzed. Particular consideration has been made on the regular review for update of ECHA's chemical safety assessment and reporting tool (Chesar) and European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances (EUSES) under REACH.

An analysis of the main areas where harmonization is needed has been initiated, including identification of the consequences of the lack of harmonization. Identification of borderline cases e.g. which do not meet persistent (P), bioaccumulative (B) and toxic (T) or POP criteria, but that may still cause a risk because highly exceeding one of the P or B criteria has been initiated to help select substances for testing. The selection of chemicals has also been discussed with the CS7 to harmonize the substances analyzed. Imidacloprid would qualify as sufficiently

bioaccumulative for testing our hypothesis and a need for further development and data collection has been identified.

CS8_OccupReproDev_KI [M1-M48], the CS has been extended from M36 to M48: A review of the EU and selected member state occupational exposure limits for reproductive toxicants 1A or 1B has been completed. The review includes comparisons of substance coverage, exposure limit level and identified critical effects (when documentation is available). Furthermore, for EU-level Occupational Exposure Limits (OELs) and REACH registrant's Derived No-Effect Levels (DNELs) for workers' long-term inhalation exposure additional key decisions in the hazard assessments were mapped out, such as applied safety margins (assessment factors), overall conclusions and cited dose-descriptors on reproductive toxicity. Data shows that OELs for reproductive toxicants are equally variable as for other types of substance and reproductive toxicity is often not considered the critical effect. Analysis of EU level OELs and DNELs show that internal safety margins to reproductive toxicity are larger than the safety margin to the identified critical effect in 85% of cases with applicable data. However, this may also be an effect of data selection. These results were published scientifically ([10.1016/j.reprotox.2024.108649](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2024.108649)) Substance specific case-studies are ongoing for four groups of chemicals. [KI (SE), TTL (FI), STAMI (NO), LSMU (LT), RSU (LV)].

CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL [M1-M36]: A questionnaire study (online survey) focusing on the awareness and practical impact of limit values and other regulatory information at workplace level, as well as on the potential challenges and good practises, was carried out in four countries (FI, NO, LV, SI) M18-M24. The survey addressed occupational safety and health managers in the field of chemicals industry (NACE C20), metal industry (NACE C24; C25), and motor vehicle maintenance and repair (NACE G45.2), and labour inspectors working in the field of chemical safety. 323 full responses were received for the workplace survey and 84 for the inspector survey. Analysis of the survey data is well underway and is expected to be completed by M32. To deepen our understanding on the survey responses and to focus more on the use of limit values to support workplace chemical RA, interviews with employer and employee organisations representatives and company representatives of the three target industries, as well as with experienced labour inspectors, were initiated M24. The interviews were completed in FI and LV by M26 and are expected to be completed in NO and SI by M31. Analysis of the interview data, and combined analysis with the questionnaire data, is expected to be completed early 2025. Dissemination activities: [Weisel J.](#) Ongoing PARC activities and Finnish participation. Oral presentation, PARC national hub workshop, Tampere, 16.4.2024; [Santonen et al.](#) Targeted activities within PARC WP4 and WP6 focus on occupational health risks and their assessment. Poster presentation, PARC Consortium meeting, Tirol, 13.-16.5.2024. [TTL (FI), KI (SE), STAMI (NO), RSU (LV), JSI (SI)].

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

Due to delays related to e.g., further data collection needs, unexpected findings, unexpected obligations, parental or sick leave, one case study (CS10) planned to end M32 will continue until M42, five case studies (CS1, CS4, CS8, CS15 and CS16) planned to end M36 will continue until M48. The extension of CS15 also entails an extension of budget and content. No deviation in deliverables related to the projects are foreseen due to these extensions.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.6.4 Task 6.4. Transposing results to regulatory RA methodologies

Leader: AGES (AT), UNIBAS (CH)

Participants: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), OFB (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), MU (CZ), AU (DK), REGIONH-GR (DK), UT (EE), EFSA (EU), SYKE (FI), Tukes (FI), UBA (DE), UFZ (DE), RPTU¹¹ (DE), USO (DE), Fraunhofer (DE), UI (IS), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), LSMU (LT), VUA (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIVA (NO), NIOM (PL), IEP-NRI (PL), UG-PL (PL), INSA (PT), ENSP (PT), UC (PT), UAVR (PT), ISCIII (ES), UCLM (SI), UGOT¹² (SE), ULUND (SE), RISE (SE), KEMI (SE), SLU (SE), AGROSCOPE (CH), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), UNIBAS (CH), BUL (UK), UKCEH (UK), UOB (UK), BPI (EL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

➤ A6.4.1. Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures

Under this activity, three projects are ongoing: “Optimizing regulatory RA and management of chemical mixtures in Europe” (P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_RWTH_OPREMIX) and “Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory RAs through the use of monitoring data and NAMs” (P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ_MONAMMIX), Skin sensitization – effect of mixtures, current practices, and gaps (P6.4.1c.Y3_CS_ReghionH_SKINSEN MIX) has started in Y3.

Since P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_RWTH_OPREMIX and P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ_MONAMMIX will end with M40, a new project Options to assess and regulate mixtures (P6.4.1.d_Y4_RE-MIX_UBA_Eawag) has been developed and submitted for Y4.

The ongoing projects are the basis to fulfill the main objective of the activity which is to identify the regulatory applicable and workable methods to achieve an effective and systematic management of mixtures across regulatory areas in environment and human health. On an activity level, we had regular meetings between activity and project leaders but also with all partners (online and hybrid at annual WP6 workshop in Stockholm 2023). The purpose of those meetings was to discuss the progress of the projects and their impact on the activity. Additionally, a meeting with EFSA took place to discuss and organize KIC meeting on mixtures in environmental mixture RA, which will be held on the 20th January 2025.

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

¹¹ AMD-101057014-118: Professor Dr Ralf Schäfer, who was involved in the activities of WP6, especially in Task 6.4 (P6.4.4.c_Y1, P6.4.4.d_Y1 and P6.4.4.e_Y1), for the German affiliated entity University of Kaiserslautern-Landau - PARC acronym “RPTU”, left the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau and started working for the University of Duisburg-Essen in Germany - PARC acronym “UDE”, on 01/07/2024. The amendment is a hand over of all the PARC activities performed by Ralf Schäfer at the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau to the University of Duisburg-Essen as of 01/07/2024

¹² AMD-101057014-118: Professor Thomas Backhaus, who was the main scientific contact involved in the activities of PARC WP6 (P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot) for the Sweden affiliated entity University of Gothenburg - PARC acronym “UGot”, left the University of Gothenburg and started working for the RWTH Aachen University in Germany - PARC acronym “RWTH”, on 01/11/2023. Consequently, UGot withdrew from PARC on 01/11/2023 and RWTH entered in PARC as affiliated entity UBA on 01/11/2023.

- **P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_RWTH [M1-M40], the CS has been extended from M36 to M40**

This project aims to perform a systematic comparative evaluation of current mixture tools (and those that are currently under development or might be developed within PARC). The mixture tools will be compared regarding their practicability, effectiveness and efficiency, level of protection, feasibility, applications domain and data demands. In this process, their current and potential usefulness in regulatory assessment of mixtures will be considered. A policy brief on the “Regulatory and practical considerations on the implementation of a MAF in REACH” with respect to the environment was prepared by UBA and published in May 2024 (Treu et al. 2024, <https://rdcu.be/dlo8E>). In addition, UBA has been working on a document on the state of play, practical experiences, and an analysis of options to address unintentional environmental mixtures in the substance-oriented legislations (to be finalised end of 2024).

The overall aim of the case studies is to test different approaches to assess mixture in different regulatory areas but also to provide results of the usefulness (or lack thereof) of the MAF in other regulatory areas beyond REACH.

CS1: Mixture toxicity assessment of priority substances under the WFD (UGoT, SE/RTWH, DE) The EU Commission published its proposal for an amendment of the WFD in October 2022. Amongst others, the aim of the proposal is to “improve the monitoring of chemical mixtures to better assess combination effects and take account of seasonal variations in pollutant concentrations”. This case study suggests an implementation strategy for this aim, using neonicotinoid insecticides as a case study. We developed appropriate Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for 6 neonicotinoid insecticides (acetamiprid, clothianidin, imidacloprid, thiacloprid, thiamethoxam), all of which are identified as priority pollutants under the revision of the WFD. We estimated acute and chronic HC05 values and the resulting relative potency factors for the six neonicotinoids for acute and chronic toxicity, which is a specific application of the Concentration Addition principle. Finally, we used the exposure data published in the WATERBASE repository (made available by the European Environment Agency) to conduct an EU-wide aquatic RA for the 6 neonicotinoids and their mixtures. Two manuscripts will result from this work. The first one documents the acute and chronic HC05 values and the resulting relative potency factors, while the second one will document the outcome of the RA. The first manuscript has already been submitted to the PARC dissemination pipeline, the second one will be submitted by the end of 2024.

CS2: Establishing assessment groups for retrospective mixture RA under the EU WFD (EAWAG (CH), UBA (DE)). The assessment group approach will be extended to all WFD endpoints for a mixture risk prediction. It will be investigated if this approach will reduce the potential overestimation of the mixture risk to primary producers, invertebrates, vertebrates, sediment organisms, birds and mammals of prey as well as human health. The retrieval and preparation of relevant monitoring data and its preparation are completed. The concurrent information of substance classification into the assessment groups is ongoing. The basic algorithms to process the data for the expected outcome has been implemented. The extension to sediment is pending and will be finalized in Y3.

CS3: Benchmarking of different approaches to calculate MAF values for use in prospective environmental RAs (EAWAG, CH), UBA, DE). Different approaches to calculate MAF values have been compared based on existing monitoring data for surface waters and published ecotox. data and PNEC or EQS. The retrieval and preparation of monitoring datasets, concurrent predicted no effect concentration PNEC values and the computation of mixture risk indicators from the MAF family has been completed. First results and insights are currently prepared for a scientific

publication while further analyses are ongoing. Intermediate results have been presented for scientific exchange at the SETAC Europe 2024 meeting in Seville.

CS4: Data-driven sizing of a MAF – male reproductive health case study (BUL (UK), RWTH (DE), BPI (EL), NIOM (PL)). HBM Data have been used to estimate the personal HI and to derive 100 individual MAFs to identify the distribution of MAF in the study population. The results of this case study are currently drafted for a peer review publication. Since BUL only cover the sensitive endpoint sperm quality. BPI in cooperation with NIOM extended this case study in June 2023 with another sensitive reproductive health endpoints testosterone level. Testosterone levels since this is a central key event in AOPs with adverse outcomes indicative of anti-androgenicity. Currently the analysis of compounds to be included in mixture RA is performed. It includes data of human biological monitoring from partners taking part in the case study, but also from other HBM studies. Additionally, the point of departure (PODs)/ reference dose (RfDS) data is collected for different endpoints in male reproductive health based on this database will be created and updated.

CS5: Evaluation of the Applicability of MAF for human health RA regarding contaminants in food (AGES; AT). The primary aim of this case study is to evaluate the applicability of the MAF concept in human mixture RA of food contaminants and whether such an approach could replace the laborious, yet not very robust existing approaches. Therefore, MAF calculations will be applied on an already available data set of mixture RAs on specific food contaminants (Vejdovszky 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2019.110812>; Vejdovszky 2021 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2020.111861>). The available cumulative RAs of Vejdovszky et al. follow a deterministic approach regarding exposure estimations. In order to refine the RA in a first step, the exposure assessment was recalculated in a probabilistic manner using the MCRA Tool developed by Wageningen University and RIVM and the MAF was calculated using the newly generated data. However, it became apparent that a probabilistic calculation based purely on the exposure estimate only allows a deterministic calculation of the MAF. Therefore, it was decided to use a similar approach as the one used by BUL (in CS4) to estimate individual MAFs. However, the MCRA Tool cannot provide such calculations and hence a method is being developed using the computing software R, which should enable probabilistic calculations of an individual MAF.

CS6: Identification of potential mixtures of Food Additive (FA) and Food Flavourings (FF) and the estimation of a potential health risk by using two tools - the modified Reference Point Index (mRPI) and the MAF (AGES, AT). A potential mixture of FA and FF will be defined and assessed. Since neither FA nor FF have been assessed as a mixture, two tools will be tested of their suitability and will be compared to each other. In the case of food additives, 48 relevant food additives and food additive groups were selected because their exposure exceeded 50% of their corresponding acceptable daily intake (ADI) and they are used in relevant food categories. Currently the toxicological data of the chosen FAs is screened to identify a common toxicological endpoint. In the case of FF, we are currently in the prioritisation process to identify the FFs that are mainly used and contribute the most to the exposure. Since this Case Study is of EFSA's interest, the case study was discussed during the PARC- KIC exposure meeting in June 2023. An Expert of EFSA was assigned for further exchange.

LMSU, ESNP, UK-CEH, UI have not been assigned to a Case Study but participated in the project and activity meetings.

- **P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ [M1-M40], the CS has been extended from M36 to M40**

The use of NAMs i.e., bioanalytical methods for untargeted exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data, to deal with unknown mixtures will be compared with mixture RA methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information. Monitoring information based on non-target chemical and bioanalytical methods will be utilized to

define unknown mixture exposures. The outcome of the project will result in conclusions on gaps and main options for how to better make use of and further develop such approaches to support and improve the regulatory assessment and management of mixtures. Several case studies relating to this overarching goal have been undertaken and will be summarized and reported in the AD6.17 (Optimizing regulatory RA including the use of monitoring data and NAMs and management of chemical mixtures in Europe).

CS1: A European WWTP Effluent Reference Mixture for testing and assessment (UFZ, DE) has been finalized in the first 18 Months

CS2: Investigate mixture risk heterogeneity in European freshwater bodies on integrated data from monitoring and effect databases (UFZ, DE). The aim was to analyze the impact of data availability on mixture risk. Data on environmental concentrations measured during different monitoring campaigns and derived from the NORMAN EMPODAT database were collected and curated so that it is machine-readable and FAIR as prerequisite for our analyses. Based on the data on MoA of CS3, mixture risks are calculated based on the concentration addition assumption and compared i) to the number of measured and detected compounds ii) between sites within and across water bodies, and iii) to the risks driven by individual chemicals. Data analyses are finished and all results will be provided in a detailed report and will be reported in AD. 17. The results provide evidence on the question of how different the chemicals are that contribute to mixture risks in the European water bodies and give guidance for chemical regulation, individually and as mixtures

CS3: A curated mode-of-action database for a list of chemicals relevant for the aquatic environment (UFZ, DE). This study provides a curated FAIR data set with qualitative information on biological MoAs as well as quantitative information on toxicity for more than 3000 environmentally relevant chemicals. Since mixture RA, based on monitoring data, requires information for each mixture component, this information will facilitate risk assessors as well as scientists. Furthermore, the approach can be implemented into schemes for further expansion of the data set. This study is finished and published: Kramer et al. 2024 (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02904-7>). The FAIR dataset is published at ZENODO (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10071824>).

CS4: Application of the complementary Mixture Risk Indicator (MRI) to identify drivers of mixture risks (UBA, DE). The development of the data analysis has been completed in 2023. Currently, the retrieval and preparation of relevant monitoring data and its preparation is ongoing. Similarly, the compilation of PNEC values of all chemicals to compute mixture risk is also still ongoing. Both are in close collaboration with CS 2 and CS3. The final analysis and preparation of a scientific publication is expected to be finalized by the end of the 6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIX project

CS5: A review of forty years of pollution of the river Krupa with polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and their mixtures (Slovenia) (NLZOH, SI) have been conducted. The project aims to identify the gaps in the current national legislation and regulations at the EU level regarding the risks of substances with PBT properties and the potential to accumulate via the aquatic and terrestrial food chains. Monitoring data on water, sediment, and biota, as well as studies on the impact on stygofauna, freshwater, and sediment communities, were evaluated to illustrate the history and evolution of environmental monitoring and regulation. A study examining the expected ratios of individual congeners in natural samples 40-50 years after contamination was prepared. Contrary to our expectations, no consistent pattern in congener ratios could be observed or predicted in various matrices sampled down the stream or over time. Based on the measured data evaluated, the draft hypothesis is that after decades, the ratios between concentrations of persistent contaminants in mixtures become highly unpredictable. Therefore, it would be difficult to use measured environmental concentrations (MEC) in the modelling of environmental exposure and

consequently within the assessment of the risk of PCBs for the environment and humans. The strength of our study lies in the fact that the contamination occurred in a complex karst environment, and 40 years have passed since the first reliable measurements.

CS6: Using groundwater and drinking water monitoring data to identify potential new mixtures in drinking water by application of the JRC TIM-tools (AGES, AT). Selected data from (national) monitoring programs within a certain period of time (currently: last 10 years) and literature search results by applying the JRC Tool for Innovation Monitoring (TIM) was analysed to identify potential chemical mixtures. Groundwater monitoring data was extracted from the water database of the Austrian Federal Environment Agency. Out of 864 chemicals, 129 were chosen for further assessment. A network analysis with the software R was conducted and 14 mixture groups were identified. For now, mixture group 2 and 3, which have the highest number of substances were assessed. The mRPI - approach was used to assess the mixtures with the assumption that the observed concentration would also be found in the drinking water. In the mixture group 2, a risk on the sensitive endpoints as endocrine, hepatic and renal was identified. The risk drivers were substances such as ammonia, boron, phosphate and uranium. In mixture group 3 a risk on the sensitive endpoints as endocrine, renal and hematological with risk drivers as nitrate and pendimethalin were identified. The identified risk drivers are now verified with Austrian drinking water monitoring data. The outcome of the literature research by using the TIM Tool did not provide any relevant information. The case study is currently under finalisation and drafted as a report.

CS7: BioAI- to understand the long-term impact of chemical mixtures on biodiversity and ecosystem functions by leveraging lake sedimentary archives, paleoecotoxicology and AI-based forecasting (UB, UK).

Biodiversity loss, often driven by cumulative environmental threats over extended periods, is typically assessed using short-term observational data. This approach often fails to capture the long-term impacts. The BioAI case study seeks to transform our understanding of how chemical mixtures affect biodiversity over time. By utilizing lake sedimentary archives and AI-based forecasting, BioAI aims to uncover the drivers of biodiversity loss and to develop tools that assist regulators and policymakers in monitoring and protecting biodiversity. The tools developed by BioAI will help prioritize conservation actions and mitigate the impact of chemicals on ecosystems.

Since its inception in November 2023, the BioAI project has made significant progress, including:

- Biodiversity Data Collection: Community-level biodiversity data has been extracted from the sedimentary archives of 10 freshwater lakes in the UK, using a recently developed metabarcoding multiplex method at the University of Birmingham (UoB).
- Sediment Core Dating: The dating of all sediment cores has been successfully completed.
- Nutrient analysis: Comprehensive analysis of nutrients (nitrogen, carbon, and phosphorus) has been completed for all sediment samples. These data support our understanding of ecosystem functional changes
- Climate data acquisition: Climate data from local weather stations has been collected to support the project's analysis.
- Pesticide use data: National survey data on pesticide use has been obtained for further analysis.
- Chemical quantification: Ongoing collaboration with the Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ) and the University of Frankfurt is focused on quantifying pesticides and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) from the same sediment cores.

- **AI Tool Development:** The University of Birmingham is collaborating with the Institute for Data Science and AI to develop forecasting tools for biodiversity based on artificial intelligence.

The work conducted so far will be reported in AD6.17. However further work is needed for this case study to achieve its final goals and this work will be conducted in Part B of the Case study under the 6.4.1.d Y4_ ReMix project.

CS8: Investigation on NAMs application in European freshwaters monitoring based on monitoring and effect data (UB, UK) was launched in November 2023. It aims to showcase the Precision Environmental Health Next-Generation RA (PEH NGRA) applicability through case studies, improving the analysis of EU water impacts while identifying hazardous components in mixtures via omics-based bioactivity monitoring. Additionally, it seeks to propose concrete regulatory ecotoxicological tools that incorporate NGRA and other environmental data into solution-oriented water quality assessments.

Progress to date includes

- identifying a UK River Basin for field sampling (collaborated with the University of Bath)
- outlining primary research methodologies
- pinpointing relevant data sources from publicly accessible databases and publications
- coordinating meetings with partners to gather chemical and bio-monitoring data

A review of WFD implementation has been undertaken, with a particular focus on river basins and application in the UK context. This has highlighted two areas of concern for the WFD: the first being that the aims to prevent deterioration in status are not comprehensively being met; and second, that the current means of determining status are of poor representation, considering the comprehensiveness envisioned by the WFD.

The progress during the first year of the project will be reported in the AD6.17. Comparative analysis between component-based and whole-mixture approaches will be conducted in Part B of the case study in 6.4.1.d_Y4_ Remix- Project to provide insights into the capacities of PEH NGRA's, improving the understanding of the mixture effect and investigating the possibility of putting a threshold based on the mixture mode of action, rather than the effects of individual chemical components.

CS9: Mixture RA of marine Arctic pollutants: exposure assessment, chemical mixture characterisation and risk driver identification (NIVA, NO) was initiated in 2023. This case study focuses on the assessment of chemical mixture risks in the Arctic marine environment. By using exposure data and existing hazard information, the study aims to develop a Source-To-Outcome-Pathway (STOP) framework to link pollutant sources, exposure, and their biological effects on Arctic species in collaboration with developing data libraries (WP7) and integrative modeling (WP8.3).

CS9 project specifically addresses the heterogeneity of chemical mixtures in space and time, with a focus on identifying high-risk pollutants, mixtures, and relevant risk drivers for marine aquatic organisms in the Arctic.

During 2024 collecting and organising spatial and temporal exposure data for the Arctic from open literature and Norwegian Monitoring data as well as prioritization of stressors, locations, and species based on available exposure data and hazard assessments to define relevant exposure scenarios have been accomplished. A follow up of the case study to achieve its final goals are planned for 6.4.1.b_Y4_ReMix Project.

Besides the work on case studies, in 6.4.1.b. a review on chemical mixtures - challenges and needs with regard to the use of monitoring data and NAMs for RA and regulation has been finalized and can be found on the Sharepoint (Review). The case studies as well as the overarching work will be summarized and concluded in AD6.17 “Optimizing regulatory RA including the use of monitoring data and NAMs and management of chemical mixtures in Europe” which is due M40.

- **P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH [M25-M72]**

The project was initiated May 2024 since then two projects meeting (27.05.2024 and 29.08.2024) have been held, a third meeting is planned for the end of 2024. Representatives from ECHA have joined the project as observers.

An overview of current knowledge gaps and practices concerning mixtures are ongoing and will be finalized early 2025.

We have identified 9 allergens, with known relevance for consumers and/or the occupational setting and 3 irritants to be combined. An algorithm for random combining the substances are being developed at STAMI. The substances are being purchased, so that the same batch of chemical will be tested in the two test sites.

Pilot experiments with the in-vitro assay (OECD guideline 497, 2023) h-CLAT are currently being performed. For the remaining project year is it planned to hire a PhD student (enrolled at the University of Copenhagen. A Dose-finding experiment will be performed with the 9 allergens and 3 irritants. Doses for the main experiments will be chosen.

- A6.4.2. Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods

The 6.4.2 Project Leads (UNIBAS, NIPH/VKM, UT) have been continuously involved in coordination activities with internal and external PARC partners (e.g., set up of an international science advisory group in 6.4.2.b). Regular Project Lead meetings have been organized to foster synergies between projects, evaluate the need to join efforts, and improve the overall alignment and coherence of the work with regard to Activity aims and objectives. UNIBAS (acting 6.4 Task-Lead, Activity Lead, Project Lead, and Data Champion) has been in addition heavily involved in a number of transversal activities (incl. activities related to an environmental focus in PARC).

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapSurvey_UNIBAS [M1-M36]**

This project aims at facilitating the use and regulatory acceptance of NAMs in chemical RA. Our approach included a scoping exercise (all partners involved), and an expert consultation based on a sequential mixed method approach, comprising a rapid scientific and grey literature review, qualitative semi-structured interviews, and quantitative online survey with human and environmental risk assessors (partners involved: UB, EAA, ISS, INERIS, BPI, UBA). The outcome of the landscaping exercise identified the status quo of integration and use of NAMS and technological, structural and cultural barriers and drivers that hinder or facilitate the use of NAMs in the daily RA practice. The work will be published in 3 articles (one manuscript accepted <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.14296>, one submitted and another one in preparation). The submitted article focuses on *human health* risk assessors’ responses given in the qualitative and quantitative expert consultation and features authors from UNIBAS, RIVM, UB, ISS, UBA, INERIS and KEMI led by the first author from UNIBAS. The article, which is currently being prepared focuses on *environmental* risk assessors’ responses given in the qualitative and quantitative expert consultation and will feature authors from UKCEH, EAWAG and KEMI, in line with the inclusion activities regarding the environmental focus of P6.4.2.a started in 2023. The data analysis,

interpretation and preparation of the manuscript, as well as dissemination activities in the form of posters and presentations (e.g., at the Swiss National Hub Meeting, international conferences, such as the Society for Risk Analysis International and Society of Risk Analysis-Europe conferences) sparked a lot of interesting exchanges across institutions within and outside of PARC. These exchanges contributed to the gaps and needs analysis. The gaps and needs analysis were extended in 2023 and 2024 (core partners UB, EAA, ISS, INERIS). In 2024, the vignettes collected from different partners were taken and extended into descriptive examples, separated by chemical sector/legal framework (partners involved: EAA, UBA, INERIS). Additionally, in 2024, a workshop on Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity (DART) was organized (International Stakeholder Network, ISTNET-DART) and two publications based on this workshop are currently under development. Due to acute staff shortage due to illness (at UNIBAS), disruptions to the planned activities, specifically the development of vignettes and further expert consultation activities (focus groups), were experienced in 2024.

In early -2024, a major shift in management at UNIBAS has taken place, which will have implications for the topical focus. The activities in this project highlighted the need to focus further activities in specific areas of application in addition to the broad approach to the regulatory acceptance of NAMs and further work in the area will be continued in the project 6.4.2.f. Overall, the work in 2024 has benefitted from the continuous and substantial input of core partners UB, EAA, ISS, and INERIS, as well as from the ad hoc input of supporting partners BPI, UBA, UT; and more generally from a regular exchange with the other Project Leads (NIPH/VKM, UT).

- **P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRA_applied_in_practice_NIPH_VKM [M1-M81], the CS has been extended from M36 to M81**

A research team consisting of the core partners NIPH (VKM), ISS, BPI, and UNIBAS have been actively involved in all three sub-projects. The whole research team meets weekly (1 hour) and the “VKM-team” have monthly meetings with our scientific advisory group. The three ongoing sub-projects are all addressing the need for implementation of systematic review methodology in chemical RAs (e.g. as described in the WHO (2021) report “Framework for the use of systematic review in chemical RA”) across different regulations. The sub-projects are (i) Creation of a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro cell culture-based studies, called INVITES-IN (IN VITro Experimental Studies INternal validity), which is needed to include in vitro data as evidence in systematic reviews and chemical RAs, (ii) a terminology study aiming to translate core terms of chemical RA into the systematic review language, and (iii) creation of a tool for evaluation of external validity of in vitro studies.

(i) Creation of a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro cell culture-based studies: Study 1 and two of the creation of the tool have been performed. Study 3 is ongoing. Study 2 took more time than anticipated, because the number of items that should be included were much higher than expected. We are currently preparing the draft tool that will be taken forward to the user testing.

(ii) Translating core terms of chemical RA into the systematic review language: The protocol for the study has been published and the study is ongoing.

(iii) Creation of a tool for evaluation of external validity of in vitro studies: When we started drafting the protocol, it became obvious that the meaning of external validity for in vitro is unclear. Therefore, as a platform for the creation of the tool, we have started to prepare an expert commentary describing this field and what the project team and the advisory group agree that this concept means for in vitro studies. This work is almost completed. It includes a literature review to prepare an overview of related concepts, the terms used to describe these concepts, and the definitions of these terms. This was followed by a focus group study including three focus

groups that discussed the meaning of external validity for in vitro studies. We are currently preparing the expert commentary.

Publications accepted 2004

- Cross-mapping of terms used in chemical RA with those used in systematic review: research protocol (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2833373X.2024.2371285>

Publication submitted 2024

- A comprehensive item bank of internal validity issues of relevance to in vitro toxicology studies (2024) <https://zenodo.org/records/13362702>

Publication in preparation 2024

- Using a modified Delphi technique to identify concepts that are important for the assessment of internal validity of *in vitro* studies (*will be submitted in 2024*)

The project has been presented at a meeting with the GRADE working group in September 2024 and presented a poster at the Global Evidence Summit (2024)

• **P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT [M1-M36]**

This project consists of four overlapping parts. The core of the exploratory part included the survey “Landscape and readiness of computational NAMs based on ML and AI approaches for chemicals’ NGRA, which underwent final preparations and was conducted in 2024 (from February to mid-May 2024). Survey results are submitted as project report and analysis of results is currently in progress and is planned to finish by the end of the year 2024 ((involved partners: (core team) UT, INERIS, UNIBAS; (contributor team) ISS, KEMI, IRFM and UG-PL) and publish.

In the review part, we collected existing experience on ML and AI QSAR NAMs for hazard identification from scientific literature and public sources accomplish an in-depth analysis of the existing knowledge of data-driven AI/ML. The review is still ongoing and has reached the phase of preparation of manuscripts. The partners involved are UT, INERIS, ISS, IRFM, KEMI and UNIBAS. Based on the literature review a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using AI/ML models for regulatory purposes will be developed. The framework will be reported in the report “Framework to facilitate an adequate reporting for the AI/ML NAMs to be used for regulatory purposes” in M32.

In the analysis and case studies part of the project plan a review was conducted recently on environmental endpoint that is oriented to NAMs and machine learning and includes example of how to use and interpret machine learning (random forest) model predictions (Kotli *et al.* 2024. *Pesticide effect on earthworm lethality via interpretable machine learning. J. Haz. Mat.* 461:132577 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.132577> [involved partners: UT]). This article included a use case for random forest model and provided an example of the transparent use of the model predictions. A similar research study followed for human health endpoint (estrogen receptor activity): Piir, G. *et al.* 2024, *Interpretable machine learning for the identification of estrogen receptor agonists, antagonists, and binders, Chemosphere*, 347: 140671, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.140671>. Involved partners: UT (EE). In 2024 one conference poster presentation Sild, S., *et al.*, 2024, The evaluation of NAMs based on machine learning and artificial intelligence (ML & AI) approaches for hazard identification in chemical next generation RA. PARC CM2024 Poster Catalogue: PARC Consortium Meeting, 14-15. May 2024, Hall in Tirol, Austria, Organizing Committee, RP13., was given (Partners involved: UT, INERIS, ISS, IRFM, UNIBAS, VKM, UKCHE). Also, oral presentation at Estonian PARC National Hub meeting was given 29. May 2024 (involved partners: UT).

➤ A6.4.3. Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy

The activity has an overall objective to improve chemical RA and management by more efficient use of available information structures in combination with new analytical tools. A specific focus is placed on supporting enforcement of chemicals and product legislation and the use of chemical information structures in exposure assessment. Evaluation of product circularity and sustainability is also explored.

The mapping of activities within and outside of PARC has resulted in several contacts for enhanced collaboration across scientific disciplines and increased interactions between science and policy. Within PARC, collaborations have primarily been established with projects under A6.2.1. and T8.2 focusing on how information on chemicals in products can be used for aggregated exposure assessment and early warning systems respectively. Contacts with T4.2 have also been established to address the urgent need (RRM) for data on mono-n-hexyl phthalate, occurrence and potential sources. Contacts outside of PARC have focused on national authorities responsible for enforcement of chemicals legislation, the ECHA forum for enforcement and the group of five member states (SE, NO, GE, NE and DE) responsible for the broad proposal to restrict PFAS. Based on the gaps and needs identified under 6.4.3a, and through communication with above mentioned stakeholders and also in response to the urgent request from the GB (RRM) to address the enforcement of the PFAS restriction proposal submitted to the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), a new project focusing on analytical methods to support enforcement was initiated in 2024 (P6.4.3b_Y3_ENFORCE_KEMI). Biweekly meetings with representatives from MU, KEMI, RISE, TUKES and VU have been held regularly since the start of the activity (M1).

Overall, the specific results obtained under 6.4.3a and 6.4.3b, along with the improved interactions between stakeholders, contributes to a stronger and more predictable regulatory framework for chemicals in products and articles to increase the level of protection for human health and the environment and promote a level playing field for industry. All partners actively supported these activities.

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU [M1-M36]**

This project is evaluating the currently available information on substances in products and materials and how this information can be used for different purposes in enforcement activities and life cycle assessments. Landscaping exercises aligned along the following 3 aspects have been performed

Gaps and needs for enforcement: Results from surveys and interviews with enforcement agencies performed during Y2 have been interpreted and synthesized into a report (AD6.14) during 2024. The report identifies gaps and needs related to analysis of chemicals in products and overall enforcement structures. Some of the needs for analytical methods have been incorporated in the development of a new project P6.4.3.b_Y3_KEMI which is described below. Some of the needs related to use of data bases to inform RA and enforcement have been incorporated in the case study on Mono-n-hexyl phthalate described below. Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI, TUKES, VUA.

Use of information from chemical databases: The comprehensive inventory of chemical databases that was largely completed during Y2 was written up as scientific paper which was submitted in 2024 and the results from the inventory were used to initiate further actions during 2024.

A case study on mono-n-hexyl phthalate was performed to test the existing information structures and track how data produced in response to regulatory structures and enforcement can be used for different purposes. The choice to focus on mono-n-hexyl phthalate and related precursor substances was guided by the urgent request for data by EEA and ECHA to support upcoming regulatory actions via the PARC rapid response mechanism. The case study included a systematic evaluation of cosmetics databases, literature screening for empirical measurements and summary of records of compounds associated with mono-n-hexyl phthalate in products. The results from the case study were communicated with T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3 in support of empirical measurements in environmental and human matrices.

A working group on chemicals in products, with participants from A6.2.1. and T8.2 was formed to facilitate transfer of results and develop recommendations for improved information transfer structures. The collective results from the case study, working group on chemicals in articles together with the inventory of databases (described above) will be summarized in AD6.15 (M36). Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI, TUKES, VUA.

Evaluation of chemical risks in LCA models: A case study on how current information structures on chemicals in materials and articles can be used as input to LCA models for evaluation of products and articles have been performed. Information on chemicals in life cycle inventories was reviewed to assess the completeness of default data sets for different materials and articles compared to other sources reviewed in Y2. The impact of input data quality on LCA toxicity assessment was evaluated during 2024 and areas for improvement will be identified. The results on LCA assessment of chemical footprints and data needs will be included in AD6.15 (M36); Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI, TUKES, VUA. A case study on plasticizers in vinyl flooring was developed to support this activity, as demonstration of links between databases (described above) and LCA models in order to highlight how gaps in product databases impact outcomes of LCA.

The collective results from the actions completed under P6.4.3.a provides a comprehensive picture of existing data sources and methodologies to assess the occurrence of chemicals in products and materials and how this information can be used for different purposes by researchers and regulators. A conceptual framework has been developed to guide future development of information structures based on identified gaps in database coverage. The overview of data sources and recommendations for further development will be of particular interest for enforcement agencies, contributing to the design of projects for compliance testing, thus, contributing to a more systematic and effective enforcement. Contacts with ECHA forum for enforcement have been established for continuous dissemination of results and feed-back of regulatory needs. In addition to the use by enforcement agencies, the inventory of information structures on chemicals in products will be used by other tasks and activities under PARC including early warning systems under T8.2 and exposure modelling under A6.2.1. In a broader sense, the insights gained from the inventory are relevant for several regulatory initiatives improving chemical information transfer such as the SCIP database (ECHA) and the development of digital product passports under the Ecodesign and Sustainability Products regulation (ESPR).

- **P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KEMI [M25-M72]**

The project aims to provide proof-of-concept methods of chemical identification for use in the enforcement of chemical safety legislation, to fulfil crucial needs identified in project 6.4.3a. The project will have a specific focus on additives in high volume plastics and PFAS in articles identified as major use categories.

Progress during 2024:

For PFAS, a systematic workflow for compliance testing of a broad PFAS restriction was developed through a series of workshops involving analytical scientists, regulators and inspectors at national agencies in Sweden, Norway and Finland. The workflow proposes a tiered approach using (i) total fluorine measurement (ii) organic fluorine screening and (iii) target screening methods for testing the different proposed PFAS limit values. Empirical testing of the different steps was carried out for an array of different articles including treated textiles, packaging electronic components as well as chemical products. Inter-laboratory comparison for a subset of articles and products was planned and initiated to be completed during 2025 (Y4) (including RISE, ÖRU and SU). The developed and tested proof-of-concept methodology will be described in a report (due M54). For additives in plastics an integrated suspect-target workflow based on high resolution mass spectrometry was developed taking advantage of the recent improvements in plastic inventory databases. Testing of optimized extraction procedures for different polymers/plastic materials was initiated during 2024. Progress in P6.4.3.b is continuously communicated with representatives from ECHA forum to ensure that the developed methods will be relevant for enforcement purposes. The results related to the systematic workflow for PFAS was also presented and discussed at a workshop for enforcement agencies from Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Finland and Austria which was held in Stockholm September 2024. Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI, TUKES, VUA, SU and ÖRU.

➤ A6.4.4. RA to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity

Project progress (as described in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWP):

- **P6.4.4.a_Y1_CS1_KEMI [M1-M81], the CS has been extended from M42 to M81**

The EU Green Deal strategies (e.g., Chemicals strategy, Farm to fork and Biodiversity strategy) have set the scene for advancing the framework for Environmental RA (ERA) to support and promote an efficient protection of biodiversity. A concept to address this has been developed in the PERA roadmap (Sousa et al., 2022) and further expanded (Axelman et al., 2024). Meanwhile project 6.4.4.a has continued to map regulatory needs to ensure relevance of the concept. Through active collaboration with EU bodies (EFSA, EEA, ECHA), these ideas and ambitions have been integrated in the project objectives of 6.4.4. to further clarify and address the regulatory needs for the development of ERA. To this end, an updated version of the Technical Report *Clarifying regulatory needs* was finalised according to plan in the beginning of 2024. The report translates problem descriptions and regulatory ERA development needs into research questions, identified knowledge and data gaps, as well as into project deliverables and reports. Contributors to the updated report *Clarifying regulatory needs* were the Activity 6.4.4 regulatory core group (KEMI, UBA, FOEN, EFSA, ANSES), project 6.4.4.a partners (LU, NIVA, UCLM, UOS) and project leaders in Activity 6.4.4 (SLU (until end of April 2024), UFZ, RTPU (replaced by UDE), ISCIII).

Some of these needs were also raised in the ZAPID workshop (Zonal Authorisation Procedure Improvements and Developments), hosted in Dec. 2023 by the German authority Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety (BVL) that was attended by risk assessors and risk managers of competent authorities in the EU. The outcome of the ZAPID workshop confirms the relevance of the research questions developed so far in 6.4.4., in particular those related to the issue of increasing complexity of ERA of PPPs and mitigation of its implications. Indeed, the reduction of unnecessary complexity by focussing on relevant factors (key risk drivers) is a cornerstone of the work in PARC 6.4.4., especially in the projects P6.4.4.b and P6.4.4.c where the goal is to improve accuracy and simplify the effect and exposure assessments. Thus, during 2024 (PARC year 3), the problem description and outline of the regulatory needs in the next version of the 6.4.4.a project report *Clarifying regulatory needs* (due M34) has been

complemented with the recent high-level considerations of key stakeholders regarding complexity of ERA. This report forms the basis for AD 6.7 Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas (due M36)

Two Forum for Exchange meetings have been held so far during 2024 inviting external research groups on relevant topics for PARC as well as the projects TerraChem and SYBERAC. The Forum meetings provide a platform for exchange between external initiatives and all partners in PARC 6.4.4 as well as relevant PARC partners from other WPs. Main responsible partners are KEMI, UBA, FOEN, EFSA and ANSES.

The mapping of external projects to develop collaborations has continued during 2024 (year 3). As a result, a startup meeting to identify opportunities for synergies was held with coordinators of the ongoing projects Horizon Europe SYBERAC, PollinERA and TerraChem and of the EFSA project PERA – *Advancing the ERA of PPPs towards a systems-based-approach*. So far, a strategic alliance has been formed between PARC 6.4.4 and the two projects PollinERA and SYBERAC, which have explicit objectives in their Description of Actions to align with other initiatives to develop Systems-based ERA. Main contributing partners were KEMI, UBA, FOEN, EFSA and ANSES.

A Multi-SF entitled “Collaboration Opportunities for Environmental RA” was conducted as part of the SYBERAC project and communicated as a collaborative event with PARC 6.4.4 and PollinERA; this was to advance a coherent development of an expanded ERA framework.

Furthermore, in collaboration with PollinERA and SYBERAC, a survey involving regulatory environmental risk assessors for Regulation EC (No) 1007/2009 has been conducted. Nearly 100 responses from risk assessors from authorities at national and EU-level have been received. The objective of this survey is to gather insights to deepen the understanding of current methodologies in ERA for PPPs, supporting the transition towards integrative and systems-based approaches. The objectives and an early version of the survey questions were preliminary shared with EFSA for feedback and to align with EFSA’s activities for stakeholder engagement in the advancement of ERA. Analysis of the survey results is ongoing. The results of the survey were further discussed at online workshops with the responding regulatory environmental risk assessors, end of October 2024. The workshops have been organised to create opportunities for risk assessors to contribute to the regulatory relevance of the work performed in PARC 6.4.4. The results of the survey and workshop will be disseminated as an integral part of the technical report *Clarifying regulatory needs* (due M34) and *AD6.7 Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas*. They will be also disseminated by end of 2024 in targeted presentations for key stakeholders within PARC (e.g. EFSA, ECHA and relevant national stakeholders). In addition, in-depth analyses of the results will be disseminated as scientific publications within the projects PollinERA and SYBERAC. Main contributing partners for the collaborative activities reported above were KEMI, UBA, FOEN, EFSA and ANSES.

Collaborations and synergies within PARC have also been strengthened during 2024. Contributions to the PARC Next-generation Environmental RAPARC (NGRA)route project (WP2) has been provided from PARC 6.4.4. This is to outline a basis for NGRARoute to align the objectives of phasing out of animal testing and promote the use of NAMs with the systems-based approach of 6.4.4 that leverage on integration of new and existing data. These contributions from PARC 6.4.4 to WP2 NGRARoute also expanded to ERA and included the regulatory needs for chemicals and biodiversity gathered in project 6.4.4.a. One of the partners in the Regulatory core group of PARC 6.4.4 has also been assigned the transversal role as PARC Methodology Leader (Kemi) for NG-ERA with a focus on chemicals and biodiversity.

The project has continued to coordinate the four research projects in monthly regular meetings between the regulatory core group of 6.4.4.a (KEMI, UBA, FOEN, EFSA, ANSES) and the project

leaders of these four projects (UFZ, RPTU (replaced by UDE), ISCIH). In addition, a two-day workshop for all partners in 6.4.4 was organised on-site at ANSES (FR) Oct 10-11, 2024. The objective was to further foster collaborations within PARC 6.4.4 and with external projects, and to deepen alignment on and shared understanding of critical terms and concepts in PARC 6.4.4. Main contributing partners to the PARC 6.4.4 workshop were ANSES, KEMI, UBA, FOEN and EFSA.

- **P6.4.4.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ [M1-M81], the CS has been extended from M36 to M81**

This project aims at exploring ways of simplifying the PEC calculations within the ERA and performing a “reality check” of the predictions through comparing them to monitoring data.

The collected dataset of MECs has been further expanded to approximately 15 million concentration measurements of around 750 pesticide substances and metabolites. It includes data from the European Environment Agency’s Waterbase and national datasets from Denmark, Germany, Poland, Sweden, and Switzerland. The data were standardized to ensure consistency in substance names, units, and descriptions of sampling methodologies. The collected MEC data was analyzed and sorted from a spatial perspective by cross-referencing geographical coordinates with relevant catchment and land-use data, enabling an assessment of environmental factors influencing pesticide concentrations across different locations. A preliminary analysis of such factors was performed. It was concluded that continued curation of the MEC data and geographical sorting is needed to evaluate a potential link between MECs and environmental parameters. Partners involved were SLU (leading the work), UFZ, UOS and IEP-NRI.

The compilation of available models for predicted environmental concentrations of pesticides was further expanded by IEP-NRI (PL) (leading the work) and UOS (DE). The team identified in total 47 different PEC models through expert consultations and literature reviews, focusing specifically on models relevant for surface water exposure. Based on criteria like accessibility, ease of use, and relevance to surface water exposure modelling for comparison with the MEC dataset, the set models were then reduced to nine models for further analysis. The reduced set of models included models such as FOCUS Steps 1, 2 and 3 models, PEC CKB, and EXPRESS. In collaboration with SLU comparisons of MECs from different locations and PECs from different models was done. Overall PECs for most models were in reasonably good agreement with high-end percentiles of MECs. Exceptions were some scenarios linked to FOCUS Step 3 simulation models for which modelled PECs were considerably lower indicate a potential risk for non-protective PECs. These findings warrant further investigations of correspondence between PECs and MECs from locations corresponding to these FOCUS pedo-climatic scenarios. The results of the PEC vs MEC comparison gave no indication of that complex simulation models provide more accurate predictions than the simplest models.

One subgroup (UOS (DE)) worked on exploring to what extent failure to match predicted concentrations with measured concentrations is due to the processes in the models and to what extent it is due to the scenarios which are used in the models. This work was initiated through comparing a very simple PEC model to measured concentrations from an extensive study in Germany, and exploring how varying the input parameters affected the fit between predicted and measured data. An assessment of which input parameters that has an explanatory power for MECs has also been done using this data set. These results were in line with PEC vs MEC comparison based on the larger dataset, i.e., that a simple model give similar accuracy as complex simulation models.

IME Fraunhofer (DE) has continued the sensitivity analyses of the models in current regulatory use for predicting surface water concentrations of pesticides, both with regards to including/excluding model processes and to varying input parameters. The analysis has been extended to Step 3 FOCUS Simulation models, which enables an evaluation of how specific

weather data used in the models affect the predictions. Collaboration with RPTU (replaced by UDE) (DE) has been initiated to provide computing power for simulations. Both sub-projects are still ongoing. The results provide a deepened understanding of how different parameters in the models interact and affect the modelling outcome. The aim of an increased understanding of model parameter sensitivity and interactions is to explore which are the most important parameters under different scenarios and if some parameters are of negligible importance. This improved understanding will enable us to explore if it is possible to reduce the complexity of the models without compromising the outcome, as well as making the predictions more transparent. The first technical report was finalised in time until M24.

- **P6.4.4.c_Y1_CS3_UFZ [M1-M81], the CS has been extended from M36 to M81**

This project is contributing in the development of a streamlined, yet protective ERA with reduced complexity and resources required while keeping it as information rich as necessary. It employs a variety of complementing approaches to achieve its goals in close association with regulatory core group (KEMI, UBA, EFSA, ANSES, UKCEH) and partners (UC, EAWAG, SLU, RPTU (replaced by UDE), ULUND, NIVA, UCLM, UOS, ISCIII). During 2024, 15 internal project meetings with project partners has been held.

1) Data Collection and Harmonization:

Monitoring data on pesticide exposure at ecosystem level associated with invertebrate effect information for approx. 2000 sites were collected (UFZ, IOS, RPTU (replaced by UDE), EAWAG, SLU, and NIVA). Data harmonization and analysis for Denmark was finalised; harmonisation for several other European countries is currently ongoing. A joint publication is planned for Y3.

To reduce the site-specific variation of community descriptors due to environmental factors other than pesticides, species were classified and grouped according to their vulnerability to pesticides. This enables a RA that can focus on the evaluation of the pesticide effect alone. Interfering factors are largely excluded. This also means that the assessment of the effect is generally independent of geographical conditions and local environmental factors. This approach (SPEAR), initially developed by UFZ has been further developed with contributions of all project partners during 2024 to:

- Provide a reality check of pesticide concentrations at the ecosystem level including chemical and biological monitoring data. A benchmarking with the existing regulatory acceptable concentrations (RAC) showed that the majority of the RAC values are set too high compared to the quantified community effects, although some are also set too low.
- Increase its robustness against community effects related to climate change and drying periods in summer Increasing the extend of the validated geographical range together with the working group of Jes Rasmussen, using field data from NIVA, Denmark. A joint publication is in preparation.
- Revealing the combined effects of insecticides and herbicides on SPEAR index at ecosystem level (Liebmann et al. 2024).

2) Process identification:

The aim is to improve the predictability of the effects; this enables better environmental protection by adjusting the protectiveness of the ERA to an appropriate level. In a first step, the UFZ identified relevant processes and mechanisms driving the effect and published the results in several peer-reviewed publications in 2024: Latent effects: Short-term pesticide exposures can cause delayed mortality, especially at low concentrations (Liess et al. 2024); Sequential exposure: timing, order, and dose of stress events (Mushtaq et al 2024); Sublethal alteration of competitive strength: Disruption of species interactions resulting in altered community structure, already at

low concentrations, causing cascading effects on ecosystem functioning and biodiversity (Schunck et al. 2024). Currently knowledge of further relevant mechanisms is collected from project partners (see sub-project 3).

3) Predicting multiple stress effects

The combined effects of environmental stressors and toxicants on population density can be predicted based on the SAM developed in 2016 by UFZ. With this approach, the highly synergistic direct effects of independent stressor combinations can be quantitatively predicted. A benchmarking with traditional approaches (EA-Effect Addition model) has been performed by UFZ, which showed that the SAM approach for predicting effects of stressors with different MoA is clearly superior to predict synergistic interactions of multiple stressors in aquatic organisms (Shahid et al., 2024). An extension of the SAM for terrestrial organisms is currently being carried out together with partners. A publication related to multi stressor effects of terrestrial organisms is published (Wehrli et al 2024). A second publication with extended terrestrial data on combined effects of stressors quantified using SAM approach with project partners from UC, Portugal is in preparation.

Finally, the SPEAR approach is used to develop a prospective streamlined effect assessment with greatly reduced complexity - the 'adaptation-based' RA approach (see following section).

4) Improving predictability/protectiveness in ERA

We suggest achieving the streamlining and simplification of RA by means of an "adaptation-based" RA approach. In doing so, we take into account the fact that the community composition is adapted to the site-specific environmental factors including e.g. temperature, pH, oxygen and toxicants mixtures. Accordingly, the composition of such an adapted community can be used directly to indicate the magnitude of impact of the stressor under investigation (e.g. pesticides). Accordingly, extension to the existing RA enables linking single substance toxicity information to the effects at ecosystem level. The basis for the assessment is given by toxicity information obtained from test systems at the sub-organism and organism level (e.g. NAMs and standard test systems). This information then enables a validated link based on field monitoring data to the prospectively predicted pesticide effects at the ecosystem level. The concept and a first draft were discussed several times together with the members of the regulatory core group from BAFU, EFSA, KEMI, UBA. After consolidation, by the end of the year 2024 all other members of 6.4.4 will be invited to join the discussion. The publication of this approach is anticipated for 2025. The final aim is to link toxicity information on pesticides with their ecosystem related effects on various levels of biological organization. For agricultural streams such a link could be established within this 6.4.4.c project from the gene to the community level (Siddique et al., 2024; see table below). During the ASRY3 period (NIVA) will contribute to extend RA for single and mixtures of stressors (cumulative RA) and with applying data spanning the molecular to population level into integrated impact assessment.

5) Model Analysis and Benchmarking

The suitability of models such as the SAM and TKTD models is under evaluation. These models will be calibrated using field data. Work on these models in different groups is in progress. The work was done with the Activity lead core group (KEMI, UBA, Agroscope, FOEN) and partners (ISCI (ES), UFZ (DE), SU (SE), UOS (DE)).

The conceptual work has so far been conducted mainly in connection with P6.4.4.a_Y3_CS1_KEMI. External presentation of the project has been given at 4 occasions. Disseminated publications during 2024 amounts to 8 (table below).

Table 7: Disseminated publications during 2024

Sequential pesticide exposure: Concentration addition at high concentrations - Inhibition of hormesis at ultra-low concentrations	August 2024	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176493
Predicting the Combined Effects of Multiple Stressors and Stress Adaptation in <i>Gammarus pulex</i>	July 2024	10.1021/acs.est.4c02014
Combined effects of herbicides and insecticides reduce biomass of sensitive aquatic invertebrates	June 2024	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174343
Revealing the cascade of pesticide effects from gene to community	January 2024	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.170472
Ultra-low esfenvalerate exposure may disrupt interspecific competition	December 2023	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167455
Latent pesticide effects and their mechanisms	November 2023	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.168368
Persistent Disruption of Interspecific Competition after Ultra-Low Esfenvalerate Exposure	July 2023	10.2139/ssrn.4510906
A dirt(y) world in a changing climate: Importance of heat stress in the RA of pesticides for soil arthropods	October 2024	10.1111/gcb.17542

Furthermore, monitoring data acquisition and evaluation has continued during 2024 involving partners NIVA, BAFU, EAWAG, SLU, UOS, CEH, UC, UDE.

- **P6.4.4.d_Y1_CS4_UDE [M1-M81], the CS has been extended from M42 to M81**

This project aims to ensure that results of independently performed ERA of a PPP can be used as a benchmark for ERAs of other PPPs, i.e. comparing and ranking risk profiles of PPPs among substances and in different areas (e.g. for selected organism groups). The project consists of conceptual development supported by analysis of existing chemical and ecotoxicological data for PPPs. During the reporting period 11 project meetings have been held between partners UDE, SU and Keml.

Conceptual development has been conducted in close collaboration with project 6.4.4.a and is ongoing. Chemical and ecotoxicology data for 290 active substances regulated under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 (PPP-regulation) has been compiled from various sources such as EFSA. Cross-project substance identifiers have been established with the Horizon Europe project SPRINT to ensure compatibility of future data sharing. Two data analysis studies have been done so far for which preliminary results are available. One study identified reasons for non-approvals of active substances and the other explored impact of higher tier data on risk characterisation. Both studies are close to submission to international peer-reviewed journals. This work was mainly conducted by RPTU (replaced by UDE) (DE).

Regarding reasons for the non-approval of active substances, the EU Pesticides database was used to identify PPP active substances that were withdrawn or approval for renewal was rejected. Fifty-six active substances met these criteria. Information detailing the reasons for their withdrawal or rejection was obtained from the EFSA conclusions, EU review reports and Commission reports. Multinomial logistic regression analysis showed that the risk factors which significantly affected the outcome included the risks to birds, mammals, aquatic invertebrates, and fish. Based on the compiled data set further analysis for internal (between substances) benchmarking is ongoing. This work was mainly conducted by RPTU (replaced by UDE) (DE).

Moreover, a targeted study has been conducted focussing on the impact of higher tier studies on calculated risk characterisations and between-ERA comparability. In addition, a targeted study was performed based on publicly available data from EFSA (EU-level RA for approval of active substances) for 24 insecticides. The purpose was to investigate consistency and comparability of existing higher tier studies on the risk characterisation. Manuscript was part of PhD dissertation at SU and is in prep. for publication in a peer-reviewed journal. At the first stage a dataset was compiled on currently approved insecticides for which higher tier studies are available. Results showed that calculated risk values decreased in the presence of higher-tier data. However, there was no detectable pattern in how relative risks between the insecticides changed with the addition of higher-tier data. Moreover, higher-tier data were highly heterogenous indicating poor comparability and that the level of protection for individual PPPs in relation other approved PPPs may be case-dependent. This has been written up as pre-print and has been part of the first technical report of P6.4.4d. This work was mainly conducted by SU (SE) and Kemi (SE).

Further analysis on the approved list of approved substances in EU that involved categorization of the 290 substances into their various pesticide functions (e.g. insecticides, fungicides, etc.) have been conducted. Implementation of the developed benchmarking concept is ongoing and stepwise. The first step involves eighteen currently approved dual function substances (acaricides and insecticides) from the EU list and has been completed. The next step involves the compilation and analysis of thirty-one insecticides and is almost concluded. Subsequently, this will be expanded to herbicides (90) and fungicides (84) and be used to finalize the internal benchmarking exercise. This work was primarily conducted by RPTU (replaced by UDE) (DE).

The work was done in collaboration with the Activity lead core group (KEMI, UBA, Agroscope, FOEN) and partners (ISCI (ES), UFZ (DE), SU (SE)). The conceptual work was discussed at a workshop in November 2023 with contributions from partners from all project in Activity 6.4.4 and the joint publication is undergoing review and will be submitted to an international peer-reviewed journal in the last quarter of 2024.

- **P6.4.4.e_Y1_CS5_ISCI [M1-M81], the CS has been extended from M42 to M81**

The project lead is ISCI and the case studies involved in this project are led by UCLM (ES), INERIS (FR), OFB (FR), UC (PT), UKCEH (UK), IEP-NRI (PL), UFZ (DE), NIVA (NO), and EAWAG (CH) supported by UAVR (PT), RPTU (replaced by UDE) (DE), and UBA (DE), have selected the case studies, developed each case study design and are starting the data collection and implementation. The other partners ULUND (SE), UOS (DE), UOB (UK), EA (UK), SYKE (FI) and the regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU) have contributed to the discussions on the conceptualization of landscape ERA and contributed to the different discussions and activities. Here it is a list of meetings, publications, etc that the project lead has carried out during the first phase of the project:

Table 8: list of meetings, publications, etc that the project lead has carried out during the first phase of the project

	Date	Action	Comments
2022	27 October	Online meeting	UCLM discussion of c.s.
	7 November	Online meeting	Kick-off meeting
	9 November	Online meeting	Kick-off meeting
	28 - 29 November	Online meeting	Meeting with Spanish Ministry - INIA
	29 – 30 November	Online meeting	1st workshop
	7 December	Online meeting	2nd workshop
	14 December	Online meeting	3rd workshop

	20 December	Online meeting	4th workshop
2023	28 February	Online meeting	Case study discussions
	1 March	Online meeting	Case study discussions
	6 September	Online meeting	Terrestrial case studies alignment
	2 October	Online meeting	Aquatic case studies alignment
	17 October	Online meeting	Hope Farm as new c.s
	7 November	Online meeting	Meeting with industry
	2024	18 January	Online meeting
9 February		Online meeting	Terrestrial c.s. sampling scheme
13 - 14 February		Physical meeting	Possible new aquatic c.s. in Cartagena (SP)
3 April		Online meeting	Poster preparation for SETAC
5-9 May		Posters presentation in congress	2 poster presentation (1 of conceptual model and 1 of the c.s.)
10 September		Publication	Conceptual model
3 October		Online meeting	Project extension drafting proposal
6 November		Physical meeting	Presentation of project in EFSA premises

Note that these actions are exclusive from 6.4.4.e daily work. Apart from these, we have participated in the general 6.4.4. coordination meetings, other European projects, EFSA meetings, etc.

The main achievement has been the finalisation of the conceptual model and its publication (Environment International <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108999>). The landscape ERA conceptual model covers the spatial variability of the agricultural European environments, and the influence of ecological conditions and agricultural management on the risk of pesticides for non-target species. The model offers a flexible and versatile framework for combining spatially explicit models and tools, and for addressing the temporal variability. The framework can be adapted to the different ERA regulatory needs (aggregated and combined PPP effects) and stakeholders needs at different levels. The conceptualisation focuses on the spatial and temporal variability of pressures/stressors (pesticide applications, other agricultural management actions, and climate change) and receptors at different ecological levels (individuals, populations, communities, ecosystems functions and services) and the integration of both for the exposure and effect assessments. A set of case studies were selected, covering terrestrial and aquatic environments in different agricultural landscapes to test the generic conceptual model for landscape environmental RA, and are in progress, the list includes:

CS1: Farmlands in central Spain, led by UCLM with contribution from ISCIII;

Agricultural areas dominated by winter cereals, vineyards and olive orchards were characterized in Spain, and a total of 30 sites with different degrees of agricultural intensification (estimated as % of area dedicated to agriculture, density of patch margins and a qualitative assessment of organic farming extension). Environmental samples have been collected to monitor pesticide usage, including soils, plants and treated seeds. Biota samplings have included transects for avian abundance and pit-fall traps for invertebrate diversity characterization, with current analyses being conducted to calculate avian population densities from transect results, as well as biodiversity indexes following the identification of trapped invertebrates. This CS is focused on improvement landscape approaches for their potential implementation in Regulation 1107/2009, to offer surrogate protection goals with ecological entity to better represent the general protection goal of preserving the environment from undesirable impacts of PPPs.

CS2: Vineyard area in the south of France, led by INRAE and OFB;

This project investigates the impact of four pesticides monitored under the EU WFD on aquatic ecosystems in rivers and lakes. Leveraging data from the latest river basin management plan (2016-2021), which includes over 3,500 river monitoring points and 890 lake points, the study has advanced in detecting pesticide effects on biological communities such as phytoplankton, macrophytes, and macrozoobenthos.

Regarding the update on the achievements done during 2024, we identified an approach to derive a set of reference landscape exposure scenarios in vineyard context along with the tools to be deployed. By the end of this year, we will have identified the main relevant landscape elements necessary to describe pesticide fate at the landscape scale along with the relevant organisms to be studied in this context. This study focuses on the regulatory framework of the use of pesticides.

Moreover, the potential for collaboration with other countries working within the framework of the WFD and other related EU directives such as the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive is being under study.

CS3: Bairrada wine producing region in Portugal, led by UC with contribution from UAVR;

CFE-UC case study is evaluating the effects of pesticide (PPP) application on soil biodiversity, functioning, and non-target organisms (NTAs) in vineyard landscapes. The study is focused on the Bairrada wine-producing region in central Portugal. The primary objectives are to assess the influence of landscape complexity and PPP management practices on NTA exposure and dynamics and to evaluate the impact of spray series on soil organisms and ecological risk. Key achievements in 2024 include analyzing collected data to assess the effects of landscape complexity, PPP use, and spray series on soil biodiversity, functioning, and NTA populations; evaluate the ecological risk for in-soil organisms posed by the spray applications; monitor NTA groups in crop and off-crop habitats, focusing on vulnerable families of predators, parasitoids, and pollinators; analyze the influence of landscape complexity on biodiversity mitigation effects; and assess the effectiveness of risk mitigation measures implemented in vineyards.

The findings of this case study have the potential to inform regulatory frameworks related to pesticide use and RA (contributing to the development of more targeted and effective pesticide RA and management strategies) landscape management (providing insights into how landscape management practices can mitigate the negative impacts of pesticide use on biodiversity and ecosystem functioning and Integrated Pest Management (IPM)).

The project team is open to collaborating with other researchers and organizations interested in similar topics. Potential areas of collaboration include data sharing, the development of new or improved methods for assessing pesticide impacts on ecosystems and policy development of evidence-based policy recommendations for pesticide management and landscape conservation.

CS4: Hope Farm arable farm in UK, led by UKCEH;

Better ERA requires identifying how species utilise field margin regions with highest PPP exposure. For this reason (in 2024) we carried out surveys under two major headings. 1) Lepidoptera: to support 2023 data, lepidopteran surveys were performed across field margin types at Hope Farm (and the adjacent Rectory Farm) at key PPP application times. The resulting DNA barcoding data is being analysed to give us comprehensive and high-resolution species distributions across margin types, and also across years. 2) Other species: to provide high-resolution species distributions for non-lepidopterans a substantial survey for other agriculturally beneficial species was performed within field margins and crops across both farms using a range

of collection methods. DNA isolation and library preparation are currently ongoing to generate large-scale meta-barcoding data.

The design and management of landscape mitigation strategies (and ERA more generally) would be improved by identifying species with the highest intrinsic PPP sensitivity. Towards this end in 2024, we developed our sensitivity prediction capacity by sequencing the basal transcriptomes of 16 lepidopteran species dominating Hope Farm. During 2024, we also determined the responsive capacities of Lepidoptera (in *M. brassicae*) following PPP exposure to two major PPPs. We are currently combining this data with publicly available genomes to catalogue and compare detoxification gene complexity, PPP receptor gene sequences, detoxification responsive capacities, and then integrating this molecular data to other sensitivity-relevant traits to generate testable predictions. Much of this work is being prepared for publication (e.g. Short et al, in prep. Divergent Xenometabolic Responses are Critical to Pesticide Sensitivity in Lepidopterans). Our molecular work across 2024 has also revealed bio-markers of PPP exposure linked to population-relevant sub-lethal outcomes. This has led to the generation of a high-throughput qPCR assay to assess the extent direct exposure to PPP in the field are driving harm. The first attempt to deploy this assay in the field will take place in 2025.

Regulatory framework(s) targets for regulatory uptake: as the case study is providing support for specific landscape management options, several organisations with regulatory roles will benefit from the insights generated. These include, the Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA) and the Health and Safety Executive (HSE). Although the UK is no longer a member of the EU, the work could also have relevance for European regulatory agencies, e.g. EFSA, that is involved in the management of plant protection products and environmental quality. Other organisations linked to PPP authorization and agronomical recommendations, and human health may also find the case study outcomes relevant. These include the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive (SUD) and the EU's common agricultural policy (CAP). Outside of regulators, the data is relevant to broad scale arable crop farmers in the UK and EU, as it increases the evidential basis for designing and implementing specific landscape mitigation strategies. For this reason, communication (via workshops) has taken place between UKCEH and the major stakeholder (the RSPB).

CS5: Pesticides and WFD in Poland, led by IEP-NRI;

This case study investigates the potential effects of pesticides monitored under the WFD on aquatic biota in Poland. The project aims to analyze existing WFD monitoring data to identify relationships between pesticide occurrence and changes in biological communities. By examining metrics such as taxonomic richness, diversity, abundance, and functional traits, the study seeks to assess the sensitivity of aquatic biota to different pesticides and explore potential synergistic effects with other environmental stressors. Key achievements in 2024 include data analysis (analysis of pesticide occurrence and biological data for the selected sites ("impacted" and "reference") is ongoing), statistical modelling using GLM or/and other relevant techniques and result interpretation.

This case study targets the following regulatory frameworks for potential uptake of the findings:

- WFD: The project aims to evaluate the effectiveness of WFD-compliant monitoring data in detecting the impact of pesticides on aquatic ecosystems. This information can be valuable for informing future revisions of the WFD and its associated monitoring guidelines.
- National Regulations on Pesticide Use: Based on the identified sensitive biological elements and metrics, the study may recommend modifications to existing national regulations on pesticide use to better protect aquatic biodiversity.

- Collaboration with other groups conducting similar case studies in other countries is still being considered. This collaboration can involve data sharing, harmonizing methodologies, and drawing comparative conclusions on the impact of pesticides on aquatic biota across different regions.

CS6: Kleingewässer-Monitoring KgM on small-medium streams in Germany, led by UFZ with contributions from UBA and RPTU (replaced by UDE);

Throughout 2024, the Kleingewässer-Monitoring (KgM) project has continued its detailed assessment of pesticide contamination in small and medium-sized streams across Germany. This project provides a unique quantitative analysis of pesticide impacts, focusing on data collected from 124 stream sections between 2018 and 2019 during peak pesticide application periods. This year, efforts have been concentrated on performing data analysis, especially regarding the correlation between pesticide contamination and macroinvertebrate community structures. Key achievements in 2024 include data integration, multiple stressor analysis, drafting of different publications (close to submission phase) and stakeholder engagement.

The study targets key regulatory frameworks for potential uptake, particularly the EU WFD and the National Action Plan for Plant Protection Products (EU-NAP). The results are also relevant for the EFSA, given their role in pesticide RAs, and Umweltbundesamt (UBA), with direct applications in national pesticide regulation and biodiversity protection strategies.

CS7: Danish stream case study, led by NIVA. This case study investigates the spatiotemporal (both space and time) effects of pesticide (PPP) exposure on macroinvertebrate communities in Danish streams. The project aims to improve landscape-scale environmental RA (ERA) by analysing how macroinvertebrate communities respond to pesticide exposure over time and how surrounding landscape characteristics influence their recovery. The study is being conducted by a PhD student at NIVA (Norwegian Institute for Water Research). Key achievements in 2024 include data analysis of existing data on pesticide monitoring, macroinvertebrate communities, water chemistry, flow, hydromorphology, and catchment characteristics and modelling landscape effects to assess the influence of landscape features (e.g., riparian vegetation, refuge areas) on macroinvertebrate recovery after pesticide exposure.

Due to the recent case study leader change, the anticipated completion date for the scientific paper has been extended to summer 2025. This timeframe aligns with the initial estimated duration of 6-12 months for the project.

The project team is actively seeking collaborators in data sharing of similar data sets on pesticide exposure and macroinvertebrate communities collected in Danish streams and expertise sharing

CS8: Aquatic biodiversity status of five agricultural sites in Switzerland, led by EAWAG.

Throughout 2024, the Comparative Study of Exposure-Activity Ratios (EAR) project has made considerable progress in assessing the relationship between chemical exposure and biodiversity status across five agricultural sites in Switzerland. The study, which uses chemical monitoring data from water, sediment, and fish, focuses on calculating EARs and comparing these with biological monitoring data to evaluate their predictive power. Key achievements in 2024 include the calculation of EARs and risk quotients (for 91 pesticides, as well as industrial chemicals, pharmaceuticals, and other pollutants), correlation analysis (between EARs, risk quotients, and biological data, including indicators from macrozoobenthos, diatoms, fish, and macrophytes collected under the national NAWA-Trend monitoring program) and biotest integration (zebrafish embryo toxicity, algae growth, cytotoxicity tests, etc.)

These findings are relevant for several regulatory frameworks, including:

- EU WFD: EARs and biological monitoring data support objectives related to water quality and ecological protection.
- SUD) and CAP: The study's findings may inform best practices in pesticide use and agronomical recommendations.
- National PPP Authorization: The study's results contribute to pesticide RAs, particularly regarding biodiversity protection.
- Collaboration opportunities remain open, particularly with groups conducting similar EAR studies in other countries. This work is expected to feed into broader regulatory discussions at both national and EU levels.

The aquatic case studies are connected to the WFD and include prospective and retrospective assessments for exploring the role of pesticide exposure as well as other stressors on environmental impacts (including biodiversity). The implementation of the CS has started during 2024, and will continue in the following year. Several case studies are also connected to other EU projects and additional interactions with these projects and those funded by EFSA have been conducted during this year and will also continue in the future. The proposed approach for landscape-level ERA covers the spatial and temporal element of a system-based approach as proposed by EFSA under the PERA (Building a European Partnership for next generation, systems-based Environmental Risk Assessment (PERA) (<https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7546>) initiative, and its regulatory relevance is confirmed by different activities launched by EFSA in this area including the grant EUBA-EFSA-PREV-2023-01: PERA - Advancing the ERA of Plant Protection Products towards a system-based approach. The intrinsic complexity of Landscape-based approaches has been highlighted as a main challenge for the regulatory implementation, and some preliminary exercises have stated this year to explore simplification options for facilitating the regulatory use of this approaches for regulatory ERA covering combined exposure to different pesticides.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

In P6.4.1a_CS_RWTH_BRUNEL_OPREMIX, one Project leader is on long term sick leave since M22. The work on the survey and on the project reports was mainly on hold. In M29 we received the news that he will probably will not come back until the end of year 2024. Therefore, the work will continue without his contribution and the outstanding reports will be finalized and included in the AD.6.17 (Optimizing regulatory RA including the use of monitoring data and NAMs and management of chemical mixtures in Europe) by the end of the Project in M40.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD6.7	Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for	UBA/KE MI/FOE N	M24 (postponed M36)		This AD was initially planned Y1 (M12) but was postponed to Y2 (M24) and then to M36 (rationale in the project description P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI)

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
	ERA development areas.				
AD6.14	Report on current screening and enforcement structures	TUKES	M24 (postponed M28)	M30	This AD was initially planned M24 but is postponed to M28: During the first year of PARC we experienced some delays in hiring and parental leave for the activity leader which resulted in a slow start for the data gathering and analysis supporting AD6.14 and AD6.15.
AD6.15	Report on existing database structures with recommended structures	MU	M24 (postponed M36)		This AD was initially planned M24 but is postponed to M36: During the first year of PARC we experienced some delays in hiring and parental leave for the activity leader which resulted in a slow start for the data gathering and analysis supporting AD6.14 and AD6.15.
AD6.16	Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory RA landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis	UNIBAS	M24 (postponed M36)		AD6.8 “Technical report: mapping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks” initially planned Y1 (M12) has been postponed to Y2 and merged with this AD6.16. This AD is postponed to Y3 to fit with the end of the projects P6.4.2.b and P6.4.2.c

1.2.7 Work package 7. FAIR Data

1.2.7.1 Task 7.1. FAIR Data Policy and implementation¹³

Co-leaders: TNO (NL), UOB (UK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), VITO (BE), MU(CZ), UZIS (CZ), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), NIVA (N), UG-PL (PL), JSI (SI), KI (SE), AUTH (EL), ISSEP (BE)

Sub-contractors: GFF (BE)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

¹³ The titles of the activities A7.1.1, A7.1.2 and A7.1.3 were not included in the AWPY1 and SRIA. These titles have been added between the submission of the AWP Y1 and the submission of the ASR Y1 and will be added in AWPY2 and its Annex PARC Portfolio project.

➤ A7.1.1 PARC Data Policy and Initial Data Management Plan

[Lead: TNO (NL); Partners Involved: UoB (UK), KI (SE), VITO (BE), UG-PL (PL), UBA (DE), UU-IRAS (NL), ANSES (FR), MU (CZ), ISS (IT), EV-ILVO (BE), UZIS (CZ), AUTH (EL), BRGM (FR), JSI (SI), UL-LACDR (NL), KWR (NL), IMM-KI (SE)]; GFF (NL) as subcontractor

In Y3 no projects were submitted from Task 7.1

Goals:

- Updating the DMP with clusters of project-level DMPs, using the online DMP tool;
- Finalisation of a scientific paper on the PFDP
- Finalization of white paper on PARC FAIR ambitions and implementation roadmap;
- Continuous “training through doing” for Data Champions, Liaisons and FIT on FIPs and use of online DMP tooling to ensure proper collection of projects specific DMPs, to build the PARC domain-specific and cross-domain tools to enable FAIR metadata and data

Project level DMPs: The Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) has just recently become available to PARC via the ELIXIR nodes, to ensure sustainable availability (as opposed to having DSW at one or a few partners only). This slightly delayed the collection of study specific data, but a start will be made with the population of project specific DMP templates based upon the information obtained from the data champions, data liaison interactions (project descriptions)) and the Reference FIPs, both PARC and domain specific FIPs. The first project level DMPs are currently being completed in the DSW tool with projects and a documented workflow is being finalized as a self-guided training material to support Data Liaisons / Champions [UoB, TNO].

PFDP scientific paper: The scientific paper related to the PARC FAIR data policy has been well advanced to the level where the coauthors are now performing the final input to the review process and will be submitted by the end of this year to Environmental Science and Technology. The paper now also includes additional work describing the retrieval of possible future topics using Large Language Model (LLM) approaches (Google Bert, Open AI). Further, an analysis is included to which extent different stakeholders (at least based upon stakeholder content) perceive the chemical RA data landscape, as well as FAIR aspects related to this (TNO, KI, UBA, KWR, UoB, VITO, TNO, JSI, ISS, GFF)

White paper on PARC FAIR ambitions and implementation roadmap; Work is ongoing towards this, and many of the (previously missing) implementation steps are now emerging, such that the roadmap and its implementation plan are becoming more concretized rather than being abstract and aspirational. The ambition and implementation plan are quite dependent on the PARC data Hub, whose initial specification was finalized in month 29, and now that this is clearer, the roadmap will be written up in more detail and supplemented with training materials and PARCopaedia content (UoB, MU, TNO, VITO, GFF, UL-LACDR, JSI, ISS, all WP7 partners).

Development of the methodology for assessing progress towards the WP7 KPI of 80% of PARC data being FAIR. A significant activity undertaken for the periodic reporting (M18) was the first evaluation of the progress towards the KPI for FAIR data. This involved: (i) defining the unit of data in PARC and (ii) evaluating existing approaches for evaluating FAIRness, including via the DSW Tool, via semi-automated workflows focusing on data repository compliance with the FAIR principles and other metrics. A key point of note is that the initial unit of data is considered a PARC publication, in which data is either generated or re-used in PARC, and the FAIRness of the resulting data is evaluated. The first round of evaluation was largely manual, but as we progress this evaluation will also be made increasingly automated. A key outcome from this work is a Checklist for PARC authors that will be completed alongside submission of publications, that

summarizes the data and where it is deposited. A process for updating of project-level DMPs with the final information on where the data linked to publications is accessible will also be implemented, via the PARC Data Hub. This will be rolled out in the last quarter of 2024 and first quarter of 2025 and accompanied by webinars to explain how it enhances the FAIRness of PARC data [UoB, MU, VITO].

➤ A7.1.2 Communication and Training: organisation and delivery across PARC

Continuous training for Data Champions, Liaisons and FIT: After their initial training in Y2, the facilitators and trainers with the FIT (mostly data liaisons) have focused on FAIR implementation in Y3, via interaction with the PARC community. As examples: PARC members (lead: UL-LACDR) were involved in the establishment of a general GO FAIR wiki (<https://github.com/gofair-foundation/gofair-wiki>) and a three-point framework for FAIRification (3PFF, in which FIPs and M4M lead to a FAIR data point) facilitator wiki (<https://github.com/gofair-foundation/facilitators/wiki>) to improve/centralize the training material for future training rounds. In addition, improvements contributed to the FAIR Supporting Resources (FSR) qualification pipeline (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/efp/efp-portal/>), streamlining the experience for future facilitators. Another example is the interaction between WP7 within the (ELIXIR) Toxicology community on the “FAIRification of toxicological research output” (May 2024) (UL-LACDR, KI, UoB, TNO). In addition, WP7 hosted the PARC Training Course on “FAIR data and databases” that took place 22-24 May 2024 in Ljubljana, Slovenia (JSI, VITO, MU, UoB). Together, further steps were made as to training the scientists within PARC, amongst which were data champions. The "train the trainer" training pyramid presented last year (Fig. 6) is still applicable: whereas in Y2 the focus was on transfer of knowledge from the Go Fair Foundation (GFF) to the data liaisons, in Y3 this has further progressed towards transfer of knowledge from the data liaisons to the data champions, and to building FAIR awareness through the PARC consortium. Note that the Training event in Ljubljana was so successful that the PARC NHCs have invited WP7 to present the overall FAIR awareness part (the first half-day of the training school) for the National Hubs (delivery date: 14th November 2024, partners UoB, JSI). to the data liaisons, in Y3 this has further progressed towards transfer of knowledge from the data liaisons to the data champions, and to building FAIR awareness through the PARC consortium. Note that the Training event in Ljubljana was so successful that the PARC National Hubs coordinators have invited WP7 to present the overall FAIR awareness part (the first half-day of the training school) for the National Hubs (delivery date: 14th November 2024, partners UoB, JSI).

Fig. 6: The GFF Training pyramid. The GFF Training pyramid, with the basic level of training in FAIR Awareness and FIPs being given to all PARC members who are interested, to all WP7 members and to the Data Champions from across PARC. This was started in Y3. The Data Liaisons (who are embedded in WP7) have received receive training to enable them to facilitate FIP training and be introduced to the Metadata for Machines (M4M) concepts (Y2). The FIT experts will be able to further specialize their skills depending on their individual interests and PARC needs with vocabulary, data schema, FAIR datapoint (FDP), or Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property (I-ADOPT) training, as shown in the training pyramid.

Dissemination activities:

- JRC Webinar on “Good practices and resources to improve the utility of research data in regulatory assessments” - 31st January 2024. Presentation by Iseult Lynch (UoB): “PARC approach to ensuring FAIR Chemical RA Data”
- “FAIR data to support Chemical RA and Regulation – the PARC approach for toxicological data”. Presentation by Iseult Lynch (UoB) at the Elixir workshop on “FAIR-ification of Toxicological Research Output: Leveraging ELIXIR Resources” on 28-29 May 2024 in Leiden, as part of the ELIXIR Toxicology Community’s Implementation Study (INTOXICOM)
- “FAIR data to support Chemical RA and Regulation – The PARC ambition and approach”, presentation by Iseult Lynch (UoB) at the PARC SynNet event as part of the SETAC Europe Annual meeting 2024, 6th May, 2024.

➤ A7.1.3 FAIR Data Use Case Coordination

[See 7.2.3 - From AWPY3 onwards use case identification and management is integrated into 7.2.3]

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

No significant problems/deviations/delays - the project level DMPs are now being implemented via the Elixir platform, which streamlines the workflow significantly.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.7.2 Task 7.2. Data libraries

Leader: MU (CZ), VITO (BE)

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Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

The projects P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO and P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO present a broad and integrated approach towards two specific domains and cut across the different activities defined under 7.2. They include use cases of several R&I projects (respectively monitoring PFAS and endocrine disruptors with T4.2, and use cases on FAIRification and (re)use of HBM datasets with several projects of T4.1, T6.2 and T8.3). These T7.2 projects provide the bottom-up use cases for concretely implementing the WP7 data sharing and reuse objectives, and for developing adapted methods and tools.

- **P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO: [Lead: MU, Participants: VITO, UFZ, BRMG, UniLu, ISSeP, JSI, ANSES, UBA, AUTH, NIVA, KWR] [M1-M42], the project has been extended from M36 to M42**

The project employed diverse methods for mapping the current environmental chemical occurrence data landscape, drawing mainly from D9.2 published by WP9 and surveys carried out by R&I WPs (WP6, WP4), the chemical RA landscaping (7.2.1) activity, identification of major resources for PARC R&I WPs, including data reuse/storage options via data champions/data liaisons interactions, and leveraging partner expertise [lead: MU, contributors: JSI, VITO, ISSeP, JSI, UniLU, UFZ, NIVA, UBA, ANSES, BRGM, AUTH]. The compilation of existing resources is a living document that will be periodically updated. It serves as a basis for project 7.2.2a project partners for prioritization of resources for further exploring their FAIRness and (meta)data structures.

Identified major resources were prioritized for further assessment [MU, BRGM, UBA, ANSES], reflecting the PARC environmental community's current needs, as well as the potential of resources to serve as repositories for PARC-generated environmental data. An as-is FIP was assessed for Stockholm Convention Global Monitoring Plan Data Warehouse (GMP DWH), and GENASIS, a repository and visualization system of harmonized environmental monitoring data [MU]. FIPs have been prepared for MassBank Europe (a database of mass spectra of emerging substances to support identification of unknown substances), NORMAN Suspect List Exchange (NORMAN SLE, a central database to access various lists of substances for suspect screening and prioritisation) and NORMAN Substance Database (NORMAN SusDat, a merged list of NORMAN substances) in 2024 following these discussions, the FIP for NORMAN EMPODAT (a database of geo-referenced monitoring and bio-monitoring data on emerging substances in environmental matrices) is underway [UniLU]. This covers the databases of most interest to PARC for data on chemicals in the environment so far. The first draft report on the FAIRness of major resources has been prepared [MU, VITO, UFZ, BRMG, UniLu, ISSeP, JSI, ANSES, UBA, AUTH, NIVA, KWR]. The as-is FIPs of other priority resources will serve as a basis for environmental occurrence data reference FIP.

Existing metadata standards, metadata schemas, vocabularies and ontologies potentially relevant for PARC environmental datasets have been listed and reviewed to explore their relevance for PARC environmental datasets [MU, VITO, ISSeP, JSI, UniLU, UFZ, NIVA, UBA].

Metadata workshops with data experts and domain experts were organized bi-weekly to develop the metadata schema for data concerning chemical occurrence in the outdoor environment [MU, ISSeP, VITO, UFZ, BRMG, UniLu, JSI, ANSES, UBA, AUTH, NIVA, KWR]. A preliminary meeting to discuss the scope and goals of metadata workshops for data concerning chemical occurrence in the indoor environment took place [MU, ISSeP]. We have also joined discussions of domain experts and stakeholders focused on database needs for data concerning chemicals in products [MU]. Further discussions on the potential for a use case are underway. The materials from the meetings (meeting minutes, recordings and presentations) are available in the WP7 Sharepoint. The workshop events are also published as nanopublications.

A blueprint of the environmental (meta)data dashboard for the environmental component of the PARC Data Hub has been prepared using MS Power BI (the link is available in WP7 Sharepoint) and is included in Milestone Report 12 (MS12) - Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD submitted on 5th September 2024 [MU], and this will be further iterated based on the outcomes of the metadata workshops.

P7.2.2a experts joined the meetings of the PFAS baseline project that was chosen as the primary use case for FAIR data management to discuss the further needs of this project, and potential of P7.2.2a involvement in the implementation of FAIR data management practices [MU].

An extension of 6 months has been requested for the project and related activities to allow for sufficient discussions with domain experts, feedback from stakeholders, and adequate time to finalize the project reports.

- **P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO: [Lead: VITO, Participants: MU, UBA, ISSEP, JSI, WR] [M1-M48], the project has been extended from M42 to M48**

VITO has continued the HBM4EU central data platform for individual HBM data as the Personal Exposure and Health data platform. A software tool for schema-based harmonisation and data validation was developed and made available for use (<https://hbm.vito.be/tools>) early 2023. Meanwhile the tool had several *ad hoc* improvements. Through a web-based platform data providers can run the tool locally on their (meta)data templates prior to sharing them [VITO]. The tool was used by HBM data providers participating in the real-life mixtures study to prepare their datasets for use in an end-to-end data exchange between HBM data providers and the MCRA modelling platform (hosted and run at RIVM) in the context of P6.2.3 (real life mixtures) and T8.3 (integrative models). For that purpose, the HBM4EU harmonized data format was mapped on the internal MCRA data model [VITO and WR]. An offline version of a software tool to calculate derived variables and summary statistics from individual HBM data has been developed. The web-based version was made available December 2024.

This workflow and tooling are the basis for harmonization and quality control of newly generated datasets added to the PEH data platform or to IPCHEM. They will also be used to add HBM datasets newly generated in PARC to the PEH data platform.

Collaboration is established with other tasks, activities and projects generating or using HBM data, including 4.1.1 projects (general HBM survey, occupational HBM studies), 4.1.3 (HBM Guidance Values) and 4.1.4 (HBM Data Analysis) in WP4, P6.2.3.a on real life mixtures and T8.3 (integrative risk modelling) to address their concrete use cases.

Further collaboration with IPCHEM staff was maintained through regular follow-up meetings (18/06/2024; 09/12/2024), to discuss further the practicalities and improvements needed for effective data exchange.

The work on the HBM data landscape is finalised [lead: VITO, contributions of JSI, WR, MU, and the IPCHEM team]. Main existing platforms identified in the EU that can host HBM data from different sources, are the PEH platform and IPCHEM. Operational definitions are proposed for HBM core occurrence datasets and extended datasets. An 'as is' FIP for the PEH platform was drafted by VITO, and one for IPCHEM by the JRC. The report R-HBMdatasets.1 *HBM data landscape* was delivered M30.

The assessment of feasibility and added value of federated systems for privacy-preserving analysis was finalized and the report R-HBMdatasets.2 - *Assessment of federated systems for*

privacy-preserving analysis was delivered M30 (lead: VITO, contributions of WR, UU, MU). While federated analysis presents a promising solution for analyzing decentralized data, significant challenges have emerged. Firstly, the complexity of IT infrastructure required for federated systems obliges each participating institution to establish and maintain its own server, security protocols, and communication interfaces leading to resource-heavy demands (technical expertise and financial investment). Furthermore, the current limitations of federated tools, particularly their capacity for handling complex statistical methods, restrict their practical utility in HBM data analysis. Lastly, federated analysis often struggles with the non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) nature of data, which can lead to convergence issues, further undermining its feasibility. Therefore, the decision was made to not adopt federated analysis to maintain operational efficiency and data quality. Hence, no use-case for a federated system will be established.

The metadata schema and template for HBM data, developed in HBM4EU, is being improved for further use in PARC. A series of metadata workshops was kickstarted in a workshop in Brussels on 20/09/2023, and the last one was held on March 15, 2024. This process is led by VITO and GFF, and includes all the partners in this project, the members of the data management team of T4.1 and IPCHEM. The content of the HBM metadata was defined [lead: VITO, contributions of MU, JSI, ISSeP, UBA], with input from WP9 for the analytical information. For the implementation of the metadata a customized PARC metadata collection tool is being developed (VITO).

VITO has finalised the conceptual part of the HBM ontology work, including the metadata dependencies and the technical datamodel. The overall model has been formalised in LinkML and has been used to create FAIR project configurations and FAIR metadata records for the relevant PARC projects and datasets, as well as to generate a Python library that is used to interact with the LinkML-based metadata and data artefacts. UoB, JSI and VITO are working on an expert review of the conceptual ontology to come to a formal, semantic representation of the HBM ontology. Common vocabularies have been identified for semantically linking HBM datasets to international standards, such as International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) and Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS). Links from the PARC HBM data format to the I-Adopt ontology have been modelled, providing a clean interoperability layer for the properties defined in the PARC catalogue of variables.

The first validated versions of these vocabularies have been contributed to the skosmos (<https://www.skosmos.org/>) hosting environment, a vocabulary publication infrastructure setup and provided by MU at <https://vocabs.eirene.eu/>. In collaboration with the P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO project, JSI developed a tailored tool (application) for GIS analyses of privacy sensitive data, which will enable derivation of spatially resolved (environmental) data by HBM data providers without sharing the geocodes of study participants. In addition, the parameters for extraction were defined and an update of the codebook was made including the geospatial variables. The functionality of the tool was tested internally by the project partners (VITO, JSI, UBA, MU). Demonstration of the tool was part of the 'FAIR data and databases' training, afterwards, a video tutorial for potential users of the tool was also prepared.

An online meeting was organized 06/05/2024 between the project on HBM (P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO) and environmental data (P7.2.2.a) to make connection and link activities (VITO, MU, JSI, T4.2 and T4.3 leads).

A consolidated PARC biomarker list, extended with both exposure markers and effect markers, has been established and published as a curated PARC resource in a format that integrates both with the PARC HBM LinkML data model and interoperability-oriented resources like the I-Adopt ontology (VITO). It is linked to existing chemical identifiers (see 7.2.4 'Identifiers for chemical entities', protein identifiers), using expert knowledge, various online resources (e.g. EBI,

Pubchem, ChEBI) and the Natural Language Processing (NLP) tool developed by IISPV in T7.3 to extract links from existing sources. [VITO].

First discussions were held with the Molgenis staff to explore the use of this software for the generation of variable catalogues for the questionnaire information collected through HBM studies available in the PEH Data Platform (VITO). A pilot study to evaluate if this tool could be used as well for the newly generated HBM datasets in PARC is under discussion. The pilot study could include 4 HBM4EU Aligned Studies in teenagers already available in the PEH Data Platform, that is GerES V (UBA), CELSPAC teenagers (MU), SLO CRP (JSI) and FLEHS IV (VITO).

Apart from the specific meetings mentioned in the text above, an overall online project meeting was held 17 September 2024 (participants: VITO, WR, MU, ISSeP, UU, UBA, JSI). Linked to the physical annual WP7 meeting, a technical project meeting was organized (October 4, participants: VITO, MU, ISSeP, JSI).

Dissemination activities:

- Presentation “Towards FAIR HBM data” at ISES Europe conference that took place 19-21 March 2024 in Berlin, Germany (VITO).
- PARC Training Course on “FAIR data and databases” that took place 22-24 May 2024 in Ljubljana, Slovenia (JSI, VITO, MU, UoB).
- Presentation “Enhancing access to HBM data in Europe: the development and utility of the European HBM dashboard” at ISES conference that took place 20-24 October 2024 in Montreal, Canada (VITO).
- Presentation “Towards interoperable modelling tools for integrative RA – the PARC model network approach” at EuroTox conference that took place September 8 – 11 in Copenhagen, Denmark (WR)

➤ A7.2.1 – Mapping the PARC Data Landscape

The landscaping activities in Y3 were under dedicated project or clusters. For the HBM and environmental data, reports on the respective data landscape have been finalized (HBM) or are under preparation (environmental data). See activities in P7.2.2a and P7.2.2b. [leads: UOB, UL-LACDR Contributors:MU, ANSES, EFSA, EV-ILVO, IISPV, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, KI, NIVA, UFZ, UNILU, UU-IRAS, UZIS, VITO].

The landscaping of toxicology data is taking place under the toxicology cluster, led by UoB and UL-LACDR, including the preparation of the FIPs for toxicology; supplementing this, a survey has been prepared and circulated by WP9 [MU].

For the purpose of integrating HBM with environmental and other geospatial data, a tailored tool for GIS analyses of privacy sensitive data was developed (in Collaboration with the P4.1.4.2.a_Y1 project, see also P7.2.2.b_Y1).

A preliminary mapping of resources relevant to non-target screening analysis was carried out in close collaboration with WP7 and T4.3, and the resources were assessed for their relevance for PARC (for further information on the follow-up action of this mapping, see sections 7.2.3 and 7.2.4). The inventory survey of chemicals in products was carried out within the T6.4, with the support of WP7. Currently, WP7 is reviewing the results of the survey in collaboration with WP9, and prioritization of resources and the assessment of FAIRness will follow.

The activities at the EC level related to the EU Common Platform for Data on Chemicals (EU-CPDC) roadmap, were followed up.

➤ A7.2.2 – PARC FAIR data hub¹⁴

The architecture of the PARC Data Hub was refined to incorporate rich FAIR semantic metadata. This was a critical step towards enhancing the interoperability of the platform across different modules, ensuring that data can flow seamlessly between them. One of the main goals was to find ways to improve the data's reusability and accessibility by embedding semantic metadata that adheres to FAIR standards. This development is particularly important for integrating data from varied sources into a unified system that supports chemical RA.

Prototyping and Partial Development of Specific Use-Case Challenges

Prototyping was a key focus, aimed at assessing the feasibility of different technological approaches. Specific examples include:

- **UI Development for Metadata Capture:** The development team explored ways to create a user-friendly UI for capturing rich metadata. While generic tools like Cedar and Describo were tested, they were found to be overly complex, cumbersome, and non-intuitive for certain use cases, leading to repetitive tasks that could slow down workflows. For example, these tools required users to perform time-consuming steps for metadata input, making them unsuitable for quick data entry in high-frequency data generation environments.
- **CKAN Extensions:** Prototyping also involved testing CKAN extensions to improve the system's ability to handle specific requirements. For instance, a plugin to support geospatial metadata standards was tested, aiming to ensure that the platform could adequately handle geographic data, which is crucial for environmental monitoring and CRA activities. Additionally, another CKAN plugin was explored for evaluating how effectively the system could extend its support for broader metadata types.

The first version of the Data Hub Portal was created. This included:

- **User Interface and Layout Design:** A clean and intuitive design was implemented to ensure ease of navigation for users, including researchers, regulators, and data publishers.
- **Information Architecture:** A well-structured navigation system was introduced, guiding users efficiently through different sections of the portal.
- **Hosting and Domain Setup:** The technical infrastructure, including hosting services and domain management, was established, ensuring the stability of the platform.
- **Deployment Workflow:** A full deployment workflow was created, guiding the process from code development to a working production system. This was essential in moving the platform from a development stage to an operational state.

The metadata repository service was developed using CKAN, an open-source data catalog system widely used in the research and regulatory community. CKAN provides basic functionality for managing metadata and supports the DCAT API for data catalog interoperability. However, additional customizations were required, including:

- **Filters:** Custom filters were introduced to allow users to search for domain-specific data quickly.
- **Metadata Standards:** Modifications were made to accommodate domain-specific metadata standards, ensuring the system could handle chemical RA data effectively.
- **Search Capabilities:** Custom search capabilities were implemented to allow users to find data based on specific criteria, such as chemicals, biomarkers, or environmental

¹⁴ Previous A.7.2.2 title: Implement a PARC FAIR data hub

factors. The repository was publicly deployed with basic UI customizations, and an organizational structure was set up, including the formation of groups and institutions to govern access and usage.

The Chemical RA Landscaping Dashboards were developed to support the visualization and management of CRA-related data. Two primary dashboards were created:

- **HBM Laboratories Dashboard:** This dashboard was designed to visualize the inventory of HBM laboratories. Several iterations were made to design lab overviews, detail pages, and filtering options, developed in collaboration with WP9. Data curation was a significant focus here:
 - a. **Data Normalization and Clean-up:** Received datasets were normalized and cleaned to ensure consistency across various data sources.
 - b. **Harmonization of Vocabularies:** Vocabularies were harmonized by mapping them to crosscutting vocabularies for matrices, chemicals, and biomarkers. This step was essential for ensuring that data could be compared and used effectively across different studies.
 - c. **Automated Data Ingestion Pipeline:** An automated data ingestion pipeline was developed to handle laboratory data. This allowed for the seamless updating and refreshing of database content, ensuring that data remains current and accurate over time.
- **Environmental Monitoring Networks Dashboard:** A second dashboard was created to visualize the inventory of environmental monitoring networks, based on landscaping activities conducted under WP9 and WP7. A prototype for data visualization was implemented using PowerBI, enabling users to analyze environmental data interactively.

FAIR Tools Development

To support the hosting of semantic artifacts, the infrastructure for deploying SKOSMOS was prepared. SKOSMOS is an open-source system used for managing and interacting with SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) vocabularies. Several key steps were taken:

- **In-house Deployment:** SKOSMOS was deployed internally, ensuring that it could host and manage the vocabularies needed for the Data Hub (vocabs.eirene.eu).
- **Governing Procedures:** Procedures for governing the vocabularies were established, and the system was made ready to host the first vocabularies approved by WP7.
- **Community Engagement:** Suggestions were provided to the open-source community for creating a dockerized version of SKOSMOS, as the out-of-the-box installation faced several inconsistencies. These improvements aim to streamline the deployment process for future users of the system.

A Milestone MS12: Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD has been submitted.

➤ A7.2.3 Solutions for FAIR data: development and implementation¹⁵

After completing the FAIRification training and FAIR assessment actions according to the GFF-lead 3-Point FAIRification Framework, a PARC Specific FAIRification methodology was developed that builds upon and goes beyond the 3-Point FAIRification Framework. The goal of

¹⁵ Previous A.7.2.3 title: Concrete solutions will further be elaborated and implemented based on specific use cases

this methodology is to facilitate the adoption of PARC FAIR practices and recommendations without each researcher having to be aware of the underlying complexities of the 3PFFramework. This is now being implemented as both a technical data structure and a set of tools that facilitate interaction with the data.

At the same time, with the FAIR Steering and Implementation teams, we have started specialised FAIR Data communities on PARCopedia where we will be building up a Body of Knowledge containing guidance and documentation on research data management, introducing a generic but holistic and integrated approach to standards adoption, DMP creation and data FAIRification, tailored to the PARC researchers.

Apart from the work reported in the projects P7.2.2.a and P7.2.2.b, work started also in other data domains (i.e., on toxicological data):

- Together with WP5 (as data provider), WP6 and WP8 (as data users) a Working group was set up to coordinate and implement work on harmonised templates for standard toxicological data. For short term purposes existing templates (i.e., templates from dose-response data, Hazard characterization, Relative potency from the MCRA platform) are used for internal PARC data exchange, whereas the process is ongoing to elaborate long term harmonised templates taking into account FAIR requirements, regulatory and scientific needs [lead: IISPV/UOB, contributors: WR, UL-LACDR, VITO].
- An action on FAIRification of omics data has been identified. [lead: UL-LACDR; participants: UOB, IISPV, UG-PL, ISS] The different PARC activities and projects using and/or generating omics data are inventorised, and the omics data working group has been established that has finalized a concrete workplan on (re)use of omics data for implementation in Y3-Y4. UL-LACDR started drafting an overview of existing data approaches/templates/repositories. This working group identified the need to include work on the use of omics data in a regulatory context. In parallel, UL-LACDR has started working on an implementation of the current OECD Transcriptomic Reporting Framework (TRF) and investigated suitability to extend the template to include TXGmapr/WGCNA as analysis step, in the context of the data used for P5.3.1.a_Y1 representing one of the first possible case studies of the working group.
- Development of the metadata capture template for the in vitro studies in WP5 Task 5.1 has been progressed, including mapping of the existing templates and approaches (ISATab, ToxTemp, MCRA etc.) and an approach to codify the common aspects into pick-lists (e.g., the chemicals tested, the endpoints being utilized in Task 5.1) and to separate information that is needed once versus metadata needed each time the experiment is performed, as a means to streamline the metadata capture process. The refined templates are currently being tested and will be further iterated and extended to other endpoints in WP5 over the rest of Y3 (UoB in close collaboration with BFR from WP5).
- KI and UG-PL have worked on the FAIRification of AOPs. In exchanges and meetings both with PARC projects (P6.1.1.a) as well as with the 'FAIR AOPs Cluster' [also attended by VITO, IISPV, UoB], it has been agreed to collaborate on possible improvements in AOP-Wiki 3.0, as well as on longer term FAIRification of AOP-Wiki (i.e., development of metadata schema of AOP Wiki and gap/issue identification, identification of 3rd party bodies needs and current status on AOP Wiki usage and data management). IISPV has presented to 'FAIR AOPs Cluster' its ongoing activity of AOPwiki-Explorer (See section 7.3.3). The schema developed for the AOPwiki-Explorer and graph database has further been discussed with US EPA as basis for future collaboration. The working group on FAIRification of AOPs has finalised its concrete workplan for implementation. The current state of the AOP-Wiki data model and its FAIRness has been evaluated. An early-version FAIR Implementation Profile was used as a starting point.

- In May 2024, PARC members (TNO, UoB, UL-LACDR) facilitated a FIP development session in an ELIXIR workshop (<https://www.aanmelder.nl/intoxicom2024firstworkshop>) focusing on Toxicological data and AOPs (event notes: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ogYAZFc-AHI_7OANZIGNvIxMc7RdAa00snh5_eJgz9k/edit#heading=h.rbbpjpsy0aagx). Among the activities underway from this are updating of the FAIRsharing records for key FAIR Enabling Resources relevant to toxicology that will be utilised in PARC, and initiation of some FAIR Cookbook recipes for key steps in FAIRification of toxicology data. This is ongoing work.
- Collaboration with WP8 – aligning work on toolboxes, models and FAIR data: A dedicated meeting was held with the Task leads of T8.1 - *Safe and Sustainable by Design* and with the responsables for SSbD of DG RTD on needs for data accessibility and the scope of the collaboration with WP7 [participants: KI, VITO, MU, UOB]. Meetings of T8.1 were attended by the data liaison [KI]. A publication on FAIR data principles and applications within the SSbD framework is currently underway, featuring collaboration among data liaisons from WP7, Task 7.2, and the dedicated team of Task 8.1, focusing on the FAIRification of the toolbox [AUTH]. For T8.2 EWS a structured dataset info file with high level information was drafted by the data liaison. No support from WP7 was requested yet at this point, but this is expected from Y3 onwards. WP7 data liaisons attended task level meetings of T8.3. A dedicated use case has been set up on use of HBM data in the MCRA model as a practical step up to further integration of data and models. NIVA developed and tested a workflow for importing experimental ecotoxicological data into NIVA Routine Assets database (RAdb) using standardized reporting templates (xlsx and prototype web-based interface). NIVA RAdb can be used as a data repository and FAIRification resource of data in PARC (T7.2), and reuse in case studies (WP6, WP7 and WP8). It will be used in the Source to Outcome Predictor and other integration tools of PARC (T8.3) and for assessments in A6.4.1. The prototype has been tested for dose-response data on national environmental monitoring data from Norway. UFZ constructed the ChEOS-mix graph database infrastructure, which integrates monitoring data sourced from the NORMAN database system alongside hazard information derived from the ECOTOX database and the IRFM QSAR models to identify chemical mixtures of concern in European surface waters. ChEOS-mix offers the flexibility required to assimilate additional data from various domains aims to align with FAIR principles. It is designed as an open-access resource, allowing external parties, including other PARC partners and entities beyond PARC, to utilize this database.
- JSI has been working on a national data repository and processing infrastructure for HBM and environmental data. A conceptual data architecture model was developed. It will further be extended to serve as one of the data hub services to link internal exposure (HBM) data and geospatial (environmental) data within PARC.
- MU led discussions with T4.3 on the FAIR non-target screening data management. A mapping of major resources was carried out in close collaboration of WP7, WP9, T4.3, and the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) platform has been identified as a potential and sustainable platform to store and manage non-target exposome data. Following this, an initiation meeting with EMBL as a strategic partner was organized to initiate discussions on (meta)data structures, data processing pipelines, and data repository requirements, as well as discussions with the ELIXIR community to provide for the sustainability of the developed solutions.
- In addition to the above-mentioned clusters (AOPs, OMICS, Regulatory) also the Imaging cluster has been established (lead: UL-LACDR) and a NTS cluster will be established at the end of Y3. These clusters are now organized as subclusters in one big Toxicology cluster (leads: Iseult Lynch (UoB) and Gerhard Burger (UL-LACDR), (partners TNO,

AUTH, EI, GO FAIR / LACDR, IISPV, Inserm, ISS, MU, NIVA, TNO) and meet regularly for planning and progress updates. The current main task is the inventory of Toxicology resources and establishments of as-is FIPS which will extend into Y4 also to incorporate the result from the WP9 questionnaire on Toxicology resources.

The bottom-up work in domain-specific use cases and clusters, and carried out in the WP7 projects, is now being expanded by applying the lessons learned to generic developments at the overall PARC level that enable the FAIRification of generic life sciences observational data, not just limited to for instance pure HBM data processing. These developments are still a work in progress, but they rely on the work that was completed in Y2 and Y3: on the one hand the theoretical Reference FAIR Implementation Profile work that allowed us to identify the missing FAIR Enabling Resources and on the other hand the workshops with domain experts in the pilot domains (HBM and ENV) that gave us both vocabulary artefacts to publish and practical insights into the practical needs of data stakeholders.

Active domains/clusters/use case are those of HBM data, ENV data, TOX data, Interoperability with IPCHEM / CDPC, FAIRification of omics data, FAIRification of AOPs and Mixture exposure and RA, while topics where we are exploring the needs and our potential for contributing include the T8.3 Integrative Modelling Network and the T8.2 Early Warning Systems Framework.

➤ A7.2.4 Standards and harmonisation¹⁶

The Semantic Implementation Team (SIT) was established to further elaborate on – among other things – a common PARC data model and vocabulary. Although in Y3 a number of artefact versions (e.g., reference vocabularies, metadata schema) have been completed, for many of them the final -and formal- versions are still a work in progress; all are at different stages of maturity and completion. A hosting environment (SKOSMOS) has been setup [MU] and allows anyone to contribute and publish verified vocabularies and that is the best location to check up on the latest state of the art in terms of completed raw PARC data standards and harmonisation efforts. Collaboration on the artefacts themselves happens mostly in either the PARC (<https://github.com/eu-parc>) or other, dedicated, github repositories.

One specific overarching use case is the need for a standardised way to reference PARC projects or tasks as the source of datasets or models. In a FAIR context, this should be done using globally accessible, dereferenceable identifiers for PARC research activities similarly to how ORCID IDs are used to refer to persons and RORs for organisations. We are now evaluating the adoption of the FAIRCORE4EOSC sanctioned RAiD Identifier (and metadata) standard (<https://raid.org>) for this use case, with a backup plan being to generate nanopublications for each project so that there is a unique globally resolvable ID for each PARC project.

CRA domains vocabulary: A draft of PARC CRA domains structure and its link with the RA process was outlined, but more discussions need to take place to narrow the objectives and scope of the CRA domains vocabulary activity. Our key discussion points revolved around refining the CRA vocabulary initiative—deciding whether it should mirror the four steps of RA process, multiple CRA PARC domains, or both, what level of granularity, and what would be the further use (and users group) of the vocabulary. We've chosen a modular approach, starting with mapping the HBM domain, PCRA and HBM4EU/PEH structure, link the core concepts to ontologies, doing the same for the environmental domain and see how they can be linked. This ontology should serve as a basis for the PARC FAIR Data Hub browser of several CRA domains' (meta)data. This process might be supported by existing projects for HBM and environmental

¹⁶ The number and title of activity A7.2.4 was not included in the AWPY1 and SRIA. This title has been added between the submission of the AWP Y1 and the submission of the ASR Y1 and will be added in AWPY2 and its Annex PARC Portfolio project.

domain (7.2.2.a and 7.2.2.b). Simultaneously, other domains are mapped within specific clusters, to which the focus shifted in Y2 and Y3. [lead: MU; participants: VITO, JSI, IISPV, UoB, UFZ, WR].

- Identifiers for chemical entities: The community has collaboratively proposed a comprehensive set of chemical identifiers, including CAS number, InChI, InChI Key, SMILES, IUPAC Name, PubChem ID, EC number, etc., to unequivocally identify chemical compounds, and to meet regulatory chemical identity requirements. Resources such as ChEBI, PubChem, and a text mining tool by T7.3 have been discussed and selected to facilitate identifier linkage. Finally, ChEBI was identified as a main resource to link the identifiers to chemical compounds, including biomarkers. A list of around 1500 environmentally significant chemicals, identified through 7.2.2.a project and 7.2.1 activity (NORMAN, GENASIS, IPCHEM), has been compiled, and a classification system based on structure, use, and properties of these chemicals was proposed. A subselection of HBM relevant compounds, has been approved and linked to the respective identifiers and meta-information (such as their role as a biomarker and their links to lab analysis results). See also P7.2.2.a and P7.2.2.b for specific lists of chemicals. [MU, VITO, IISPV].
- HBM Ontology: see P7.2.2.b.
- NIVA developed controlled vocabularies to report experimental ecotoxicological data. Vocabularies are based on PUBCHEM, NCBI, OBO, BRENDA, AOPwiki and other ontologies from OLS and inhouse terminology/nomenclature. [partners involved: NIVA]
- Aggregated exposure modelling – the conceptual model developed under WP8 by domain experts is followed up in the SIT meetings for further development of a corresponding ontology [WR].
- The development of the PBPK ontology, initiated in 2023, has continued into this year with IISPV progressing from conceptualization to implementation. Over 500 terms related to kinetic modeling were collected, enriched with descriptions, mapped to existing ontologies, and structured into classes and properties. The ontology, created using the ROBOT tool and converted with the Ontology Development Kit (ODK), is available as an open-source resource on GitHub under the name "pkonto," with its first version published. It is now integrated into PBPK modeling workflows and reporting templates for tasks T8.3 and T6.2 (Led by WR). Knowledge modelling and tool developments activities are supported by T7.3.4. A two-day training workshop in October 2024, led by WP6 and WP8, trained the PARC community in PBPK model harmonization. Conceptual data model enabling to link internal exposure (HBM) data with spatially resolved (environmental) data (see P7.2.2.b) [JSI]

A CRA Model inventory is part of the aggregated exposure research strategy as described in the AD6.3 Roadmap deliverable (https://www.eu-parc.eu/sites/default/files/2023-08/PARC_AD6.3.pdf)

This is a work in progress. [IISPV, WR]

- The FIP2DMP Controlled Vocabularies are supporting resources for the PARC Project DMP tooling that is being developed in the FAIR Implementation Team. A first version is finished and published, but it will continue to evolve to address DMP needs that are still being investigated [TNO, UoB, GFF].
- Mapping of toxicology experimental approaches (sample preparation, observations / measurements of cell / organism / animal response to toxicant challenge) to the SOSA ontology, and to the NERC Vocabularies for Instrument types and Assays as part of an initial assessment of the cross-domain transferability of established models (mapped to DDI-CDI framework via the 2nd Dagstuhl workshop on the WorldFAIR CDIF. These mappings will form the basis of the metadata schema, controlled vocabularies, metadata dependencies and the technical data model for the Toxicology Cluster [UoB], as well as facilitating integration across Toxicology, Environment and HBM datasets to facilitate CRA.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

Note on allocation of resources: allocation of activities of FST and FIT to 7.1.3 or 7.2.3 was sometimes less clear leading to partners allocating PMs to both or one of both Tasks. From AWPY3 onwards use case identification and management is therefore integrated in 7.2.3

Due to reorganization of the project team at VITO (new project leader, people leaving and newly hired in the team), an extension of 6 months was requested for the P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO project (from M42 to M48).

The assessment of the FAIRness of priority resources, and consequently the preparation of the report on the environmental data landscape, has been delayed due to its reliance on extensive training provided by GFF at the beginning of the project. Additionally, a need to extend the duration of the metadata schema workshops has been identified by the project partners to thoroughly discuss the metadata requirements and structure for chemical occurrence data. Therefore, an extension of 6 months (from M36 to M42) for P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment was requested to allow sufficient discussions with domain experts, feedback from stakeholders, and adequate time to finalize the project reports.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
MS12	Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD	VITO	M24	05/09/2024 (M29)	There is a short delay due to the PARC WP7 ambition of creating detailed and technical specifications together with the main architecture. The task encountered some technical challenges, since the proper way to implement the FAIR principles is still evolving, and indeed FAIRification is often discussed in terms of “flying the plane whilst still building it. Many of the potential tools for supporting FAIRification are only prototypes and themselves require a lot of technical development and testing before they can be integrated into the PARC Data Hub. The expected plug-and-play solutions have not materialised, requiring adaptation of our expectations and approach. There was lack of expertise within the WP7 team on the technical aspects of FAIR implementation and FAIR orchestration, that required intensive and ongoing training. The training by doing approach covered

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
					<p>multiple activities related to implementation of FAIR principles at the technological level and was required to be able to successfully finish the specification of the architecture and the detailed design of the PARC FAIR DataHub.</p> <p>Despite the short delay in finishing the design and architecture of the PARC Data Hub (and given that it is anyway a living document), implementation of the well-defined modules has already started, namely the modules on Chemical RA dashboards for laboratories and environmental monitoring networks. This work is done in collaboration with WP9, and provides a blueprint for implementation of other data-rich modules.</p>

1.2.7.3 Task 7.3. Innovative analyses

Leader: IISPV (ES), UOB (UK)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), IMROH (CR), INRS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), KWR (NL), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UL-LACDR (NL), UNIVIE (AT), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), VITO (BE), WR (NL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

- A7.3.1 Innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

Lead: VITO, Co-lead: AUTH

(Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, IISPV, KI, ANSES, UFZ, IMROH, INRS, UOB, UL-LACDR, UNIVIE, NIVA, MU, WR)

In Y2, the scoping review on innovative methods for combining heterogeneous data (“Advancing RA through Heterogeneous Data Integration: Challenges, Methodologies, and Future Trends”) was finished, and for the implementation and evaluation of these methods, 5 use cases have been defined, based on inputs from WP4, 5, 6 and 8. These 5 use cases involve the integration of different data sources within or across domains, and thus the variability and uncertainty of heterogeneous data need to be considered, which is consistent with the overall goal of T7.3 and a potential synergy with A7.3.2, and implementation got underway during Y3 as follows:

Use case 1 (lead: AUTH, partners involved: VITO, INRS, IMROH, UoB): This use case deals with the integration of metabolomics data from multiple cohorts and/or multiple technologies (e.g., LC-MS AND NMR). Epidemiological data, HBM data and metabolomics data will be combined and

linked with health outcome information. Appropriate statistical tools as proposed in the scoping review will be integrated into a pipeline for data analysis and probabilistic machine learning models development. VITO will focus on a metabo-lipidomics analysis to unravel mechanisms underlying the association between chemical mixture exposure and immune-related effect markers. The case study will use metabolomics and lipidomics measured by both LC-MS and NMR and will cover methodologies for different levels of data integration, 1) the analysis of a broad chemical mixture including exposure biomarkers measured in blood and/or urine 2) the combined (within-omics) analysis of high-dimensional omics measurements from different technologies (LC-MS and NMR), 3) the (cross-omics) integration of multiple omics layers (metabolomics and lipidomics). Literature on suitable methods has been collected, but analyses only started end 2024 due to delays in finding a PhD student working on this topic.

Use case 2 (lead: VITO, partners involved: AUTH, ANSES, IISPV, JSI, WR, KWR): This use case, linked to T6.3.2 (Real-life mixtures project), will evaluate statistical methods for mediation analysis which can integrate multi-dimensional exposure, biomarker, and health outcome data. The application of such multivariate mediation methods can help to unravel biological mechanisms as they enable the assessment of combined effects and relative importance of the various mixture components and the identification of relevant biomarkers in the pathway between exposure and health effect. Part 1 of this use case (finished) has focused on the setting of a single exposure biomarker, because many of the existing multivariate mediation methods cannot handle multiple exposures (in the sense that they don't do penalization/variable selection on exposures). This use case also handled the pooling of data from two studies. In addition to single-mediator models, four different multiple-mediator methods have been applied and evaluated (Clark-Boucher et al., 2023): HDMA, mediation analysis via fixed effect model (MedFix), the BSLMM, and HDMM. Part 2 of this use case will integrate data from a hotspot (3M study in Zwijndrecht) and a reference population (FLEHS IV) and will focus on methods which can handle multiple mediators as well as multiple exposure biomarkers and will be performed by a PhD student (starting November 2024).

Use case 3 (Lead: UL-LACDR, partners involved: UoB): This use case will deal with innovative methods for multi-omics integration. Data from in vitro assays including transcriptomics, metabolomics, and phenotypic imaging data will be used. UL-LACDR had significant delays for this use case because of difficulties in hiring personnel. This has been solved for Y4 as detailed in the planning.

Use case 4 (Lead: NIVA, partners involved: IISPV): This use case concerns heterogeneous multi-year environmental data that can support integrated and innovative analysis solutions. Exposure data from the Arctic and North Sea will be combined with effects data for Arctic and surrogate marine species to develop a STOP. The data sets represent potential illustrations for how the conceptual framework of the AEP and the AOP can be combined into a STOP. Additional data sets from the exposure (i.e. AEP) and the effects continuum (i.e. AOP) have been used to develop other innovative analysis solutions (e.g. multivariate analysis).

Use case 5 (Lead UoB, partners involved: IISPV): This use case is on the enrichment of existing background knowledge resources for chemical RA through multi-modal data analysis.

Development of scientific knowledge and provenance networks has consisted of adding to efforts to FAIRify existing AOP resources as a necessary pre-requisite. We have linked up with several other teams interested in this, organised around the AOPWiki community, referred to as the AOP Cluster. Initial findings from joint landscaping show that requirements for building FAIR knowledge networks first requires appropriate extraction and representation of entities from e.g. AOPWiki, since these are currently largely stored in text. Our AOPWiki-Explorer software provides an initial solution for extracting, representing, and querying AOP data based on extraction of entities based on the BERN2 model. Several works are being developed in the AOP Cluster community on this

task, ranging from direct AOPWiki extraction to unified extraction and integration with PubMed and other resources. A position and landscaping paper is currently being written amongst the grouped stakeholders in the AOP Cluster working group on this subject, to describe existing approaches and set a future direction. This has also led to initial work to create a unified ontology for AOP representation, which we will align to the PARC model.

AOPBot was developed (7.3.3) to extract relevant entities from biomedical texts, with a primary use-case on pubmed. Y3 has extended capabilities of this software for rule-based extraction of entities, providing dual modes for different settings. Work is on-going to implement grammatical rule extraction of named relations from text, which will then be transitively exploded into networks and validated (though this validation requires structural availability of verified AOPWiki data. In addition to the existing AOPBot information extraction methods, we have developed a new entity linkage approach based on a semantic search approach and expect this to be submitted as a publication very soon. This contributes integration of state of the art LLM-based approaches to entity linkage with ontological approaches to knowledge representation, providing a background knowledge basis for the entity extraction process itself. We expect the approach to be especially applicable to the cases of differentiating complex chemical names and other relevant entities for enriching AOPs (as well as the extraction of entities from AOPWiki text itself, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7: A new entity linkage approach based on a semantic search has been developed to support differentiation of complex chemical names and other relevant entities for enriching AOPs.

Required integration of digital phenotyping data has occurred based on existing resources, integrating Kafkas 2021 with Collier 2022, creating a large integrated resource describing phenotypes for common and rare diseases, characterising and clinically validating it (which had not previously been done). This appears alongside an effort to capture multi-perspective understandings of disease based on the associative methods developed and is published in

(Slater 2024). These resources can be integrated into linked AOP representations when methodological efforts surrounding representation of AOPs produce those semantic artefacts. Furthermore, this work provides a model for integrating and producing these models for other entity interactions, which will be undertaken on the basis of the prioritised chemicals.

This is occurring alongside development of capability for associative analysis of text. While the work mentioned in the previous step uses existing work, especially in the human phenotyping space, we discovered that methodological considerations have not been well explored. The findings of our investigation show that choices of e.g., correlation coefficient, NER method, and association cut-off, weigh heavily upon the background knowledge base results, etc, and, critically, any subsequent downstream analysis. This is an interesting finding given that this type of derived associative knowledgebase is used in a wide range of biomedical tasks, including gene enrichment, protein-protein interaction, differential diagnosis, etc., and of course will form the basis of knowledge enrichment for AOPs (in addition to the grammatical relation extraction model (though this has its own parameterisation considerations)). This work is being undertaken in the context of developing a knowledge resource based on phenotype prevalence in human populations (which will be integrated as another source of background information. Work is ongoing to formalise these results, including consideration of chemical entities and AOP datasets: we expect that once AOPWiki has been FAIR-ified and is directly queryable for entities, and critically that it has been verified, it can be used as a ground truth basis for downstream tasks that utilise it.

- A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA

Partners involved: IISPV, ANSES, AUTH, ISSeP, JSI, KWR, NIVA, UL-LACDR, UU, UZIS, VITO, WR, MU, UoB

An inventory of methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification will be made, and methods selected as a basis for harmonisation in RA. For their implementation and evaluation use cases will be identified for exposure, hazard, risk and HIA, and IATAs, and started, in collaboration with WP4, 5, 6.

The planned scoping review has been completed. Different groups related to prioritized outcomes were constituted: a CG with expertise in methods for uncertainty analysis; six specialty groups for exposure, hazard, human health risk characterization, health impact assessment (HIA), IATAs and ERA. The groups comprising IISPV, ANSES, AUTH, KWR, VITO, WR, MU, UU actively participated in the regular discussion and significantly contributed to drafting and developing of this scoping studies. This collaborative work will result in a manuscript. Selection of use cases has already been started for each specialty group in collaboration with WP6 and WP8, and some initial case studies have already been started.

The following case studies are underway, and are at different stage of development:

PFAS uncertainty analysis (lead MU, participating partners: IISPV, WR)

To fulfil the main aim of the activity A7.3.2, MU developed and designed a case study “Assessment of uncertainty in PBPK models of PFAS exposure in humans and reverse dosimetry (uncertainty in PFAS exposure)”. The aim of the case study is to establish and implement a selected PBPK model for exposure to PFAS for some subgroups from the European population and to use the PBPK model to link internal and external exposure. The main focus of the case study is on uncertainties through all workflow of the case study (in input data, model

parametrization, etc.) with the following implementation of the model and a method for uncertainty assessment on a user-friendly PARC platform (T8.3, e.g., MCRA).

Following activities have been completed:

- Data on 4 selected PFASs in European food and drinking water were collected. The data set encompasses over 7,000 records for PFOA, PFOS, PFHxS and PFNA, enabling to estimate statistical distributions of these compounds in different food items either dependent or independent on time. The EFSA – expo 2 codebook was used for the food classification.
- External (dietary) exposure model was finished. The model implements different options of treating uncertainty in input data (PFASs concentrations, food frequencies, portion sizes), including Monte-Carlo estimations and Fenton-Wilkinson approximations.
- Data request was approved and data on food frequencies and PFASs blood concentrations from 9 European countries were provided by the PEH platform.
- The selection process of the PBPK model for reverse dosimetry in teenagers was finished in coordination with T6.2.2 and the best suitable model was selected (the model being developed by RIVM).
- A preliminary version of a review of methods for sensitivity testing and uncertainty propagation was completed, suggesting a use of the Extended Fourier Amplitude Sensitivity Testing and Metropolis-Hastings Monte-Carlo Markov-Chain methods for an assessment of the PBK model parametrization sensitivity.

Ongoing activities consist of:

- a parametrization of the selected PBK model for teenagers in cooperation with T6.2.2,
- a development of a detailed uncertainty assessment strategy using the two methods mentioned above,
- a comparison of different methods of the uncertainty propagation within the results of the external exposure model
- a comparison of results of the PBK model reverse dosimetry with the results of the external exposure model.

Finally, the following activities will encompass:

- a thorough comparison of results of the reverse dosimetry with the results of external exposure modelling, including their uncertainties, distributions and discussion of the results, publishing of the first suggested paper,
- a selection of another model or an adaptation of the selected PBK model for the other suggested subpopulations (adults, pregnant women),
- second data request, modelling and publishing the second suggested paper.

Uncertainty analysis of Bioassays trigger values calculation (Lead KWR, Partners: IISPV)

In 2023-24, KWR lead this case study on Bioassay trigger values, focusing on drinking water. The case study was initiated by KWR that concerns the probability of having a harmful substance in tested water at an observed exceedance of an evidence-based trigger value in bioassays. This is done with a Bayesian analysis to assess bioassay performance. The major out of this work was a bioassay predictive values paper (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108733>).

➤ A7.3.3. Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data

• **P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV [M1-M60]**

(Lead: IISPV Partners involved: ANSES, AUTH, ISSeP, JSI, KWR, NIVA, UL-LACDR, UU, UZIS, VITO, MU)

Based on scoping study and inventory of different text-mining approaches applied in biological domain. A custom framework is designed following the initial workflow mentioned in Fig. 8. Following the workflow of AOP-BOT, modular components were proposed for independent development and later integration of modular components to build customizable framework. The first prototype of AOP-Bot first as a Python package is currently being developed by a team of software developers at IISPV. The development of different tools was broken down into 3 separate software components which are being independently developed as a modular component. The three components are as follows:

Fig. 8: A workflow of AI-based text mining tools used for the AOP development

Ranker: It helps in prioritizing the literature extracted using keywords and context given by the user and rank them based different ranking criteria. It will implement various methods like rule-based and context-based heuristic to rank the literature based on their usefulness for further processing.

Extractor: This component (separately developed as BotAnnotator) implements various NLP based information extraction algorithms ranging from rule-based and machine learning methods for Named Entity Recognition (NER) to relation extraction (RE) for extracting relations from natural text. The BotAnnotator also includes other tasks like entity linking, grounding, and entity normalization (with linked ontologies).

These components were initially developed individually, with the Ranker component leveraging deep learning embedding models to score abstracts based on the natural language context provided by the user. However, this method has a limitation: users must first extract a subset of articles based on keywords from PubMed or other resources, which might result in missing important articles.

The Extractor component leverages assembled NER tools in BotAnnotator to annotate documents and establish relationships between entities based on the co-occurrence of concepts in similar articles and sentences. Since defining relations solely based on concept co-occurrence is unreliable, a bidirectional encoder representations from transformers (BERT)-based deep learning model was also used to classify sentences mentioning biological concepts into different relation types. Fine-tuning the model on various relation types, however, limits the tool's flexibility for unobserved cases.

A combined framework called S²CIE (Syntactic, Semantic, and Contextual Information Extraction) was developed (Fig. 9). It leverages the BotAnnotator component for concept identification and open-source tools such as SciSpacy to perform segmentation and sentence-level annotation of articles. Sentence-level annotations for Part of Speech (POS), Lemma, and Dependency Graph provide flexibility to define rules for extraction using co-occurrence, dependency graph relations, and more. This framework also integrates context-based ranking to score articles after keyword and rule-based searches are performed.

In the initial AOP-Bot prototype, extraction was performed only on a subset of articles. With S²CIE, extraction is performed on the entire literature database of 33 million articles (and more) in real-time, providing flexibility for defining custom rules and integrating different rankers or classification models.

Fig. 9: Architecture of S²CIE information extraction framework

Visualization: This component provides different visualization supports for extracted and integrated data/information. As network-based information representation is widely adapted by the community, visualization component currently supports enriched network analysis. Co-occurrence based network visualization is developed separately and is available at (<https://github.com/Crispae/AOPbotvisualizer>). This visualization also integrated in S²CIE along with concept distribution and co-occurrence heatmap. Integration with other sources as plugin is under development and multiple resources have been assembled and structured as knowledge graph using FAIR principles. An information exchange schema for AOP is being developed to provide discrete scoring of AOP event using ontology assistance. This component also links AOPwikiExplorer helping with direct mapping available information of AOP-wiki. To calculate confidence in hypothesis and evidence, Omics data integration is currently developed (*UL-LACDR*), which will be integrated with AOP-BOT visualization.

AOP-FAIRification: This is a further integration in the tools for harmonization of AOP following the FAIR principles. AOP-sketchpad provides a bottom-up approach to build an AOP in FAIR way using nanopublication. The tool is under development.

Case studies for AOP developments: Various case studies are in different phases of development in collaboration with WP5 where these tools will be tested and used for the selected hazard endpoints.

AOP-helpFinder v2 (Inserm). To support the use of alternative methods in regulatory assessment of chemical risks, the concept of AOP constitutes an important toxicological tool. AOP represents a structured representation of existing knowledge, linking MIE initiated by a prototypical stressor that leads to a cascade of biological key event (KE) to an adverse outcome (AO). Biological information to develop such AOP is very dispersed in various data sources. To increase the chance of capturing relevant existing data to develop a new AOP, the AOP-helpFinder tool was recently implemented to assist researchers to design new AOP. Here, an updated version of AOP-helpFinder proposes novel functionalities. This work was done in collaboration with WP5.3.2a and WP8.2.4. The main one being the implementation of an automatic screening of the abstracts from the PubMed database to identify and extract event-event associations. In addition, a new scoring system was created to classify the identified co-occurred terms (stressor-event or event-event (which represent key event relationships) to help prioritization and support the weight of evidence approach, allowing a global assessment of the strength and reliability of the AOP. Moreover, to facilitate interpretation of the results, visualization options are also proposed. The AOP-helpFinder source code is fully accessible via GitHub, and searches can be performed via a web interface at <http://aop-helpfinder-v2.u-paris-sciences.fr/> (doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.108017.). A version 3 is ongoing with more data integration.

- A7.3.4 – Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

The objective of this activity is to identify emerging needs in PARC for innovative analyses on the one hand, and promising innovative techniques on the other hand. For this year, we have taken two case studies for the scoping study, which will be further refined and implemented in subsequent years.

For 7.3.4.a. Pharmacophore modeling using machine learning for screening blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeation of xenobiotics. This activity also complements other ongoing efforts within PARC, such as the data generated from project P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer and the development of computational tools for the early warning system in Task 8.2. During the 2023-24 period, significant efforts were made to collect additional chemical data; however, the anticipated data generation from the PARC project has faced minor delays. New data have been collected from P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK (IISPV), and more data from WP5 is expected in the coming year. Additionally, this activity has focused on improving the data processing pipeline, enhancing scaffold generation, and developing new pharmacophore fingerprint methods, including both receptor- and ligand-based approaches.

UU published the CPSign software for uncertainty modeling in QSAR with conformal prediction (Arvidsson et al. J Cheminformatics. 16, 75, 2024). UU developed and refined Predicted Target Profiles service, where chemical compounds are described with their predicted interactions to a large number of targets from ChEMBL ($n > 800$). The method uses Conformal Prediction and Venn-Abers predictors to account for uncertainty in modeling. An online service is being implemented and a manuscript is in preparation.

The UFZ developed and improved the deepFPlearn chemical-effect prediction approach, which now includes graph neural networks and comes with improved prediction performance. It associates the chemical based on its molecular structure to an endpoint of concern, like endocrine disruption.

The manuscript has been accepted for publication: deepFPlearn+: Enhancing Toxicity Prediction Across the Chemical Universe Using Graph Neural Networks; K. Soulios, P. Scheibe, M. Bernt, J. Hackermüller and J. Schor; Bioinformatics. (<https://zenodo.org/record/8146252>)

UoB have been exploring the potential for integration of hydrological data on flows / fluxes, especially those related to extreme weather events as a means to map likely exposures to legacy pollutants that are re-mobilised by extreme fluxes. This will feed into the EWS in WP8 and is being developed into a use case for implementation in AWPY4 and beyond, and will showcase the integration of currently disparate datasets to support innovative exposure-driven CRA.

Ontology development support

The development of the PBPK ontology, initiated in 2023, has continued into the current year to support T7.2.4 activities. Initially, IISPV began with the conceptualization of the proposed PBPK ontology and then advanced to the implementation phase. This phase involved collecting and organizing basic terminology related to various aspects of kinetic modeling, encompassing over 500 terms. These vocabularies were further enriched with textual descriptions, mapped to existing ontologies, and structured into classes, subclasses, and properties. Cross-referencing to publicly available ontologies was also performed.

The implementation was carried out using the ROBOT tool, with the ontology first drafted in an Excel format to facilitate mapping between the existing and newly created ontologies. The Ontology Development Kit (ODK) was employed to convert vocabularies into ontology form. The resulting PBPK ontology, named "pkonto," is an open-source resource, publicly accessible via GitHub, with the first version already published.

The ontology has now been integrated into the workflow of PBPK modeling (A5.3.4), with model reporting templates for aggregate exposure modeling (T8.3) and task T6.2 currently in progress. Additionally, a two-day joint training workshop, led by WP6 and WP8, was conducted in October 2024. This workshop provided training to members of the PARC community on harmonizing PBPK models.

Communication and dissemination activities

- Pronk et al. 2024, Bioassay predictive values for chemical health risks in drinking water, Environment International, Volume 188, June 2024, 108733, (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108733>)
- PBPK ontology, Eurotox 2024
- Text mining, Eurotox 2024

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.8 Work package 8. Concepts and Toolboxes

1.2.8.1 Task 8.1. Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)

Leader: RIVM (NL), EMPA (CH), AUTH (EL)

Participants: INERIS (FR), BNN (AT), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UNINA (IT), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), FMUL (PT), NIC (SI), INSST (ES), IVL (SE), BUL (UK), Cefas-Defra (UK)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Focus has been paid to the development of an efficient communication plan and infrastructure blueprint for an effective science-policy-user interphase. This has resulted in an inclusive dialogue with the EC, users and relevant stakeholders inside and outside PARC, that led to a collection of first indication on the gaps, barriers, and incentives to gain insight in the completeness, feasibility and applicability of the EC JRC framework. Of particular importance were the in-depth interaction with the chemical industry. We conducted in depth interviews and focus groups with 10 companies on how they currently approach the topics of safety and sustainability in their innovation process and in what way we can learn from this in a SSbD perspective.

Based on the review of existing tools (models, software, methods) for safety and sustainability, as well as the mapping of the user needs, the computational implementation of the toolbox has been carried out and the version 0.1 has been developed. In this version of the toolbox, an extensive list of tools for safety and sustainability has been compiled and is included in the main interface of toolbox (<https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/>). Along with this list, there is also a list of databases relevant for the purposes of an SSbD assessment. Finally, following the review of the existing tools, a mapping of the tools in relation to the five innovation stages and the five SSbD steps has been conducted. This mapping illustrates how a tool can be employed across different innovation stages, based on the data availability and the use scenario. The toolbox's primary interface (<https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/>), server infrastructure, and key functionalities have been established, ensuring smooth user interaction, authentication, and connectivity with external tools like Integra and Vega. During this year, a new element of the toolbox has been developed, the SSbD Wizard. It serves as a user interface to guide the user through the entire assessment process and generates the SSbD assessment workflow based on user inputs. Another new element of the PARC toolbox has been developed, the SSbD scoring system. It is based on the evaluation and scoring system proposed by JRC in the SSbD case study report. It converts the outcomes of each SSbD step assessment into scores. The scoring system provides an interface for each SSbD step, where the relevant SSbD endpoints that need to be addressed are included. During year 3, work focused on completing test case including predominantly and encompassing tools for the different SSbD Steps. The use cases have been defined with a view to allow the testing of the applicability of the EC SSbD criteria and methodology, engage relevant stakeholders along the value chain, consider barriers as well as incentives for implementation relevant to the stakeholders that are involved in the use cases. Second iteration of the BPA and alternatives case study for the different tools and analyze of the results with the objective of extracting key learnings and provide feedback to the toolbox development. The focus of the case study is to get a first experience with running several selected computational tools and identify important questions for future development of the toolbox. Work carried out regarding knowledge sharing and education has been focused on the development of a systematic approach for knowledge sharing on SSbD for chemicals as well as education and training within PARC and with relevant stakeholders outside PARC. This shall be executed via the establishment of a knowledge sharing platform on SSbD. The report on the survey on stakeholder needs for SSbD was published at the PARC website. The conclusions from this survey are further elaborated in a manuscript for a peer review publication on contributions to a learning agenda on safe and sustainable by design which will outline SSbD learning goals, identify target audience, and address core knowledge, skills/competences, values, and attitudes related to chemical innovation and development processes.

➤ A8.1.1. Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation

In Activity 8.1.1, particular focus has been paid to the development of an efficient communication plan and infrastructure blueprint for an effective science-policy-user interface, resulting in an inclusive dialogue process with the EC, users and relevant stakeholders inside and outside PARC. EU project IRISS is an important partner in addressing the specific needs of the value chains. On top of that, and to keep pace with the state of the art and the lessons learned, a collection of first indications regarding gaps, barriers, and incentives to gain insight in the completeness, feasibility and applicability of the EC JRC framework has been carried out. This was also highlighted in the respective technical kick-off meeting of the activity that took place on 20/09/2022 where the links with the policy developments through contributions from DG RTD, JRC and ECHA were made explicit. To facilitate the process, a communication plan has been coined with the aim to cover:

Structured dialogue with the EC; (AUTH, RIVM, DTU)

We have engaged in monthly to six-weekly meetings with the EC (RTD) and the JRC. The meetings were also attended by representatives of the IRISS project. Focus of the meetings was manifold:

- Exchange of SSbD relevant information
- Exploring synergies between IRISS, PARC and the work from the JRC
- Update on the SSbD toolbox developments
- Discussing the joint effort in organizing the first SSbD Bootcamp
- Coordinate mutual activities in conferences and symposia
- Addressing the specific questions, such as the need to harvest the knowledge developed in previous, already completed EU projects on SSbD.

Structured dialogues with industry (RIVM, AUTH, EMPA, KI, IVL, NILU)

In year 2 and 3 we have engaged in in depth interaction with the chemical industry. We conducted in depth interviews and focus groups with 10 companies on how they currently approach the topics of safety and sustainability in their innovation process and in what way we can learn from this in a SSbD perspective.

The results of the company interviews are submitted in a milestone and are planned to be translated into a scientific article in Year 4. The results of the interviews are feeding both into the toolbox, approach to the case studies, as well as future activities in 8.1.1.

Follow-up of the company interviews is foreseen and connected to operationalization of SSbD (e.g. Scoping analysis, Trade offs), toolbox development and testing and case studies.

Preparation for dialogues and connections outside PARC

- An inventory was made of relevant SSbD projects under Horizon EU 2023/24 and an analysis performed to identify potential connections to the PARC SSbD developments. The analysis has been expanded to other EU projects with relevant (finished) EU content to harvest potential useful information for PARC activities 8.1.1 till 8.1.4. (AUTH, IVL, RIVM)
- We published a paper on conceptualizing fair data in the context of SSbD in RSC Sustainability (<https://pubs.rsc.org/en/Content/ArticleLanding/2024/SU/D4SU00171K>). The focus in this paper is on the need for and the importance of FAIR data (RIVM, KI, NILU, AUTH, EEA, ISS, UNINA) in the context of an SSbD assessment, and recommendations on how to move in this direction.

- We are exploring the exchanges and alignment between SSbD and EU regulation on chemicals and products, as well as corporate guidelines (RIVM, EEA, UBA, ISS, UNINA, EMPA, AUTH, BNN). An inventory and an analysis of chemical regulations relevant for SSbD has been drafted. A paper detailing the result is under development. This thread of work is the first in the series of analysis of how SSbD and chemical regulation can have distinct goals,
- Performing an SSbD analysis is complex and requires a careful scoping of the problem and clear process-steps of which actions to take and why. In 2024 we have investigated the possibilities of a 'scoping approach' with the aim to identify potential working methods that enable us to develop a systematic working method (e.g. a workshop format) that supports SSbD assessment (RIVM).

Dissemination

- Regular PARC 8.1 (monthly to 3 monthly) meetings hosting a variety of speakers on the topic of SSbD, from other contexts and EU projects,
- SPINE SSbD policy meeting addressing developments in PARC SSbD in the context of policy developments in EU member states.
- Presenting SSbD Developments PARC NH meeting in Brussels (Belgium)
- Organization of Dutch PARC NH meeting in the Netherlands (November 5) with the focus on the knowledge needs from policy and industry.
- Presenting PARC SSbD Developments on the sustainable chemicals event in Brussels (December 9) organized by the Flemish Ministry of Economic Affairs.

➤ A8.1.2. Toolbox development

Based on the review of existing tools (models, software, methods) for safety and sustainability, as well as the mapping of the user needs, the computational implementation of the toolbox has been carried out and the version 0.1 has been developed. In this version of the toolbox, an extensive list of tools for safety and sustainability has been compiled and is included in the main interface of toolbox (<https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/>). Along with this list, there is also a list of databases relevant for the purposes of an SSbD assessment. Finally, following the review of the existing tools, a mapping of the tools in relation to the five innovation stages and the five SSbD steps has been conducted. This mapping illustrates how a tool can be employed across different innovation stages, based on the data availability and the use scenario.

The toolbox's primary interface (<https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/>), server infrastructure, and key functionalities have been established, ensuring smooth user interaction, authentication, and connectivity with external tools like Integra and Vega.

Regarding the back-end development, it handles several critical functions that ensure the robustness and reliability of the toolbox:

1. Complete Auth Functionality: The server is equipped with a fully functional authentication system. It supports user registration, login, password recovery, and session management, providing Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) to protect sensitive features based on user roles (e.g., admin, user).
2. SSbD Evaluation and Scoring System Service: A dedicated back-end service supports the SSbD Evaluation and Scoring System. This service manages the evaluation logic, processes data input for each SSbD step, and computes scores based on assessment results. It also integrates with the front-end to provide real-time feedback and result visualization for users.

3. API Services: Two major external API services have been integrated:
 - Integra API Service: The Integra API enables seamless integration with external systems for data retrieval interoperability with the Integra tool.
 - Vega API Service: ensures connectivity, allowing users to access Vega tool directly from the toolbox.
4. Connectivity with Integra and Vega Tools: The toolbox communicates efficiently with both Integra and Vega tools, offering data exchange, error handling and task execution capabilities. This connectivity has been crucial in extending the toolbox's functionality.

As for the front-end development, the user interface (UI) of the toolbox is now well-structured, consisting of several core components:

1. Admin Panel and Admin Pages: The admin section provides complete management functionalities, allowing admins to modify system settings, and control task-related operations.
2. Dashboard Page: A dedicated dashboard page provides an overview of the most useful user- related task data. It displays task statuses and recent activity, giving users a snapshot of their progress.
3. Task Management: A well-organized task list offers users a clear overview of completed, pending, and failed tasks, with full CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) functionality for efficient task handling.
4. Wizard: The first version of the wizard has been implemented. This tool guides users through multi-step processes within the toolbox.
5. SSbD Evaluation and Scoring System: The evaluation and scoring system is fully functional. It converts the outcomes of each SSbD step assessment into scores, facilitating decision- making. The system provides an interface for each SSbD step, allowing users to input necessary outputs and address the relevant endpoints for evaluation.
6. Profile Management: The UI allows users to access and modify their profiles. Users can update information and manage account settings easily through a clean interface.

The deployment infrastructure has been set up for both development and production environments, ensuring that the toolbox can be rolled out smoothly across different platforms. It uses modern containerization (Docker) and cloud orchestration tools, allowing for continuous integration and delivery (CI/CD) pipelines to streamline updates and feature releases (GA). Unit tests have been developed to validate key functionalities. These tests cover various critical components such as user authentication, API responses, and task management features, ensuring that new updates do not introduce bugs or break existing functionality. Database migrations are fully implemented. These migrations ensure that updates to the database schema can be applied incrementally and without data loss. This allows the development team to introduce new features without disrupting existing data or user activity.

During this year, a new element of the toolbox has been developed, the SSbD Wizard. It serves as a user interface to guide the user through the entire assessment process and generates the SSbD assessment workflow based on user inputs. The SSbD Wizard has been designed to incorporate the five SSbD steps across the five development stages of chemicals and materials, following the stage-gate model, to create a final product. To initiate the assessment process, a series of questions are posed to the user aiming at guiding them towards a proper evaluation. In addition, based on the innovation stage and the SSbD step, the Wizard provides recommendations for tools that align with the respective step and stage, as well as the input

requirements. In the version 0.1 of the toolbox, it has an informative form, including relevant information for an SSbD assessment for each step and innovation stage, but it is not definitive and will be elaborated.

Two tools have already been included in the toolbox, VEGA and INTEGRA. The integration of these tools into the platform has been done through an API. The APIs of the tools have been provided by IRFMN and AUTH, respectively. VEGA is a software including tens of QSAR models. It has been developed by IRFM (T8.1 partner), and can be used for predicting hazard and physicochemical properties. INTEGRA is a unified computational platform that integrates environmental fate, exposure and internal dose. It has been developed by AUTH. Most of the exposure models of INTEGRA are available in the toolbox v0.1.

Another new element of the PARC toolbox has been developed, the SSbD scoring system. It is based on the evaluation and scoring system proposed by JRC in the SSbD case study report. It converts the outcomes of each SSbD step assessment into scores. The scoring system provides an interface for each SSbD step, where the relevant SSbD endpoints that need to be addressed are included. In the version 0.1 of the toolbox development, the user will execute a series of manual tool pipelines in order to undertake an SSbD assessment. Upon completion of the performance assessment and result collection, the Scoring System provides an opportunity for the evaluation of the assessment by means of inputting the necessary outputs for each step. A specific script in the R language has been developed and integrated into the toolbox along with its interface for this scoring system. This version of the scoring system is not definitive, and it will be further developed.

Dissemination activities

- The toolbox has been presented to a large number of stakeholders in a virtual workshop that has been held on 17/06/2024. In the workshop, the PARC SSbD toolbox concept, the long-term vision, the current progress, the co-creation approach, and the next steps were presented, together with the main functionalities of the toolbox, and a showcase of the steps in the toolbox for executing the bisphenols and alternatives case study. In addition, the process for providing feedback to the developers team has been explained. Overall, 180 participants have attended the PARC SSbD Toolbox workshop.
- 10th Summer School on Sustainable Chemistry for sustainable development (8-10 July 2024): Demonstration and workshop on the toolbox and presentation of results from the BPA case study at 10th Summer School on Sustainable Chemistry for sustainable development, organized by Leuphana University Lüneburg/IRISS 2024 (IVL, AUTH)
- Oral presentation at EUROTOX 2024 (8-11 September, 2024): “A computational toolbox supporting the development of Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials”, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2024.07.161>
- Poster presentation at EUROTOX 2024 (8-11 September, 2024): “The Safe and Sustainable by Design toolbox: guiding the user across the innovation stages through the SSbD Wizard”, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2024.07.700>
- 2nd SSbD Boot Camp in Thessaloniki organized by AUTH (22-25 October, 2024): The 2nd SSbD Boot Camp is being organised by AUTH and will be held in Thessaloniki, from 22 to 25 October. It will be a two half and two full days of getting insights into the concepts and assessment methods for SSbD. The total number of applicants was 86, and approximately 70 to 80 of them are expected to participate.
- Oral presentation at AIChE annual meeting 2024 (27 – 31 October 2024): “A computational toolbox supporting the development of SSbD chemicals and materials”
- Oral presentation at the 86th LCA Discussion Forum on “Safe- and Sustainable-by-Design”, April 25, 2024, “Development of a Toolbox for Safe and Sustainable by Design”.
- Oral presentation at SSbD24, Monte Verita (10-15 November, 2024), Switzerland “

➤ A8.1.3. Towards operationalisation: Use case & indicators

In Activity 8.1.3, during year 3 work focused on completing test case including predominantly and encompassing tools for the different SSbD Steps.

The following is a list of actions that were undertaken to facilitate the development of the toolbox through case studies:

A survey has been carried out to investigate the maturity of SSbD understanding and application of the JRC SSbD framework at the time when PARC started (Paper accepted <https://authors.elsevier.com/tracking/article/details.do?aid=103909&jid=ENVSCI&surname=lavicoli>) (UNINA, IVL, AUTH)

- Finding suitable case studies and organizing case studies (ongoing) (IVL, UNINA)
- The first iteration of calculations in the case study related to bisphenol and alternatives was concluded during year two. During year three, task forces, one for each step of the SSbD Framework and a transversal task force to discuss crosscutting issues, are in the process of drafting several manuscripts based on the results. (IVL, UNINA, EMPA, NILU, RIVM, EEA, AUTH, IRFMN, TTL, ISS, INSST, UG/QSAR Lab, RECETOX, BNN, DEFRA, BRUNEL)
- BPA Case study Workshop, 24/5 (3h). The objective of the workshop was to facilitate the exchange of experiences, conclusions and learnings derived from the task force work. Additionally, the event aimed to promote the sharing of experiences among the various working groups, with a view to identifying common lessons learned. (IVL, UNINA, EMPA, NILU, RIVM, EEA, AUTH, IRFMN, TTL, ISS, INSST, UG/QSAR Lab, RECETOX, BNN, DEFRA, BRUNEL)
- Tools have been tested in collaboration with Mistra SafeChem (MSC) case studies. (IVL, RISE, EMPA, AUTH, IRFMN)
- Determination of Gaps and Opportunities (continuously updated from the case study findings) (RIVM, EMPA, UBA, IVL, BUL, UNINA, NILU, TTL, EEA, AUTH)
- "D8.4 – 1st Report on the testing and uptake of the SSbD toolbox through use cases" was submitted on the Funding and Tenders platform, but not yet available at PARC website. (IVL, UNINA, EMPA, NILU, RIVM, EEA, AUTH, IRFMN, TTL, ISS, INSST, UG/QSAR Lab, RECETOX, BNN, DEFRA, BRUNEL)
- Summary of learnings and feedback to EC (Feedback to JRC of the SSbD Framework submitting feedback on the SSbD framework) (IVL, UNINA, EMPA, NILU, RIVM, EEA, AUTH, IRFMN, TTL, ISS, INSST, UG/QSAR Lab, RECETOX, BNN, DEFRA)
- 8.1.3 activity leads and task force representatives for the BPA case study have co-organised, planned, prepared and participated in the 2024 SSbD Bootcamp along with 8.1.2 and 8.1.1. (IVL, AUTH, IFRM, EMPA)
- Plenary Meetings 8.1.3 held once or every second month at following dates: 24/1, 28/2, 17/4, 19/6, 21/8, 10/10, 18/12(ca 20 participants each meeting)
- 8.1.3 lead meeting (3-6 participants) once a month (IVL, UNINA)
- Ongoing meeting series starting M23 for each Task force, 3-8 meeting among each task forces (IVL, UNINA, EMPA, NILU, RIVM, AUTH, IRFMN, TTL, ISS, INSST, UG/QSAR Lab, RECETOX, BNN, BRUNEL)

The use cases have been defined with a view to allow the testing of the applicability of the EC SSbD criteria and methodology, engage relevant stakeholders along the value chain, consider barriers as well as incentives for implementation relevant to the stakeholders that are involved in the use cases (AUTH, IVL, EMPA, RIVM, EEA, UNINA).

During the period M21-M32, the focus has been on completing the case studies. Second iteration of the BPA and alternatives case study for the different tools and analyze of the results with the

objective of extracting key learnings and provide feedback to the toolbox development. (IVL, UNINA, EMPA, NILU, RIVM, EEA, AUTH, IRFMN, TTL, ISS, INSST, UG/QSAR Lab, RECETOX, BNN, DEFRA, BRUNEL)

The “D8.4 – 1st Report on the testing and uptake of the SSbD toolbox through use cases”, status April 2024, outlines the initial evaluation of the SSbD toolbox developed within the PARC project. The report focuses on the practical testing of in-silico tools designed to support SSbD assessments across different innovation stages, as defined by the European Commission's framework.

The focus of the case study is to get a first experience with running several selected computational tools and identify important questions for future development of the toolbox. The use cases which were selected are a well-known and extensively researched chemical (Bisphenol-A) used in two distinct applications (polycarbonate used in reusable water bottles and epoxy resins in paint), and three potential alternatives including Bisphenol-A itself.

In brief, the idea was to apply a selection of computational tools included in the toolbox to BPA and two BPA alternatives, Isosorbide and BPAP. The intention was that the outcome of the study will help us include relevant input into the first drafts of the PARC toolbox. Please note that the aim of the case study was not to find an optimal alternative to BPA, but rather to apply the tools and the toolbox and identify challenges of the toolbox procedure.

Key findings include insights into the applicability of the tools at different stages of the innovation process. The report suggests that certain tools, requiring minimal data, are more suitable for early-stage screening, while others, requiring more detailed information, are better suited for later innovation phases. Additionally, the report identifies gaps in data, complexities in tool integration, and differences in tool predictions. These findings will inform the further refinement of the SSbD toolbox to ensure it supports stakeholders in assessing the safety and sustainability of chemicals and materials throughout their lifecycle.

The case study also stresses the importance of further operationalizing the SSbD framework by incorporating new methodologies and tools to address data gaps and enhance model reliability across different chemical assessment phases.

In early February 2024 six dedicated task forces were formed, one for each SSbD step, and one overarching transversal taskforce. The task forces consist mainly of the participants who have tested the different tools but also of other experts from the PARC consortium. The task forces have had weekly meetings where the results from the tool testing have been discussed and questions of concern have been identified. Each task force was also asked to focus on a set of questions and identify areas for each step that need specific focus and continued work. The taskforces discussed the following questions:

1. What is the overall applicability domain (chemicals) of the toolbox?
2. Which EC SSbD framework endpoints are covered by the tools? Which endpoints predicted by the tools are not included in the EC SSbD framework?
3. What are the gaps in applying the tools?
4. What is the level of detail of the tools, in terms of the underlying model, input or output?
5. What are potential operational barriers for working with the tools? E.g., is there any input data that is difficult to obtain in order to use the tool?
6. For which innovation stage is/are tool(s) suited?
7. The taskforces were also asked to assess the results from the different tools within each SSbD step.
 - a) Comparison of tools: is the outcome consistent among different models within each step?
 - b) Is there a valid explanation for this discrepancy?

The work from the task forces have delivered task force reports used as input to the deliverable D8.4 and the feedback on the SSbD Framework to JRC. Further, several task forces currently are working on scientific manuscripts based on the findings from the case study.

TF1 (IVL, EMPA, AUTH, IRFMN, TTL, ISS, UG/QSAR Lab, MU-RECETOX, UNINA,)

TF2 (IVL, AUTH, TTL, INSST, UG/QSAR Lab, RECETOX, BNN, UNINA)

TF3 (AUTH, UG/QSAR Lab, MU-RECETOX, IVL, UNINA,)

TF4 (NILU, IVL, RIVM)

TF5 (IVL, BUNEL) Discontinued due to budget limitations

TF Transversal (IVL, AUTH, EMPA, RIVM, INSST, UG/QSAR Lab, MU-RECETOX, BNN, UNINA)

Indicators

The work of compiling a gross list of indicators as provided by the tools as reviewed in 8.1.2, and another list of indicators as requested in the JRC SSbD framework, continues. The purpose of compiling the list is to compare to what extent they are, or can be, aligned and identify gaps that potential new tools can fill.

Dissemination activities

- Demonstration of the toolbox and presentation of results from the BPA case study at 10th Summer School on Sustainable Chemistry for sustainable development, organized by Leuphana University Lüneburg/IRISS 2024 (8-12 July)
- Poster presentation at SETAC Europe Annual Meeting Seville 2024 (5-9 May, 2024): 7.04.P-We578 “Testing tools for sustainability for SSbD in early phases of innovation, applied to BPA and alternatives”,
- Oral presentation at Lifecycle Innovation conference (LCIC) Berlin, biannual meeting 2024 (3-5 July 2024): “Safe and sustainable by Design chemicals and materials (SSbD): First broad testing of tools for early stages of innovation and substitution”
- Poster presentation at SETAC Europe 26th LCA Symposium 2024 (21-23 October, 2024): “Testing SSbD tools for chemical substitution: a walk in the PARC”

➤ A8.1.4 Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalisation

Work carried out in Activity 8.1.4 has been focused on the development of a systematic approach for knowledge sharing on SSbD for chemicals as well as education and training within PARC and with relevant stakeholders outside PARC. This shall be executed via the establishment of a knowledge sharing platform on SSbD.

For developing a blueprint of such a knowledge sharing platform an inception plan has been used in Y1 and Y2 to present the actions performed and progress achieved. Starting with Y3, the blueprint developed has been discussed with several partners within Task 8.1 and with different actors of relevant other tasks in PARC (but also with SSbD experts outside PARC, e.g. JRC) for decision making on further steps and cooperation on different elements of the future knowledge sharing platform.

Actions in M21-32 focused on three different areas:

- Initial realisation of the knowledge sharing platform (provision of first sets of material)
- Criteria-based approach to select education material, training programs and information sharing material for the knowledge sharing platform

- Development of a user-friendly selection tool for the repository of SSbD educational material
- Strategy to select actual material for the knowledge sharing platform

The knowledge sharing platform on SSbD will consist of nine different elements (introduction to SSbD, regulation and its link to SSbD, test guidelines, tools and methods, data and databases, education and training, case studies, user community, announcements). Work on all elements has been performed (*inter alia* drafting of landing pages, development of a selection tool and repository of education material, testing of PARCopedia group for user community exchange, development of FAQs, tools to allow for feedback to the knowledge sharing platform) (UBA, RIVM, AUTH, UNINA, IUSS, TTL, IVL, INSST, FMUL).

In M21-32 six activity meetings took place at which the different actions of Y2 and Y3 of PARCs were presented, discussed and work in smaller groups was continued (UBA, RIVM, AUTH, UNINA, IVL, INSST, FMUL). In addition, three meetings with Task 9.4 took place focusing on a joint selection tool for education and training material within PARC (RIVM, UBA, FMUL, INSST). Two meetings with Task 2.2 were held to discuss the use of a PARCopedia group to establish a user community space on SSbD (UBA, RIVM). Two meetings with Task 3.2 focused on the technical implementation of the knowledge sharing platform on SSbD as a separate branch of the PARC website (UBA, RIVM). At task 8.1 meetings further decision making on the knowledge sharing platform on SSbD with all task members took place. Meetings of the activity 8.1.4 co-leads took place via web conference, phone and in person. An additional in person meeting between the leads of the other activities took place in Zurich in April 2024.

In M26 the report on the survey on stakeholder needs for SSbD which took place in Y2 was published at the PARC website (UBA, RIVM). The conclusions from this survey are further elaborated in a manuscript for a peer review publication on contributions to a learning agenda on safe and sustainable by design which will outline SSbD learning goals, identify target audience, and address core knowledge, skills/competences, values, and attitudes related to chemical innovation and development processes (FMUL, INSST, RIVM, UBA).

Dissemination activities:

- Publication of the report on the survey on stakeholder needs for SSbD at the PARC website (25 June 2024): PARC survey on stakeholder needs highlights central requirements for a platform to foster knowledge sharing and education on Safe and Sustainable by Design | Parc (eu-parc.eu)
- Joint PARC IRISS workshop on SSbD knowledge sharing and education at the ANTHOS`24 conference (Vienna, 4-7 March 2024)

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

The work on the toolbox development and the case study on BPA and alternatives has been extensive and required more resources and time than expected.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D8.4	1st Report on the testing and uptake of the SSbD toolbox through use cases	EMPA	M24	M28	Delay due to revision and improvement of the draft as well as to the summer break. Version 1 was delivered M24 and the revised version delivered M28 (Delivered to the Funding and Tenders platform)

1.2.8.2 Task 8.2. Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks

Leader: SLU (SE), INSERM (FR)

Participants: INRAE (FR), AU (DK), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), UniLU (LU), UU-IRAS (NL), VUA (NL), WR (NL), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), DGS (PT), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), ORU (SE), IVL (SE), SLV (SE), UMU (SE), EA (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Standardized protocols for early warning monitoring tools are currently under development in collaboration with the work done in WP4, with a particular focus on suspect/non-targeted/EDA-based tools for both environmental and human samples. Protocols for effect-based monitoring have been detailed with a particular focus on SPM and wastewater. In line with the introduction of NAMs in the RA process, metabolomics-based biomarkers have been defined, together with computational tools that allow their proper interpretation, such as AI methods and advanced bioinformatics algorithms. Also, a literature analysis of existing AI systems in EWS and the summarizing overview in the context of their reliability and usefulness for chemicals prioritisation regarding toxicity is currently ongoing. Towards the development of the identification framework further databases with chemical structure and identifier information have been selected to facilitate the development of computational method for systematic identification and prioritization of new substances with a particular focus on the contribution of international databases. Work on the evaluation of existing computational methods and selection of the most promising tools in the context of prioritization framework has been continued. In this sense, particular emphasis has been paid to Big Data Analytics and the need for developing a system capable of processing large volumes of data from multiple sources (ideally in real time). A review of existing studies has been conducted to identify potential case studies for validating early warning monitoring tools and a prioritization framework for humans and products, and two case studies have been initiated. The initial concept of the EWS computational system was further elaborated. The first steps for the integration of the existing computational tools that could be implemented and applied in a first version of an in silico driven EWS have been carried out. Overall, the concept of the computational platform to support the EWS is based on a workflow that starts with a systematic search for NERCs using automatic data mining and curation of any inventory aiming at delivering molecular structure information for further processing and if available experimental data. The evaluation of the available in silico systems and chemical and toxicological screening data for the development of a systematic scoring system to rank and prioritize substances using multicriteria decision analysis is carried out, and the gaps identification will feed the design of the PARC EWS. To increase the chance of capturing relevant existing data to develop a new AOP, the AOP-helpFinder tool was recently implemented to assist researchers. Here, an updated version of

AOP-helpFinder (v2) proposes novel functionalities and this work was done in collaboration with WP5.3.2a and WP 7.3.3. A stakeholder mapping and questionnaire has also been devised, to evaluate stakeholder needs and expectations of the output from the PARC EWS (IVL, EFET, AUTH, OVAM, SLU, SEPA, UMU, WFSR, GCSL). Work has also been performed concerning the policy interface of the EWS. The decision by the Commission to implement an EU EWS entailed that possible synergies as well as differences between the PARC and EU EWS be evaluated as the EU EWS might implement tools developed within PARC. The policy working group has also been developing guidelines for the adoption of NTS and effect-based data. This work was further used in a publication within Task 4.3 for the handling of signals in an EWS. The questionnaire has been reviewed by existing EWS and will be circulated first for context validity and then to gather replies.

➤ A8.2.1 EW monitoring tools

Within T8.2.1, standardized protocols for early warning monitoring tools are currently under development (SLU, INRAE, UniLU, NILU, AU, MTM-ORU, NKUA, UU, VITO, EA), in collaboration with the work done in WP4, with a particular focus on suspect/non-targeted/EDA-based tools for both environmental (SLU, MTM-ORU, ISS) and human samples (INRAE, UOC, VITO). Protocols for effect-based monitoring have been detailed as part of 8.2.3 (suspended particulate matter (SPM) samples) and 4.3 (wastewater). In line with the introduction of NAMs in the RA process, metabolomics-based biomarkers have been defined, together with computational tools that allow their proper interpretation, such as AI methods and advanced bioinformatics algorithms (WFSR, UMU, MTM-ORU, INSERM, UG, AUTH, IRFM, NKUA, UU, IISPV). WFSR has made the first attempt using raw data from MS2 spectra to directly predict toxicity, without intermediate translation into structure-related ‘fingerprints’. The MS2 spectra database has been matched to the toxicological database for this purpose, whereby the data has been preprocessed so that it can be used for machine learning models for toxicology prediction. So far, this has not been successful, and it is unclear whether this is due to the chosen data sources, the preprocessing steps, or the associated model implementation assumptions. In the coming year, WFSR will further investigate whether use of more/other data sources and/or data-driven methods can be better suited for the early warning signal detection of chemical food safety hazards in the food chain.

Towards the aim of information collation, monthly meetings have been organised (SLU). A PARC workshop on “EWS and Prioritization of Chemicals” has been held in Athens, Greece, 4-5 June 2024 organized by T8.2 and T4.2 Co-leading Teams. Close collaboration has also been ensured with a dedicated project under Task 4.3 (SLU, AU, UU, VITO) to ensure good integration of EWS expectations with regard to innovative screening methods. Moreover, results of monitoring studies (in collaboration with other partners and WP4) are currently analysed to prioritise substances which are “safe” or with adverse properties, also considering the JANUS software for prioritisation (IRFM). Scoping out metadata terms and suspect lists relevant for this task, along with prioritisation of use data in collaboration with Task 4.2, as well as keywords for scientific and grey literature search for monitoring tools to support EWS in food safety that are using AI and/or big data analytics (WFSR, UMU, MTM-ORU, INSERM, UG, AUTH, IRFM, NKUA, UU, IISPV) has also been carried out, to search public scientific databases and various EWS systems were identified (AUTH). Main features of the identified systems are now detailed and reported.

Also, a literature analysis of existing AI systems in EWS and the summarizing overview in the context of their reliability and usefulness for chemicals prioritisation regarding toxicity is currently ongoing, while an extensive review of the operational EWS from England, namely Prioritisation and Early Warning System (PEWS) for chemicals of emerging concern, has also been completed (EA, AUTH).

➤ A8.2.2: Identification framework

Towards the development of the identification framework in A8.2.2, further databases with chemical structure and identifier information have been selected to facilitate the development of computational method for systematic identification and prioritization of new substances (NKUA, UMU, AUTH), with a particular focus on the contribution of international databases like REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of Chemicals) or the Global Harmonized System (GHS) of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals. The framework for assimilating HBM data has been elaborated with updated algorithms to accelerate the process of exposure reconstruction under complex exposure scenarios (AUTH). Additional molecular features related to adverse or critical chemical hazard effects (IRFMN, AUTH), were collected, initially characterized by structural alerts (thus local, molecular features) and global parameters (thus properties related to the whole molecule). The work on the metadata terms and suspect lists relevant for this task has been continued, along with prioritization of use data in cooperation with WP7 and WP4 (AU, INERIS, SLV, MTM, NMBU, SLU, NKUA, UBA, EA).

Work on the evaluation of existing computational methods and selection of the most promising tools in the context of prioritization framework has been continued (UMU, INSERM, AUTH, IRFMN, UG, UniLU, UU), to further update methods to determine and identify emerging risks (AUTH, SLU). In this sense, particular emphasis has been paid to Big Data Analytics (AUTH, IRFMN, NKUA, UMU), and the need for developing a system capable of processing large volumes of data from multiple sources (ideally in real time). This allows for the timely detection of trends, anomalies, and patterns related to chemical risks. Towards these directions, the need to implement AI and ML algorithms has been identified (AUTH, IRFMN, NKUA, UMU), used to detect early warning signs by analyzing historical data and identifying correlations between certain conditions (e.g., industrial activities) and chemical releases. In order to bring together different pieces of information and various stakeholders, the need for integrated communication platforms that can send alerts and warnings to stakeholders via various channels (e.g., mobile apps, email, social media, etc.) has also been highlighted (AUTH, IRFMN, NKUA, UMU).

The overall work of the EWS identification framework has been concluded in the D8.2 - Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS that has been published in 2024.

➤ A8.2.3: Applicability and performance testing of EW toolbox

A review of existing studies has been conducted to identify potential case studies for validating early warning monitoring tools and a prioritization framework for humans (SLU, AUTH, INRAE, IISPV, UOC, VITO), the environment (SLU, MTM, SLV, UOC, EFET, UU), and products (SLU, INRAE, UU).

A core group dedicated to case studies has been established (ORU, SLU, UBA, NKUA, AU, EFET). The group has identified available capacities (both human and analytical), as well as existing cases, data, and samples. Accordingly, two case studies have been initiated. The first case study aims to identify hazardous chemicals in the environment by effect-based monitoring, effect-based analysis, together with spatial and temporal analysis. SPM samples collected from German rivers by UBA, Germany, are used. In Y3, SPM samples have been extracted and analysed using NTS and EDA approaches (SLU, ORU, UBA) and the data evaluation and dissemination of the results will be in Y4. The second case study involves identification of hazardous chemicals in fish samples intended for human consumption collected from Greek rivers by NKUA and the sampling and extraction will be finalized and in Y4 suspect screening (NKUA) and NTS (SLU, ORU, AU) will be performed, with a RA to be carried out by EFET.

➤ A8.2.4: Computational framework to support EWS

The initial concept of the EWS computational system was further elaborated. The first steps for the integration of the existing computational tools that could be implemented and applied in a first version of an in silico driven EWS (AUTH, NKUA, UMU) have been carried out. Overall, the concept of the computational platform to support the EWS is based on a workflow that starts with a systematic search for NERCs using automatic data mining and curation (AUTH, NKUA, UMU) of any inventory (NKUA, UMU, SLU, UniLU, EFET, GCSL) aiming at delivering molecular structure information (IRFMN) for further processing and if available experimental data. We have also started analyzing patent data as a critical early source for identifying potential emerging hazardous chemicals (UMU). This is in particular aiming at identifying and decoding molecular structure information to formats readable by exposure and hazard models. Here we will also use NLP methodologies to create workflows for automatization. The next step covers parallel assessment of exposure (AUTH, NKUA, EFET, GCSL) and effects (AUTH, IRFM, UMU) that will feed information for a weighing of an overall score of hazard and ultimately identification of potential NERCs. In these directions, the design of the first version of the computational framework to support the EWS has been carried out (AUTH, IRFM, NKUA, UMU), aiming to deliver the first version by the end of April 2025. The IT implementation of this version (AUTH), will include a broad array of links with chemical databases (NKUA, UMU, MTM, SLU, UniLU, EFET, GCSL) and a broad array of models (AUTH, IRFM, NKUA, UMU, IISPV, UG-PL, INSERM), and an EWS wizard (AUTH, UMU, NKUA), that will guide the user on the tools and data to use to evaluate the potential signals.

Given the importance of access to data to feed the EWS, active collaboration with WP7, regarding the FAIR principles to make them accessible for researchers, regulators, policy and other stakeholders (e.g. NORMAN) is currently ongoing (NKUA, UMU, SLU, Inserm, UniLU). The evaluation of the available in silico systems and chemical and toxicological screening data for the development of a systematic scoring system to rank and prioritize substances using multicriteria decision analysis is carried out (IRFM, UG-PL), and the gaps identification will feed the design of the PARC EWS (AUTH).

Updates on the NORMAN Suspect List Exchange (NORMAN-SLE) relevant for this task are continuously feeding the development of the computational framework to support the PARC EWS (NKUA, UMU, MTM, SLU). Details on the EWS computational system are included in the AD8.3 entitled Conceptualization of a computational system for the EWS which was submitted after review in December 2023.

Work has also been performed concerning the policy interface of the EWS. The decision by the Commission to implement an EU EWS entailed that possible synergies as well as differences between the PARC and EU EWS be evaluated as the EU EWS might implement tools developed within PARC (IVL, EEA, UBA, EFET, AUTH, AU, OVAM, SEPA, UMU, GCSL). The policy working group has also been developing guidelines for the adoption of NTS and effect-based data. This work was further used in a publication within Task 4.3 for the handling of signals in an EWS (IVL, NKUA, AUTH, AU, ORO, GCSL). A stakeholder mapping and questionnaire has also been devised, to evaluate stakeholder needs and expectations of the output from the PARC EWS (IVL, EFET, AUTH, OVAM, SLU, SEPA, UMU, WFSR, GCSL). The questionnaire has been reviewed by existing EWS and will be circulated first for context validity and then to gather replies.

Moreover, to support the use of alternative methods in regulatory assessment of chemical risks, the concept of AOP constitutes an important toxicological tool. AOP represents a structured representation of existing knowledge, linking MIE initiated by a prototypical stressor that leads to a cascade of biological KE to an adverse outcome (AO). Biological information to develop AOPs are dispersed in various data sources. To increase the chance of capturing relevant existing data

to develop a new AOP, the AOP-helpFinder tool was recently implemented to assist researchers. Here, an updated version of AOP-helpFinder (v2) proposes novel functionalities and this work was done in collaboration with WP5.3.2a and WP 7.3.3 by Inserm. The main one being the implementation of an automatic screening of the abstracts from the PubMed database to identify and extract event-event associations. In addition, a new scoring system was created to classify the identified co-occurred terms (stressor-event or event-event (which represent key event relationships) to help prioritization and support the weight of evidence approach, allowing a global assessment of the strength and reliability of the AOP. Moreover, to facilitate interpretation of the results, visualization options are also proposed. The AOP-helpFinder source code is fully accessible via GitHub, and searches can be performed via a web interface at <http://aop-helpfinder-v2.u-paris-sciences.fr/> (doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.108017.). The development of a third version is on-going with more data integration.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D8.2	Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	SLU	M12 (postponed M17)	M21	There were some delays to appoint the reviewers for this deliverable. Once reviewed, WP8 co-leaders asked for some time for other T8.2 partners to react to the modifications done
AD8.3	Strategy document on IATA for more complex endpoints	AUTh	M18	M21	

1.2.8.3 Task 8.3. Integrative models

Leader: WR (NL), AUTH (EL)

Participants: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), UU-IRAS (NL), WU-TOX (NL), NIVA (NO), NMBU (NO), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), UU (SE), UOC (EL)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

The development of the general framework for integrating models was informed by (user) requirements derived from the case studies, other PARC projects, and feedback from external stakeholders. In terms of development regarding the conceptual framework, the conceptual part

covers the whole source to effect and impacts continuum, developed in an iterative process. Refinements were made for modeling activities in the domains of (aggregate) exposure assessment, toxicokinetic simulation, HBM exposure assessment, QSAR modeling and simulation, and RA. Initial efforts on application of the conceptual framework focused on identifying domains and model classes within the model network, outlining key entities and properties of these for the model inventory, and mapping modeling tools to workflows and user requirements. Harmonization of the conceptual models across domains was initiated. Related to this, Task 8.3 participated in the WP7 FAIR steering team and semantic implementation team, to support FAIR data sharing and model integration within the PARC model network. An initiative for FAIR PBK models was started by T8.3, in collaboration with T6.2 and T7.3. With regard to the technical framework, a focus group defined the technical components for interoperability between models in the network and for connecting them in workflows. In a series of meetings the group defined levels of interoperability for modeling tools at the level of data, interfacing, and workflow automation. Automatic interfacing between modeling tools was explored by AUTH using APIs for delivering functional links between INTEGRA and MCRA. The inventory of modeling tools in view of T8.3 was updated based on the developments of the general framework for model integration. Integration of the model inventory with the PARC data hub that is developed in WP7 was explored. Work began on developing a general interface/access point to the model network through the inventory. Several case studies are currently ongoing to evaluate and to further guide the development of individual models and modelling platforms. In the context of these case studies workflows were released, in particular workflows for HBM-based mixture risk assessment.

➤ A8.3.1: Design, implementation and application of the PARC integrative model network

In year 3 the PARC model network was further developed according to the strategy that was described in D8.3 and AD8.4. Firstly, the general framework for integrating various models used in chemical RA was refined and secondly models were improved, and model links were implemented for workflows in practical case studies. Overall project meetings on these topics were held on January 26, February 23, March 15, June 5, September 24, and November 19 (participants: AUTH, WR, MU, IISPV, NIVA, VITO, IFMN, UU, INERIS, SYKE, ANSES). Bi-weekly meetings between the T8.3 co-leads have been held regularly (WR, AUTH).

The development of the general framework for integrating models was informed by (user) requirements derived from the case studies, other PARC projects, and feedback from external stakeholders. To achieve this, the co-leads of task 8.3 (AUTH, WR) maintained close contact with other PARC tasks, in particular WP2 (AUTH), WP5 (WR, IISPV, AUTH), T6.2 (WR), WP7 (WR), and T8.1 (AUTH). Additionally, together with PARC T6.2, we presented and discussed workflows for integrative RA (WR). These discussions were held with EFSA (March 19, June 11), PARC GB members (May 3,6,7) and DG-Sante (May 27) (WR, ANSES).

The general framework for integrating models is divided into a conceptual and a technical part.

- Conceptual framework: as described in the D8.3 the conceptual part covers the whole source to effect and impacts continuum. It is being developed in an iterative process. In Y3, refinements were made for modeling activities in the domains of (aggregate) exposure assessment (WR, ANSES, VITO, NIVA), toxicokinetic simulation (WR, INERIS, IISPV), HBM exposure assessment (WR, VITO), QSAR modeling and simulation (IRFM, UT), and RA (WR, ANSES). Initial efforts on application of the conceptual framework focused on identifying domains and model classes within the model network (AUTH), outlining key entities and properties of these for the model inventory (WR), and mapping modeling tools to workflows and user requirements (WR, AUTH, NIVA IISPV, MU). Harmonization of the conceptual models across domains was initiated (WR). Related to this, Task 8.3

participated in the WP7 FAIR steering team and semantic implementation team, to support FAIR data sharing and model integration within the PARC model network (WR).

- Technical framework: a focus group defined the technical components for interoperability between models in the network and for connecting them in workflows (AUTH, WR, UU, MU). In a series of meetings the group defined levels of interoperability for modeling tools at the level of data, interfacing, and workflow automation (January – March 2024). These partly followed from a review of the approach taken and lessons learned in other initiatives (OpenRiskNet, FNS-cloud, RAKIP, Elixir bio.tools). Automatic interfacing between modeling tools was explored by AUTH using APIs for delivering functional links between INTEGRA and MCRA. For PBK modeling, the T8.3 initiative for FAIR implementation of these models was continued (WR, IISPV, INERIS). Together with PARC T6.2 a two-day workshop on this topic was organized on October 7 and 8 to train the PARC community in PBK model harmonization.

The inventory of modeling tools in view of T8.3 was updated based on the developments of the general framework for model integration (MU, WR, AUTH, ANSES, NIVA). Integration of the model inventory with the PARC data hub that is developed in WP7 was explored (MU, WR). Work began on developing a general interface/access point to the model network through the inventory (AUTH, WR).

With regard to individual model development and establishing model links in the network:

- The workflow for mixture RA using HBM data was released (WR, ANSES, VITO) and used by HBM study owners in PARC T6.2.3. The MCRA platform was selected as the chosen environment within the PARC integrative model network for this workflow, since it is well recognized by e.g. EFSA for mixture RA. Four variations of the workflow were considered, corresponding to the methodology that was used in the T6.2.3 case studies on pesticides, PFAS and metals. Key differences between these variations included the risk metric used, the biological matrices considered, the use of reverse-dosimetry and incorporation of variability and uncertainty. All these aspects were validated by an independently developed implementation of each workflow variation in R (ANSES, WR). To facilitate future (regulatory) implementation an update to the MCRA user-interface was initiated. This update will enable users to apply the workflows in a harmonized way by modifying only a limited set of key settings, similar to EFSA's standard regulatory actions for mixture RA. The links between MCRA (WR) and tools for HBM data (VITO) were updated, to support PARC HBM codebooks v2.0 – 2.4 and codebooks for occupational data in the future (collaboration with T7.2). In addition, functionality in the MCRA platform for pre-processing of HBM data was updated and aligned with the WP4 statistical analysis plan. With a view towards future developments of this workflow, data formats for in-vitro studies (for dose-response modeling) were discussed with WP5 and WP7. Together with T6.2.3 participants guidance documents for the use of the workflow were developed and trainings were organized for T6.2.3 partners and EFSA (WR, ANSES). In addition, it was explored how the outputs produced by the case studies could be conveniently communicated to regulatory stakeholders, for instance via a dedicated dashboard.
- Development of a generic workflow for aggregate exposure assessment was continued, focusing on the PARC T6.2.1 methodology and its requirements (WR, ANSES, NIVA). The workflow builds upon the framework for aggregate exposure assessment implemented in MCRA in the EuroMix project. Two mechanisms were explored for linking exposure models to MCRA (WR). Firstly, a harmonized data format for exposure estimates was proposed (WR, ANSES) which was implemented in MCRA. This format was based on the conceptual refinements for (aggregate) exposure modeling activity. A demonstrator was created based on the T6.2.1 case study on PFOA aggregate exposure estimation. The demonstrator combined dietary exposure estimates from MCRA with estimates from

personal care products obtained in PACEMweb (WR). A proof-of-principle for integration of the low-tier RSEXPo exposure models in MCRA was developed, linking the RSEXPo dust exposures module in MCRA. This was demonstrated for on PFOA exposure assessment (WR, ANSES). The close collaboration with PARC T6.2 led to discussions with EFSA regarding about possible synergies with the ExpoAdvance roadmap.

- Development of functionality to link low-tier (absorption factors, kinetic conversion factors) and high-tier toxicokinetic models (PBK models) to MCRA was continued (WR, ANSES, INERIS). In year 3, efforts focused on exploring the possible technical data exchange formats for development of FAIR PBK models (WR) based on the Systems Biology Markup Language (SBML) and semantic annotation of the PBK ontology (IISPV). Efforts focused on developing a strategy for annotation of PBK models using the PBK ontology, development of examples for testing and demonstration purposes, promotion of the FAIR PBK modelling initiative, and a proof-of-principle implementation of support for FAIR PBK models in MCRA (WR, IISPV, INERIS, RIVM, AUTH).
- In collaboration with PARC T6.2.4 a case study on implementing EBD (EBD) calculations was initiated (WR, ANSES, VITO). As a proof-of-concept the EBD model used in the T6.2.4 pyrethroids – ADHD case study was implemented in MCRA and linked to the various exposure assessment models in the tool.
- A case study on chemical grouping by QSAR was initiated linking models from VEGAHUB to MCRA (IRFM, WR) was initiated. Several meetings were held to discuss the integration of VEGA into MCRA. The VEGA tool was applied to evaluate endocrine disruptors' activity. Several models, covering multiple endpoints (androgen, estrogen, thyroid, glucocorticoid, steroidogenesis) have been used. New models developed by IRFM (in particular for steroidogenesis) will be used to improve the case study. The goal of the case study is to perform a cumulative RA on CAGs (Cumulative Assessment Groups) for pesticides. The case study on propagation of uncertainty in workflows that connect models from different domains was continued, in collaboration with PARC T7.3 (MU, IISPV, WR). A workflow for PFAS exposure assessment integrating HBM-based exposure assessment, dietary exposure assessment and forward reverse dosimetry using PBK models was selected as test case (MU). The workflow was implemented in R and implementation of the workflow in MCRA was initiated, linking to the workflows described above (MU, WR). In year 3, exposure pathway of the workflow was elaborated, PFASs occurrence data were collected and their uncertainty assessed and the dietary exposure model was built and used for running different scenarios.
- A comprehensive PFASs occurrence dataset in food and drinks was completed and harmonized for four selected PFASs: PFOA, PFOS, PFNA and PFHxS. From 64 scientific papers and reports, 7400 records were wrapped, each providing a point estimate of a PFAS concentration in a given European country (region), year and food item. EFSA expoHierarchyCode codebook was used for coding the food items at level 2, however the information on the most detailed level (2 to 6) was also stored in the database. The EFSA expoHierarchyCode codebook is recommended for coding food items when integrating dietary exposure models in future.
- An external (dietary) exposure model was developed, tested, and debugged using R. The model treats input data uncertainty by five approaches, depending on the input data types and desired outcome. For each combination of PFAS, country, food item, and time span, either a static log-normal distribution over specified time range or a temporal trend in concentration is derived using either the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) or simple moments of the distribution (GM, GSD). In the first phase of the modelling, all inputs are treated as independent: to estimate the overall exposure and its uncertainty, either Monte Carlo simulations or Fenton-Wilkinson approximation were applied.

- The external (oral) exposure model was tested on the CELSPAC subcohort of 309 Czech individuals with PFAS levels in blood and dietary survey. The input data consisted of the PFAS occurrence dataset, consumption frequency from the cohort questionnaire, and portion sizes of the corresponding food items. For all input data, statistical distributions were estimated using MLE. The output consists for each individual of statistical distributions for external exposure to each PFAS per kg of body weight and day (ng/kg/day). For the purposes of future models integration, a harmonized way of representing input and output values by either theoretical or empirical distributions should be suggested.
- For the HBM exposure pathway of the workflow, a PBK model was selected in cooperation with T6.2.2 and T6.2.3. Since the parametrization of the model consists of a solid set of values, in the second half of year 3, an assessment of uncertainty for the model parameters is ongoing. We expect to use the same harmonized way of characterizing uncertainty of parameters as in the case of model inputs and outputs (statistical distributions either theoretical or empirical).
- Additionally, a review of uncertainty estimation methods was conducted in collaboration with T7.3.2, providing 20 common methods. Extended Fourier amplitude sensitivity testing, and Metropolis-Hastings Markov chain Monte-Carlo methods were selected for prioritized testing on both the PBK and dietary models.
- A generic modular design was developed for the case studies described above (WR). This design was used in MCRA to support integration of the different workflows over time. Examples of possible integrations include linking the aggregate exposure assessment workflow with the HBM-based mixture RA workflow allowing for e.g. identification of the routes and sources of exposure of the mixture risk drivers. A demonstrator was developed highlighting the use of the FAIR PBK workflow in the aggregate exposure assessment workflow.
- The developers of INTEGRA (AUTH) keep working on the link of internal dose estimates of parent compounds and metabolites with system biology models (UOC, IUSS), towards systems biology based AOPs (INSERM). In order to render INTEGRA interoperable with the rest of the model network, modifications have been done in the direction of following the common input-outputs formats (entry points) that will be commonly decided in T8.3 for the PARC model network, including necessary modules for adapting to the required spatial and temporal scale(s). Huge efforts have been performed in order to render INTEGRA interoperable and as a result that all components of INTEGRA will also be provided as individual APIs which can be interconnected with the other parts of the PARC model network.
- INTEGRA coding has been translated from AcslXreme into R, while efforts are ongoing for upgrading the multimedia model from level 3 to level 4 model. More functionalities are under construction including backward running for the multimedia model and exposure reconstruction framework. The generic PBPK model of INTEGRA has been translated into R as well and there is ongoing work to be release its REST API. Specific discussion has been addressed to integrate the in-silico models within VEGAHUB with INTEGRA (and in the future with other platforms). Oral exposure models (both Dietary and Non-dietary modules) have been translated as well as the inhalation exposure model. A first version of REST API has been created and the first APIs are to be released by the end of 2024. Last but not least, we (AUTH) have developed a module for a virtual population generation that will be in probabilistic simulations and modelling of the INTEGRA platform. The framework for risk characterization combining internal dose and in silico NAMs methods using the data from ToxCast21 has been developed (AUTH, UOC, UL-LACDR).
- Development, potential use of, integration and alignment of the Source To Outcome Predictor (STOPredictor) for environmental RA within the model suite of WP8.3 is currently

ongoing. The main focus has been on developing a review and model decision support tool for characterising the AEP continuum (NIVA) and linking exposure data to multi-species hazard data compiled from open literature. A dedicated import module for quantitative effects data (qData) has been developed in collaboration with WP5.1.2 and WP7.2 (NIVA), case studies for Arctic pollutants defined in WP6.4.1 (NIVA) and effects data generated in WP5.1.2 (NIVA) to populate the STOP model with demonstration data. A prototype user interface has been built using R shiny dashboards to demonstrate integrated STOP analysis. Discussion on how to link STOP to existing WP8.3 initiatives such as PBPK modeling (WR, IISPV), non-human QSAR hazard predictions by VEGA-HUB (IRFM), and take larger advantage of linkage between human and environmental assessments has been launched.

- Serving of AI models via SciLifeLab Serve was explored (UU) and the concept of Collections was implemented for grouping relevant AI models in e.g. a domain or consortium. UI and API developments with Gradio was evaluated. Identifying suitable AI models relevant for PARC was initiated.

Many of the developments described above were detailed in additional deliverable AD8.4 (submitted M27). Other dissemination activities include:

- Training of HBM mixture RA workflow to EFSA staff on March 19 in Parma, Italy (WR, ANSES)
- Presentation of HBM mixture RA workflow to PARC GB members in a series of webinars organized by T6.2 on May 3, 6 and 7 (WR, ANSES)
- Presentation of HBM mixture RA workflow in T6.2 meeting with DG SANTE on May 27 (WR, ANSES)
- PARC Training Course on Chemical Exposure & Modeling that took place on June 10 – 12 in Brno, Czech Republic (WR, MU)
- Presentation on PARC model network in session S13 – *Integrating Exposome and RA Approaches: A Joint Strategy for Chemical Mixture Assessment* at EuroTox 2024 in Copenhagen, Denmark (WR)

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD8.4	Initial results of the application of the integrative model network in use cases	AUTh	M24	M27	Late review and finalisation of the AD
D8.4	1st Report on the testing and uptake of the SSbD toolbox	EMPA	M24	M28	Delay due to revision and improvement of the draft as well as to the summer break.

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
	through use cases				

1.2.9 Work package 9. Building Infrastructural and human capacities

1.2.9.1 Task 9.1. Laboratory networking

Leader: ISCIII

Participants: ANSES, INERIS, Oniris, BRGM, LNE, ISSeP, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, RSU, NPHSL, LNS, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, FMUL, INSA, SZU-SK, UK, CSIC, FISABIO, FINIBIC¹⁷, BPI, GCSL

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Consultations with other WPs on the laboratory networking needs, priority areas and existing networks/laboratories have been performed on an ongoing basis, especially with WP4, on HBM and environmental monitoring.

The structure and characteristics of the laboratory catalogues are being defined in collaboration with Task 7.2 and 9.2.

The work on Task 9.1 to create the laboratory networks was organized by field, addressing first HBM laboratories, followed by air and water domains. Task 9.1 partners with expertise in those domains have been consulted in collaboration with Task 9.2 as the work advanced addressing the different fields. The identification of specific partners contributing to the creation of each laboratory network has been done, aiming for their participation in the design of the specific questionnaire and in the identification and attraction of new laboratories to the networks. ISCIII led this activity, with the key contribution of CSIC in the fields of air and water laboratories and the rest of the partners from Task 9.1-

Regarding the HBM laboratory network, the information about the analytical capacities of the laboratories (matrices, biomarkers, analytical methods, etc...) was carried out during 2023, thanks to a detailed questionnaire designed by ISCIII in collaboration with HBM-experienced Task 9.1 partners (*ANSES, LNE, ISSeP, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, NPHSL, LNS, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, FMUL, INSA, SZU-SK, UK, CSIC, FISABIO, FINIBIC, BPI, GCSL*), and implemented by FMUL in LimeSurvey tool. The database was cleaned, and the results were analysed during 2024 by ISCIII. The interactive laboratory map was launched in May 2024 including the information of HBM laboratories in collaboration with T3.2 partners. The design and visualisation of the HBM interactive laboratory map were discussed in a meeting between ISCIII and Task 3.2 partners (NCPHP and EEA) in April 2024.

¹⁷ AMD-101057014-118: The Spanish affiliated entity Fundación Profesor Novoa Santos - PARC acronym "FNS", has changed its name to Fundación Pública Galega de Investigación Biomédica INIBIC (FINIBIC) as of 06/05/2024. The list of affiliated entities must be updated accordingly. The acronym FNS must be replaced by FINIBIC in the WP9 where they are contributors

Regarding laboratories on air (including indoor air), after reaching the laboratories with interest in taking part of the network during the first 12 months of PARC, a detailed questionnaire has been designed during the first months of 2024, led by ISCIII and CSIC (with the collaboration of LNS, LNE, MU, NMBU, INSA, SZU-SK, UK, FISABIO, FINIBIC), and implemented in LimeSurvey by FMUL. To discuss first, the final design of the questionnaire and then, its implementation in the LimeSurvey software, two meetings were held on 14 May 2024 and 21 May 2024 between ISCIII and CSIC, and ISCIII, CSIC and FMUL, respectively. The survey was launched on 1 October 2024 to the laboratories within the network to collect their specific analytical capacities (survey open until 31 October 2024). Furthermore, an advertisement entitled “Join the PARC European Air Laboratory Network” was published on 7 October 2024 in the “News & Events” section of the PARC website, in collaboration with T3.2, inviting all European laboratories to participate in this initiative by completing the questionnaire and highlighting the benefits of joining to work in the improvement of air quality monitoring and chemical RA across Europe.

Additionally, the work on water laboratories started also with a survey launched in February 2024 to identify laboratories working in this domain and interested in joining the network. The rate of answers was really low, consequently, the number of laboratories reached was also low. During the autumn of 2024 the work focused on creating a working group with expertise on water (WWG) to design the specific questionnaire to collect analytical capacities of laboratories in this domain, and to try to get more laboratories involved in the network. The activity was led by CSIC and coordinated by ISCIII, and the WWG formed was composed of the following partners: INERIS, LNE, BPI, NMBU, INSA, JSI. A meeting was held between ISCIII and CSIC on 5 July 2024 to coordinate the different activities. The first meeting of the WWG was carried out on 30 September 2024 to agree on strategies to attract more laboratories to the network, the first steps in the design of the specific questionnaire and the distribution of work activities among the members of the WWG. The second meeting of the group was scheduled for 17 October 2024.

New strategies to expand the networks and to include new laboratories have been driven during these months, including publications on social media and contacts with already created networks (i.e. AQUILA, NORMAN).

Even though (eco)toxicological laboratory network was planned from Y4, the work has already started in collaboration with Task 9.2, designing a survey to collect information about (eco)toxicological capacities in Europe, including laboratories. The activity was led by MU, with input from ISCIII in the section of laboratory capacities, and comments from other partners AUTH, CSIC, FINIBIC, INERIS, INSA. A meeting was held on 18 September 2024 between MU and ISCIII to identify synergies and define the collaboration between Task 9.1 and Task 9.2 in this field, in order to avoid duplications.

Articles and consumer products have been postponed. We will start this work through the consultation with WP6, specifically with the project 6.4.3.1 “A comprehensive review and application of databases and testing methods for Substances in Products and Materials” to follow a comprehensive and aligned approach on this field.

Subtasks 9.1.2 and 9.1.3 address the development of networking activities to ensure the coordination and activity of the networks and the promotion of the less developed networks. These activities have slowly started with the definition of the first list of coordination and linkage activities (led by CSIC in collaboration with 9.1.3 partners, MU, ISSeP, STAMI, NMBU, FMUL, LNS, ISCIII, FINIBIC, INSA, LNE, BRGM, VSCHT, GCSL, INERIS), and the main key points to identify these less developed networks (led by FISABIO in collaboration with 9.1.2 partners, MU, NPHSL, LNS, ISSeP, NMBU, FMUL, NIPH, ISCIII, FINIBIC, AU, INSA, GCSL, BRGM, VSCHT, Sciensano, LNE, INERIS) in a meeting carried out on 5 March 2024 between ISCIII, CSIC and FISABIO. The previously mentioned lists of activities and criteria have not been implemented yet,

since the work has mainly focused until now on the creation of the networks, the involvement of laboratories and the collection of capacities.

In Subtask 9.1.4, once the initial concept and design of the laboratory dashboard had been included in D9.1, the work has been focused on meetings with Task 9.2 and Task 7.2 to guarantee the implementation of the laboratory dashboard in the PARC Data Hub (on-going work led by MU). Information on the design and data from laboratories to be included in the dashboard have been provided by ISCIII to MU. Initially, information on the analytical capabilities of HBM laboratories, collected through the detailed questionnaire, was transferred from ISCIII to MU to feed the laboratory dashboard. Several meetings were performed during Y2 (7 October 2023 between MU and ISCIII; 20 October 2023 with T9.1 partners) and Y3 (13 June 2024 between MU and ISCIII) to discuss the best design approaches for the laboratory dashboard.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

Although the majority of the activities were carried out according to plan, some of them have been delayed due mainly to the difficulty for involving partners on the tasks, but also for the low rate of response from laboratories to be included in the networks. Specifically, we had a very low rate of response from water laboratories. This leads to the definition of new strategies to increase the number of laboratories in the networks and to better explain the benefits of taking part in the networks.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.9.2 Task 9.2. Building exposure monitoring capacities

Leader: MU

Participants: ANSES, Inserm, Oniris, LNE, SpF, ISSeP, Sciensano, IMROH, AU, NCPHP, NPHSL, LNS, UU-IRAS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, SZU-SK, CSIC, ISCIII, AUTH, BPI, GCSL

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

MU has led the activity with the contribution of Task 9.2 partners from ANSES, AU, AUTH, GCSL, INSERM, NPHHC, RIVM, SpF, and UU-IRAS.

Initial catalogues of environmental monitoring networks were developed (Power BI) and distributed for partners to collect feedback and start preparing updated D9.2 (M. In cooperation with WP7, design of PARC Data Hub was discussed and presented at various meeting (T9.1, WP9 annual meeting, WP4 annual meeting, WP7 annual meeting). On toxicological resources, a cross-WPs survey was developed (WP5, 7, 9) and distributed to partners in relevant WPs. On 24th October 2024 a webinar was organised where the rationale behind the questionnaire was explained and feedback collected. In cooperation with WP6, first prototype of consumer products database was prepared (Power BI) and distributed among relevant partners in WP6 and WP9 for update. The feedback collected was incorporated the prototype. In cooperation with WP4, the design of HBM /population studies/networks was discussed. In addition, the development of catalogues on air monitoring (in cooperation with 4.2) and HBM/population studies/networks (in collaboration with 4.1) and on networks related to articles/indoors (in cooperation with 6.4.3), including the available sample and data collections in support of their further use in WPs 4-8, was

initiated, where the initial inventories were made available by M12 in D9.2 (AU (domains: air, articles, indoor), CSIC (domain: air), ISCI (domain: HBM), ISSeP (domains: air, articles, indoor), FMUL (domain: HBM), NPHSL (domain: air), with contributions from BPI, GCSL, IMROH, INSA, JSI, LNE, LNS, ONIRIS, STAMI, SCIENSANO, SZU-SK, ENSP, UU-IRAS, VSCHT).

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

Engagement of partners, effective cooperation among WPs.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

NA

1.2.9.3 Task 9.3. Joint activities – harmonisation

Leader: WR (NL)

Participants: ANSES, INRAE, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, UNIVIE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, RegionH-RH, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, UNN, INSA, JSI, NLZOH, CSIC, ISCI, FINIBIC, BPI, GCSL

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

The work in T9.3 is performed by five working groups (WGs), four on chemical analyses: WG1 sampling (lead AU, LNE), WG2 performance criteria (lead MU), WG3 interlaboratory comparability (lead ANSES, LNE), WG4 (reporting/acceptability of data, lead ONIRIS, LNS), and one on toxicity testing (WG6, lead NIPH, STAMI). Each WG held online meetings with their contributors, and completed an inventory of existing definitions, protocols/guidances, and criteria with emphasis on chemicals, application domains and techniques/assays applied in Y1-Y3 in WP4 and WP5. In addition, the WGs prepared the first draft of the guidance documents. An in-person meeting for T9.3 contributors was held 27-28 Feb 2024 in Amsterdam to present the progress and discuss QA/QC matters. Online core group meetings were held to monitor the progress of the WGs. T9.3 interacted with WP4 (mostly 4.1) to align on approval/comparability of laboratory performing sample for the aligned HBM studies, and reporting formats as developed by VITO. Input was provided for the PARC website, and online meetings were attended to investigate synergies with networks and projects outside PARC.

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

As indicated in ASRY2, initiation of 9.3 QA/QC activities and alignment with those in WP4 and WP5 took more time than anticipated. As a consequence of this, the first deliverable has been postponed, and a second cancelled.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D9.4	1st Generic guidance documents for QA/QC on sampling; chemical analysis; toxicity, EDA, & toxicokinetics studies	WR	M24 (postponed M36)		QA/QC is an integral part in many WP4/WP5 projects, and alignment of scope of activities done within T9.3 and WP4/WP5 projects took time and effort as projects were largely under construction in Y1-Y2. This resulted in re-defining of scope and activities in T9.3, and also slowed down the progress of the work. While the scheduled inventory of existing QA/QC was largely done, digesting this information and identifying gaps and needs was delayed. This resulted in a delay of the establishment of generic QA/QC guidance documents. Hence the foreseen deliverable date of M24 for the first draft of guidance documents could not be met.
D9.6	Update 1 of the Generic guidance documents for QA/QC on sampling; chemical analysis; toxicity, EDA, & toxicokinetics studies	WR	M32		D9.6 is cancelled as the new delivery date for D9.4 is M36

1.2.9.4 Task 9.4 Training

Leader:

Participants: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), ONIRIS (FR), BRGM (FR), LNE (FR), UMIT (AT), Sciensano (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), IRFM (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), ULFFA (SI), NIJZ (SI), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FINIBIC (ES), KI (SE), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR), UEF (FI)

Summary of the work achieved for the task for the period M21-M32

Following the established in PARC training plan (published in AD9.1, submitted by M23), three in person training courses have been held, namely on *FAIR data and databases* (from 22 to 24.05.2024 in Ljubljana, Slovenia, under the coordination of JSI, SI), on *Chemicals Exposure and Modelling* (from 10 to 12.06.2024 in Brno, Czech Republic, under the coordination of MU,CZ),

and on *Health RA of Chemicals – principles and applications* (from 18 to 22.06.2024 in Stockholm, Sweden under the coordination of IMM-KI, SE). In addition to these, an in-person training course on SSbD – the *2nd SSbD Boot Camp*, was also held under PARC from 22 to 25.10.2024 in Thessaloniki, Greece, under the coordination of AUTH, GR. For all these courses, Task 9.4 has collaborated with scientific coordinators, and Task 3.2 leaders on the 1) preparation of all the materials needed for course dissemination on PARC website and social media, namely, application form, practical information file, course agenda; 2) notification of acceptance of trainees; 3) data collection on trainees' satisfaction and 4) release of a short news item on the course (both before and after the course).

From M21 to M32, Task 9.4 partners have also developed some e-learning materials on topics identified in the 1st PARC training needs survey for non-formal learning. These include video presentations and a FAQ sheet on *Standardised sample collection and processing* for Occupational Surveys (coordinated by LNS, LU and ENSP, PT). An e-book on the *Use of specific in silico models and read-across tools*, applied to specific substances has also been developed under the coordination of IRFMN, IT. These materials will take part of a training library, currently under development in close collaboration with T8.1.4 and T3.2, that will include not only training materials developed under PARC, but also external materials, that are continuously identified by T9.4 partners.

The mechanism for staff exchange has been disseminated both at the Consortium Meeting, held in May 2024, in Austria, and in PARC Sampler (July 2024). among partners using a digital flyer. Considering that there is no dedicated budget to this activity, Task 9.4 partners have identified possible funding opportunities for these exchanges in case trainees wish to apply for financial support; these listing of opportunities can be found in the dissemination flyer.

In this period, Task9.4 partners have mainly articulated their work by email exchange; a few bilateral meetings with T9.4 leaders and training scientific coordinators or key partners were also held. An updated situation was presented to all T9.4 partners in the annual WP9 meeting held in October 2024. Detailed information on all the activities carried out under T9.4 between M13 and M30 is available on D9.5 (submitted for review in October 2024).

Problems encountered /Deviations during the implementation of the work planned for this task during the period M21-M32, if any, and their consequences:

NA

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones for the task to be achieved during the period M21-M32, from 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD9.1	Training plan, version 1	INSA	M18 (postponed M19)	M23	This AD was initially planned M18 and was postponed to M19. Due to the previous delay in D9.3 (training needs), the AD9.1 was delayed to mid-November.

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D9.5	Report on Training events Y2	INSA	M24 (postponed M30)		D9.5 is postponed from M24 to M30. This is because the first PARC training courses are not scheduled until May/June 2024 (as outlined in AD9.1 of the PARC Training Plan). By delaying the deliverable until M30, we will be able to include valuable insights from both the May and June training courses, as well as the progress made on developing online resources, allowing for a more comprehensive and informative report.